

CHIEF ALBERT LUTHULI MUNICIPALITY

FINAL

INTEGRATED DEVELOPMENT PLAN – IDP

2022 - 2027

INDEX

ACCRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

ABET	Adult Based Education and Training
AIDS	Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome
ASGISA	Accelerated Shared Growth Initiative South Africa
CBO's	Community Based Organizations
CETA	Construction Education and Training Authority
CHBC	Community Home Base Care
CIP	Comprehensive Infrastructure Plan
CFO	Chief Financial Officer
CMIP	Consolidated Municipal Infrastructure Programme
CM	Community Services
DAC	District Aids Council
DBSA	Development Bank of South Africa
DALA	Department of Agriculture and Land Administration
DARDLA	Department of Development and Land Administration
DCOGTA	Department of Corporative Government and Traditional Affairs
DHS	Department of Human Settlements
DLA	Department of Land Affairs
DM	District Municipality
DME	Department of Minerals and Energy
DPWR&T	Department of Public Works, Roads and Transport
DRDLR	Department of Rural Development and Land Reform
ECA	Environmental Conservation Act
EPWP	Expanded Public Works Programme
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EIP	Environmental Implementation Plan
EPWP	Expanded Public Works Programme
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EIP	Environmental Implementation Plan
EPWP	Expanded Public Works Programme
FBS	Free basic Services
FBE	Free Basic Electricity
GIS	Geographic Information System
GSDM	Gert Sibande District Municipality
HoD	Head of Department
HDI	Human Development Index
IS	Information System
IDP	Integrated Development Planning
IT	Information Technology
IGR	Intergovernmental Relations
IWMP	Integrated Waste Management Plan
ICT	Information and Communication System
IT	Information Technology
ITP	Integrated Transport Plan
KPA	Key Performance Area
ITP	Integrated Transport Plan
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LED	Local Economic Development
LM	Local Municipality
LTO	Local Tourism Organization
LUMS	Land Use Management System
MEC	Member of Executive Committee

MF	Mining Forum
MFMA	Municipal Finance Management Act
MHS	Municipal Health Services
MIG	Municipal Infrastructure Grant
MPCC	Multi-Purpose Community Centres
MSIG	Municipal Systems Improvement Grant
MM	Municipal Manager
NEMA	National Environmental Management Act
NEPAD	New Partnership for Africa's Development
NER	National Electricity Regulator
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NSDP	National Spatial Development Perspective
PED	Planning and Economic Development
PGDS	Provincial Growth and Development Strategy
PHC	Primary Health Care
PMS	Performance Management System
RBIG	Regional Bulk Infrastructure Grant
SACOB	South Africa Chamber of Business
SALGA	South Africa Local Government and Administration
SANAC	South African National AIDS Council
SAPS	South African Police Service
SDBIP	Service Delivery and Budget Implementation Plan
SETA	Sector Education Training Authority
SDF	Spatial Development Framework
SETA	Sector Education Training Authority
SLA	Service Level Agreement
WSA	Water Services Authorities
WSDP	Water Services Development Plan

Contents

Foreword by the Executive Mayor.....	11
OVERVIEW BY THE MUNICIPAL MANAGER.....	12
CHAPTER 1	14
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	14
1.1. INTRODUCTION	14
1.2. POLICY AND LEGISLATIVE CONTEXT	15
1.3. NATIONAL AND PROVINCIAL FRAMEWORKS GOVERNING GERT SIBANDE DISTRICT MUNICIPALITY (GSDM) AND ITS LOCAL MUNICIPALITIES	15
1.3.1. NATIONAL SPATIAL DEVELOPMENT PERSPECTIVE (NSDP)	15
1.3.2 NATIONAL GROWTH PATH.....	16
1.3.3. NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN (NDP)	17
1.3.4 GOVERNMENT OUTCOMES	17
1.4. MPUMALANGA ECONOMIC GROWTH AND DEVELOPING PATH (MEGDP)	18
1.4.1. AGRICULTURE	18
1.4.2. FORESTRY	19
1.4.3. MINING	19
1.4.4. TOURISM AND CULTURAL INDUSTRIES	19
1.4.5. THE GREEN ECONOMY AND ICT	20
1.4.6. REGIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION	20
1.5. MPUMALANGA RURAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME (MRDP)	20
1.6 TASKS THAT WERE DEVELOPED TO TAKE SOUTH AFRICA FORWARD FOR THE FIVE 5 YEAR PERIOD	21
1.6.1 BACK TO BASICS APPROACH IN DETAIL	21
1.6.1.1 Governance.....	21
1.6.1.2 Administration	21
1.6.1.3 Sound Financial Management.....	21
Table 1.1: Contribution to the District per industry & region	19
CHAPTER 2	20
SITUATIONAL ANALYSIS	20
2.1. GEOGRAPHY	20
2.2. DEMOGRAPHY	21
2.3. POPULATION	22
2.3.1. MIGRATION	22

2.3.4.	GENDER COMPOSITION	24
2.4.	HEALTH PROFILE	25
2.5.	EDUCATION PROFILE	26
2.5.1.	Matric Performance per Circuit	27
2.5.2.	Higher Education and Training	28
2.6.	HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX	28
2.7.	EQUALITY: GINI COEFFICIENT	28
2.8.	POVERTY	29
2.9.	CRIME	29
2.10.	LOCAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT	29
2.10.1.	ECONOMY	29
	CONTRIBUTION TO THE PROVINCIAL ECONOMY BY MUNICIPAL AREA.....	30
2.11.2.	GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT	30
2.11.3.	GROSS VALUE ADD (GVA) AND SECTOR COMPOSITION	31
2.11.4.	LABOUR	31
2.11.5.	POVERTY, INEQUALITY AND UNEMPLOYMENT	31
2.11.6.	ECONOMIC OPPORTUNITIES	34
2.13.	BASIC SERVICE DELIVERY	39
2.13.1.	WATER PROVISION	39
2.13.2.	FREE BASIC WATER	41
2.14.	SANITATION	42
2.15.	ELECTRICITY	43
2.16.	REFUSE REMOVAL	45
2.17.	ROADS AND PUBLIC TRANSPORT	46
CHAPTER 3.....		48
IDP PROCESS		48
Vision		48
Mission		48
Value System		48
3.1. Integrated Development Plan		48
3.1.1.	The Process	48
3.1.2.	The Legislative and Policy Context	48
3.2. INTER-GOVERNMENTAL PLANNING		50
3.3. National and Provincial Policy Frameworks		51
3.4. The Status of the IDP		51

3.4.1.	The IDP Process.....	51
3.4.2.	The IDP Process Plan	52
3.4.3.	The Implementation of the IDP Process Plan.....	52
3.5.	Review of the IDP.....	57
3.5.1.	Strategic Objectives.....	57
3.5.2.	Strategic Objective 1: To ensure Good Governance	64
3.5.3.	Policies and procedures.....	64
3.6.2.	MUNICIPAL FUNCTIONS.....	68
3.6.3.	GOVERNANCE AND ADMINISTRATION.....	70
3.6.4.	DEMOCRATIC AND ACCOUNTABLE GOVERNMENT	71
3.6.5.	LEADERSHIP.....	72
3.7.	COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION AND SATISFACTION	73
3.7.1.	Community Needs	73
3.7.2.	Ward Committees.....	73
3.7.3.	TRADITIONAL LEADERSHIP.....	74
3.9.	OFFICE-BEARERS AND MAYORAL COMMITTEE	76
3.10.	Marketing and communication	79
3.11.	Legal and compliance	79
1.11	. Risk management.....	79
CHAPTER 4		83
FINANCIAL PLANNING		83
4.1.	Background.....	83
3.12	Financial Management Structure	83
4.3.	Financial Management Framework.....	83
4.4.	Overview of financial management policies.....	84
4.4.1.	Tariff Policy	84
4.4.2.	Rates Policy	84
4.4.3.	Free Basic services policy.....	84
4.4.4.	Indigent Support Policy	84
4.4.5.	Credit Control and Debt Collection Policy.....	85
4.4.6.	Budget Policy	85
4.4.7.	Cash Management and Investment Policy	85
4.4.8.	Asset Management Policy.....	85
4.4.9.	Capital Investment and Infrastructure Development Policy	85
4.4.10.	Borrowing policy	85

4.4.11. Funding and Reserves Policy	85
4.4.12. Accounting Policy	85
4.4.13. Supply Chain Management Policy	86
4.4.14. Transport and Subsistence Policy	86
4.5. Financial Management Status	86
4.6. Table 4.2: Capital Programs and Projects:	92
4.7. Public Participation	94
Issues emanating from Public Participation.....	94
4.8. Programmes and Projects for Land Use Management and Township Establishment.....	124
5.1. National Legislative Framework	139
5.2. Department of Public Works, Roads, and Transport	139
5.3. Department of Agriculture	139
5.4. Department of Human Settlements.....	150
Proposed Projects:	151
5.5. Department of Health.....	152
5.6. Department of Rural Development and Land Reform.....	152
5.7. Department of Community Safety, Security and Liaison	153
5.8. Department of Culture, Sports, and Recreation	156
5.9. Department of Social Development	159
5.11. Department of Education.....	160
5.12. LIST OF ESKOM PROJECTS	161
5.9. Gert Sibande District Municipality	162
PROJECTS BY DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION / gsdm	162
ANNEXURE B: LIST OF DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION (DBE) PROJECTS	164
CHAPTER 6.....	169
SECTOR PLANS.....	169
6.1. Background.....	169
6.2. Skills Development Plan	170
6.3. LED Strategy	170
6.4. Waste Management.....	171
6.5. Cemeteries	174
6.6. Safety	174
6.7. Traffic Management	175
6.8. Disaster Management, Firefighting, Emergency and Rescue Service.....	175
6.8.1. Drought	176

6.8.2. Fires and Accidents	176
6.9. Social Development	176
6.9.1 Culture, Sport, and Recreation Pillars:	177
6.9.2 Welfare and Disability Coordination and Support	178
6.9.3. Youth Development	179
6.9.4. Gender	181
6.9.5. Children’s Rights	182
6.9.6. Thusong Services Centre	182
6.9.7. Library Services	183
6.9.8. HIV/AIDS, Home Based Care and Orphans	184
6.10. Strategic Objective 5: To ensure Provision of Basic Services (Electricity, Water and Sanitation)	184
Figure 6.7: Basic Services Key Performance Areas	185
6.10.1. Access to Electricity	185
6.10.1.1. The Energy Plan	186
6.10.2. Access to Water	187
6.10.3. Provision of Sanitation	190
6.10.3.1. Status of Sanitation Services	191
6.10.3.2. Green Drop Performance	191
6.10.3.3. Access to Sanitation	191
6.10.3.4. Status of Sewer Treatment Plants and Related Bulk Infrastructure	192
6.10.3.5. Operations and Maintenance Plan	192
6.10.4. Access to Roads and Transportation Systems	195
6.10.4.1. Roads and Storm Water	196
6.10.4.2. Status of Arterial Roads or Internal Roads	196
6.10.4.3. Integrated Roads and Storm-water Master Plan	196
6.10.4.4 Resources available to support the delivery of the service	196
6.10.5 Infrastructure Development and Maintenance	197
CHAPTER 7	199
PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (PMS)	199
7.1. Background	199
7.2. The Legal Premise of the PMS Framework	199
7.3. PMS Key Role Players	200
7.4. Status of Performance Management System in the Municipality	201
7.4.1. Corporate Scorecard	201

7.4.2. Individual level.....	201
7.4.3. Cascading of PMS to lower levels.....	201
7.4.4. Performance Agreements.....	201
7.4.5. Monitoring, evaluation and reporting processes and systems.....	202
CHAPTER 8	212
DISASTER MANAGEMENT	212
8.1. INTRODUCTION.....	212
8.2. THE CUSTODIAN OF THE PLAN.....	212
8.3. THE PURPOSE OF THE PLAN.....	213
8.4. OVERVIEW OF THE CALM	213
8.4.1 Geographical location	213
8.4.2 Demographic Profile	214
8.4.3 Development Profile	215
8.4.4 Economic Profile	215
8.4.5 Infrastructure	215
8.4.5.1 Transport	215
8.4.5.2 Basic services	216
8.4.6 Critical facilities	217
8.5. THE CALM DISASTER RISK MANAGEMENT INSTITUTIONAL CAPACITY.....	217
8.5.1 Management Committee.....	217
8.5.2 Disaster Risk Management Advisory Forum.....	217
8.5.3. NGO Forum	219
8.6. DISASTER RISK ASSESSMENT FOR THE CALM.....	220
8.7. THE DISASTER RISK PROFILE OF THE CALM.....	221
8.7.1 Macro hazard assessment	221
8.7.2 Macro Vulnerability Assessment.....	223
8.8. FORMAL CONSULTATIVE MECHANISM FOR DISASTER RISK REDUCTION PROJECTS	230
8.8.1 IDP projects contributing to vulnerability and hazard reduction.....	230
8.8.1.1 Fire (Shack).....	230
8.8.1.2 Fire (Veld).....	231
8.8.1.3 Flooding.....	231
8.8.1.4 Severe weather conditions	231
8.8.1.5 Hazardous materials (storage, transportation and usage)	231
8.8.1.6 Sinkholes.....	232

8.8.1.7	Special events	232
8.8.1.8	Mission Critical Systems Failure (MCFS)	232
8.8.1.9	Transportation accidents	232
8.8.1.10	Building collapse	232
8.9.	DISASTER RISK MANAGEMENT PLANNING PRIORITIES FOR THE CALM	232
8.10	RESPONSE TO CORONA (COVID19) PANDAMIC	233
8.10.3	SCOPE	233
8.10.5	Financial impact of COVID 19.....	234
8.10.8	IDENTIFIED QUARANTINE AREA.....	235
8.10.9	CONCLUSION	235
ANNEXURE A: CHIEF ALBERT LOCAL MUNICIPALITY		236
A.	GLOSSARY	1
4.	Purpose of the SDBIP	3
5.	Legislative requirement.....	3
11.	Strategic Focus of Local Government	6
12.	Financial Plan.....	6
A:	FINANCIAL PROJECTIONS.....	8
Table 2:	Revenue (schedule A4).....	8
Table 3:	Expenditure: Departmental allocation	8
1.	TABLE 4: CAPITAL PROJECTS 2021/2022 – 2023/2024.....	9
B.	SUMMARY OF STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES AND KEY PERFORMANCE AREAS AND TARGETS	12
2.	STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 1: TO ENSURE GOOD LEADERSHIP AND GOVERNANCE	13
3.	STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 2: TO ENSURE EFFICIENT AND EFFECTIVE INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT).....	17
4.	STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 3: TO ENSURE TRANSFORMED INSTITUTION WITH COMPETENT AND CAPABLE HUMAN CAPITAL	19
5.	STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 4: TO ENSURE FINANCIAL HEALTHIER AND SUSTAINABLE ENVIRONMENT 20	
6.	STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 5: TO ENSURE PROVISION OF BASIC SERVICES.....	23
7.	STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 6: TO ENSURE SUSTAINABLE LOCAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT	26
2.2.	INTRODUCTION	1
2.2.	DIAGNOSTIC SUMMARY	4
i.	Integrated Service Provisioning	12
ii.	Demographic and District profile	14
iii.	Economic Positioning.....	16
iv.	Governance and Administration	17

Foreword by the Executive Mayor

According to Section 25 of the Local Government: Municipal Systems Act, 2000 (Act 32 of 2000), each municipal council must, after the start of its elected term, adopt a single, inclusive and strategic plan Integrated Development Plan (IDP). For the development of the municipality, which links, integrates and coordinates plans and takes into account proposals for the development of the municipality, and which aligns the resources and capacity of the municipality with the implementation of the said plan.

An Integrated Development Plan is a super plan for an area that gives an overall framework for development. It aims to co-ordinate the work of local and other spheres of government in a coherent plan to improve the quality of life for all the people living in a municipality. It takes into account the existing conditions and problems and resources available for development. It looks at economic and social development for the area as a whole. Municipalities use it as a tool to plan short and long-term future development.

The IDP of the Chief Albert Luthuli Local Municipality (CALLM) is the principle strategic planning instrument that guides and informs all planning, budgeting, management and decision-making processes of the municipality. On 1st of November 2021, community of Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality has voted for the new political administration that will lead them for the next five years. Therefore, it is quite important that the municipality consult the communities in all wards, to find their needs and take those needs and prepare the five-year document.

Chapter 4 of the Municipal Systems Act 32 of 2000 makes community participation in the affairs, programs and activities of the municipality a legal obligation. This IDP is therefore the culmination of a lengthy process of consultation with the local community. Therefore, this IDP must be seen as a beacon of hope that will continue to guide us over the next financial year in our collective endeavors of building a better life for all our communities. Critical to this is the question of compliance with the laws of the Republic. For an example, before the end of May 2022, we must have presented to Council the final budget for the first coming financial year. In this regard, section 24 of Municipal Finance Management Act 56 of 2003 prescribes that "...the final budget must be tabled 30 days before the start of the budget year."

This IDP together with its projects and implementation focus relates more strongly to the capital budget. Our IDP and 2022/27 Budget will go a long way in improving the quality of life of our community by broadening accessibility and alleviating poverty.

As we continue on our march to deliver on our Manifesto commitments, we pledge ourselves to continue to work with our people to leave no stone unturned in fulfilling our objectives by accelerating and doubling our efforts to bring about a better life to all our people. We will do so in an accountable and ethical manner, as we have been proven to do over the years. As we look back with pride as we approach the final phase of the current term of our political office. It is this achievement, coupled with our confidence, commitment and loyalty, which will see us standing proud at the end of our political term.

This is the final product of the various engagement processes of the stakeholders and the communities in all the 25 wards of the Chief Albert Luthuli Local Municipality.

LET'S BUILD BETTER COMMUNITIES TOGETHER

CLLR DP NKOSI
EXECUTIVE MAYOR

03-05-2022

DATE

v.	Spatial Restructuring	18
vi.	Infrastructure Engineering	19
vii.	COVID-19 Impact	21
2.2.	VISION (OVERALL DESIRED FUTURE).....	21
2.2.	STRATEGIES	26
2.2.	IMPLEMENTATION PLAN	32
2.2.	CONCLUSION	35
2.2.	ANNEXURE: CATALYTIC COMMITMENTS	36

OVERVIEW BY THE MUNICIPAL MANAGER

The Integrated Development Plan (IDP) spells-out what the municipality intends to do to advance development in its area of jurisdiction. The Local Government: Municipal Systems Act (Act 32 of 2000) regards the Integrated Development Plan (IDP) as a principal strategic planning instrument which guides and informs all planning and development, and all decisions with regards to planning, management and development. Municipalities are bound by legislation to produce a new five (5) year planning

document that reflects the hopes and aspirations of its citizens, and essentially, it must be imbued with a visceral sense of commitment to development. In order to ensure that the municipality formulates a document that is commensurate with the needs of the people, and guided by Section 28 of the Local Government: Municipal Systems Act (Act 32 of 2000), the municipality adopted an IDP/Budget Process Plan in the August of 2021 which principally outlines the process to be undertaken in the compilation and adoption of the five (5) year IDP Document. The Process Plan also sets the tone and maintains the rather delicate balance of ensuring quality standards with regards to the compilation of the IDP and interaction between the community insofar as soliciting needs and synergy with other spheres of government – with the ultimate goal of developing a ‘One Plan’ through the District Development Model (DDM).

Since local government exists to provide municipal services to all residents, it is imperative that it interacts with the people living within the boundaries of the municipality and obtains their input in their elected government’s plans and vision. From this position, it suffices to say that local government is ‘*where the rubber meets the road*’ insofar as rolling out of services is concerned. In compiling this IDP, the municipality aimed to interact with as many residents as possible. At several public meetings, we discussed our plans and asked communities for their inputs on key deliverables, which we believe will bring much-needed development to many parts of our sprawled municipality.

The following mediums were utilized in the publication of the IDP/Budget Process Plan and submission of public comments.

Item Description	Electronic medium
Advertising of the notice for online submission of public comments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal Website (https://www.albertluthuli.gov.za/draft-calm-2022-2023-idp-process-plan/) • Municipal Facebook page
Receiving of Public comments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal email address and in spatially separated contact sessions in accordance with the latest proclaimed regulations.
Accessing the document	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal website • Municipal offices • Municipal libraries

Fellow citizen and stakeholder, we have compiled this IDP cognizant of the fresh electoral mandate that the people bestowed on the newly installed political dispensation following the Local Government Elections of 01 November 2021. This vision inter alia speaks of *'choosing the path of unity, hard work, development, inclusivity and shared prosperity for the betterment of all lives'* and identifies job creation, poverty alleviation and sustainable economic opportunities, especially for young people who constitute the majority of our population as an immediate priority. The impact of COVID-19, two (2) years of its onset, continues to impact all segments of economic and social lives. While its ricocheting highs and lows on the public administration has diminished, albeit tenuously, we still find ourselves with a threatening or insecure environment. This new fifth (5th) generation of an IDP will be the catalyst for growth not least since it postulates the vision 2030 as derived from the NDP: Local Government Outcome which essentially aims at creating a developmental local state that is accountable, focused on citizen's priorities and capable of delivering high-quality services sustainably through cooperative governance and participatory democracy. Within the fifth (5th) generation IDP, the focal areas are; in terms of the NDP, spatial transformation, alignment and implementation of the 'one plan'. The end product is an IDP based on results (outcomes).

Another key element is with reference to Chapter 3 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa wherein it provides for cooperative governance implemented under the auspices of the Intergovernmental Relations Framework Act 13 of 2005 as it pertains to the District Development Model or (DDM) for short which addresses the gaps in planning and coordination of government services, and will be the key driver in our coordination of the other spheres of government, social partners, etc. The DDM is anchored on institutionalizing a programmatic approach to improve integrated planning across government through formulation and implementation of single joined-up plans ('One Plan') for each of the 44 District and 8 Metropolitan geographic spaces. Further to this, due consideration was given to the policy directives of National and Provincial Government in the compilation of this IDP to ensure consistency inter alia with Revised IDP Guidelines and Revised FSPAPPs, MFMA Circular 88 Addendum 2, 2019-24 MTSF 7 Apex Priorities, Outcomes-Based Planning, DDM One Plan (coordinated all-of-government plan to jointly plan and budget for impact), Municipal Support and Intervention Plan & Economic Reconstruction and Recovery Plan. Borrowing once again from the wisdom of Abraham Lincoln, who, in November 19, 1863 at the height of the American Civil War where spoke of a **"government of the People, by the People, for the People"**. These remarks, 158 years later, still have resonance as we continue on the partnership with civil society to deliver services and improve the quality of life of our people.

MR MGT MNISI
ACTING MUNICIPAL MANAGER

03/05/2022
DATE:

CHAPTER 1

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1. INTRODUCTION

The objects of local government are – (a) to provide democratic and accountable government for local communities; (b) to ensure the provision of services to communities in an equitable, fair and sustainable manner; (c) to promote social and economic development; (d) to promote safe and healthy environment; and (e) to encourage the involvement of communities and community organizations in the matters of local government. The Constitutional mandate for municipalities is to strive, within their fiduciary and administrative capacity to achieve these objects, and carry out the developmental duties assigned to local Government.

Municipal Council therefore takes charge of the following principal responsibilities:

- The provision of democratic and accountable government,
- To encourage the involvement of the local community
- To provide all members of the local community with equitable access to the municipal services that they are entitled to
- To plan at the local and regional levels for the development and future requirements of the area
- To monitor the performance of the municipality by carefully evaluating budget reports and annual reports to avoid financial difficulties and if necessary, to identify causes and remedial measures for the identified financial and administrative challenges.
- To provide services, facilities and financial capacity, within the guidelines provided by the Constitution and Legislative Authority.

Integrated Development Planning is a process through which a municipality, government sector departments, various service providers and interested affected parties come together to identify development needs, outline clear objectives and strategies which serve to guide the allocation and management of resources within the municipality's jurisdictional area. From this planning process emanates the Municipal Integrated Development Planning (IDP), with its main objective being the improvement of coordination and integration of planning, budgeting and development within the Municipal area. As a five (5) year budgeting, decision-making, strategic planning and development tool, the IDP is used by the municipality to fulfill its role of developmental local governance. Central to this are the overarching objectives and strategies encapsulated in the plans which guide the Municipality in the realm of:

- Municipal Budgeting;
- Institutional restructuring to realize the strategic intent of the plan;
- Integrating various sectors in the form of Infrastructure, Land Use, and Agriculture with socio-economic and ecological dimension; and
- Performance Management System

This document therefore presents the Municipal Integrated Planning as part of its 2021/2022 IDP Review a process. It is prepared in fulfillment of the Municipality's legal obligation in terms of Section 34 of the Local Government: Municipal Systems Act, Act 32 of 2000.

1.2. POLICY AND LEGISLATIVE CONTEXT

In addition to the legal requirement for municipalities to compile an Integrated Development Plan as referred to in section 1 above, the Municipal Systems Act, (Act 32 of 2000) also requires that:

- o The IDP be implemented
- o The Municipality monitor's the implementation of the IDP
- o The Municipality evaluates its performance about the IDP's implementation; and
- o The IDP is reviewed annually to effect improvements where necessary.

Section 34 of the Act deals with the Review and Amendment of the IDP and states that:

"The Municipal Council:

- a) must review its Integrated Development Plan
 - i. annually in accordance with an assessment of its performance measures in terms of Section 41 and ;
 - ii. to the extent that changing circumstances so demand and
- b) may amend its Integrated Development Plan in accordance with the prescribed process"

The annual review process thus relates to the assessment of the municipality's performance against organizational objectives as well as implementation. It also takes into cognizance any new information or change in circumstance that might have arisen subsequent to the adoption of the previous IDP. The review and amendment process must also adhere to the requirements for public participation as articulated in chapter 4 of the MSA (2000).

In terms of the IDP Review Guidelines, IDPs are reviewed based on four primary areas of intervention, i.e. Annual IDP Review, the IDP process, Amendments in Response to changing municipal circumstances, and comments from the MEC of COGTA.

The process described and outlined in Figure 1 below represents a continuous cycle of planning, implementation, monitoring and review. Implementation commences after the Municipal Council adopts the Final Draft IDP, budget and performance management system for the subsequent financial year.

1.3. NATIONAL AND PROVINCIAL FRAMEWORKS GOVERNING GERT SIBANDE DISTRICT MUNICIPALITY (GSDM) AND ITS LOCAL MUNICIPALITIES

There are sector-specific legislations such as housing, transport and environment; while others are broad in nature encompassing the planning processes, alignment of planning processes and proposals, and the legal requirements pertaining to plans to be compiled. Moreover, a plethora of national, provincial and local plans and policies exist to provide further guidance and direction to planning in South Africa. The development of the IDP is consequentially depended on, and driven by these legislations and policy positions. The following are some of the pieces of legislations and plan that guides the development of IDPs:

1.3.1. NATIONAL SPATIAL DEVELOPMENT PERSPECTIVE (NSDP)

The National Spatial Development Perspective (NSDP) was initiated in 1999 with the aim of not only providing a strategic assessment of the spatial distribution and socio-economic characteristics of the South African population, but gaining a shared understanding of the distribution of economic activities and potential across

1.4.2. FORESTRY

- Key areas intervention to facilitate growth and job creation in the forestry include:
- Comprehensive investment in the sector to facilitate local economic development and foster local beneficiation.
- Acceleration settlement of land claims under forestry.
- Comprehensive support to SMMEs, particularly cooperatives:
- Investing in infrastructure

1.4.3. MINING

Key areas for intervention to facilitate growth and job creation in the mining industry are as follows

- Upgrading and maintenance of the coal haulage network.
- Increase the level of higher skilled graduates.
- Expand the water network and increase reliance on water transfer scheme.
- Increase South Africa's load and improve alternate energy supply.
- Establishment of a mining supplier park to enhance enterprise development in the province
- Resolve land claims to release land for development
- Comprehensive support to small-scale mining enterprise to exploit opportunities presented by corporate social investment initiatives, retreatment of sub –economic deposits and dumps, and dimension stones
- Improving rail haulage of minerals to reduce shipping costs (currently done by road)

1.4.4. TOURISM AND CULTURAL INDUSTRIES

Key areas for intervention to facilitate growth and job creation in the tourism and cultural industries include the following:

- Broadening and diversifying the primary and cultural tourism segments happening in the municipality, particularly in the traditional councils.
- Nature-based tourism product offerings in the Municipality which feed off into the economy of Mpumalanga through activities such as conferencing, sports events, food stalls that subsequently grow the economy to create jobs.
- Sustained investment in all aspects of the industry- new products, destination marketing, human capital development in the service industry
- Investing in economic infrastructure, such as guest houses, tea rooms, off-road tracks, Centre, tourism routes, and other capital infrastructure projects.
- Comprehensive support to SMMEs and Co-Operatives to fully benefit from opportunities in the tourism and cultural industries

Outcome 4: Decent employment through inclusive economic growth

Outcome 5: A skilled and capable work force to support inclusive growth

Outcome 6: An efficient, competitive and responsive economic infrastructure network

Outcome 7: Vibrant, equitable and sustainable rural communities and food security

Outcome 8: Sustainable human settlements and improved household life

Outcome 9: A responsive, accountable, effective and efficient local government system

Outcome 10: Protection and enhancement of environment, assets and national resources

Outcome 11: A better South Africa, a better and safer Africa and world

Outcome 12: A development-orientated public service and inclusive citizenship.

1.4. MPUMALANGA ECONOMIC GROWTH AND DEVELOPING PATH (MEGDP)

The primary objective of the Mpumalanga Economic Growth and Development Path (MEGDP) is to foster economic growth that creates jobs, reduce poverty and inequality in the province. The following are the main economic sectors (all of which occur in the Gert Sibande District) that have been identified as pivotal in spurring economic growth and employment creation:

- Agriculture and forestry,
- Mining,
- Tourism and cultural industries,
- The green economy and ICT,
- Manufacturing.

1.4.1. AGRICULTURE

Agriculture could be the driver for economic growth in the municipality if driven in a mixed-system approach where agrarian reform is epitomized by support for both commercial farmers as well as the substantial farmers. Together with the Department of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environmental Affairs; the municipality supports emerging farmers with inputs and market identification. There is also support for the small-scale subsistence farmers; most of whom dig backyard gardens.

Key areas for intervention to facilitate growth and job in the agriculture sector include:

- Assistance (technical, material and finance) to the identified agricultural co-operatives in traditional areas as well as the establishment of the Fresh Produce Market
- Massive drive in infrastructure development.
- Massive drive in skill development.
- Comprehensive support to small-scale farmers and agri-business.
- Fast-track the settlement of the outstanding land claims.
- Optimal utilization of restituted and distributed land.
- Increase acquisition of agriculture land for the previously disadvantaged.
- Revisit current legislation to create balanced development in areas of competition between mining and farming.

to change the character of the South African economy and ensure that the benefits are shared more equitably among all people, particularly the poor.

The following targets have been set nationally, with Mpumalanga Province (including Gert Sibande District Municipality) having to proportionally contribute towards the achievement of these and has done so by initiating projects and programmes in line with these drivers, namely:

Jobs driver 1: Infrastructure

Jobs driver 2: Main economic sectors

Jobs driver 3: Seizing the potential of new economies

Jobs driver 4: Investing in social and public services

Jobs driver 5: Spatial development (regional integration)

1.3.3. NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN (NDP)

The National Development Plan envisages an economy that serves the needs of all South Africans- rich and poor, black and white, skilled and unskilled, those with capital and those without, urban and rural, women and men. The vision is that, in 2030, the economy should be close to full employment, equip people with the skills they need, ensure that ownership of production is less concentrated and more diverse (where black people and women own a significant share of productive assets) and be able to grow rapidly, providing the resources to pay for investment in human and physical capital. Subsequently, the NDP proposes to create eleven million jobs by 2030 by ensuring that there is an environment which is conducive for sustainable employment and inclusive economic growth consequently promoting employment in labour-absorbing industries. Furthermore ensure the strengthening of government's capacity to give leadership to economic development through raising exports and competitiveness, and mobilizing all sectors of society around a national vision.

1.3.4 GOVERNMENT OUTCOMES

In January 2010, cabinet adopted 12 Outcomes within which to frame public-service delivery priorities. Cabinet ministers accordingly signed performance agreements linked to these Outcomes. More detailed delivery agreement has since been developed to extend targets and responsibility to national and provincial department, agencies and municipalities.

All municipalities are expected to consider the 12 Outcomes when reviewing their IDPs and developing their annual budgets. Below are the 12 Outcomes and the related outputs, together with indicative areas where Mpumalanga province and municipalities have a role to play either contributing directly to the realization of the Outcomes or facilitate the work of national and provincial departments in realizing them. Moreover the Outcomes which are listed below are further elaborated on in relation to GSDM in the following chapter of the IDP:

Outcome 1: Improve the quality of basic education

Outcome 2: Improve health and life expectancy

Outcome 3: All people of South Africa are protected and feel safe

the South African landscape. Based on the research conducted, and with key trends and issues identified, the NSDP currently delineates a number of guidelines for infrastructure investment in South Africa.

The rationale behind the guidelines is rooted in the argument that instead of investing in physical infrastructure to improve the quality of life of people living in low productivity areas, government should rather invest in people. The logic of the latter argument is that investing in people is a more efficient use of government resources. Investing in people potentially results in increased opportunities and choice to relocate to high growth areas. Investing in places can leave people trapped in low growth areas without any guarantee that this will attract new investment into the area.

In essence, the NSDP argues that government's social objectives will be best achieved through infrastructure investment in economically sustainable areas with proven development potential. Therefore, areas displaying little or no potential for growth should only be provided with the constitutionally mandated minimum levels of services, and the focus of government spending should rather be on the people, namely; social development spending. Social development spending may involve developing labour market intelligence, human resource development, health and social transfers. Crucially, this kind of "development spending" is specifically aimed at enabling the South African population, particularly youth located in areas in which they have no hope of finding employment, to gradually gravitate to areas with high economic potential.

Emanating from the broad philosophy and actions put forward by the NSDP, five principles are given below:

Principle 1: Economic growth is the prerequisite for the achievement of other policy objectives such as poverty eradication and equitable development.

Principle 2: Government infrastructure investment- beyond basic service delivery- will be in areas of high development potential or economic growth. These are areas of development potential identified into corridors and/or nodes. The focus is to reverse the settlement patterns of the previous dispensation where settlements were established far outside of the places of work.

Principle 3: Efforts to address inequalities should focus on people and not places.

Principle 4: Areas with high levels of poverty and high development potential should receive investment beyond basic services to exploit this potential.

Principle 5: Areas with high levels of poverty and low development potential should receive investment to provide basic services as well as social transfers, HRD, and labour market information.

1.3.2 NATIONAL GROWTH PATH

The new Growth Path provides bold, imperative and effective strategies to create the millions of new jobs of South Africa needs. It also lays out a dynamic vision for how we can collectively achieve a more developed, democratic and equitable economy and society over the medium-term, in the context of sustainable growth.

The shift to a new Growth Path requires the creative and collective efforts of all sections of South African society. It requires leadership and strong governance. It further takes account of the new opportunities and the strengths available, and the constraints to be overcome. It requires the development of a collective action

1.4.5. THE GREEN ECONOMY AND ICT

Key areas for intervention to facilitate growth and job creation in the green economy and ICT are:

- Investing in the development of technological infrastructure to reduce reliance on paper and make the municipality a paperless institution
- Invest in research for new technologies to promote green economy
- Invest in Infrastructure for ICT development
- Train and assist SMME's to provide them with necessary tools for moving their business online.

1.4.6. REGIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION

The growth path also states that the proximity of Mozambique, Swaziland and other SADC countries, including Memoranda of Understanding (MOU) signed with few overseas countries, provide Mpumalanga with Regional and International trade, investment and tourism opportunities. In regard to neighboring countries; road, rail and air infrastructure is key terms of facilitation of trade and other economic opportunities, for example efficient and smooth transit at border posts between Gert Sibande District Municipality and Swaziland, and to improve road networks and rails.

1.5. MPUMALANGA RURAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME (MRDP)

The Mpumalanga Rural Development Programme was introduced in 2001, coordinated by the Office of the Premier and technically supported by the German Technical Cooperation (GTZ) and the German Development Services.

The main objectives of the programme are to contribute towards an 'improvement of the social an economic situation of the rural poor'. The programme focuses on the creation of income and employment in rural areas, and the key concept of the programme include:

- Self-reliance/ empowerment: strengthen the self-help capabilities of the communities and emphasized on development and planning
- Economic Growth: encourage local economic development, employment and income generation through the promotion of small and micro- sized rural enterprises and participation of the private sector
- Sustainability: Improve viable and sustainable natural resource utilizations
- Outreach: upgrade and broaden the facilitation of government services to the impoverished
- Capacity Building: strengthen, advise and train service providers
- Innovation: develop innovative concepts for public service delivery
- Mainstream: get innovations on track
- Coping with HIV/AIDS: plan, design and implement relevant strategies in order to cope with HIV/AIDS
- Stakeholder's participation: ensuring participation by all concerned.

It is important for GSDM and its local municipalities to draw the concepts and principles of this plan down to ward level through spatial development and rural development strategies and other applicable policies.

Integrated Support Plan (ISP) for Accelerated Municipal Service Delivery

This Integrated Support Plan for local government is developed by the Mpumalanga Department of Cooperative Governance and Traditional Affairs (COGTA) to ensure that all 18 municipalities in the province are functional and provide services to communities in a sustainable manner both now and in the future. A

functional municipality is defined in this ISP as a municipality that successfully; strive within its financial and administrative capabilities to achieve the five objects of local government as set out in chapter 7 of the Constitution including the objectives on financial management as outlined in the Municipal Financial Management Act (MFMA) which are:

- a) To provide democratic and accountable government for local municipalities
- b) To ensure the provision of service to communities in a sustainable manner
- c) To promote social and economic development
- d) To promote a safe and healthy environment
- e) To encourage the involvement of communities and community organizations in matters of local government
- f) To secure sound and sustainable management of the fiscal and financial affairs of municipalities and municipal entities by establishing norms, standards and other requirements.

1.6 TASKS THAT WERE DEVELOPED TO TAKE SOUTH AFRICA FORWARD FOR THE FIVE 5 YEAR PERIOD

- o Back to Basics Approach: setting clear benchmarks of performance in our efforts to ensure that all municipalities perform their basic responsibilities every day without fail;
- o Responding to the immediate crises;
- o Understanding and responding to the structural challenges;
- o Continuing to build resilient local government institutions and
- o Collectively constructing more rigorous systems of intergovernmental relations.

1.6.1 BACK TO BASICS APPROACH IN DETAIL

1.6.1.1 Governance

- o All municipal council structures must be functional and meet regularly
- o Clear delineation of roles and responsibilities between key leadership structures of the municipality (Executive Mayor, Chief Whip, Speaker and Municipal Manager)
- o Oversight committees must be in place and perform their responsibilities without any interference, e.g. Audit Committee and MPAC
- o Transparency, accountability and regular engagements with Communities

1.6.1.2 Administration

- o All municipalities enforce competency standards for managers and appoint persons with the requisite skills, expertise and qualifications
- o All managers to sign performance agreements and
- o Implement and manage performance management system

1.6.1.3 Sound Financial Management

- o All municipalities to have a functional financial management system
- o Rigorous Internal Controls
- o Cut wasteful expenditure
- o SCM structures and controls with appropriate oversight
- o Cash-backed budgets
- o Post Audit Action Plans are addressed and
- o Act decisively against fraud and corruption.

Table 1.1: Contribution to the District per industry & region

Industry	Chief Albert Luthuli	Msukaligwa	Mkhondo	Dr Pixley Ka Isaka Seme	Lekwa	Dipaliseng	Govan Mbeki
Agriculture	16.2%	19.9%	25.1%	7.2%	14.8%	6.6%	10.1%
Mining	8.1%	11.8%	4.5%	0.7%	11.1%	0.6%	63.3%
Manufacturing	1.7%	4.2%	6.3%	1.0%	6.4%	1.2%	79.3%
Utilities	9.1%	13.3%	10.8%	7.8%	16.6%	5.6%	36.8%
Construction	9.2%	15.4%	10.9%	11.2%	10.3%	3.6%	39.4%
Trade	9.3%	21.2%	14.9%	4.5%	11.6%	4.7%	33.9%
Transport	10.5%	28.5%	13.7%	4.7%	10.2%	3.2%	29.2%
Finance	7.3%	23.7%	11.4%	4.3%	12.4%	2.7%	38.1%
Community services	17.5%	20.9%	12.0%	5.0%	11.3%	3.4%	29.9%
Total	8.8%	15.5%	9.9%	3.3%	10.8%	2.6%	49.0%

CHAPTER 2

SITUATIONAL ANALYSIS

2.1. GEOGRAPHY

The Municipality is located on the eastern escarpment of Mpumalanga Province. The Municipality spans an area of approximately 5,560km², and according to StatsSA 2016 Community Survey, is home to some 187,630 people, which have increased. The Municipality consists of a diverse society that faces various social, economic, environmental and governance challenges. The rural community faces challenges such as lack of access to services like water, good roads, proper sanitation and access to job opportunities. The urban community, on the other hand experiences challenges such as skyrocketing prices for services which cannot be dove-tailed to fit the income levels.

Figure: 2.1 Albert Luthuli Areas - 5,560km²

Cities/Towns: Carolina, Emanzana (previously Badplaas), Elukwatini, Empuluzi, Ekulindeni.

Carolina - Carolina is town situated on the main arterial road from Johannesburg to Eswatini; which is linked to N12, N4, R33 and N17. The town lies in the grass and wetlands region of Mpumalanga province. It is a seat of the Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality; and is an area of mixed farming and small-scale coal mining. The total area of Carolina is 14.66km² with a total estimated population of 16,846 (C.2011).

Emanzana – formerly known as Badplaas, Emanzana is a small town on the R38 in the eastern side of the municipality. It is mostly a tourist town with resorts, hotels, game farms and guest houses. The total area is 37.97km², and the population is estimated to be around 11,080 (C.2011).

Elukwatini – Elukwatini is a semi-urban to rural town incorporating the residential villages of Nhlazatshe and the township Elukwatini. The area is the most populated of the towns of Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality with 41,780 people, which is about 31% of the total population. Elukwatini is a retail town.

Empuluzi – Empuluzi is a town a town to the south of the municipality and borders Mkhondo and Msukaligwa municipalities. The town is a plantations area with one sawmill adjacent to other several sawmills in Mkhondo and Msukaligwa. Empuluzi total area is 11.80km², with a population of 19,547.

Ekulindeni – this lovely little town lies on the southern border of the picturesque Songimvelo Nature Reserve, and it is from this Nature Reserve that most of the town's income is generated. The town lies at the foot of the historic Makhonjwa Mountains, and is home to the deserted Msauli asbestos mine. The D481 road is the main thoroughfare connecting the town with the rest of the municipality and outside world. The total area of the town is 3.15km² with a population of 4,871.

2.2. DEMOGRAPHY

Analytical Overview of Population Dynamics. This section will define the demographic variables as each one of them influences the shape the Integrated Development Plan (IDP) will take, in order to respond to the situational realities existing in Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality. This aims to highlight the state of development in the Municipality as well as the demographic analysis of the municipal area. Further to this chapter, various statistical data relevant to the Municipality were sourced from the Statistics South Africa, 2011 and 2016 Census information, and it is acknowledged sources such municipalities.co.za

Improvement with household services in Chief Albert Luthuli between 2011 and 2016 according to the CS (Community Survey) of Stats SA – some challenges, however, remained in terms of access to flush/chemical toilets, as well as increased backlog numbers in piped water and informal dwellings.

Number of informal dwellings increased from 2 857 in 2011 to 5 206 in 2016 – increase of 2 349 households and 9.7% of the households still lived in informal dwellings.

In 2016, the number of households with access to piped water was 43 656 or 81.6% of total households. This was lower/worse than the percentage access in 2011 and 18.4% of households still without access to piped water in 2016.

Number of households with access to flush/chemical toilets deteriorated between 2011 and 2016. Only 12 559 households or 23.5% of total households with access – 1 801 households without any toilet facilities.

The share of households connected to electricity improved to a level of 96.4% in 2016, however, 1 902 households not connected to electricity at all.

Fifth - lowest/worst in the province with household services index (2019) but improving trend between 2016 and 2019. Questions however, around the quality of some of the services. Lack of safe and reliable water supply.

Chief Albert Luthuli ranks fourth in Mpumalanga in the Out of Order Index by News24 and 52 over 100 (where 100 is the best).

2.3. POPULATION

According to Stats SA (2016 Community Survey - CS), the population of Chief Albert Luthuli increased from 186 010 in 2011 to 187 630 people in 2016 – tenth largest population in the province and 16.5% of Gert Sibande's population.

Youth population (15-34 years) formed 38% of the total population in 2016.

In 2016, the share of the female population was 52.9% and that of males 47.1%.

Population grew by 1 620 between 2011 and 2016, a population growth rate of only 0.2% per annum (p.a.), which was considerably lower than the annual average economic growth rate of 2.9% p.a. over the same period.

The population number for 2021 is estimated at 184 682 or 14.6% of Gert Sibande's population.

CSIR Green Book population projection for 2030 is 173 189 people or 13.2% of Gert Sibande's population – will put pressure on infrastructure, service delivery and economic/employment opportunities.

Between 2011 and 2016, the number of households in Chief Albert Luthuli increased from 47 705 to 53 480 (almost 6 000 households). The household size declined from 3.9 to 3.5 over the same period.

Population movement in the region appears to follow the pattern of economic activity and access to urban services, with net outflow towards Gauteng, as well as the Emalahleni / Middelburg area, Mbombela, and Ermelo.

2.3.1. MIGRATION

Migration of population from the Municipality is an important contributing factor to the decrease of population growth. Migration has implications for the Labour force, social services, infrastructure, housing and backlogs in basic household services. The greatest population concentrations (approximately 80%) occur in rural villages in the eastern regions. The two main service centres (Carolina and Emanzana) are home to approximately 27 900 people (15%). It is followed by the farming and forestry areas of the Municipality which is home to approximately 9 300 people (5%).

2.3.2. POPULATION DENSITY

The Map below indicates the population density within Chief Albert Luthuli LM in terms of people per hectare:

Figure 2.2: Population density

This assist in indicating areas of residence within Chief Albert Luthuli LM. The average annual growth rate is 0.2% with a population size 187 629 according to the 2016 community survey. There are 53 480 households within Chief Albert Luthuli with a growth rate of 2.3%. According to Map 3, the main population is located (areas with a higher population density) in rural areas. Carolina services a vast hinterland consisting of agriculture, forestry and mining. Scattered parts of the eastern areas of the Municipality; (Dundonald, Empuluzi and Fernie areas). These areas will be where the need arises for goods and services such as water, sanitation, electricity, and housing as well as social infrastructures such as schools, clinics and police stations. Roads in areas with a high population require higher maintenance due to an increase in traffic volumes.

2.3.3. AGE PROFILE

Figure 3 below illustrates the age pyramid for Chief Albert Luthuli LM. The Municipality has a sizeable female population (53% of the population), with most of the population (56%) can be classified as 'working age'. The Municipality also has a significant number of people below the age of 14 (36%). Those between the ages 15-25 are considered teen and early adulthood and constitute 24% of the population. Whilst the older population of 65 and above represents 7% of the population. The current age profile implies that the active labour-force (15-64) which represents 56% of the population must work and support 67% of the population as the age group of 0-14, age group 15-25 and age group of 65 and above are an economically dependent burden in the sense that they are non-productive members of the society and must be supported by the economically active labour-force and the state in the case of old age grant earners

Figure 3: Chief Albert Luthuli Age Pyramid, 2011

2.3.4. GENDER COMPOSITION

Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality's male/female split in population was 48% males and 52% females per 100. The Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality has significantly more females (52%) than males, when compared to a typical stable population. This is most probably an area with high male out migration to look for work elsewhere.

Table 2.1: Gender Composition

Female Total 14-34 yrs.	Male Total 14-44 yrs.	Total	%	Female Total	Male Total	Sex ratio	
37 259	34 032	71 291	38,0	99 244	88 386	89,1	38 131
	Population	187 630		52%	48%		

2.4. HOUSEHOLD POPULATION

The Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality comprise of 53 480 households according to the 2016 Community Survey. This represented a 2.3% annual growth from the 47 705 from the 2011 Census. Estimated number of households in 2021 is 53 480, with the projected number expected to be down to 50 202 by 2030 (CSIR Green book).

Figure 4: Number of Households

2.4. HEALTH PROFILE

According to the Department of Health, the HIV prevalence rate of Chief Albert Luthuli was measured at 34.6% in 2013 (latest available figure) – fifth lowest of all the municipal areas in the province. The HIV prevalence rate decreased from 42.4% in 2012. A concern worth noting is the high prevalence of HIV in the Municipality that means the 43,2% of the population requires treatment for HIV, and food to support the use of the treatment. This technically relates to the demand for work, so that people can sustain themselves without expecting the State to support them with food parcels, etc. The economic outlook of the people of the Municipality tells the story of their ability to pay for services.

The Municipality has a HIV/AIDS Framework in place, which is implemented as an intervention strategy that will bring about significant changes in the incidence and prevalence of HIV. The Local AIDS Council (LAC) is the last level of the purposefully formed coordination structures as a strategic response to the pandemic ravaging communities. It follows the National AIDS Council, the Provincial AIDS Council, and the District AIDS Council.

It is imperative that the political and administrative leadership is empowered on HIV and AIDS to ensure that oversight, monitoring and evaluation are implemented. In addition, it should also ensure that the activities of the LAC are strengthened. Strategies to prevent HIV infection are in place but need to be increased - these include the distribution of condoms and encouraging the use thereof; education and distribution of information regarding HIV and AIDS; and medical male circumcision. More people are coming forward for counseling and testing for HIV. Changing sexual behavior is one of the few potentially effective ways in combating the spread of HIV/AIDS and behavioral risk factors a National HIV Survey showed that the proportion of people

reporting multiple sexual partners seems to increase.

2.5. EDUCATION PROFILE

Chief Albert Luthuli's Grade 12 pass rate decreased slightly from 80.1% in 2014 to 78.0% in 2021, which was the fifth highest of the municipal areas in the province. It improved between 2020 and 2021 by 6.6 percentage points, and in 2021 it reached very good level.

The area also improved its admission rate to university/degree studies from 28.4% in 2020 - joint fifth - lowest in the province) to 35.1% in 2021, which was the third - highest of the 17 municipal areas.

The challenge is to accommodate the educated young people in the area - inadequate economic opportunities. Provision of adequate educational & recreational infrastructure as well as skills development activities to meet the needs of the community.

In 2020, the functional literacy rate (81.0%) was the fifth - lowest in the province but showed an improving trend.

Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality is predominantly a municipality whose population does not have tertiary education. Of the total population of the area, only 5% has university degree qualification; 33% have matric, 30% with some secondary education. 15% of the population has primary education, and 15% do not have any education. According to the 2016 CS of Stats SA the population in Chief Albert Luthuli aged 20+ completed grade 12, increased from 31 122 in 2011 to 38 131 (increase of 7 009) in 2016 – an increase of 22.5% in the relevant period. Chief Albert Luthuli's grade 12 pass rate decreased from 80.9% in 2016 to 79.0% in 2017 which was the seventh - highest of the municipal areas of the province. The area achieved an admission rate to university/degree studies of 28.6% in 2017. The challenge is to accommodate the educated young people in the area – a matric is no “ticket” to a job in the labour market – employability of the youth. Provision of adequate educational, recreational infrastructure and skills development to meet the needs of the community

Figure 5: Education profile (Stats-SA 2016)

2.5.1. Matric Performance per Circuit

The performance per circuit in the last three (3) years [2019 – 2021]; shows that during the first year of COVID, four (4) Circuits performed between 70% - 75%, except for Badplaas with a performance of 62%. in 2021, four Circuits – Badplaas, Carolina, Dundonald, Mpuluzi – registered improved performance from the previous year, but only Dundonald and Mpuluzi bridged the 80% mark: with 84.3% and 82.5% respectively. Mashishila Circuit is the only circuit that recorded a drop from 2020, recording 72.5% in 2021. This in essence means that schools in Dundonald and Mpuluzi were able to return to pre-COVID performances in 2021.

Figure 6: Performance by Circuit (DOE: 2019-2021)

2.5.2. Higher Education and Training

The Gert Sibande TVET College has one campus in the Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality area. Situated in Glenmore near Mayflower, the Sibanesetfu TVET College offers courses in Office Administration, Electrical Infrastructure Construction, Civil Engineering Construction, Engineering and related design, Marketing, Computer Technology, Hospitality, and General Management.

2.6. HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX

HDI is the combination of three basic dimensions of human development: A long and healthy life, knowledge and a decent standard of living. On a technical note, the HDI can have a maximum value of 1, indicating a very high level of human development, while the minimum value is 0, indicating no human development.

2.7. EQUALITY: GINI COEFFICIENT

The Gini coefficient is a summary statistic of income inequality. It varies from 0 to 1 Gini-coefficient. The Gini-coefficient is one of the most used measures of income inequality. The Gini-coefficient is derived from the Lorenz curve, which is a graphical depiction of income distribution. The Lorenz curve is a graphical presentation of the relationship between the cumulative percentage of income and the cumulative percentage of population. The coefficient varies from 0 (in the case of perfect equality where all households earn equal income) to 1 (in the case where one household earns all the income). South Africa has one of the highest imbalanced income distributions in the world. The national; the Gini-coefficient was calculated to be 0.63 in 2015. Despite improving (declining) from a level of 0.66 in 2001, the most recent national level still reflects a more unequal income distribution. Mpumalanga 0.61 Limpopo on 0.59, the lowest inequality and Gauteng

(0.64) the most unequal. In 2015, Gert Sibande registered the highest Gini-coefficient of 0.61 among the three districts. Share of income earned by poorest 40% in South Africa, Mpumalanga & districts Gert 7.5% in 2011 and 2015, 7.8%.

2.8. POVERTY

Poverty level is still high although it dropped slightly in 2016 to 10.3% down from 10.9% in 2011. Grants and other subsidies received as a percentage of total income accounted for 75.1% in 2011 and in 2016 the contribution of grants and other poverty alleviation subsidies.

Table 2.2: Poverty Index

		2011		2016	2016 cs	Sex ratio	
Chief Albert Luthuli	2015 Grants and subsidies received as a % of Total income	Poverty headcount Intensity of poverty	%	headcount of poverty	Intensity of poverty	Ratio	Completed matric over 20 yrs. old
B4	75,1%	10,9%		10,3%	41,8%	89.1	

2.9. CRIME

The IHS Composite Crime Index makes use of the official SAPS data, which is reported in 27 crime categories (ranging from murder to crime injuries). These 27 categories are divided into two groups according to the nature of the crime: i.e., violent crimes and property crimes. Crime prevalence in Albert Luthuli Municipality involves stock theft, commercial crimes, theft and burglary, murder, sexual offences, assault, robbery and drugs.

2.10. LOCAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

2.10.1. ECONOMY

Chief Albert Luthuli's contribution to the Mpumalanga economy in 2020 was 2.5% – seventh - smallest economy in the province, while the contribution to the district economy was like the contribution of Mkhondo at 9.4% in the same period. Community Services, Agriculture and Transport are the main economic contributors into the Gert Sibande economy.

Average annual economic growth rate for Chief Albert Luthuli was 2.4% p.a. over the period 1996 to 2020. For the period 2015-2020 the economy contracted by 0.5% p.a. in line with the weak economic climate in the country. Estimated contraction in 2020 of between -5% & -6% due to the COVID-19 lockdown. Construction, transport, manufacturing and trade & tourism most severely affected.

Expected growth of about 4% in 2021 from a low base, as the country emerges from lockdown and the economy discovers its niche under the new normal. The estimated average annual GDP growth for Chief Albert Luthuli between 2020 and 2025 is relatively low at 1.4% per annum.

In 2020, the size of the economy was estimated at almost R9.8 billion in current prices; - community services, mining, trade (including tourism) and finance were the largest industries in the economy of Chief Albert Luthuli.

Together these four industries contributed almost three quarters to the local economy, while industries such as mining, agriculture, as well as tourism enjoyed comparative advantage. In 2015, tourism spend totalled R659.9 million or equal to 8.9% of the local GDP. It decreased to only R311.4 million, which was equal to only 3.2% of the local GDP.

CONTRIBUTION TO THE PROVINCIAL ECONOMY BY MUNICIPAL AREA

2.11.2. GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT

The economic performance of Chief Albert Luthuli LM will be evaluated by making use of secondary data obtained from the Quantec Resource Database and Statistics SA. In order to determine the value and performance of the various economic sectors, growth rates were calculated in terms of expansion or contraction of the economy in terms of GVA values

The economic performance of a region can be measured by Gross Value Added (GVA) in terms of, factors such as production activities. The GVA can be used to provide oversight of the region's economy, in this case, the economy of Chief Albert Luthuli LM. In addition, it can provide insight into the structural composition of the economy as well as the growth rate of production. This allows us to identify the comparative advantages for the given region, to determine the vulnerability (concentration) of the economy and the overall welfare of the community.

2.11.3. GROSS VALUE ADD (GVA) AND SECTOR COMPOSITION

The purpose of this section is to provide an updated Economic Profile using the latest economic data available, and additional economic techniques were utilized in order to add value to the previous profile. This provides an overview of the current economic situation in the study area. This overview incorporates sectoral performances and composition as well as overall growth performance in the economy.

2.11.4. LABOUR

Of notable concern is the high unemployment rate amongst people in the 14 to 64 age group; the age group of economic productivity and employability. In 2016 about 36 000 people in this age group were not working (Statistic SA- CS2016). The overall unemployment rate in the Municipality is 36.4%. Of that total, 42% is for female unemployment, and 28% for male. Youth unemployment is a massive 45%, influenced by a variety of factors such as lack of job / economic opportunities on the one hand to lack of skills required by the job market in the other. The highest number of unemployed (54%) is in Ward 12 (Ekulindeni area) and the lowest number (20%) is in Ward 21 (Carolina area).

2.11.5. POVERTY, INEQUALITY AND UNEMPLOYMENT

The high unemployment rate amongst people in the 14 to 64 age group, being the economic productive years, is a noteworthy concern. In 2011 about 36,000 people in this age group were not working (Statistic SA 2011). The unemployment rate in the Municipality is 35,4% (2011); females 42% and males 28% - and the unemployment rate for young people is alarmingly high at 45%, which is mainly influenced by the lack of economic opportunities in the municipal area. The highest number of unemployed (54%) is in Ward 12 (Ekulindeni area) and the lowest number (20%) is in Ward 21 (Carolina area). Employment in the Municipality increased with 8,600 jobs between 2001 and 2011, and the number of employed individuals is 29 141 (0.12%). The percentage of employment in formal sector was 65.6%, and in the informal sector 21,9% (StatsSA 2011). Unemployment rate (%) 35,4%.

2.11.6. COVID-19 IMPACT ON THE TRIPLE CHALLENGES – POVERTY, INEQUALITY, AND UNEMPLOYMENT

Unemployment, poverty, and inequality observations

Increase in both the provincial unemployment rate (expanded definition) and poverty rate since 2015, in line with the weak economic environment and low provincial economic growth rate. Inequality also deteriorating the last couple of years if one looks at the share of income by poorest 40% of MP households as indicator. Mpumalanga's unemployment rate (expanded definition) was very high at 49.7% in Q3 of 2021 (the highest ever) and increased from 46.5% in Q2 2021 – fourth - highest of the 9 provinces. Mpumalanga's unemployment rate according to the strict definition 37.5% in Q3 of 2021 – the highest ever. At the end of Q3 2021, the expanded unemployment rate of males (45.4%) in the province was lower than the female unemployment rate of 54.2%.

The expanded unemployment rate of youth of working age (15-34 years) in Mpumalanga was 65.4%, whilst the unemployment rate of adults (35-64 years) was 34.1%.

At 71.0%, the female youth unemployment rate was considerably higher than the male youth unemployment rate of 60.5%.

The expanded unemployment rate of the 18-24-year age cohort was 79.2% in Q3 2021 and the 18-24-year-old female unemployment rate was 83.6%.

Almost 142 000 net job losses in Mpumalanga in the period 1 April 2020 to 30 September 2021 with high losses in community services, construction, and trade. SA's net job losses 2.1 million in the same period.

Net provincial job losses in the first 9 months of the year almost 44 200. Only manufacturing, private households, transport, and utilities gained jobs in the relevant period. The job losses in finance, trade, and mining are of concern.

Graduates' unemployment rate relatively low. Very high unemployment rate for people without a diploma or degree

LABOUR MARKET IN CHIEF ALBERT LUTHULI

The expanded unemployment rate of Chief Albert Luthuli deteriorated from 42.6% in 2016 to 43.6% in 2020. It is very high in comparison with the 6% target by 2030.

In 2020, the expanded unemployment rate for females was 47.3% and that of males 39.6%.
In 2020, the expanded youth - 15-34 year - unemployment rate was 58.4%.

There is concern about the high share of unemployed youth & especially females – there appears to be a mismatch between their offering of education and skills (or lack thereof) and the demand of the labour market, but also a lack of investment to create jobs.

Importance of quality and relevant education and training in line with the economic needs of the province to improve their employability but also a need to retain businesses and attract new investment. Importance and relevance of the UMP and TVETs in this regard.

In 2020, Chief Albert Luthuli contributed 2.5% to total employment in the province. Between 2016 & 2020, employment declined by 0.3% p.a. The average annual employment growth deteriorated compared with the 2011 to 2015 increase of 4.9% per annum.

The job losses in 2020, due to the COVID-19 lockdown, was estimated at 2 457. In the 4-year period between 2016 and 2020, Chief Albert Luthuli lost 342 jobs, which clearly demonstrates the devastation COVID-19 brought to the labour market in 2020. In 2020, the largest employing industries in Chief Albert Luthuli were trade (including tourism), community services, manufacturing, finance and agriculture.

GRAPHICAL ILLUSTRATION OF EMPLOYMENT BY INDUSTRY

Total employment number must rise from 1.24 million in Q4 2019 and to more than 2.1 million by 2030 – more than a million jobs required between 2019 and 2030 of which half a million should be between 2019 and 2024.

Revised the more than 70 000 jobs pa (MEGDP) to an average of 105 000 new & sustainable jobs to be created annually between 2019 and 2030 – employment growth of more than 6.0% per annum required. The unemployment rate (strict definition) must decrease to 6% by 2030 in line with NDP & Vision 2030. These targets challenging to achieve, given the weak economic environment and performance nationally and provincially the last couple of years and also the negative impact of COVID-19 and the lockdown. Mpumalanga achieved (as an average) more or less a quarter of its job creation target over the last 10 years.

Job losses in 8 of the 10 employment industries in 2020 (mainly due to COVID-19 and the lockdown). Only agriculture and finance recorded job gains in 2020.

Job losses impact negatively on consumer spending and eventually also poverty and inequality. The provincial poverty rate (LBPL – lower bound poverty line) was 50.2% in 2020, a level last seen in 2009. Despite recovery in the provincial labour market in Q3 2020 & Q2 2021, provincial net job losses of more than 62 000 were recorded in Q3 2021, the fifth-largest job losses among the 9 provinces. The Q3 2021 provincial employment level of 1.1 million is 141 816 jobs short of the 1.25 million persons employed in Q1 2020 before the lockdown was instituted.

2.11.6. ECONOMIC OPPORTUNITIES

Economic opportunities in Chief Albert Luthuli are supported by the presence of national and regional roads network, availability of a labour force, and the potential around the key economic drivers in the area.

Around Agriculture, opportunities exist around agro-processing and the completion of the local Agro-Hub in Dundonald. Tourism and cultural tourism offer a huge potential for economic growth. Cultural tourism is particularly poised to benefit local Cooperatives and SMMEs.

Rejuvenation of township businesses with initiatives to transform townships and villages from labour and consumption reserves into thriving productive investment hubs, through SMME-support and Cooperative's development on the provision of services for the social safety net.

MPUMALANGA ECONOMIC CLUSTERS AND POVERTY NODES

CATALYTIC PROJECTS OF THE MERRP

The Mpumalanga Economic Reconstruction & Recovery Plan (MERRP) seeks to address the negative impact of COVID-19 on the provincial economy and livelihoods of the Mpumalanga citizens.

The MERRP aims at re-igniting the provincial economy through focusing on the following seven priority interventions:

- a. Planned 'massive' rollout of infrastructure.
- b. Growth through industrialization, localization, and export promotion - roll-out of the Mpumalanga Industrial Development Plan (MIDP) i.e., establishment of 3 Industrial Technology Parks, Nkomazi SEZ & Mpumalanga International Fresh Produce Market
- c. Sufficient, secure, and reliable energy supply and Green Economy initiatives.
- d. Employment stimulus - i.e., increased access to funding for SMMEs and Cooperatives.
- e. Growth and recovery of tourism.

- f. Agriculture and Food Security - increase in agricultural production, for example Phezukomkhono Mlimi & Zonda Indlala).
- g. Gender and economic inclusion.

Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality must implement the Mpumalanga Provincial Government's prioritized catalytic intervention projects. This must be done with a clear understanding of the local economic activities and the economic drivers of Chief Albert Luthuli, taking cue from the identified government interventions, which are:

- 6 Rehabilitation of the Coal Haulage Network
- 7 Improvement of tourism road infrastructure
- 8 Mpumalanga International Fresh Produce Market
- 9 Upgrading of Moloto Road
- 10 Integrated Human Settlements
- 11 Disaster Relief Intervention
- 12 Establishment of the Nkomazi SEZ
- 13 Establishment of the Petrochemical Industrial Technology Park
- 14 Rejuvenation of Ekandustria
- 15 Growing the circular economy
- 16 Green cluster – Just Transition Programme
- 17 Social enterprise Development Programme
- 18 Food nutrition programme
- 19 EPWP
- 20 Siyatentela Roads Maintenance Programme
- 21 National Youth Service
- 22 Paving of township and municipal roads
 - Emerging Contractor Development Programme
 - Skills development through incubation
 - God's Window Skywalk
 - Barberton Makhonjwa Mountains World Heritage Site
 - Railway Heritage Tourism Project
 - Phezukomkhono Mlimi Crop Production
 - Livestock Development Programme
 - Zonda Indlala Horticulture Programme
 - Inclusive Agro-processing Industry & Market Access Programme
 - Release of state land for Agricultural Development Programme

District wide high impact projects

- Employment stimulus and inclusion of women and youth
- Private sector investment initiatives

2.11.6.1. ECONOMIC DRIVERS FOR THE MUNICIPALITY

*** Community Services Sector**

The main economic driver in the Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality is Community Services Sector, in the form of the various government departments that are the main employers, the Municipality included. The government job intervention programmes like the Expanded Public Works Programme (EPWP) projects, Community Works Programme (CWP) projects, Siyathuthuka Programme, and social security grants through the Department of Social Development contribute immensely in the household income.

*** Retail Sector**

The Retail Sector is another key economic driver in the Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality. There are shopping precincts in Carolina, at The Crossing (Elukwatini), Emanzana, and Mayflower/Fernie. These retail chains contribute towards job creation and food security.

*** Agriculture and Forestry Sector**

Commercial farming is largely exercised by established farmers, who are mostly from the White population group. They are found in the Carolina-Emanzana grassland area. The main activities are grain farming (white maize and yellow maize, varieties of legumes, (sunflowers), potatoes, and cattle feed. In addition, there are livestock farmers as well who farm with mainly cattle and sheep, but there has been a growth in game farming as well. Forestry companies such as Komatiland Forests and York Timber operate the timber and plantations operations, which stretch from Diepdale to Carolina, covering all the plantations along the N17 from Oshoek, Lochiel, The Brook and Milliken.

*** Mining Sector**

Mines submit their Social and Labour Plans (SLPs) to the Municipality. These plans mainly cover the Human Resources Programme; the Local Economic Development Programme; and the Management of Downscaling and Closure Programme. The Human Resource Programme mainly focuses on the mine's internal staff skills development plan. Learnerships and bursaries for internal and external applicants, and the budget allocation for such programme are stipulated in the Plans.

- o The Local Economic Development Programme is funded by the mine's budget equivalent to 1% of its pre-tax profits. The figure fluctuates and differs from one mine to another.
- o The Management of Downscaling and Closure Programme provides for cases of retrenchments by the mine. This must, where possible, practicable and reasonable cover the skilling of people either in basic life skills, financial skills and SMME training.

*** Tourism Sector**

The Municipality has vast prime tourism real estate based on communal and land claim areas. The inherent development potentials are as a result of the Municipality's location in the Mpumalanga 'Grass and Wetland Region' which is a well-established nature-based tourism destination. Tourists are offered a wide range of tourism activities within the Municipality and in its immediate surrounding areas.

The Makhonjwa Mountain world heritage site, the Skurweberg mountain pass from Machadodorp to Emanzana and from Emanzana via the Nelshoogte Pass to Barberton; the Rooihoogte Pass from Emanzana to Lochiel, and the Matotoland Lake District in Chrissiesmeer. The communal land areas in the Municipality provide further opportunities for guided horse trails and hikes as well as easy access to tourism products based on local traditional culture (Emaswati cultures) in the nearby villages, including overnight 'home stays.'

Table 2.3: Economic Sectors and contribution

Sector	Activities	Contribution to Employment	Contribution to Economy
Community Services	Public administration, government departments / agencies, municipalities; membership of organizations; recreation/culture/sport; washing/dry-	28,8%	37,1%

Sector	Activities	Contribution to Employment	Contribution to Economy
	cleaning of textiles and fur products; hairdressing/beauty treatment; funeral and related activities		
Trade/Retail	Wholesale and commission; retail trade; repair of personal household goods; sale/maintenance/repair of motor vehicles/motorcycles; hotels/restaurants/bars/canteens/ camping sites/ other provision of short-stay accommodation	21.4%	13.6%
Agriculture	Establishments primarily engaged in farming activities, including commercial hunting and game propagation, and forestry, logging, and fishing. Types of primary production: Micro enterprise broiler producers; small holder vegetable producers; small scale fruit growers; dry land maize and sugar beans farming; cattle farming. Secondary activities: sawmills, game farming.	16.8% (decreasing)	11.2%
Mining	Extracting, beneficiating of minerals occurring naturally, including solids, liquids, crude petroleum, gases; underground and surface mining, quarries, operation of oil and gas wells and all supplemental activities for dressing and beneficiating for ores and other crude materials	7.6%	7.9%
Construction	Site preparation, building of complete constructions or parts thereof, civil engineering, building installation, building completion, renting of construction or demolition equipment with operators	4.9%	2.9%

Table 2.4: Planned Council Meetings

Municipal name	MII F	Council Sittings 2022 - 2027	Frequency of Council meetings					Total
			2022/23	2023/24	2024/25	2025/26	2026/27	
Chief Albert Luthuli Local Municipality	B4	20	4	4	4	4	4	20
Total		20	4	4	4	4	4	20

2.13. BASIC SERVICE DELIVERY

2.13.1. WATER PROVISION

Figure 11 outlines the type of access households have to water at their dwellings. About 23% of the households in all three study areas have access to water inside their dwellings. Compared to the District and Province, Chief Albert Luthuli LM has a significant number of households with no access to piped water.

Source: Urban-Econ Calculations based on Quantec Easydata, 2018 and StatisticsSA, 2011

Map 8 indicates the areas with below basic, or no access to water. Basic access to water is defined as having access to a minimum of 25 litres of water per person per day. The maximum distance to have access to water is 200 metres. The water should also be available on a regular daily basis (Department of Water Affairs and Forestry, 1994).

Table 2.6: No Access to water

Description	2017-18	2018-2019	2019-20	2020-21
	Actual No.	Actual No.	Actual No.	Actual No.
Water: (above min level)				
Piped water inside dwelling	12 429	12 429	20240	20240
Piped water inside yard (but not in dwelling)	28 303	28 303	22644	22644
Using public tap (within 200m from dwelling)	6 330	6 330	4821	4821
Other water supply (within 200m)				
<i>Minimum Service Level and Above sub-total</i>	47 062	47 062	47 705	47 705
<i>Minimum Service Level and Above Percentage</i>	88%	88%	89%	89%
Water: (below min level)				
Using public tap (more than 200m from dwelling)				
Other water supply (more than 200m from dwelling)	6 418	6 418	5775	5775
No water supply				
<i>Below Minimum Service Level sub-total</i>	6 418	6 418	5775	5775
<i>Below Minimum Service Level Percentage</i>	12%	12%	11%	11%
Total number of households*	53 480	53 480	53 480	53 480
* - inclusive of informal settlements				

Source: Statistics South Africa, 2011 via MapAble, 2019

The areas that have the highest proportion of households with below basic access to water or no access to water are in the eastern areas. These areas also coincide with the areas which have lower levels of access to electricity. Figure 12 indicates the source of water for households in the Province, District and Local Municipality. The primary sources of water in all three study areas are either through a local or regional water scheme or by means of a borehole.

Figure 2.2: Basic and No Access to Water

Source: Urban-Econ Calculations based on Quantec Easydata, 2018 and StatisticsSA, 2011

Map 9: Source of Water - Majority of Households, 2011

Source: Statistics South Africa, 2011 via MapAble, 2017

According to Chief Albert Luthuli LM IDP (2017/18), there is a water provision backlog of 43 656 households. Map 9 above shows that the majority get water from a borehole and river.

2.13.2. FREE BASIC WATER

COMMENT ON FREE BASIC SERVICES AND INDIGENT SUPPORT:

Free basic services are provided to qualifying indigent households. In the 2020/21 financial year an average of 90% of qualifying households received free basic water and sanitation services, 16% of qualifying households in the Municipality's supply area (Carolina and part of Emanzana) received free basic electricity, and less than 1% of qualifying households received the discounted refuse removal service. Due to the rural nature of the municipal area, it is not possible to provide the refuse removal service to all households.

T 3.6.2

Free Basic Services to Low Income Households										
	Number of households									
	Total	Households earning less than R1,100 per month								
		Total	Free Basic Water		Free Basic Sanitation		Free Basic Electricity		Free Basic Refuse	
		Access	%	Access	%	Access	%	Access	%	
2015-16	47	47	1 300	3%	34 606	73%	1 300	3%	1 278	3%
2017-16	53	53	1 759	3%	40 591	76%	1 759	3%	536	1%
2017-18	53	53	1 759	3%	40 591	76%	1 759	3%	536	1%

T 3.6.3

2.14. SANITATION

Figure 13 indicates the toilet facilities available to households in the study areas. Less than 20% of households have access to toilets while 21% of households have access to flush toilets, while the majority of households use a pit latrine with ventilation (38%). In 2011, Chief Albert Luthuli LM had 473 households still using the bucket system.

Table 2.7: Access to Sanitation

Description	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21
	Actual No.	Actual No.	Actual No.	Actual No.
<u>Sanitation/sewerage: (above minimum level)</u>				
Flush toilet (connected to sewerage)	10 245	10 245	10 744	10 744
Flush toilet (with septic tank)	813	813	2032	2032
Chemical toilet	1 500	1 500	2000	2000
Pit toilet (ventilated)	26 519	26 519	20062	20062
Other toilet provisions (above min.service level)	12 572	12 572	17100	17100
<i>Minimum Service Level and Above sub-total</i>	51 649	51 649	51 938	51 938
<i>Minimum Service Level and Above Percentage</i>	96,6%	96,6%	97,1%	97,1%
<u>Sanitation/sewerage: (below minimum level)</u>				
Bucket toilet	0	0	0	0
Other toilet provisions (below min. service level)	30	30	30	30
No toilet provisions	1 801	1 801	1 542	1 542
<i>Below Minimum Service Level sub-total</i>	1 831	1 831	1 542	1 542
<i>Below Minimum Service Level Percentage</i>	3,4%	3,4%	3,3%	3,3%
Total households	53 480	53 480	53 480	53 480

Source: Urban Econ Calculations based on StatsSA, 2011 and Community Survey, 2016 via Quantec, 2018

Figure 14 above compares the proportion of households with access to a pit latrine with ventilation and without ventilation for 2011 and 2016. This information was obtained by using the community survey from StatsSA 2016 and population census 2011. There has been a reduction in the proportion of households who

use a pit latrine without ventilation, and an increase in the percentage of households who have access to a pit latrine with ventilation. There is a backlog of 13 603 households for sanitation provision

Map 10 indicates the proportion of households in Chief Albert Luthuli LM with below basic or no access to sanitation services. Providing basic sanitation means *“the provision of an appropriate basic sanitation facility which is environmentally sustainable, easily accessible to a household and a consumer, the sustainable operation of the facility, including the safe removal of human waste, grey-water and wastewater from the premises where this is appropriate and necessary, and the communication and local monitoring of good sanitation, hygiene and related practices”* (Department of Water and Sanitation, 2016)

2.15. ELECTRICITY

Access to electricity is measured on whether a household has access to electricity for cooking, heating and light. The majority of households have access to electricity for lighting purposes. However, less than half of the population in Chief Albert Luthuli LM has access to electricity for heating and cooking purposes.

Map 7 indicates the areas in Chief Albert Luthuli LM where households have no access to electricity for lighting purposes. Areas, where more than 50% of households have no access to electricity for lighting, include Empuluzi, Dundonald, Elukwatini, Nhlazatje and Tjakastad.

Map 7: No Access to Electricity: Lighting, 2011

Source: Statistics South Africa, 2011 via MapAble, 2017

Based on the Community Survey (StatsSA, 2016), access to electricity for lighting has improved in the Province, District as well as the Local Municipality.

According to the Chief Albert Luthuli LM Annual report of 2020/21, the municipality has an electrification backlog of 1 800 households.

Table 2.8: Access to Electricity

Description	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21
	Actual No.	Actual No.	Actual No.	Actual No.
<u>Energy: (above minimum level)</u>				
Electricity (at least min-service level)	50 998	50 998	50 998	50 998
Electricity - prepaid (min-service level)	309	309	339	339
<i>Minimum Service Level and Above sub-total</i>	51 307	51 307	51 337	51 337
<i>Minimum Service Level and Above Percentage</i>	95,9%	95,9%	96%	96%
<u>Energy: (below minimum level)</u>				
Electricity (< min-service level)	271	271	271	271
Electricity - prepaid (< min. service level)	0	0	0	0
Other energy sources	1 902	1 902	1 872	1 872
<i>Below Minimum Service Level sub-total</i>	2 173	2 173	2 143	2 143
<i>Below Minimum Service Level Percentage</i>	4,1%	4,1%	4,0%	4,0%
Total number of households	53 480	53 480	53 480	53 480

Challenges

Theft and vandalism of electricity infrastructure;
 Exceeding of Notified Maximum Demand;
 Shortage of own plant machinery (crane truck);
 Shortage of Staff;
 Unavailability of Master Plan and Operation & Maintenance Plans; and Ageing of infrastructure

2.16. REFUSE REMOVAL

The majority of households in all three study areas have their own refuse dump. In Chief Albert Luthuli LM, only 23 % of households have their refuse removed by the local authority at least once a week.

Table 2.9: Access to Refuse Removal

SOLID WASTE SERVICE DELIVERY LEVELS				
DESCRIPTION	HOUSEHOLDS			
	2017-18	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21
	ACTUAL NO.	Actual No.	Actual No.	Actual No.
<u>SOLID WASTE REMOVAL: (MINIMUM LEVEL)</u>				
REMOVED AT LEAST ONCE A WEEK	12909	12909	13410	13410
MINIMUM SERVICE LEVEL AND ABOVE				
SUB-TOTAL	8 041	12909	13410	13410
MINIMUM SERVICE LEVEL AND ABOVE				
PERCENTAGE	15,0%	27	27	27
<u>SOLID WASTE REMOVAL: (BELOW MINIMUM LEVEL)</u>				
REMOVED LESS FREQUENTLY THAN ONCE A WEEK	516	516	1314	1314
USING COMMUNAL REFUSE DUMP		3 522	3 522	3 522
USING OWN REFUSE DUMP	33 922	33 922	33 922	33 922
OTHER RUBBISH DISPOSAL	119	119	119	119
NO RUBBISH DISPOSAL	7 360	7 360		
BELOW MINIMUM SERVICE LEVEL SUB-TOTAL	45 439	45 439	45439	45439
BELOW MINIMUM SERVICE LEVEL				
PERCENTAGE	85,0%	73	73	73
TOTAL NUMBER OF HOUSEHOLDS	53 480	53480	53480	53480
<i>T 3.4.2</i>				

Map 11 indicates the proportion of households within the Chief Albert Luthuli LM who receive less than basic, or no refuse disposal services. According to the National Policy for the Provision of Basic Refuse Removal Services for Indigent Households (Department of Water and Environmental Affairs, 2010), basic refuse removal can be defined as: *"The most appropriate level of waste removal service provided based on-site specific circumstances. Such a basic level of services is attained when a local municipality provides or facilitates waste disposal through:*

- On-site appropriate and regularly supervised disposal in areas designated by the municipality (applicable to remote rural areas with low-density settlements and farms by waste management officer)
- Community transfer to central location point (medium density settlements).
- Organized transfer to central location points or kerbside collection (high-density settlements)”

Map 11: Proportion of Household with below Basic or No Access to Refuse Disposal Services, 2011

Figure 16 indicates the change in access to refuse disposal in the three study areas. There has been an overall increase in households who use communal refuse dump, while removal once a week and own refuse dump have not changed much from 2011. However, there is an increase in households who do not have any access to refuse disposal.

Source: Urban Econ Calculations based on StatsSA, 2011 and Community Survey, 2016 via Quantec, 2018

2.17. ROADS AND PUBLIC TRANSPORT

The Public Works section is mainly responsible for maintenance and upgrading of existing roads infrastructure (gravel and surfaced), bridges, and storm water drainage system in the entire Municipality. The maintenance involves activities such as blading, patching of potholes, construction of concrete water channels, laying of kerbs, and re-gravelling in trying to elongate the life-span of the road infrastructure and also create conducive and safely infrastructure for users. Currently the Municipality has a total road network of about 649km of which 81% are considered as gravel roads, and most of the gravel roads are at the worsen situation and located on the rural areas of the municipality as some are bladed to pipeline and eroded due to heavy rainfall.

Challenges

During the 2020/21 financial year, the Roads and Storm Water Section was unable to perform its activities at peak, such as construction of footbridges since there is immensely demand from deep rural areas. This could be in the main be attributed to recurring breakdowns of graders and inadequate heavy/ yellow fleet. Unavailability of other construction machinery also contributed to the Section's failure to carry out its activities effectively. Furthermore, the Section experienced abnormal heavy traffic on municipal owned roads, which shortens the lifespan of infrastructure and development of many potholes, especially in Carolina.

CHAPTER 3

IDP PROCESS

Vision

" The transparent, innovative, and developmental municipality that improves the quality of life of its people."

Mission

To provide a transparent and accountable government by rendering affordable and sustainable services and encouraging economic and social development through community participation.

Value System

The Core Values of the Municipality are: -

- Honesty,
- Transparency,
- Integrity,
- Responsiveness, and
- Accountability.

3.1. Integrated Development Plan

3.1.1. The Process

Integrated development planning is a process through which a municipality, sector departments, various service providers, and interested and affected parties come together to identify development needs, and to outline clear objectives and strategies that serve to guide the allocation and management of resources within the Municipality's jurisdictional area. From this planning process emanates the Municipal Integrated Development Plan (IDP) with its main objective being the improvement of coordination and integration of planning, budgeting and development within the municipal area. The IDP aligns the local development agenda, strategies and policies with that of Provincial and National government.

The main purpose of the IDP is to foster more appropriate service delivery by providing the framework for economic and social development within the Municipality. In doing so it contributes towards eradicating the development legacy of the past, operationalizes the notion of developmental local government, and fosters a culture of co-operative governance amongst the three spheres of government. The IDP on its own is a plan without money; it should be budgeted for in order to be implemented. It is linked to the Annual Budget in a plan that is called the SDBIP. Through quarterly reports, the Municipal Manager and Audit Committee advise Council on the compliance with the SDBIP.

3.1.2. The Legislative and Policy Context

The Constitution (1996) and other pieces of legislation regulate and direct the operations and existence of the local sphere of government which include the following:

Section 152 of the Constitution (1996) states that a municipality must strive to achieve the objectives to provide democratic and accountable government for local communities; to ensure the provision of services to communities in a sustainable manner; to promote social and economic development; to promote a safe and healthy environment; and to encourage the involvement of communities and community organization in matters of local government.

Section 153 of the Constitution (1996) requires a municipality to structure and manage its administration and budgeting and planning process to give priority to basic needs of the community and to promote the social and economic development of the community; and to participate in national and provincial development programmes.

Section 25 of the MSA (2000) requires each municipal council to, after the start of its elected term, adopt a single, inclusive and strategic plan for the development of the Municipality which links, integrates and co-ordinates plans and takes into account proposals for the development of the Municipality and which aligns the resources and capacity of the Municipality with the implementation of the plan.

The Act also requires that the IDP be implemented; that the Municipality monitors the implementation of the IDP, evaluates its performance about the IDP's implementation; and review the IDP annually to effect improvements where necessary.

Section 26 of the MSA (2000) prescribes the following components that an IDP must reflect on:

- The municipal council's vision including the municipal critical development and transformation needs
- An assessment of the existing level of development in the municipality.
- The council's developmental priorities and objectives including its local economic development aims.
- The council's development strategies which must be aligned to national and provincial sector plans.
- A spatial development framework which must include the provisions of basic guidelines for a land use management system.
- The council's operational strategies.
- A financial plan which must include a budget projection for the next three years; and
- The key performance indicators and performance targets determined in terms of Section 41.

The Municipal Structures Act (Act 117 of 1998) provides for the following:

- Chapter 5: Stipulates the general functions and powers of municipalities
- Section 83 (1): Each municipality has powers and functions assigned to it in terms of the provisions of the Constitution
- Section 83 (2): Powers and functions must be divided between the District Municipality and the Local Municipalities

Municipal Finance Management Act no 56 of 2003 which emphasizes secure sound and sustainable management of the financial affairs of the municipalities and other institutions in local government. It provides clarity on municipal budgetary processes and how these budgets should be utilized. This act addresses three

critical aspects in the IDP implementation plan, namely:

- Transformation of the procurement approach.
- Alignment of the IDP, budgeting and performance management processes.
- Linkage of IDP timeframes with budget time frames.

The Municipal Planning and Performance Management Regulations (R796 of 2001) set out further requirements for an IDP:

- An institutional framework is required for the implementation of the IDP and to address the municipality's internal transformation.
- Investment initiatives.
- Development initiatives including infrastructure, physical, social and institutional development; and
- All known projects, plans and programmes to be implemented within the municipality by any organ of state

Intergovernmental relations framework Act no 13 of 2005 which provides clarity on how all the three spheres of government must work together. The Act is a response to the limited successes in the alignment efforts among the three spheres of government. It creates a framework to support intergovernmental cooperation and coordination as required by the Constitution in its definition of "cooperative governance". It provides for the obligation of all spheres to participate in the planning processes of the municipality and in turn allow their own planning processes to be influenced by the municipal IDP's. The Act establishes structures and processes that enhance inter – governmental planning and monitoring processes for local, provincial, and national spheres of governance

3.2. INTER-GOVERNMENTAL PLANNING

The Municipal Planning and Performance Management Regulations (2001) sets out the requirements for an IDP as an institutional framework for implementation of the IDP and to address the municipality's internal transformation; internal investment initiatives to be clarified; internal development initiatives, including infrastructure, physical, social, and institutional development; and all known projects, plans, and programmes to be implemented within the municipality by any organ of state.

Inter-governmental Planning - Section 41(1) of the Constitution (1996) contains the principles of co-operative government and inter-governmental relations, and determines that all spheres of government and all organs of state within each sphere:

- Must preserve the peace, national unit, and indivisibility of the Republic
- Secure the well-being of the people of the Republic.
- Provide effective, transparent, accountable, and coherent government for the Republic as a whole
- Be loyal to the Constitution, the Republic, and its people; and
- Respect the constitutional status, institutions, powers, and functions of government in the other spheres.

Local authorities should work together to provide citizens with a comprehensive package of services. They must assist and support each other, share information and coordinate their efforts. Implementation of policies and government programmes particularly require close cooperation between the three spheres of government

The DDM is an all-government approach to improve integrated planning and delivery across the three spheres of government. The District and Metropolitan spaces are focal points of government and private sector investment. It will assist monitoring Government's development programmes through the concept of a joint "One Plan" in relation to 52 development spaces/impact zones. This approach will help accelerate economic, social, and environmental impact and sustainability.

3.3. National and Provincial Policy Frameworks

The IDP forms the policy framework and general basis upon which the annual budget is based and should be compatible with the national and provincial development plans and planning requirements. The National and Provincial planning frameworks that affect the Municipality are as follows:

- The National Spatial Development Perspective (NSDP).
- The National Growth Path
- The National Development Plan (NDP)
- The Government Outcomes
- The Medium-Term Strategic Framework (MDSF)
- The Mpumalanga Growth and Development Path
- The Mpumalanga Rural Development Programme (MRDP)
- The Vision 2030 Plan
- The State of the Nation Address
- The State of the Province Address on Local Government.

3.4. The Status of the IDP

This IDP replaces all previous IDPs that have been approved by previous Municipal Councils. The IDP is a legal document that must be approved by Council. Section 26 of the MSA (2000) requires that the Municipal Spatial Development Framework (MSDF) must be aligned to the IDP. All other spatial plans must be aligned with the MSDF. Therefore, no spatial plan of the municipality may contradict the MSDF or the IDP. Section 35(2) of the MSA (2000) indicates that a spatial development framework contained in the integrated development plan prevails over a plan defined in Section 1 of the Physical Planning Act (1991). Section 1 of the Act defines plan as a national plan, a regional development plan, a regional structure plan or an urban structure plan. This document therefore represents the draft Integrated Development Plan of the Municipality. It is submitted and prepared in fulfillment of the Municipality's legal obligation in terms of Section 34 of the MSA (2000).

3.4.1. The IDP Process

The Integrated Development Plan (IDP) is a legal document that must be approved by the Council according to Section 26 of the MSA the Municipal Spatial Development Framework (MSDF) must be aligned to the IDP.

All other spatial plans must be aligned with the MSDF. Therefore, no spatial plan of the municipality may contradict the MSDF or the IDP. Section 35(2) of the MSA, indicates that a spatial development framework contained in the integrated development plan prevails over a plan defined in section 1 of the Physical Planning Act, 1991 (Act No 125 of 1991). Section 1 of the Physical Planning Act defines plan as a national plan, a regional development plan, a regional development plan, a regional structure plan or an urban structure plan. Drafting an IDP requires a comprehensive planning process and the involvement of a wide range of internal and external role players. The preparation process is referred to as the "IDP Process Plan" and should guide the municipality in drafting or reviewing of the IDP. The elected council is the ultimate IDP decision-making authority. The role of all stakeholders is to inform, negotiate and comment on decisions during the planning process. An IDP Process Plan enhances integration and alignment between the IDP and the Budget, thereby ensuring the development of an IDP-based budget. In addition, it identifies the activities in the processes around the key statutory annual operational processes of the Budget and the IDP compilation, performance management implementation and the adoption of the municipal annual report. The process described and outlined in the Table 1.2 represents a continuous cycle of planning, implementation, monitoring, and review. Implementation commences after the Municipal Council adopts the Final Draft IDP and Budget for the subsequent financial year, and implementation feeds into the Performance Management System of the Municipality. Public participation remains pivotal through the IDP process.

3.4.2. The IDP Process Plan

The purpose of the IDP Process Plan is to outline the operational plan (an integrated process plan) for the development of the IDP for the municipality. This Process Plan is based on the unique character and circumstances of the Municipality, taking due cognizance of the process plan requirements as outlined in the MSA (2000), section 34 and Guidelines for Integrated Development Planning provided by the Department of Cooperative Governance and Traditional Affairs. The Municipality adopted its draft Process Plan for the 2017-22 IDP in August 2016 for public participation. All wards in the Municipality were consulted as per the schedule of meetings (Table xx). The final Process Plan was adopted by Council on 30 August 2016 (CL1.139) and a total of 9 different meetings were held with different stakeholders where communities raised needs were captured. These series of meetings produced a comprehensive lists of community needs from a total of 240 subjection and villages of the municipality from the 25 wards of the municipality, a kind of a concise list from all the 25 wards per section per programme is also part of this document, this is a product of community participation and all interested stakeholders, the mountains of needs as parked in this document clearly shows the level of development that the municipality with the help other spheres of government and private sector would need to cover and do, though this way take years and years however at the end of the term of this council some degree of development would have to be registered, even if by 10%.

3.4.3. The Implementation of the IDP Process Plan

3.4.3.1 Analysis

During this phase information is collected on the existing conditions within the municipality. It focuses on the types of problems faced by people in the area and the causes of these problems. The identified problems are

assessed and prioritized in terms of what is urgent and what needs to be done first. Information on availability of resources is also collected during this phase. At the end of this phase, the municipality will be able to provide an assessment of the existing level of development, details on priority issues and problems and their causes and information on available resources.

3.4.3.2. Strategies

During this phase, the municipality works on finding strategic solutions to the problems assessed during the analysis phase. This entails developing a vision, which in the case of the Municipality the current vision was confirmed as relevant and was retained with no changes.

3.4.3.3. Defining development Goals and Objectives

Development objectives are clear statements of what the municipality would like to achieve in the medium term to deal with the problems outlined in Phase 1, as contained in the departmental business plans.

3.4.3.4. Developing Strategies

To align its annual plans and strategic goals and objectives, the Municipality held its Strategic Planning Session at Ndalo Hotel, Emanzana; from 17 – 18 February 2022. From that StratPlan, the municipality came out with annual plans with possible programme projects per internal department, to respond to the needs raised by communities.

Figure 3.1: The process undertaken to produce the IDP consists of 5 phases:

3.4.3.5. Identification of Key Projects

During this phase the municipality works on the design and content of the projects identified during Phase 2. Clear details for each project must be worked out in terms of:

- Who is going to benefit from the project?
- How much is it going to cost?
- How is this project going to be funded?
- How long would it take to complete?
- Who is going to manage the project?

Clear targets must be set, and indicators worked out to measure performance as well as the impact of individual projects.

3.4.3.6. Integration

Once all projects had been identified, the Municipality must check again that it contributed to meeting the objectives outlined in Phase 2. These projects will provide an overall picture of the development plans. All the development plans must then be integrated. The Municipality should also have overall strategies for issues such as dealing with AIDS, poverty alleviation, and disaster management. These strategies should be integrated in the overall IDP.

3.4.3.7. Approval

The IDP is presented to the Municipal Council for consideration and adoption. The Council may adopt a draft for public comments before approving its final Integrated Development Plan. As per the approved IDP Process Plan, IDP Representative Forum Meetings are scheduled to be held as indicated in the following table:

Table 3.1: IDP Process - Roles and Responsibilities:

Stakeholder		Roles and Responsibilities
INTERNAL ROLE PLAYERS		
1.	Municipal Council	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt an IDP process plan • Take responsibility for the overall management and coordination of the planning process • Adopt and approve the final IDP; and • Ensure that annual business plans, budget and related development activities are based on the approved IDP
2.	Mayoral Committee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manage the IDP through the Municipal Manager • Recommend the IDP review process to Council • Recommend the IDP revisions to Council • Allocate resources for review of the IDP
3.	IDP Steering Committee, comprising -	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide terms of reference for all review and

Stakeholder	Roles and Responsibilities
INTERNAL ROLE PLAYERS	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal Manager • Directors/Managers • IMATU and SAMWU representatives <p>planning activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commission IDP planning studies, programmes, and projects • Process, summarize and document outputs from sub-committees, teams, etc. • Recommend amendments to the content of the IDP • Prepare, facilitate, and document meetings and workshops • Ensure alignment and participation in the determination and prioritization of plans and programmes in the spirit of cooperative governance
4.	<p>Municipal Manager Coordinating Committee (IDP Broad Planning Technical Committee), comprising –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal Manager • Managers/Officers: Office of Municipal Manager, Speaker, Executive Mayor, Budget Office, Supply Chain Management, Performance Management, Planning, Project Management and IDP • Administrative support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare the IDP review process plan • Identify resources • Coordinate and manage the components of the review process, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder meetings • Meeting deadlines • Horizontal and vertical alignment • Compliance with national and provincial requirements
5.	<p>Ward Councillors will play a pivotal role in the preparation of the IDP process, both in terms of the technical and community participation probes; they will act as the main interface between council and the community</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organize public consultation and participation at ward level • Disseminate information from council to constituents and vice versa • Identify issues and projects at ward level • Participate in the approval and ongoing monitoring of the approved IDP • Identify and encourage unorganized groups to participate in the IDP process
6.	<p>Municipal Manager and Manager: IDP The Municipal Manager will delegate these functions to the Manager: IDP, but remains accountable for the overall IDP process as dictated by the Municipal Systems Act (2000)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amongst other, the following responsibilities are allocated to the Manager: IDP for the IDP process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure that the Process Plan is finalized and adopted by Council • Adjust the IDP according to the proposals of the

Stakeholder	Roles and Responsibilities
INTERNAL ROLE PLAYERS	
	<p>MEC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify additional role players to sit on the IDP Representative Forum • Ensure the continuous participation of role players • Monitor the participation of role players • Ensure appropriate procedures are followed • Ensure documentation is prepared properly • Carry out the day-to-day management of the IDP process • Respond to comments and enquiries • Ensure alignment of the IDP with other IDPs within the District Municipality • Co-ordinate the inclusion of sector plans in the IDP • Co-ordinate the inclusion of the PMS in the IDP • Submit the final IDP to relevant authorities
7.	<p>Municipal Officials will be ultimately responsible for the implementation of the IDP process and as such will play a key role in the development of the IDP's specific activities that will be undertaken by officials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide relevant technical and financial information • Develop strategies and project plans • Provide inputs regarding the financial and technical feasibility aspects of projects and strategies identified by committees
8.	<p>Gert Sibande District Municipality</p> <p>The district municipality will have the same role as the local municipality, but only in the preparation of the District IDP Framework, but the role of the district municipality on the local level is the coordination of IDP processes of local municipalities, and these include the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the horizontal alignment of IDPs of the municipalities in the district area • Ensure the horizontal alignment between district and local planning • Facilitate vertical alignment of IDPs with the government sphere and sector departments • Prepare joint strategy workshops with local municipalities, provincial and national role players, and other specialists
9.	<p>IDP Advisory Committee (National, Provincial, Business Sector, Parastatals)</p> <p>The National and Provincial government departments as well as major stake holders like the sectors of manufacturing, mining, and business will serve on the committee</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assist Council in rendering technical (i.e., investment opportunities) and financial support to ensure that Council meets its goal of playing a role in the global economy

3.5. Review of the IDP

Section 34 of the MSA (2000) deals with the review and amendment of the IDP and requires that a municipal council must review its integrated development plan annually in accordance with an assessment of its performance measures in terms of Section 41; and to the extent that changing circumstances so demand; and may amend its integrated development plan in accordance with the prescribed process.

The annual review process thus relates to the assessment of the municipality's performance against organizational objectives as well as implementation and takes into cognizance any new information or change in circumstances that might have arisen after the adoption of the previous IDP. The review and amendment process must also adhere to the requirements for public participation as determined in the MSA (2000) in Chapter 4. In terms of the IDP review guidelines, the IDP is reviewed based on four primary areas of intervention, viz: the annual IDP review, the IDP Process Plan, amendments in response to changing municipal circumstances, and the comments from the MEC for local government. During the review cycle, changes to the IDP process and content may be necessitated due to institutional issues; amendments in response to changing circumstances; needs to improve the IDP process and content; and comments of the MEC for local government.

3.5.1. Strategic Objectives

The below-mentioned plans will address what the municipality will be doing for the next five years, and which will be revised annually through the IDP review process contained in the IDP Process Plan. These plans are based on the 6 key strategic objectives. However, it is worth mentioning that more than one department can contribute to the successful carrying out of a particular KPA, as the functions cut across. Alignment of duties and functions is therefore an important aspect of planning, so that there are no queries and misunderstandings by the time Performance Assessment is done.

Table 3.2: Summary on the basic services key strategic objectives for the five-year period 2022-2027:

Municipal KPA		Service Delivery and Infrastructure Development								
Problem statement and root causes per KPA:										
One Plan Transformation Area	Integrated Service Provision Infrastructure Engineering									
2019-24 MTSF Priority	Spatial Development, Human Settlements and Local Government									
Municipal Priority	Delivery of quality municipal services									
Impact statement: Accessible services to communities	MTSF Target: 100% access to piped water, sanitation, electricity and 75% to weekly waste removal									
Outcome (Strategic Goals)	Outcome indicator (Strategic Objectives)	Baseline	Situational analysis	5 year IDP target	Intervention/ Programme	ANNUAL TARGETS				
						2022/23 Outputs	2023/24 Outputs	2024/25 Outputs	2025/26 Outputs	2026/27 Outputs
Improved access to basic services	% Increase of households with access to basic services	81.6% (43 656HH)	Poor water quality, aging infrastructure, WTW reaching capacity, illegal connections, water losses	100% (53 480 HH)	Upgrading of existing WTW and bulk line and capacitation of maintenance teams and construction of mini labs	85% (45 458 HH)	90% (48 132 HH)	95% (50 806 HH)	100% (53 480HH)	-
		(51 679HH) 96.6%	Sewer spillages, WWTW reach capacity	100% (53 480HH)	Upgrading of wastewater treatment plants,	97% (51 876HH)	98% (52 410 HH)	99% (52945HH)	100% (53 480 HH)	-

						Conducting public awareness														
	(51 383 HH) 96%,	Ageing of Infrastructure, illegal connections, Theft and Vandalism	100% (53 480 HH)	Electrification of households, replacement of ageing infrastructure, upgrading of infrastructure	96.5% (51 608 HH)	97% (51 876HH)	98% (52 410HH)	99% (52 945HH)	100% (53 480HH)											
	111,139km (17, 1%)	Ageing of infrastructure, Eroded gravel roads	+25km (21%)	Construction and upgrading of roads, resealing of existing surfaced roads.	5km (17, 9%)	5km (18, 7%)	5km (19, 4%)	5km (20, 2%)	5km (21%)											
	(8 000 HH) 39%,	Old fleet always broken, illegal dumping, 2 landfills not permitted, no IWMP	75% (12 500 HH)	New landfill site, development of IWMP	50% (9 000 HH)	60% (11 000 HH)	65% 12 000 (HH)	70% (12 500 HH)	75% (13 500 HH)											

Municipal KPA										
Spatial Planning and Rationale										
Problem statement and root causes per KPA:										
One Plan Transformation Area										
2019-24 MTSF Priority										
Municipal Priority										
Eradication of informal settlements, establishment of townships										
Impact statement: Accessible services to communities										
MTSF Target: spatial intergradation to fast track transformation, integrated service delivery, settlement transformation and inclusive growth in urban and rural places										
Outcome (Strategic Goals)	Outcome indicator (Strategic Objectives)	Baseline	Situational analysis	5 year IDP target	Intervention/ Programme	ANNUAL TARGETS				
						2022/23 Outputs	2023/24 Outputs	2024/25 Outputs	2025/26 Outputs	2026/27 Outputs
Township establishments	NUMBER OF STUDIES CONDUCTED FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT OF CEMETERIES (NUMBER OF CEMETERIES ESTABLISHED)	1		2 CEMETERIES ESTABLISHED		0	1	1	0	0
	NUMBER OF STUDIES CONDUCTED FOR TOWNSHIP FORMALIZATION	3		3 TOWNSHIPS FORMALISED		0	0	1	1	1
	NUMBER OF STUDIES	1		3 TOWNSHIPS ESTABLISHED		0	0	1	1	1

	CONDUCTED FOR TOWNSHIP ESTABLISHMENT			(500 SITES EACH)						

Municipal KPA										
Local economic development										
Problem statement and root causes per KPA:										
One Plan Transformation Area	Economic repositioning									
2019-24 MTSF Priority	Economic transformation and job creation									
Municipal Priority	Job creation, create enabling environment for investment for business and business expansion									
Impact statement: Accessible services to communities										
MTSF Target: unemployment reduced to between 20%-24% with new jobs created, economic growth between 2% -3% and growth of investment to 23% of GDP										
Outcome (Strategic Goals)	Outcome indicator (Strategic Objectives)	Baseline	Situational analysis	5 year IDP target	Intervention/ Programme	ANNUAL TARGETS				
To promote local economic development	NUMBER OF LED STRATEGY PROJECT IMPLEMENTED	1		2 LED STRATEGY PROJECTS		2022/23 Outputs	2023/24 Outputs	2024/25 Outputs	2025/26 Outputs	2026/27 Outputs
	NUMBER OF CORPORATIVE OFFERED SUPPORT	38		250 CO-OPERATIVES		1	0	1	0	1
	NUMBER OF	4		20		50	50	50	50	50
						4	4	4	4	4

	TOURISM AWARENESS CAMPAIGNS CONDUCTED																
	NUMBER OF LED RELATED FOURMS/MEETING COORDINATED	1	20		4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4

3.5.2. Strategic Objective 1: To ensure Good Governance

Good governance objective has been defined under the following key performance areas:

Figure 3.2: Good governance key performance areas:

3.5.3. Policies and procedures

Key policies and procedures have been developed and implemented. The municipality is not where it should be in terms of development and implementation of these key policies. Several initiatives are being taken in ensuring that the control environment is sound.

3.6. Governance structures and leadership

The municipality strives to always operate under the premise of good governance and leadership. The following structures are currently in place to ensure that

achievement of this objective:

- Ward Committee meetings.
- Council meetings,
- Mayoral Outreach Programmes.
- IDP Representative Forum Meetings
- Records management.
- Secretariat services.
- Monitoring and oversight Committee
- Premier Coordinating Forum and the MunMec structures
- Gert Sibande District Municipality Municipal Manager's Forum
- Executive Mayor Forum Approved Fraud Prevention Policy.
- Mayoral committee; and
- Audit committee

3.6.1. STRUCTURAL ARRANGEMENT OF MUNICIPAL DEPARTMENTS

Figure 3.3: Structural Arrangement of Municipal Departments

Figure 3.4: Top Management

3.6.2. MUNICIPAL FUNCTIONS

The table below shows the distribution of functions in the locals and the district municipality:

MUNICIPAL / ENTITY FUNCTIONS		MUNICIPAL FUNCTIONS	
		Function Applicable to Municipality (Yes / No)*	Function Applicable to Entity (Yes / No)*
Constitution Schedule 4, Part B functions:			
Air pollution		Yes	No
Building regulations		Yes	No
Childcare facilities		No	No
Electricity and gas reticulation		Yes	No
Firefighting services		Yes	No
Local tourism		Yes	No
Municipal airports		No	No
Municipal planning		Yes	No
Municipal health services		No	Yes
Municipal public transport		No	No
Municipal public works only in respect of the needs of municipalities in the discharge of their responsibilities to administer functions specifically assigned to them under this Constitution or any other law		Yes	No
Storm water management systems in built-up areas		Yes	No
Trading regulations		Yes	No
Water and sanitation services limited to potable water supply systems and domestic wastewater and sewage disposal systems		Yes	No
Beaches and amusement facilities		No	No
Billboards and the display of advertisements in public places		Yes	No
Cemeteries, funeral parlours, and crematoria		Yes	No
Cleansing		Yes	No
Control of public nuisances		Yes	No
Control of undertakings that sell liquor to the public		Yes	No
Facilities for the accommodation, care, and burial of animals		No	No

MUNICIPAL / ENTITY FUNCTIONS		MUNICIPAL FUNCTIONS	
		Function Applicable to Municipality (Yes / No)*	Function Applicable to Entity (Yes / No)*
Constitution Schedule 4, Part B functions:			
Fencing and fences		Yes	No
Licensing of dogs		No	No
Licensing and control of undertakings that sell food to the public		Yes	No
Local amenities		Yes	No
Local sport facilities		Yes	No
Markets		Yes	No
Municipal abattoirs		Yes	No
Municipal parks and recreation		Yes	No
Municipal roads		Yes	No
Noise pollution		Yes	No
Pounds		No	No
Public places		Yes	No
Refuse removal, refuse dumps and solid waste disposal		Yes	No
Street trading		Yes	No
Street lighting		Yes	No
Traffic and parking		Yes	No
* The municipality does not have a municipal entity			

3.6.3. GOVERNANCE AND ADMINISTRATION

- Municipal Councils and administrations should strive to achieve the developmental objects of Local Government as set out in the Constitution:
- Democratic and Accountable government
- Encourage the involvement of communities and community organizations in the matters of local government
- Provision of services in a sustainable manner
- Promote Social and Economic Development
- Promote a safe and healthy environment

The Municipal Systems Act¹ lists the following administrative / managerial functions for municipalities to achieve the above:

- Develop and adopt Plans strategies and programmes with targets for service delivery
- Develop and adopt policies
- Promote and undertake development
- Establish and maintain an administration
- Administer and regulate its internal affairs and the local government affairs of the local community
- Implementing applicable national and provincial legislation and by-laws
- Providing municipal services to the local community, or appointing appropriate service providers in accordance with the criteria and process set out in section 78
- Monitoring and where appropriate regulate municipal services where those services are provided by service providers other than the municipality
- Preparing, approving, and implementing its budgets
- Imposing and recovering rates, taxes, levies, duties, service fees and surcharges on fees, including setting and implementing tariff, rates and tax and debt collection policies
- Monitoring the impact and effectiveness of any services, policies, programmes, or plans
- Establishing and implementing performance management systems
- Promoting a safe and healthy environment
- Passing by-laws and taking decisions on any of the above-mentioned matters
- Doing anything else within its legislative and executive competence

3.6.4. DEMOCRATIC AND ACCOUNTABLE GOVERNMENT

The Chief Albert Luthuli Municipal Council had 49 Councilors (seats) up until 24 March 2022 and currently has 48 (1 Councillor is deceased). Twenty-Five (25) are elected as Ward Councilors and the other twenty-four (24) Councilors were elected to represent Political Parties because of proportional representation. The Chief Albert Luthuli Municipal Council is comprised of the same 5 political parties as 2016, namely:

- African National Congress (ANC), with a decreased majority – 37 seats
- Economic Freedom Fighters (EFF), the official opposition – 8 seats
- Democratic Alliance – 1 seat
- Inkatha Freedom Party – 1 seat
- African People's Convention – 1 seat

The following table illustrates the number of voters, the votes cast and the seat calculation for the 2021 municipal elections:

Total Valid Votes Cast (All Parties)	Total Seats Available in Municipality	Independent Ward Councillors Elected	Ward Councillors Seats from Parties with no PR
79,213	48	0	0

Quota - (Q) 2,186

Total Valid Votes Cast for All Parties - (A) 79,213

Total Seats Available in Municipality - (B) 49

Independent Ward Councillors Elected - (C) 0

Ward Councillors Seats from Parties with no PR List (D) 0

Name of Municipality	Number of Wards pre-2021	Number of Wards post- 2021
Chief Albert Luthuli	25	25

Figure 3.3: Municipal council number of seats:

3.6.5. LEADERSHIP

The following table indicates the seat allocation of the various parties for each of the municipal councils in the Chief Albert Luthuli

Party Name	Total Valid Votes 2021	Total Votes Percentage 2021 (%)	Total Valid Votes 2016	Total percentage (%) 2016	Seat Allocation 2021	Total Wards Won 2021
African National Congress	60,324	76.06%	90,168	83.49%	38	25
African People's Convention	548	0.69%	1,870	1.73%	1	0
Democratic Alliance	2,128	2.68%	3,707	3.43%	1	0
Economic Freedom Fighters	13,166	16.60%	8,792	8.14%	8	0
Inkatha Freedom Party	1003	1.39%	1,049	0.97%	1	0
Total	107,066		107,066		49	25

3.7. COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION AND SATISFACTION

3.7.1. Community Needs

From the public participation (consultation) process of 2019, the needs of the community were received from all twenty-five (25) wards. The community needs can be summarized as follows:

- Drilling and refurbishment of boreholes,
- The need for high mast lights
- Provincial roads urgently requiring tarring
- Maintenance of other roads and streets by blading, re-gravelling, patching of potholes and erection of visible signage and road markings.
- Need for sports facilities
- Need for RDP houses which cuts across all wards
- Upgrading of Water Schemes
- Renovation of community hall
- Provision and upgrading of bulk sewer networks
- Construction of taxi ranks
- Constructions of motorway bridges
- Construction of footbridges
- Refuse removal – provision of household refuse bins, Skipmaster bins, and dumping sites.

3.7.2. Ward Committees

There are 25 wards in the Chief Albert Luthuli Local Municipality. The Municipality is still busy with establishment of Ward Committees in all 25 wards. There should be 250 seats in total, currently, 238 of those seats are filled, with 12 vacancies in Ward 02.

In 2019, a Ward Committee Summit was held under the theme "Effective Public Participation to Enhance Revenue collection". The aim of the summit was to realize the following objectives.

- a) Follow-up on the induction of Ward Committee members, clarifying the Roles and responsibilities of the different stakeholders in Public Participation.
- b) The role of Ward Committee members in encouraging community members to pay for services rendered by the municipality
- c) Attend to matters and issues raised by Ward Committees
- d) Declare Ward Committees as Agents of Revenue Enhancement for the municipality.

All elected ward committee members have been inducted on Municipal processes in pursuit to better equip them to carry out their respective responsibilities. The Guidelines for the Establishment and Operation of Municipal Ward Committees, issued by the Minister of Provincial and Local Government in the Government Gazette dated 24 June 2005, provides that "A ward committee must meet at least quarterly" (item 11 (2) (d)). For the 2020/21 municipal financial year, ward committees at Chief Albert Luthuli Local Municipality met, on average, monthly.

3.7.3. TRADITIONAL LEADERSHIP

In South Africa, after attaining democracy in 1994, the drafters of the Constitution sought to ensure that traditional leadership was recognised and was entrenched in the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, in Chapter 12, which recognised the institution, status and the role of the traditional leadership. Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality is predominantly a traditional leader's area, with a total of twelve (12) traditional councils, however during the current financial year we lost our traditional leader of Ka-Mantjolo Traditional council Inkosi MB Mnisi. The table below represents the traditional councils, leaders, and area of jurisdiction.

3.7.3.2. ROLE OF TRADITIONAL LEADERS IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF IDP

The Local House of Traditional Leaders is established in accordance with the Traditional Leadership and Framework Act, 2003. The functions of the local house of traditional leaders, as stated in Chapter 4 of the Act; is--

- (a) to be involved in the development of planning frameworks that have an impact on traditional areas, the development of by-laws that impact on traditional communities; communities as an object; or evaluating government programmes in rural communities.
- (b) to participate in local government programmes that have the development of rural communities as an object; or
- (c) to participate in local initiatives that are aimed at monitoring, reviewing, or evaluating government programmes in rural areas.

Table: 3.1: List of Traditional Councils and Traditional Leaders

NO	TRADITIONAL COUNCIL	TRADITIONAL LEADER	AREA/LOCALITY	CONTACT
1.	Ka-Mantjolo Traditional Council	Vacant	Emanzana / Ka-Mantjolo	
2.	Embhuleni Traditional Council	Prince CM Dlamini	Emanzana	082 662 7209
3.	Ka-Mandlamakhulu Traditional Council	Inkosi KJ Malaza	Tjakastad	072 188 2916
4.	Somcuba-Bhevula Traditional Council	Inkosi TD Nkosi	Ebuhleni / Mooiplaas	082 963 2447
5.	Enkhaba Traditional Council	Inkosi SI Nkosi	Enkhaba	082 867 1435
6.	Ebutisini Traditional Council	Inkosi TP Nkosi	Steynsdorp	079 593 5716
7.	Enikwakuyengwa Traditional Council	Inkosi RA Nkosi	Litjelembube	071 772 4613 (royabnerinkosi@gmail.com)
8.	Kwa- Duma Traditional Council	Inkosi MS Mnisi	Bettysgoed	082 841 6513
9.	Emfumbeni Traditional Council	Inkosikati B Hlatshwayo	Robinsdale	071 552 2953
10.	Kwa-Madlangampisi Traditional Council	Inkosi JA Tshabalala	Swallows' Nest	079 364 0338
11.	Kwa-Mpisikazi Traditional Council	Inkosi JV Nhlapho	Dundonald	082 788 9432 (jvnhlapho@polca.co.za)
12.	Ka-Ndlela Traditional Council	Inkosi TM Nkosi	Diepdale / Fernie	082 783 1539 (tmr.nkosi@vodamail.co.za)

3.9. OFFICE-BEARERS AND MAYORAL COMMITTEE

The Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality was determined by the MEC of CoGTA to constitute the Executive Mayoral System, with SIX (6) full-time members of Mayoral Committee (MMCs). In addition, the Speaker, Chief Whip, and Chairperson of MPAC full-time councillors as per the determination.

- **SPEAKER** – Cllr SV Gininda
- **EXECUTIVE MAYOR** – Cllr DP Nkosi
- **CHIEF WHIP** – Cllr LL Sidu
- **Members of Mayoral Committee** –
 - **FINANCE** – Cllr ES Dhlamini
 - **TECHNICAL SERVICES** – Cllr SN Dube
 - **PROJECT MANAGEMENT UNIT** – Cllr NG Thomo
 - **CORPORATE SERVICES AND ADMINISTRATION** – Cllr JT Mathebula
 - **PLANNING AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT** – Cllr SP Nkosi
 - **COMMUNITY AND SAFETY SERVICES** – Cllr GG Zulu
- **Municipal Public Accounts Committee Chairperson** – Cllr RM Motaung

Figure 3.4: Office-bearers & Mayoral Committee

Figure 3.5: Other Councillors' Grid

3.10. Marketing and communication

- Marketing and communication function is in place to ensure that municipal services are well placed and communicated to its community. Structures such as Communications and Liaisons, several awareness campaigns, ward committee management and public participation engagements are in place.
- The Communication Strategy is being developed, and will incorporate all forms of communication media, channels and platforms. Traditional media includes the issuing out of notices on notice boards and to newspapers, and the use of local radio stations.
- In addition to that, there is a municipal website which is running and is being updated regularly. An official Facebook page also exists and is run by the staff in the Office of the Executive Mayor.
- The communication channels listed above are used as tools to maintain regular stakeholder mobilization and public participation.
- Public consultation meetings are conducted by the ward councillors on a regular basis, and the Mayoral Outreach programmes are there to enhance the mobilization and consultation mechanisms.
- Integrated Development Plan Representative Forums are also another way in which the key stakeholders are consulted and reported to.

3.11. Legal and compliance

The municipality has an established legal and compliance section to deal with all legal matters. Several legal firms are contracted to ensure that this deliverable outcome is achieved. Legal division deals with the following matters amongst other:

- The Legal Division intends to conduct legal audit on all legislation having an impact on the municipality in the next financial year.
- To be able to strictly monitor compliance each relevant department and to be able to render the professional legal advice.
- The Unit commits to ensure a more effective, accountable, and clean local government that works together with national and provincial government.
- Ensures that the Council Fraud Prevention policy will be continuously updated and diligently implemented; and
- Service Standards for all municipal services will be compiled, published, and applied as far possible.

3.12. Performance reporting

Performance reporting function is in place, and it is supported by the functioning performance management system, developed IDP and SDBIP.

3.13. Risk management

Risk Management as one of the key pillars for good governance practices and it is a continuous process that enables improvement in strategy design and strategy implementation as well as an organization's systems and operations. The effective management of risk is prioritized to ensure that business risks across

the organization are identified and managed on an on-going basis for the achievement of the municipality is vision to become the leading community driven municipality in the provision of sustainable services and developmental programmes.

Council has an existing Risk Management Policy and Framework that enables management to proactively identify and respond appropriately to all significant risks that could impact on business objectives. In line with the approved Risk Management Policy and Framework a top-down approach has been adopted in developing the risk profiles of the organization. The results of the strategic and operational assessments were used to compile a risk register. Risk Management in the municipality is guided and monitored by various committees at Council and administrative level such as the Municipal Public Accounts Committee (MPAC), Risk Management Committee and the Audit Committee. Additionally, the municipality appointed an Internal Auditor and a Chief Risk officer as part of the reasonable steps taken to maintain an effective efficient and transparent system of financial and general risk management. In year 2020 and 2021 Risk Management unit has been appointed to assist in the monitoring and implementation of COVID 19. COVID 19 Action plan has been developed and monitored by the Unit and OHS unit. For the financial year 2020 and 2021 risk management unit has identified eight strategic risks.

Figure 3.6: Eight identified top risks

No	Top Six Risks
1.	Unsuitable financial viability and revenue collection
2.	Inadequate provision of basic services
3.	Inadequate implementation of governance processes
4.	Inadequate to ensure efficient and effective ICT information
5.	Global pandemic (Infection with Corona Virus/COVID-19)
6.	Inadequate institutional transformation
7.	Inadequate economic growth
8.	Unavailability of land for development

3.14. Internal Audit

Internal Audit Function provide an independent, objective Assurance and Consulting Services that add value and improve the municipality's operations. The Function assist the Municipality to accomplish its objectives by bringing a systematic, disciplined approach to evaluate and improve the effectiveness of risk management, control, and governance processes. The Function evaluates risk exposures relating to the Municipality's governance, operations, and information systems regarding the:

- Reliability and integrity of financial and operational information.
- Effectiveness and efficiency of operations.
- Safeguarding of assets; and
- Compliance with laws, regulations, and contracts.

The function comprises of Chief Audit Executive, x1 Senior Internal Auditors, x1 Junior Internal Auditor and a Panel of co-sourced Internal Audit Services Providers. The below legislations and prescripts underpin the establishment of the function:

- Municipal Finance Management Act No. 56 of 2003 section 165.
- Internal Audit Framework (IAF) National Treasury Republic of South Africa March 2009 (2nd Edition) section 3.
- International Standards for the Professional Practice Standards effective January 2017; and
- King III and IV Code Governance Reports.

The internal audit function report administratively to the Accounting Officer (Municipal Manager) and functionally to the Audit Committee on the following Policies and Procedures as approved by the Audit Committee and Council.

3.15. Information Communication and Technology

To ensure that the information technology infrastructure resources are available, operational and always save to support and provide uninterrupted services to the Municipality and the community. This ICT system, infrastructure and services are critical for the Municipality in rendering its mandate which is service delivery. The department strives for the protection of the Municipality’s information assets from internal and external information security threats, the security of the networks, data and communications, expansion of the wireless and fibre networks (WAN) in the rest of the Municipality and ensure that reliable fibre channel are installed where necessary. The remote offices are linked on a MPLS which in turn enables officials to interconnect as if they are in the same building. The plan is to increase migrate to digital two-way radios, data radios and fibre coverage in the rest of the MP301. The Municipality has recognized that there is a need to move with speed into the fourth industrial revolution (4IR) to improve efficiencies, effectiveness, and seamless way that services are provided to the Community with in MP301. The Municipality wants to improve the interaction and collaboration between its administration, political, community and other stakeholders by providing digital and SMART solutions to improve service delivery and cut costs and reduced unnecessary processes.

3.16. Ward Councillor report-back meetings

Section 152(1), of the Constitution of South Africa, Act 108 of 1996, requires that local government encourages and promotes public participation in the matters of local government and ward councillors are expected to interact through report back meetings with the community. The ward councillor report-back meetings must be conducted at least quarterly to the community on the performance of the municipality.

For the 2021/2022 municipal financial year in Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality, three councillor report back meetings were conducted on average for the year per ward:

No. of Wards	Submission rate (April – May 2022)	Sum of public report-back meetings			
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
25	Submission for Budget/IDP Consultation Meetings	0	0	25	25

Report-back meetings were held during the third and fourth quarters of the 2021/2022 financial year due to the public hearings for budget, IDP and Annual Performance Report as per the myriad of legislative frameworks.

3.17. Complaints Management Systems

The Municipal Systems Act, section 17 (2) (a) provides that a municipality must provide for the receipt, processing and consideration of petitions and complaints lodged by members of the local community. Hence, a functional complaints management system (CMS) is a critical tool to register and monitor complaints recorded. This tool is an indication of the level of openness and transparency to solve customer complaints faster and in an organized manor. This ensures effective redress of communities' complaints.

Currently, the municipality is reliant on a manual reconciliation system for Complaints Management. The departments of Community Services, Public Safety and Technical Services keep registers for complaints and job cards to track the progress and status of each complaint lodged by the public. The Municipality also implements a comprehensive customer relations management which interfaces with various initiatives also launched by the Provincial Government, e.g., Satise Silalele, an application downloadable from the App Store for complaints management.

3.17.1. Protests

The municipality recorded protests in Ekulindeni, Carolina, Enhlaba, Emanzana, and Elukwatini since the commencement of this term of Council.

The issues of contention included allegations of maladministration, employment issues in the mines, sale of RDP houses, and maintenance of infrastructure (Carolina); leadership and governance issues (Emanzana), maintenance of infrastructure (Elukwatini), and disputes over labour issues in Ekulindeni and Enhlaba.

To summarize, the protests were in ward 12, 17, 15, 21, and 22.

3.17.2. Customer Survey

The Office of the Speaker (OTS) has developed tools to be used in conducting community survey. The methodology to be used is a questionnaire to be handed to ward committee members with the officials from the office doing the quality checks.

In addition to that, suggestion boxes are placed at all the administrative offices for members of the community to drop-in their complaints, suggestions, and satisfaction indications.

CHAPTER 4

FINANCIAL PLANNING

4.1. Background

The Municipality aims to fully comply with prevailing municipal financial legislation to ensure sound financial management and governance to achieve a clean audit status. It is important that the financial affairs of the municipality are managed in an efficient and effective manner to sustain a sound financial position towards sustainable service delivery.

The directorate is responsible for the function of budgetary and accounting and expenditure and revenue management and maintenance of the financial system. Municipality is a developing and growing municipality striving for service delivery excellence. Therefore, many challenges are faced with regards to financial planning and are ever changing due to the dynamic setting of local government.

3.12 Financial Management Structure

The diagram below shows the current management structure within the financial department:

Figure 4.1: Finance Management Structure:

The directorate is responsible for the function of budgeting and accounting, expenditure and revenue management, and maintenance of the financial system. The Municipality is a developing and growing municipality striving for service delivery excellence. Therefore, many challenges are faced with regards to financial planning and the ever-changing dynamic setting of local government.

4.3. Financial Management Framework

The priority from a financial perspective is to ensure that the municipality's financial position remains sustainable and viable. To indicate to this effect, the following Framework has been put in place:

Figure 4.2: Financial Management Framework:

4.4. Overview of financial management policies

The purpose of budget-related and financial policies is to provide a sound environment to manage the financial affairs of the municipality. The following are key budget relating policies which municipality has approved and where the policy doesn't exist the process of development will be looked at:

4.4.1. Tariff Policy

The policy prescribes the procedures for calculating tariffs. This policy is required in terms of Section 74 of the Local Government Municipal Systems Act, Act 22 of 2000.

4.4.2. Rates Policy

The policy required by the Municipal Property Rates Act, Act 6 of 2004. This policy provides the framework for the determining of rates. It further ensures certainty and clarity as to amounts payable in respect of property rates.

4.4.3. Free Basic services policy

This policy aims to enhance the delivery of Free Basic Services to poor households, and assist municipality in developing innovative, reliable and integrated billing systems that would allow for improved delivery of services and an effective and efficient billing system for the debtors/consumers of the municipality.

4.4.4. Indigent Support Policy

To provide access to and regulate free basic services to all indigent households. The indigent threshold will

be determined by Council.

4.4.5. Credit Control and Debt Collection Policy

To provide for credit and debt collection procedures and mechanisms to ensure that all consumers pay for the services that are supplied.

4.4.6. Budget Policy

This policy set out the principles which must be followed in preparing a medium-term revenue and expenditure framework budget. It further ensures that the budget reflects the strategic outcomes embodied in the IDP and related strategic policies.

4.4.7. Cash Management and Investment Policy

This policy was compiled in accordance with the Municipal Investment Regulation R308 and ensures that cash resources are managed in the most efficient and effective manner possible.

4.4.8. Asset Management Policy

The objective of the policy is to prescribe the accounting and administrative procedures relating to property, plant, and equipment (assets). The asset management policy it has incorporate the asset disposal processes.

4.4.9. Capital Investment and Infrastructure Development Policy

The policy is not yet in place, but strategies and programmes are being developed, they will be identified to form part of the financial plan to achieve the desired objective of improving financial viability, sustainability of the municipality, and capital investment on infrastructure. The policy will give guides on alternative funding models such as donor funding etc.

4.4.10. Borrowing policy

The strong capital market in South Africa (banks and other lending institutions like DBSA, INCA etc.) provides an additional instrument to access financial resources. However, the municipality cannot borrow to balance its budget and pay for overspending. The municipality's credit rating should also look at. The finance will develop the policy during the second year so that it forms part of public consultation in March 2013.

4.4.11. Funding and Reserves Policy

Will set out the assumptions and methodology for estimating, projected billings, collections and all direct revenues, the provision for revenue that will not be collected, the funds the Municipality can expect to receive from investments the dividends the Municipality can expect to receive from Municipal entitles; assets; the Municipality's borrowing requirements; and the funds to be set aside in reserves.

4.4.12. Accounting Policy

The policy prescribes the basis of presentation of the annual financial statements in accordance with the

General Recognized Accounting Practices and Accounting Standards, the policy will be reviewed during the preparation of annual financial statement.

4.4.13. Supply Chain Management Policy

This policy is developed in terms of Section 111 of the Municipal Finance Management Act, Act 56 of 2003. The principle of this policy is to give effect to a fair, equitable, transparent, competitive and cost-effective system for the procuring of goods and services, disposing of goods and selecting of contractors in the provision of municipal services.

4.4.14. Transport and Subsistence Policy

This policy regulates the reimbursement of travelling and subsistence cost to officials and councillors undertaking official trips / visits.

4.5. Financial Management Status

The world economy is expected to grow by 4.4 per cent this year. This is lower than the 4.9 per cent that was anticipated when tabling the medium-term budget policy statement (MTBPS). The Omicron variant of the coronavirus caused many countries to impose restrictions to manage its spread. In addition, continued imbalances in global value chains have limited the pace of the world's economic recovery.

The South African economy has not been shielded from these global developments. National Treasury has revised South Africa's economic growth estimate for 2021 to 4.8 per cent, from 5.1 per cent at the time of the MTBPS.

This revision reflects a combination of the impact of changes in the global environment, along with South Africa's own unique challenges. Commodity prices, which have supported South Africa's economic recovery, slowed in the second half of 2021.

Also, violent unrest in July, and restrictions imposed to manage the third wave of COVID-19 further eroded the gains South Africa made in the first half of the year.

Industrial action in the manufacturing sector, and the re-emergence of loadshedding, also slowed the pace of the recovery. Real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth of 2.1 per cent is projected for 2022. Over the next three years, GDP growth is expected to average 1.8 per cent.

Headline inflation is expected to remain between 3 to 6 per cent target range over the 2022/23 MTEF.

In summary, the tax revenue in 2021/22 was higher than projections and this was mainly due to commodity price rally. However, these are projected to be short term, and as such long-term spending commitments should not be made based on short term revenue benefits. There are measures in place to reduce expenditure to narrow the budget deficit.

Similar to the rest of government, municipalities face a difficult fiscal environment. The weak economic growth has put pressure on consumers' ability to pay for services, while transfers from national government are growing more slowly than in the past. Some municipalities have managed these challenges well, but others have fallen into financial distress and face liquidity problems.

There is a need for municipalities to focus on collecting revenues owed to them and eliminate wasteful and non-core spending.

Municipalities must ensure that they render basic services, maintain their assets and clean environment. Furthermore, there must be continuous communication with the community and other stakeholders to improve the municipality's reputation. This will assist in attracting investment in the local economy which may result in reduced unemployment. Some municipalities are experiencing serious liquidity challenges.

Therefore, the new leadership is advised to:

- Decisively address unfunded budgets by reducing non-priority spending and improving revenue management processes to enable collection; and
- Address service delivery failures by ensuring adequate maintenance, upgrading and renewal of existing assets to enable reliable service delivery.

It should be noted that it is easier for consumers to pay for services if they are reliable and when the environment is well maintained.

In this regard municipalities are reminded to take note of the Constitutional Court decision in *Mazibuko and Others vs City of Johannesburg and Others* (CCT 39/09) [2009] ZACC 28; 2010 (3) BCLR 239 (CC); 2010 (4) SA 1 (CC) (8 October 2009). The Constitutional Court confirmed that a municipality has the right to disconnect the water service in the event of non-payment. In the case of registered indigent users, water may not be disconnected but can and should be restricted to the national policy limit of 6 kilolitres of water monthly.

Funding Depreciation: From the analysis of the mSCOA data strings it is evident that a number of municipalities are allocating non-funding as the funding source in the fund segment for depreciation charges.

Depreciation charges must be funded from operational funds such as service charges for electricity if assets are utilised for electricity purposes, service charges water for water management purposes, waste and wastewater management in the same manner and property rates for services like roads that is primarily funded from property rates. When depreciation is funded, it will assist the municipalities to accumulate sufficient surpluses that must be transferred to cash backed reserves.

Depreciation is the method to provide for the replacement of the assets. If depreciation remains a journal without the funds being ring-fenced, municipalities will not be in a financial position to fund future infrastructure assets.

In line with Circular 115 the following macro-economic forecasts have been considered upon the preparation of the 2021/22 – 2023/24 MTREF:

DESCRIPTION	2022/23	2023/24	2024/25
GENERAL REVENUE	6%	6%	6%
ELECTRICITY REVENUE	9.6%	8.9%	8.9%
ELECTRICITY BULK PURCHASES	9.6%	8.9%	8.9%
SALARIES AND WAGES	4.9%	4.9%	4.9%
GENERAL EXPENDITURE	5.8%	5.8%	5.8%

MEDIUM TERM REVENUE AND EXPENDITURE FRAMEWORK (MTREF): BUDGET SUMMARY - 2022/23 - 2024/25				
R	Adjustment Budget 2021/22	Budget Year 2022/23	Budget Year 2023/24	Budget Year 2024/25
Total Revenue	R 930 162 932,02	R 1 016 554 480,00	R 1 040 859 644,00	R 1 078 974 644,00
Total Expenditure	R 929 557 805,00	R 1 016 047 465,00	R 1 038 334 334,00	R 1 072 290 440,00
Surplus/Deficit	R 605 127,02	R 507 015,00	R 2 525 310,00	R 6 684 204,00

The MEDIUM-TERM REVENUE AND EXPENDITURE FRAMEWORK (MTREF): BUDGET SUMMARY - 2022/23 - 2024/25 was prepared based on the expected revenue to be generated from exchange and non-exchange transactions. The previous 3 financial years, the division of revenue and circular 115 from the NATIONAL TREASURY was used as a benchmark for costing purposes.

Revenue generation remains a key focus area for the Municipality in order to ensure sustainability in terms of delivery of services as a result of the Electricity distribution losses are a major central point. In light of the challenges faced CALM has managed to equivocally strike the balance of preparing a funded, credible and realistic budget

MEDIUM TERM REVENUE AND EXPENDITURE FRAMEWORK (MTREF): REVENUE BY SOURCE - 2022/23 - 2024/25				
R	Adjustment Budget 2021/22	Budget Year 2022/23	Budget Year 2023/24	Budget Year 2024/25
Property rates	R 105 643 601,50	R 116 197 186,00	R 116 308 382,00	R 116 308 382,00
Service charges - electricity revenue	R 43 426 923,34	R 49 721 082,00	R 49 768 663,00	R 49 768 663,00
Service charges - water revenue	R 48 321 825,68	R 52 375 353,00	R 52 425 473,00	R 52 425 473,00
Service charges - sanitation revenue	R 12 925 881,68	R 14 281 041,00	R 14 294 705,00	R 14 294 705,00
Service charges - refuse revenue	R 11 074 847,14	R 12 207 296,00	R 12 218 978,00	R 12 218 978,00
Rental of facilities and equipment	R 134 303,06	R 142 361,24	R 150 902,92	R 159 957,10
Interest earned - external investments	R 190 001,82	R 2 386 491,76	R 2 380 371,08	R 2 371 316,90
Interest earned - outstanding debtors	R 8 042 454,26	R 38 042 602,00	R 38 079 006,00	R 38 079 006,00
Fines	R 190 001,82	R 213 634,00	R 213 837,00	R 213 837,00
Transfers recognized	R 352 626 000,00	R 392 462 000,00	R 417 844 000,00	R 447 905 000,00
Other own revenue	R 511 091,72	R 932 433,00	R 933 326,00	R 933 326,00
Capital Projects	R 347 076 000,00	R 337 593 000,00	R 336 242 000,00	R 344 296 000,00
Total Revenue	R 930 162 932,02	R 1 016 554 480,00	R 1 040 859 644,00	R 1 078 974 644,00

Total revenue has been appropriated from realistically anticipated projections based on thorough, accurate and adequate historical billing information. Total Revenue of R1 016 554 480 which amounted to an increase of R86 391 548.00 at a rate of 9.3%

Revenue remains a key focus area of consideration as this constitutes the fundamentals of a funded and credible budget. We are a grant dependent Municipality with very limited revenue streams:

1. Transfers and Subsidies: R730 055 000 (71.8%)

The existence of informal areas limits cost reflective charges forcing the Municipality to levy a flat rate on some services

2. Own revenue: R286 499 480 (28.2%)

Revenue Increase at 6%

Electricity Revenue increase at 9.6%

MEDIUM TERM REVENUE AND EXPENDITURE FRAMEWORK (MTREF): EXPENDITURE BY SOURCE - 2022/23 - 2024/25				
R	Adjustment Budget 2021/22	Budget Year 2022/23	Budget Year 2023/24	Budget Year 2024/25
Employee related costs	R 178 548 480,00	R 187 664 503,00	R 192 145 710,00	R 195 145 710,00
Remuneration of councillors	R 27 948 386,00	R 30 534 651,00	R 33 617 458,00	R 35 617 458,00
Debt impairment	R 45 326 761,00	R 50 113 720,00	R 50 161 675,00	R 70 161 675,00
Depreciation & asset impairment	R 26 039 413,00	R 38 058 022,00	R 38 592 755,00	R 38 092 755,00
Finance charges	R 541 002,00	R 1 794 407,00	R 1 796 123,00	R 1 796 123,00
Bulk purchases	R 94 990 264,00	R 101 897 752,00	R 112 014 400,00	R 137 014 400,00
Other materials/ Repairs and Maintenance	R 29 444 575,00	R 35 384 296,00	R 29 891 048,00	R 40 791 048,00
Contracted services	R 119 223 337,00	R 175 035 151,00	R 185 256 238,00	R 227 256 238,00
General Expenditure	R 60 419 587,00	R 57 968 962,00	R 58 616 926,00	-R 17 900 968,00
Other expenditure	R -			
Capital Projects	R 347 076 000,00	R 337 596 001,00	R 336 242 001,00	R 344 316 001,00
Total Expenditure	R 929 557 805,00	R 1 016 047 465,00	R 1 038 334 334,00	R 1 072 290 440,00

Total Expenditure of R1 016 047 465 which amounted to a R86 489 660 increase at a rate of 9.3%

Electricity Bulk purchases VS Electricity revenue

3. R101 897 752 vs R49 721 082: 48.8%

The biggest contributing sources of expenditure include:

4. Capital Spending
5. Employee Related Costs
6. Bulk Purchases
7. Contracted Services

Cost containment measures remain a priority at the Municipality.

Technical Services and Project Management have the largest chunk of the Budget at 29% and 33% respectively. Within the Financial Services department, we have centralised provision for non-cash items.

MEDIUM TERM REVENUE AND EXPENDITURE FRAMEWORK (MTREF): DEPARTMENTAL ALLOCATIONS - 2022/23 - 2024/25

R	Adjustment Budget 2021/22	Budget Year 2022/23	Budget Year 2023/24	Budget Year 2024/25	% Allocation
Planning and Economic Development	R 14 918 703,00	R 15 783 987,77	R 16 699 459,06	R 17 668 027,69	2%
Corporate Services	R 93 807 904,00	R 109 248 762,43	R 110 585 190,65	R 109 999 131,71	11%
Financial Services	R 108 490 590,00	R 114 783 044,22	R 121 440 460,78	R 128 404 007,51	11%
Project Management Unit	R 313 076 000,00	R 337 596 001,00	R 336 242 001,00	R 344 316 001,00	33%
Municipal Manager	R 9 143 071,00	R 9 673 369,12	R 10 234 424,53	R 10 828 021,15	1%
Council General	R 48 899 577,00	R 51 735 752,47	R 54 736 426,11	R 57 911 138,82	5%
Community Services	R 76 724 445,00	R 87 174 462,81	R 92 233 581,65	R 97 583 129,39	9%
Technical Services	R 264 497 515,00	R 290 052 085,18	R 296 162 790,21	R 305 500 982,72	29%
Total Expenditure	R 929 557 805,00	R 1 018 047 485,00	R 1 038 334 334,00	R 1 072 290 440,00	100%

4.6. Table 4.2: Capital Programs and Projects:

IDP No	PROJECT DESCRIPTION	REGION SEGMENT	2022/2023 DRAFT BUDGET FORECAST	2023/2024 DRAFT BUDGET FORECAST	2024/2025 DRAFT BUDGET FORECAST
Currency			R	R	R
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0002_MIG	Upgrading of Emanzana water scheme	17 & 23		10,000,000	15,000,000
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0005_MIG	Upgrading of Carolina Water Treatment Works: Phase 4	15, 21 & 22	5,000,000		
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0007_MIG	Replacement of AC Pipes at Empuluzi Water Scheme	4	5,000,000	15,000,000	10,000,000
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0013_WSIG	Water Services Infrastructure Grant (WSIG)	To be determined	62,745,000	50,000,000	52,690,000
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0014_RBIG	Upgrading of Eerstehoek, Empuluzi & Methula Water Bulk Supply.	01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 07, 09, 10, 11, 13, 14, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 23, 24 & 25	165,142,000	170,000,000	170,000,000
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0015_MIG	Upgrading of Empuluzi Wastewater Treatment Works (WWTW)	4,5,7,9 & 11	15,000,000	10,000,000	10,000,000
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0018_MIG	Upgrading of Elukwatini Wastewater Treatment Works (WWTW)	10,13,14,16,18,20,24 & 25	15,000,000	10,000,000	10,000,000

2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0019_MIG	Installation of SmartSan or Environsan Toilets	Arhemburg, Kromkrans, Emanzana, Mayflowergate, Fernie, N17 & Khuzulwandle	12,500,000		
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0024_MIG	Construction of Mahoxo Ring Road	2	10,000,000		
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0028_MIG	Construction of Paving Road in Silobela	15	8,000,000		
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0030_MIG	Construction of Paving Road in Nhlatzatshe 2 & 4	20 & 25			8,613,650
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0031_MIG	Construction of Paving Road in Nhlatzatshe	24		10,000,000	10,000,000
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0032_MIG	Construction of Paving Road in Dundonald	5	8,000,000		
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0034_MIG	Construction of High mast lights	01, 03, 06, 08, 09, 11, 15, 17, 19, 20 & 22	13,000,000	15,029,900	20,000,000
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0038_INEP	Integrated National Electrification Project (INEP): Mandela (30); ZCC/Dundonald (20); Rocky Pack (250); Honingklip (90); Lochiel (60) & Faith Section (50)	To be determined	10,000,000	12,000,000	12,539,000
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0041_MIG	Construction of Ekulindeni Sport Fields	12	2,500,000	10,000,000	10,000,000
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0043_MIG	Construction of Dundonald Taxi rank	4,5,7,9 & 11		10,000,000	5,000,000
2022/23_CALLM_TEC_0044_MIG	Construction of Emanzana Transfer Station	17&23	720,700	9,000,000	5,000,000
Total Budget			332,607,700	331,029,900	338,842,650

4.7. Public Participation

4.7.1. 2022/2027 Identified Needs per Ward

Issues emanating from Public Participation

The following section will reflect the needs as emanating from the public participation on the Draft IDP 2022/2027. The needs are reflected as they were received from the community, and the next section (Section 4.7.2); will list the top three (3) priority needs for consideration in the 2022/2027 budget.

Table 4.3: Community Needs from Public Consultation

Community needs/priorities	Key issues	Affected Ward and Location	2022-27 IDP Intervention	Funding Source
Water	Need for communal tanks and refurbishment of boreholes Electrical boreholes in Syde, Nordeen	Ward 1, Nordeen, Syde, Edukwini	Procurement of Tanks, refurbishment of boreholes	WSIG
	Upgrading of Methula Scheme Fixing of water leaks at Boxer Section Bulk water Supply and Reticulation network – Entokozweni Section, Mantini Section, Gogo Khumalo Street, Lukhele Street, Vutha Section	WARD 2, Water Scheme, Boxer Section Entokozweni, Mantini,	Upgrading of Methula Scheme phase?	RBIG
	-Bulk Water Supply – Upgrading of Methula Scheme -Maintenance of boreholes	WARD 3, Various areas	refurbishment of boreholes Upgrading of Methula Scheme phase	WSIG RBIG
	Replacement of AC pipes in section A including the pipe from reservoir Construction of reservoir for ward 4 Provision of Jojo tanks at	WARD 4, Mayflower, Maufumbe Caithness, Ndonga, Phola, Goba, Emanyeveni and Gardens	Replacement of AC pipes Upgrading of Methula Scheme phase	MIG RBIG DDM/sectors

	<p>Mafulumbe Extension of water network in Caitness, Ndonga, Phola , Mafulumbe , Goba park 185 , Emanyevereni and next to gardens 4 Jojo tanks Need for communal water tanks</p>	<p>WARD 5, Various areas</p>	<p>Request funding from GSDM</p>	<p>DDM</p>
	<p>1ML Water Reservoir in Sithobela/holeka Need for additional boreholes (4) Bulk water system and reticulation in Oshoek, Hartebeeskop, Sithobela, Ouboom and Mashonamini Yard connections in Oshoek, Hartebeeskop, Sithobela, Ouboom and Mashonamini Need for water tanks in Mashonamini and Robinsdale. Need for boreholes in Sithobela (2), Robinsdale (2), eNkontjini (1), Oshoek (2), and Mashonamini (1).</p>	<p>WARD 6</p>		<p>WSIG RBIG</p>
	<p>Communal water tanks Water reticulation Mayflower gate and Mafulumbe</p>	<p>WARD 7</p>		<p>OPEX</p>
	<p>Bulk water supply pipe and reservoir to Houtbosch and Tykloof Drilling and refurbishment of six (6) boreholes CWP scholar patrols on N17 Upgrade services at the Oshoek Post Office Raised steel tank in TV to reticulate water to TV, Ekuphumuleni, Ekukhanyeni</p>	<p>Ward 8, Tykloof and Houtbosch Various area</p>		<p>RBIG</p>
	<p>Reticulation in Sincobile Hereford, Ngodini, Ntababovu, Waverley, Esandleni need</p>	<p>WARD 9</p>		<p>WSIG</p>

	boreholes Upgrading of electric borehole and a need for additional boreholes to be drilled Fencing of Redhill Reservoir and provision of security to man it Need for communal Jojo tanks at rocky park A and C New steel tank for Elukwatini c Steel tank at Faith section (Jericho church hill) Reticulation at Rocky Park A and B Reticulation at Madiba view, behind old Elukwatini cemetery. Reticulation at Elukwatini C farms. Borehole at Enkhanini with Jojo tank Water Reticulation at Navara section behind Mahlalentabeni	WARD 10 Elukwatini, Arhemburg, Rocky Park, Farm areas		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Bulk water supply to Masuku Section Fix water leaks Upgrading of the Empuluzi Bulk Water Supply Scheme	Ward 11, Masuku Section, Glenmore Entire ward Empuluzi		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Stable water supply in Ngonini and Nhlaba Increase pumping capacity of water at plant to fill up the reservoir Communal tanks needed	Ward 12, Ngonini & Nhlaba Ekulindeni Water Treatment Works Sahhulube, Ngonini & Nhlaba		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Completion of water reticulation project Khuzulwandle, Erma – RDP, Dwaleni, and Mkhomazane Steel tank Dwaleni and Khuzulwandle Drilling and equipping of boreholes Water leaks fixing on Madiba	Ward 13, Khuzulwandle, Entire ward		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG

	Drive				
	Water reticulation in Rockview Water supply network in New Village Upgrading of the Elukwatini / Eerstehoek Water Treatment Works	Ward 14, Rockview New Village Eerstehoek Water Treatment Works			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Installation of bulk water and household taps as well as sewer network (h/h connection) in the settlement next to DSD offices	Ward 15, Silobela			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Bulk water supply to KaNtjwele, Lochiel Communal taps in Phaphama Yard connection and water meters in KaNtjwele, Lochiel Bulk water supply and reticulation in The Brook Upgrading of the Elukwatini / Eerstehoek Water Treatment Works Water reticulation and booster to Sun City (Nhlazatshe 1), New Stand, and the Maketango Section. Booster supply to Sithembe Supermarket until CD Preschool Yard connection to 50 houses in Phumula Section, Nhlazatshe 3 Yard connection to the New Stand (Emasimini) for 30 houses Improve the water supply intervals to the whole area	Ward 16, Lochiel / KaNtjwele Phaphama KaNtjwele / Lochiel The Brook			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Replacement of AC pipes Emanzana town and Dlamini Extension Water reticulation and 200-yard connections in Dlamini E (New Section)	Ward 17, Emanzana town & Dlamini Extension Dlamini E Various areas Magudu			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG

	<p>Drilling and equipping of new boreholes (10) with reticulation network Casting of new reservoir Equipping of the solar borehole in Magudu</p>			
<p>Steel tank for Sun City & Mbhejeka Upgrading of Avontuur Package plant. Reticulation from Holoba to Mbejeka Main pipeline from Holoba to Mbhejeka Fix water leakages Standpipes Zwelisha, Mbejeka, Avontuur, and in Tjakastad 3 boreholes electrified boreholes Repair of the reticulation network to Zwelisha Standpipes in the sports grounds</p>	<p>Ward 18, Mbhejeka Avontuur Mbhejeka Mbhejeka Entire ward Stimbela, Mbejeka Entire ward</p>		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG	
<p>Reconstruction of Enkhomeni reticulation. Upgrading of package plant in Mooiplaas. Refurbishment of existing reticulation system at Mooiplaas and Steynsdorp. Maintenance of 8 boreholes and drilling of additional ones Need for 2 x communal water tanks in Enkhaba.</p>	<p>Ward 19, Enkhomeni Section Mooiplaas Mooiplaas & Steynsdorp Entire ward Enkhaba</p>		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG	
<p>250 houses requiring household water connection Nhlatzatshe 4C two streets need house water connection Increase pumping capacity for water and repair water leaks</p>	<p>Ward 20, Nhlatzatshe 2 and Nhlatzatshe 4 Nhlatzatshe 4C Entire ward</p>		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG	

	<p>Drilling and equipping of new boreholes for: Suikerboschfontein, Ebesuthwini, kaPiet, Moedig, Brakpruit, Dorsbult, kaGary, Eikendal, Lieliefontein x2, kaMgoshi</p> <p>Bulk water supply for Kromkraans</p> <p>Water reticulation in Onbekend and Groenvlei (Putting water meters in these areas can assist in revenue enhancement</p> <p>Extension of piped water from Industrial to Ebuhleni</p> <p>Extension of water pipe from the borehole to the households in Vaalbank</p> <p>Equip windmill to supply water to the communities in Lieliefontein</p> <p>Repair and maintenance of all broken boreholes (Hand pumps and electrified) – consideration should be made on the sinking of windmills to cut on maintenance and energy costs on boreholes</p> <p>Extension of water pipe to kaMthimunye in Caro Park</p> <p>Water quality to be improved</p>	<p>Ward 21, Various farm areas</p> <p>Kromkraans Onbekend / Groenvlei</p> <p>Carolina Vaalbank</p> <p>Lieliefontein</p> <p>Entire ward</p> <p>Caropark</p>	<p>DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG</p>
	<p>Communal water tanks in Tembisa, New Stand, Honingklip, Mahlathini, Magesini, Lekkerloop, Mkingoma, Weergevonden, Ka – Mphuzi D6</p> <p>A booster reservoir in Emanzana</p> <p>Electrical boreholes and reticulation in the following areas</p> <p>Reticulation network (pipes) to collect water from the different</p>	<p>Ward 22 Bulkwater network at Extension 2 Silobela with standpipes</p> <p>Ward 23, Honingklip 125 household, D6 100 household, Mdumane 10 household, Engelsedraai 130 household, New Stand60 houses, kaNgodosi 22 houses and Tenline, Lekkerloop, Mondafili, Weergevonden</p> <p>Weergevonden 1800, Vygeboom 1700, Malahleka 800, Theeboom 2000</p>	<p>WISG</p> <p>DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG</p>

	deep rural areas with electrical borehole areas source to the people in metres with standpipes Replacement of AC pipes in Emanzana Reticulation in the new settlement Diamini D Engabezweni Improve pressure and pumping capacity Embhuleni Lomdzala and area next to reservoir	Ward 24, Ekobheni Nhlatzatshe 5 Ekukhanyeni Plots Nhlatzatshe 5 – The Crossing Town	DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Water reticulation in Ekobheni, booster reticulation Nhlatzatshe No 5 behind Mkhomazane Primary Bulk water supply to Ekukhanyeni Palace Main pipeline in Nhlatzatshe 5 – The Crossing		
	Jojo tanks in the new village Nhlatzatshe 2 next to graveyard Replacement of AC pipes in the whole of Nhlatzatshe Water reticulation in Nhlatzatshe 4C Need for additional boreholes in Sebentani (3)	Ward 25, Nhlatzatshe 2 / Steyns Section Entire ward Nhlatzatshe 4C Sebentani Farm	DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
FOCUS AREA FOR THE MUNICIPALITY: ROADS AND STORMWATER			
Roads and Stormwater	Paving of road next to Jaman Store until to Bakery Maintenance of the main road (Provincial): improve drainage system, attend to the encroaching donga, resurfacing of the road, construct speed-calming measures on the road. Humps to control speeding / road signs and resurface interchange/junctions	Ward 1,	DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG

	<p>Speed humps and footbridges Road Gravelling and Paving of streets Bus Stop along the Diepdale main and arterial roads 14 footbridges needed across the ward to facilitate rural mobility and access</p>	Ward 2		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	<p>Stop street and traffic lights in front of Fernie Shoprite Gravelling for five streets – Shoprite Street, Malinga to Vutha, Mkhaliphi to Mokaba, Clinic to Ema-Aerilini, Maduna Section 13 x footbridges – Highway Section, Ema-Aerilini, Extension 05, Lindzalokuhle to Boxer Installation of traffic lights in front of Shoprite Shopping Precinct Continuation and completion of Mahoxo ring road Construction of the storm damaged Vutha to Mokaba bridge</p>	Ward 3		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	<p>Footbridges Road maintenance and paving of streets Construction of 6 footbridges Paving of streets in Goba Phola main road; completion of section A street. Construction of taxi rank at Mayflower</p>	<p>Ward 4 Entire ward From Timber via Emanyeveni, Veli Panel beaters Phola Section Mayflower Taxi Rank</p>		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	<p>Footbridges A footbridge connecting Dundonald and Sibanesetfu FET College (Glenmore) Streets gravelling and blading Paving of ring road Taxi rank renovation and upgrade</p>	<p>Ward 5 Entire ward Dundonald to Glenmore Entire ward Slovo to Vilakazi Section and Embalenhle School</p>		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG

	<p>Reconstruction of the Slovo bridge - at the Slovo ring road near Hloniphani School. Paving 14 kilometres (Gininda to Vilakazi, Ekuphakameni to Discount, Training center to KaMbatha store) Footbridges (Ka Ngwenya to Mbalenhle cemetery, KaMtshali to Ligugu, Ka Thomo to Glenmore, Ka Zwane to Hloniphani school 4 vehicle bridges (Ka Mndebele to Hloniphani and Mbalenhle school, Ka Maberere to Ligugu, Ka Chief Nhlapho to Ligugu, Ka Gininda to Mbalenhle school.</p>	<p>Dundonald Taxi Rank Slovo Ekuphakameni Various areas</p>		
<p>Paving of Swallowsnest ring road from Ka-Manana to Magotjwa Secondary School. Paving of Bettysoed ringroad from Terminator Tavern to Main Road (via Lusushwane Water Plant) Paving of road D2962 and D2963 connecting villages Bettysoed, Swallowsnest, Robinsdale, Sithobela, and Hartebeeskop to the N17 and Sibanesetu College in Glenmore Paving of Oshoek ringroad via Sports Complex to Oshoek Taxi Rank Road and reconstruction of Robinsdale bridge Road regraveling and street blading. Motorway bridge connecting Mashonamini and Oshoek Construction of Oshoek Taxi</p>	<p>Ward 6 Entire ward Robinsdale Entire ward</p>			<p>DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG</p>

	<p>Rank</p> <p>Footbridges – Etisiteni Primary, Chris Hani, Ka-Jim and Ka-Mbokane</p> <p>Maintenance of Mayflower Main Road</p> <p>Need for a motorway bridge to Ka-Jim, and footbridges at various points</p> <p>Re-gravelling of main roads in Mayflower Gate, Mafufumbe, Ka-Jim, Solomon</p> <p>Re-gravelling of streets</p> <p>Paving of road Mayflower gate and Solomon</p> <p>Paving of road to and beyond Empuluzi High School</p>	<p>Ward 7</p> <p>Etisiteni, Chris Hani, Ka-Jim, Mbokane</p> <p>Main road Ka-Jim</p> <p>Mayflower Gate, Mafufumbe, Solomon, Ka-Jim</p> <p>Entire ward</p>	<p>DDM/sectors</p> <p>WSIG</p> <p>RBIG</p>
	<p>Rank</p> <p>Motorway bridges in Belvedere (3), Tykloof (1)</p> <p>Footbridges in Belvedere, Houtbosch, Lijelembube (Hartebeeskop), Aankomst, Ekuphumuleni, TV Trust, Oshoek</p> <p>Motorway bridges in Belvedere</p> <p>Grading and Re-gravelling of streets</p>	<p>Ward 8</p> <p>Oshoek Taxi Rank</p> <p>3 in Belvedere, 1 in Tykloof next to Maseko</p> <p>3 in Belvedere, 2 in Houtbosch, 3 in Hartebeeskop, 2 in Aankomst, 1 Ekuphumuleni 1 in Oshoek, 2 in TV Trust</p> <p>3 motorway bridges in Belvedere</p> <p>Entire ward</p>	<p>DDM/sectors</p> <p>WSIG</p> <p>RBIG</p>
	<p>Paving of road and street maintenance</p> <p>Footbridges needed in various parts of the ward</p> <p>Paving of Sun City Road</p> <p>Paving of road in Sincobile, Waverly and Esandleni</p>	<p>Ward 9</p> <p>Entire ward</p> <p>Ngodini, Hereford, Esandleni, Waverley Sun City</p> <p>Entire ward</p>	<p>DDM/sectors</p> <p>WSIG</p> <p>RBIG</p>
	<p>Bridge across the river linking Sabatha to Nhlazatshe block 06</p> <p>Speed humps on road D481 at Rocky Park.</p>	<p>Ward 10</p> <p>Sabatha</p> <p>Rocky Park</p> <p>At appropriate points on D481 road</p>	<p>DDM/sectors</p> <p>WSIG</p> <p>RBIG</p>

	<p>Pedestrian sidewalks on road D481. Taxi Passenger Shelters along all taxi routes Paving/ tarring of ring roads Shiba A to Mganwini. Paving / tarring at Elukwatini C access road. Paving / tarring of Sabatha to Nhiazatshe block 06. Paving/ tarring of Mganwini to Madiba view ring road. Paving of Enkhanini access road to Tjakastad main road. Completion of Paving on Embhuleni hospital to D&C ring road Storm water drains at Navara, Faith, Shiba A, Shiba B, Enkhanini, Nazarene. Footbridges at Hapeville and Emganwini.</p>	<p>Various roads Navara, Shiba, Enkhanini & Nazarene Emganwini</p>	
	<p>Paving of ring road from Mhlongo Section to Sidu (4km) A footbridge connecting Dundonald and Sibanesetfu FET College (Glenmore) Re-gravelling of streets 6 Footbridges needed Need for bus shelters along the Glenmore – Robinsdale main road Patching of potholes, stormwater drainage and general maintenance of Glenmore Main Road (Tarred Road)</p>	<p>Ward 11 Mhlongo Section Glenmore – Dundonald Entire ward Various areas Various points along the road</p>	<p>DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG</p>
	<p>Re-gravelling of internal streets Improvement to the existing storm water drainage system and</p>	<p>Ward 12 Entire ward Entire ward</p>	<p>DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG</p>

	<p>erection of new system Completion of Ekulindeni ring road paving project Provide access road to Ncakini Construction of footbridge at Ncakini and Ebutisini Paved road from Nhlaba station to the clinic Paved road from Ngonini station to Ngonini Primary</p>	<p>Ekulindeni Ncakini Ncakini and Ebutisini Nhlaba Ngonini</p>		
	<p>Paving of Khuzulwandle via Mandlamakhulu road. Paving of road to Mbali School via Thubelisha. Maintenance and re-gravelling of streets Road pavements (sidewalks) Pavement from Top centre to Emabovini Pavement from Star shop to Emathuneni Resurfacing of Madiba Drive Footbridges Mkhomazane bridge and traffic calming ridge on the Mkhomazane road</p>	<p>Ward 13 Tjakastad Thubelisha Entire ward Main road Makhosonkhe, Khuzulwandle (3), Mkhomazane (2),</p>		<p>DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG</p>
	<p>Road / street maintenance in Nhlazatshe 3 Footbridges (Nhlazatshe 3 to Dlomodlomo School) Improvement of storm water drainage system Elukwatini Main Road from bridge to Public Works. Paving of ring road in Riverside and Julius Mkhonto village Paving of Nhlazatshe 3 to Traffic Department Road – the remaining stretch of the road.</p>	<p>Ward 14 Nhlazatshe 3 Nhlazatshe 3 / Riverside Elukwatini Main Road Julius Mkhonto Village Nhlazatshe 3 – Traffic Department Elukwatini – Julius Mkhonto Road</p>		<p>DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG</p>

	<p>Paving of roads – Elukwatini Clinic Road, Roma Ring Road Julius Mkhonto.</p> <p>Paving of connecting streets at Mzamo section.</p> <p>Re-gravelling of streets at Mzamo, Caropark Extension, and Silobela X 4, part of Carolina town.</p> <p>Patching of potholes in Carolina town targeting adjacent streets.</p> <p>Construction of Foot Bridges (one between Pump Station and Sobhuza cemetery; one between Silobela X4 and Carolina hospital).</p> <p>Construction of sidewalk paving between Silobela X4 and Carolina town along the R36 National road).</p> <p>Paving of ring road linking Silobela Ext 1, 3 & 4</p> <p>Paving of Ngwenya street behind Silobela community hall – about 200m stretch of road.</p> <p>Paving street from DSD offices to Silobela stadium – about 500m stretch of road.</p>	<p>Ward 15</p> <p>Carolina Town</p> <p>Caropark, Carolina Town and Silobela Extension 4</p> <p>Carolina / Silobela</p> <p>Silobela Extension 4</p> <p>Silobela Extension</p> <p>Silobela Old Location</p> <p>Silobela Old Location</p>		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
<p>Footbridge from Sisukumile Section to Lochiel Primary School</p> <p>Motor bridge from Belvedere A to Belvedere B – from Khubalolemaswati to Linda)</p> <p>Need for speed humps on N17 in front of Lochiel garage.</p> <p>Paving of the Lochiel ring road</p> <p>Paving and Regravelling of streets</p>	<p>Ward 16</p> <p>Lochiel</p> <p>Belvedere</p> <p>N17 Lochiel</p> <p>Lochiel</p> <p>Entire ward</p>			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG

	<p>Paving of Barcelona Ring Road Paving of the Radebe road from Nhlazatshe 3 to Traffic Department. Paving of road from Nhlazatshe Primary to Emathuneni via Hlabangemehlo Secondary School. Paving of road from Emathuneni in Nhlazatshe 1 via Maketango to R38, and construction of a bridge over Nhlazatshe River Two (2) bridges on Lukhele Farm Road Need for a speed hump in front on Mhisi Taxi Owner next to Uncle Joe's Paving of Nhlazatshe 1 main road to Nhlazatshe 3 V-Drains in all the roads proposed for paving</p>			
	<p>Continue with Phase 2 of the paving of roads in Dlamini C Paving of road in Dlamini B, E Paving of Brink and Pilmont Street Micaridge Area from Thandabantu Lekkerloop road by Public Works Extend the paving in Dlamini A to the R38 Stormwater drainage in the roads as the paving is continuing Resurfacing of the Four Rand Road Resurfing of Asphalt Road – Fourie, Robertson, Wallack, Goodman and the Chrissiesmeer road</p>	<p>Ward 17 Dlamini C Dlamini Emanzana town Emanzana Lekkerloop Dlamini to R38 road Entire ward Dlamini Emanzana town Entire ward Dlamini A Emanzana in front of Disco / Total Garage Entire ward</p>		<p>DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG</p>

	Footbridge Dlamini A and B Footbridge on Ngeza stream Dlamini A Overhead bridge on R38 next to Disco Regravelling and blading of other streets				
	Paving of Mbhejeka road from the tarred road Paving of Zwelisha road Construction of Mkhobongo bridge Construction of bridge KaMibhed'uyajika Construction of bridge Emanyeveni Section Construction of bridge from Mtheshi to Sun City Pavement of Maqhawuzela road to Package plant and JM School Mbhonga Bridge at Mbhejeka and at Mkhobongo V- drain and Stormwater drainage system in Phola Emganwini Bridge next to Eyethu Tavern and the one next to Clinic needs to be elevated above flood lines Resurfacing of Madiba Drive and installation V-drains and subsoil drainage and speed humps Speed humps Ekukhanyeni Paving from Insika School to Clinic Gravelling of Sun City to Phola – and all sections Ka – Mhisi (Zwelisha) to Ekukhanyeni paving and bridge Refurbishment of Uitgevonden bridge	Ward 18 Tjakastad Mbhejeka Mbhejeka Phola / Emganwini Mbhonga Bridge Clinic Madiba Drive Insika School Sun City Ekukhanyeni		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG	
		Ward 19 Uitgevonden		DDM/sectors WSIG	

			RBIG
<p>3 x footbridges</p> <p>Completion of 3km ring road in Ebuleni (Mooiplaas)</p> <p>Paving of Nkhaba, Enkhomeni, Bossville and Steynsdorp roads</p> <p>Regravelling of streets</p> <p>Need for a low-level culvert bridge in Bossville</p> <p>Completion of D481 road (Mooiplaas to Ekulindeni.)</p> <p>Tarring / Paving of the provincial road Ebutisini (Nhlaba) to Oshoek.</p>	<p>Bossville</p> <p>Various areas</p> <p>Entire ward</p> <p>Bossville</p> <p>Bossville / Etingobiyane</p> <p>Ebutisini to Oshoek</p>		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
<p>Footbridge from Emseni to Nhlazatshe 1</p> <p>Regravelling of road from KFC to Doctor Shongwe</p> <p>Regravelling 2 for JOY to Puma Garage</p> <p>Paving of road from Puma Garage to Elukwatini with a bridge</p> <p>Re-gravelling of other streets</p> <p>Footbridge from Dlomodlomo Section to Elukwatini (over the Nhlazatshe stream)</p> <p>Footbridge from Tholulwazi to Elukwatini (children go to school in Elukwatini Primary from Nhlazatshe 4, crossing Nhlazatshe stream)</p> <p>Tarring/Paving of the access road from Nhlazatshe 4 Clinic to Puma Garage</p>	<p>Ward 20</p> <p>Emseni</p> <p>Nhlazatshe 4</p> <p>Nhlazatshe 4 & 5</p> <p>Nhlazatshe 4</p> <p>Nhlazatshe 4</p> <p>Nhlazatshe 4</p> <p>Nhlazatshe 4</p> <p>Nhlazatshe 4</p>		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
<p>Re gravelling and blading of access roads</p> <p>Patching of potholes around Carolina town</p>	<p>Ward 21</p> <p>Entire ward</p> <p>Carolina Town</p>		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
<p>Footbridge to Sobhuza School and Silobela Cemetery</p>	<p>Ward 22</p> <p>Silobela Extension</p>		DDM/sectors WSIG

	<p>Paving of streets</p> <p>Speed humps Matyeka Street, and on the ringroad at Ext 2 cemetery</p> <p>Access road for trucks in town</p> <p>V-drain Matyeka Street, Mtsweni Street, Landa passage to Roma and Sobhuza</p> <p>Stormwater drainage at Roma Pond (pool)</p>	<p>Entire ward</p> <p>Silobela</p> <p>Carolina town</p> <p>Silobela/Carolina</p>	<p>RBIG</p>
	<p>Bridges in Mkhingoma (2), behind Mkhingoma (2), Engelsedraai (1), Mondafill (1)</p> <p>Footbridges in Honingklip, Malahleka, and Ka-Makhatane (3)</p> <p>Speed humps on roads in front of schools Engabezweni, Diyane</p> <p>Paving from Malahleka R541 to KJ Malaza access road</p> <p>Continue paving the ring road from Ka 4Rand to town</p> <p>Paving of Thela Street</p> <p>Resurfacing of the Four Rand Road and improve drainage</p> <p>Re-gravelling and blading of streets in the whole ward (very critical)</p> <p>Develop partnership with public works on public works roads, KaMantjolo, Schoeman and Ngodosi and Mondafill</p>	<p>Ward 23</p> <p>Farm areas</p> <p>Farm areas</p> <p>General</p> <p>Malahleka</p> <p>Dlamini</p> <p>Dlamini</p> <p>Entire ward</p>	<p>DDM/sectors</p> <p>WSIG</p> <p>RBIG</p>
	<p>Paving of roads in Nhlazatshe 5, 6 & 7</p> <p>Stormwater drainage along roads</p> <p>Roads regravelling and maintenance of streets</p>	<p>Ward 24</p> <p>Entire ward</p> <p>Entire ward</p> <p>Entire ward</p>	<p>DDM/sectors</p> <p>WSIG</p> <p>RBIG</p>
	<p>Paving of Nhlazatshe 2 ring road</p>	<p>Ward 25</p> <p>Nhlazatshe 2</p> <p>Nhlazatshe 1 – Nhlazatshe 3</p>	<p>DDM/sectors</p> <p>WSIG</p> <p>RBIG</p>

	Resurfacing of Barcelona ring road and construction of a pedestrian pavement along that road in Nhlazatshe 1 & 3 Footbridges – Roma Crèche, St. Johns, and Sebentani Farm to Nhlazatshe 1 Re gravelling of roads in the ward Foot bridge next to St. Johns	Nhlazatshe 1 / Riverside Barcelona Ring Road Entire ward Nhlazatshe 1		
FOCUS AREA FOR THE MUNICIPALITY: ELECTRICITY				
Electricity	10 x high mast lights Need for household electricity connections in the ward – about 50 houses need electricity connection	Ward 1 Entire ward Entire ward		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	14 x electricity post connections Need for high mast lights – 6 high mast lights in total	Ward 2 Various areas Vutha, Entokozweni, Ema-Aerilini & Mahoxo		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Maintenance if high mast lights	Ward 3 Entire ward		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Electrification of households (48) Provision of 11 high mast lights	Ward 4 Goba, Ndonga Entire ward		
	Electrification of boreholes 4 high mast light needed and maintenance of 6 existing high mast lights.	Ward 5 Various areas Entire ward		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Electrification of houses in parts of Sithobela, parts of Robinsdale, and Beeskop Ka-Mkhize. Highmast lights in Oshoek (1), Ouboom (1), and Bettysgoes (1).	Ward 6 Sithobela, Robinsdale, and Ka-Mkhize		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Electrification of boreholes High mast lights (2) – Mayflower gate and B3 Household electrification in Chris	Ward 7 Ka-Jim, Mafumbe Chris Hani		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG

	Hani High mast lights required in various areas	Solomon Section, Maufumbe, Mayflower Gate and Ka-Jim		
	Electrification of 150 houses across the ward 20 high mast lights in various areas of the ward	Ward 8 Various areas		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Sun City the lower section has no electricity Electrification in Hereford Maintenance of high mast lights Need for 8 additional high mast lights	Ward 9 A section of Sun City Hereford Entire ward Entire ward		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Streetslights from CBD to the Municipality Road High mast lights (maintenance of existing ones and need for 8 additional allocations across the ward.	WARD 10 The Crossing Town Entire ward		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Maintenance of the existing high mast lights 7 new high mast lights needed	Ward 11 Entire ward		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	14 High mast light for the entire ward Provide Electricity at Ncakini, Kranskop and Josefsdal	Ward 12 Entire ward Ncakini, Kranskop & Josefsdal		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	60 houses without electricity in Khuzulwandle, Mahlabathini, Top Centre, Mkhomazane Need for high mast lights (10) The 9 streetslights must be energized	Ward 13 Khuzulwandle Entire ward		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Additional high mast lights in Elukwatini A and Rockview Maintenance of streetslights in Loan Homes	Ward 14 Elukwatini A & Rockview Loan Homes		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Installation of high mast lights targeting dark areas (behind	Ward 15 Silobela		DDM/sectors WSIG

					RBIG DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Ezenzeleni School). Electrification of 50 houses in the new village in Lochiel Electrified boreholes in Lochiel, Daaspoort 1&2, Mission, Belvedere, Milliken and Phaphama Need for high mast lights (15 in Lochiel, 13 in Nhlazatshe 1&3, 4 in The Brook, 4 in Milliken and Phaphama, and 2 in Mission. 30 houses need electricity connection in New Stand (Emasimini), and 10 houses in New Stand (Emabuyeni) 4 houses have no electricity next to Roma Church in Nhlazatshe 3	Ward 16 Lochiel, Mangcuzu N17 rural communities			
	Upgrading of electricity infrastructure Emanzana town Backlog of household electrification in Farm areas Erection of new high mast lights (10) Maintenance of existing high mast lights and streets lights Dlamini A streetlights not energized	Ward 17 Emanzana Substation 15 Farm areas Entire ward Emanzana town Dlamini A			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	10 x high mast lights Maintenance of existing high mast lights Ekukhanyeni high mast light never got energized since it was erected by Komati Mine Communities are complaining that FBE coupons are not Household electrification for 50 houses	Ward 18 Entire ward Emkhukhwini, Etimbokodvweni, Emphelemdaba.			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Electrification of Enkhomeni New Stands.	Ward 19 New Stands			DDM/sectors WSIG

	14 x high mast lights	Entire ward	RBIG
	Crime fighting strategies need to be implemented immediately Need for high mast lights to prevent crime in the community	Ward 20 Entire ward	DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Completion of household connection left by Eskom in Moedig area project known as Helpmekaar cluster Public lighting ERF 500, Groenvlei, Ebuhleni & Asithandaneni Households' electrification in farm areas	Ward 21 Moedig / Helpmekaar Groenvlei Farm areas	DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	High mast lights needed in the township – 6 high mast lights	Ward 22 Silobela	DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Electricity connection for 300 households Streetslights from 4Rand to Enkomo; and 9 high mast lights needed Kalkloof and KaNgodosi, D6 and Mondafill electrification – the farm owners refuse to grant way leave. 15 rural areas need electrical boreholes	Ward 23 Schoeman, Mkhingoma, New Stands, Lekkerloop, Mondafill Emanzana	DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Need for high mast lights in Nhiazatshe 5, 6 & 7	Ward 24 Entire ward	DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Additional high mast lights LVM Connections Maintenance of high mast lights and streetslights	Ward 25 Entire ward Entire ward Entire ward	DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
FOCUS AREA FOR THE MUNICIPALITY: REFUSE REMOVAL			
Refuse Removal	Provision of households bins: 1000 section A; 1800 Goba; 400 Phola and provision of skip bins	Ward 4 Goba, Section A, Phola	DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG

	Waste removal and dumping site in Oshoek and Swallowsnest	Ward 6 Swallowsnest			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Shipmaster bin at Redhill – Madi Garage / Postal Agency Convert the dumping site into a landfill site Household bins to be provided for 200 households	Ward 9 Madi Garage Precinct Redhill / Ntababovu Sun City			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Refuse Bins and Collection in all sections. Shipmaster bins must be emptied weekly	Ward 10 Entire ward Entire ward			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Legalized refuse collection site, fenced according to standards Extension of waste refuse removal to other areas such as Nhlaba, Ngonini and Ekulindeni RDP Extension	Ward 12 Ekulindeni Nhlaba & Ngonini			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Need for skip bins (5)	Ward 13 Entire ward			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Need for 2 x Skip bins in Nhlazatshe 1 Skipmaster bin next to Derrick Nhlazatshe 1 Skipmaster bin next to Themba Skhiya Skipmaster bin next to Hlabangemehlo School Skipmaster bin towards Emathuneni Nhlazatshe 3, and next to Barcelona Tavern, and next to Kali Supermarket	Ward 16 Nhlazatshe 1 Nhlazatshe 3			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Need for the development of new landfill site Provide households with household bins and 4 Skipmaster bins	Ward 17 Emanzana Entire ward			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Household refuse bins	Ward 22			DDM/sectors

		Entire ward			WSIG RBIG
	10 Skipmaster bins	Ward 23 Entire ward			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
FOCUS AREA FOR THE MUNICIPALITY: CEMETERIES					
Cemeteries	Identification of land for the establishment of a new graveyard and formalization thereof.	Ward 1 Etinkhulungwane			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Fencing of old graveyard: palisade fencing	Ward 4 Mayflower Old Cemetery			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Identification of a site for cemetery, and upgrading of existing cemeteries Fencing of Bettysoed cemeteries.	Ward 6 Various			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Fencing of old graveyards Paving of road to the new cemetery	Ward 9 Mayflower Sun City			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Paving of Glenmore Cemeteries Road	Ward 11 Glenmore			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	A fully serviced and well fenced site for new cemetery	Ward 12 Ekulindeni			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Fencing of cemetery in Tjakastad and debushing and weeding of the graveyard Need for development of new cemetery	Ward 13 Tjakastad cemetery			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Fencing of Sobhuza Cemetery and paving of the entrance and exit streets at the cemetery precinct.	Ward 15 Silobela Cemetery			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Fencing of graveyard in Nhlazatshe 1, 3 and Lochiel	Ward 16 Nhlazatshe / Lochiel			DDM/sectors WSIG

	Water connection to the cemeteries in Nhlazatshe 1 and 3 Toilets in both cemeteries – Nhlazatshe 1 & 3				RBIG
	Need for new graveyard Fencing of Miccaridge Farm Cemetery	Ward 17 Emanzana			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Fencing KaLamthuna cemetery Identify land for new cemeteries Fencing of all other communal cemeteries	Ward 18 Tjakastad			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Fencing of Silobela (Sobhuza) Cemetery Public toilets at Silobela cemetery	Ward 22 Silobela			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Cemeteries / Fencing of cemetery	Ward 24 Nhlazatshe			RBIG
FOCUS AREA FOR THE MUNICIPALITY: PUBLIC AMENITIES					
Public Amenities	Sports facilities Need for a new community hall Youth development projects with assistance by parastatals such as Komatiland Forests	Ward 1 Etinkhulungwane Syde			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Need for a public library Renovation of Fernie Community Hall	Ward 2 Fernie B Fernie B			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Renovation and maintenance of Fernie Thusong Centre	Ward 3 Fernie Thusong Centre			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Provision of an old – age home Upgrading of Empuluzi Post Office	Ward 4 Mayflower Mayflower			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Need for a public Library Police station Renovation of schools - Ligugu, Ekuphakameni, Hloniphani, Mlambongwane and Mbalenhle	Ward 5 Dundonald Dundonald Dundonald Circuit			DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG

	Fence at Ligugu and Ekuphakameni	Ward 6 Oshoek Postal Agency Sithobela, Hartebeeskop, Oshoek		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Multipurpose Centre in Oshoek Public Library in Oshoek Water shortage in Oshoek Clinic and Bettysgoed Clinic Upgrade services at the Oshoek Post Office Mobile telephony signal coverage is a problem across all major providers Recreational Park Fencing of Swallowsnest Community Hall			
	Clinic in Sun City / Redhill Police station Need for a community hall	Ward 9 Sun City / Red Hill Dundonald Redhill		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Need for a community library in Arhemburg Need for proper structure at Arhemburg clinic.	Ward 10 Arhemburg		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Rehabilitation of Glenmore Stadium and Community Hall Complex Construction of Tsatselani School Hall	Ward 11 Glenmore		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Renovation of Ekulindeni Community Hall and furniture New community hall in Nhlababa Renovation of Ekulindeni Stadium Construction of a combo court at Ekulindeni	Ward 12 Ekulindeni Nhlababa Ekulindeni Ekulindeni		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Public library and Wi-Fi connectivity Skills Centre Elevate the Police Station to be a fully-fledged police station	Ward 13 Entire ward		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Indoor sporting facilities – Silobela	Ward 15		DDM/sectors

	Community Hall	Silobela Community Hall		WSIG RBIG
	Youth Development Centre SAPS Mobile Multipurpose Centre	Ward 16 Lochiel		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Upgrading of Emanzana Cultural Centre Wi-Fi improvement at the public library Renovation of the structure in Magudu used as a Voting Station (Inyathane Old School) Badplaas Shelter to be built into a formal structure	Ward 17 Emanzana Magudu Magudu Emanzana		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Need for a community hall in Mooiplaas Need for community multipurpose (Library, internet services etc.) centre at Steynsdorp and Mooiplaas.	Ward 19 Ebhleni Steynsdorp		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Gymnasium and Park Renovation of the Silobela Community Hall Construction of Sports ground and outdoor gymnasium Construction of creche Construction of Training Centre Gardening project next to Nhlapho	Ward 22 Silobela Silobela Silobela		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	3 Community Halls, and renovation of the one in Schoeman	Ward 23 Malahleka, Engabezweni, Alliance / Weergevonden		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Community Hall in Nhlazatshe 7 Library Secondary School FET College Sports Facility	Ward 24 Nhlazatshe 5,6, and 7		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG

	Youth Skills Training Centre Community Library Construction of a Combo-Court	Ward 25 Entire ward		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
FOCUS AREA FOR THE MUNICIPALITY: SANITATION				
Sanitation	Need for toilets for the community - SmartSan	All wards		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Provision of sewer network for various areas	Ward 4, Ward 7 Goba and surroundings, Phola Provision of VIP toilets for sections: Part of Goba, Bakery, Ndonga, Mafufumbe, Caithness and part of Phola		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Need for SmartSan toilets	Ward 11 Glenmore		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Continuation of the erection / installation of EnviroSan/SmartSan toilets for Nhlaba, Ngonini, Kranskop, Ncakini, Ka-Mboyi, Sahhulube and Josefsdal Completion of sewer network in Ekulindeni	Ward 12 Various areas Ekulindeni WWWTW		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Maintenance and upgrading of sewer network VIP toilets in New Village Maintenance of sewer network in Julius Mkhonto to mitigate spillage	Ward 14 Elukwatini WWWTW New Village Julius Mkhonto Village		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Installation of sewer network (bulk and h/h connections) at Silobela X4 – Two areas / sections badly affected (for more than eight years now).	Ward 15 Silobela Extension 4		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Need for water reticulation and sewer connection in Lochiel,	Ward 16 Lochiel / The Brook		DDM/sectors WSIG

	Nhlazatshe 1, The Brook VIPs / SmartSan in Lochiel, The Brook, Milliken, and Phaphama. VIP toilets full in Nhlazatshe 1 and 3, need for honey sucking Need for SmartSan toilets in Nhlazatshe 1 and 3	Entire ward		RBIG
	Waterborne sewer and toilet structures in Dlamini Extension VIP toilets / SmartSan (about 300) Maintenance of old VIPs	Ward 17 Emanzana Entire ward Entire ward		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Sewer connection in Dlamini, Phola and Moolman VIP toilets need (critical) VIP toilets are beyond carrying capacity 50 houses in Diyane need to be supplied new VIPs Flushing VIPs – waterborne sewer	Ward 23 Dlamini Extension, Phola, Moolman Farm areas Dlamini		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Honeysucker	Ward 24 Nhlazatshe 5,6, and 7		WSIG
FOCUS AREA FOR THE MUNICIPALITY: LED				
LED	Intervention on Youth Centre Project	Ward 1 Entire ward		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Reviving of Mayflower Mall project and refurbishment Mayflower complex Opportunities should be made available for the SMMEs Mall or shopping centre	Ward 4 Mayflower Shopping Complex SMMEs and Co-Operatives		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
		Ward 5 Dundonald		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Fresh produce market in Oshoek	Ward 6 Oshoek		DDM RBIG
	Fresh produce market in Oshoek	Ward 8 Oshoek		DDM RBIG

	Shopping Complex Job opportunities and cooperative support	Ward 9 Mayflower Entire ward		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Repositioning of the hawkers at the 4-way junction – designated hawkers' stalls	Ward 10 The Crossing Town		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Skills development and cooperative support Revive Tjakastad bakery and Lusizo lomphakathi Township establishment in Khuzulwandle	Ward 13 Entire ward Khuzulwandle		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Need for a Shopping Complex in Emanzana Retailers to be improved Thembela Skills Development Centre to be repositioned to perform the functions it was initially intended to perform	Ward 17 Emanzana		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Skills development and job creation and support for SMMEs Isibindi Care Workers can be placed in schools as part of skills development. Backyard garden support	Ward 18 Tjakastad Agriculture		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Job creation is paramount Regravelling of road from KFC to Doctor Shongwe Regravelling 2 for JOY to Puma Garage SASSA Pay points should be identified nearby	Ward 20 Entire ward		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Industrial site in Dlamini, and a Shopping Centre Youth Development and SMME support	Ward 23 Entire ward		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
	Request to be allocated a Community Development Worker	Ward 23 Community		DDM/sectors WSIG

	(CDW) in the ward. Formalization of New Stand into a township 10 rural areas need electrical boreholes Designated grazing land			RBIG
	Youth Development and SMME Support	Ward 24		DDM/Sectors
	Resuscitation of the poultry farm in Nhlazatshe 1 Need for a decentralized shopping mall near the Lochiel / Emanzana / Nhlazatshe junction	Ward 25 Nhlazatshe 1 Weergevonden Farm / Crashers		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG
FOCUS AREA FOR THE MUNICIPALITY : HUMAN SETTLEMENTS				
Human Settlements	Need for RDP houses	All wards need allocation for RDP houses		DDM/sectors WSIG RBIG

4.8. Programmes and Projects for Land Use Management and Township Establishment

Spatial Proposals

The spatial proposals for the Municipality were aligned with the development principles of the GSDM SDF. The method used in developing the spatial proposals include:

- a) Examine and investigate current urban and rural form
 - Urban Edges: The three main urban centers in the Municipality are Carolina, Badplaas and Elukwatini.
 - In Carolina, there are a number of vacant municipal stands that can be made available for future development. The town is not rapidly growing, hence, there is no need to increase the urban edge. Rather it is more vital to encourage intensification so that the Municipality is able to provide basic services and curb urban sprawl.
 - Badplaas is a key tourism node. Future expansion of the town will be vital to take the development of the urban edge into consideration which will be dependent on the growth trend of the town.
 - Elukwatini is the fastest growing node in the Municipality. The growth trends in the area will result in the need to identify future growth patterns and manage and encourage intensification.
- b) Environmental management areas
 - CALLM is home to several areas of high biodiversity and centers of endemism around eManzana. As such, to comply with SPLUMA and to protect environmentally sensitive areas, and "Environmental Protection Zone was constructed, which is referred to as "Environmental Management Area".
 - Below is a map of the Environmental Management Areas in CALLM
- c) Identify important corridors and activity spines
 - There are five major corridors that traverse the Municipality. These include: the N17 corridor linking Johannesburg to Oshoek border; the R541 that serves as a north south link between the R38 and N17; the R36 which links Ermelo to Carolina, via Breyten; the R33 that connects Carolina and eMkhondo via Warburton and Amsterdam; the R38 which links the four most prominent roads in the district (R23, N17, N11 and R36) and is economically important as it links Barberton, Nelspruit, and Malelane.

Spatial proposals per node:

The SDF further targets key urban and rural areas in the Municipality indicating where the various spatial proposals are directed.

Carolina / Silobela:

A: Pieter de Bruin Park and Carolina Extension 3 (Proposed Mixed Use Zone)

- Currently, the portion of land on both sides of the R33 regional road is vacant and municipal owned. An approved General Plan of the area does exist. It is proposed that this area is developed as a mixed-use zone. Mixed-use is inclusive of residential, small business and community facilities.
- Mixed Use Development in Pieter de Bruin Park, Carolina Ext 3 & Silobela Ext 4 is priority for the next Year 5 – Year 10 period.

B: Central Business District

- Carolina is still the largest service node in the CALLM in terms of economic and community services provided e.g. offices, retail, service industries, medical facilities, schools etc. It is recommended that all business and retail activities be restricted to this area. Protecting and enhancing the CBD.
- Protecting and enhancing of the CBD is a priority for the next Year 0 – Year 5.

C: Built-up areas (densification: vacant land)

- All vacant land within the urban edge must first be developed before any future extensions are considered. A mixed land use approach could be considered e.g. residential, community facilities, retail (at a smaller scale as proposed in the CBD area).

D and E: Industrial Zone and Future Industrial Development Zone

- There are limited industrial activities that exist within the CALLM however, Zone D and Zone E relates to industrial land uses in Carolina. The figure below proposes that the area marked with a (C – Proposed truck stop) should become a node for truck transport related activities which could include parking, repair workshops, tyre sales etc.

- Protecting and enhancing the Industrial Area (D&E) and the development of land use proposals for the industrial area catering for truck transport related activities should be prioritised for Year 5- Year 10.

Carolina industrial area

F: Proposed Future Extension

- Once all vacant land and proposed mixed-use zones are developed, only then should any proposed future extensions be considered in Zone F. Zone F is prone to environment sensitivity and development within this proposed area should be discussed with the relevant environmental authorities before any development commence.
- Mixed use development in Zone F may become a priority within the Year 10 – Year 20 timeframe. However, development on the edge of the existing urban footprint should only happen when no more vacant or developable land is available elsewhere.

G: Future Mixed Use Developments

- Walking and cycling become more viable by grouping residential, commercial, and recreational uses in close proximity to one another. Mixed land use zones also enhance the livability of a certain area. Zone G should, therefore, be a priority for mixed use development.
- Mixed use development in Zone G may become a priority within the Year 10 – Year 20 timeframe. However, development on the edge of the existing urban footprint should only happen when no more vacant or developable land is available elsewhere.

Existing Infrastructure Projects – Short term projects 2015 -2016

Projects	Project Description/Feasibility	No of Units	Funding Requirements
Project 1: Carolindia Ext 2	The site was previously used as a landfill site. Conduct a feasibility on its suitability to be used for residential purposes	200	R 200 000.00
Project 2: Carolindia Ext 3	The site is located west of the R33 towards Warburton. Geotech investigation will be required accompanied by an environmental screening report.	250	R 200 000.00
Project 3: CPA Farm at Silobela (Portion 4 and the RE of the farm Droogvallei 41 IT)	The farms are however being developed with many houses without the required planning. The sites should be investigated to determine if the respective development complies with the relevant legislation.	30	R 250 000.00
Project 4: Silobela Ext 4	A draft layout exists for the area. The township establishment process needs to be finalised including the registration of the General Plan. Services have been installed and only road infrastructure is required	1051	R 1 787 750.00
Project 5: Silobela Ext 3	The area has an approved General Plan and the engineering services have been installed in the area. The units in the area have not settled according to the layout and need to be relocated to conform to the layout.	2000	R 1 200 000.00
Project 6: Carolina Ext 3	A developer has been granted an option to develop Carolina Ext 3. The development will comprise of 350 potential sites which will accommodate 150 low income, 100 rental stock, 200 FLISP and high-income sites.	350	R 5 953 350.00
Project 7: Pieter de Bruin Park	The development will comprise of 500 potential sites which will accommodate 275 low income, 200 rental stock and high-income sites.	500	R 850 500.00
Project 8: Water reservoir	The current water capacity of the municipality is not able to accommodate the existing and future settlements in Carolina and Silobela. Upgrade required.		R 13 million
Project 9: Silobela Ext 3	The township requires the construction of 1500 top structures.	1500	R111 900 000.00 (R74600 unit cost)

Medium Projects 2017 – 2018

Projects	Project description/feasibility	No of units	Funding requirements
Project 10: Flood area Silobela	Many informal units are in the flood area. Many informal units are in the flood area. The houses that are in the 1:100-year flood line area need to be relocated to alternative areas.		R 250 000.00

Project 11: Portion 7 Droogvallei	The area has been earmarked as one of the SDAs in the municipality. A feasibility assessment needs to be undertaken to determine the suitability of the portion of land for future development.	100	R 200 000.00
Project 12: Portion 4 Goedehoop	The portion of land is registered to the Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality.	2000	R 350 000.00
Project 13: Carolindia Ext 3	Once the ownership of the area between the rail and the R33 has been confirmed the municipality should procure the portion of land.		
Project 14: Carolindia Ext 2	Township establishment	500 (FLISP 200, Rental 150, Low cost 300)	R 850 500.00
Project 15: Carolina Ext 3	Ensure that sufficient bulk engineering capacity is available for the development of Carolina Ext 3	350	R 789 600.00
Project 16: Pieter de Bruin Park	Ensure that sufficient bulk engineering capacity is available for the development of Pieter de Bruin Park.	500	R 1 128 000.00
Project 17: Silobela Ext 4	The township establishment process should be completed. The stands have already been occupied with informal units; therefore, the new structures will replace the informal units.	700	R 52 220 000.00 (R74600 unit cost)

-Badplaas/eManzana

A and B: Tourism Zone

- Tourism plays a vital role within the economy of CALLM. The identified tourism zone should be enhanced.

C: Business Node

- Limited business activities exist within the Badplaas node. The existing business node should be strengthened to serve the existing residents and lure potential tourists to the area.
- Protecting and enhancing zone C, the business node, is a priority for the next Year 0 – Year 5 period. Whiles strengthen business node is an ongoing priority for the next Year 5 – Year 10.

D: Future Mixed Use Developments

- Walking and cycling become more viable by grouping residential, commercial and recreational uses in close proximity to one another. Mixed land use zones also enhance the livability of a certain area. Zone G should, therefore, be prioritised for mixed use development.
- Mixed use development in Zone D may become a priority within the Year 10 – Year 20 timeframe. However, development on the edge of the existing urban footprint should only occur when no more vacant or developable land is available elsewhere.

E: Existing Agricultural Land

- Agricultural land is important within any Municipality. This zone should be preserved for the use of only agricultural land.
- Existing agricultural land should always be protected unless proven otherwise.
- Agricultural Potential - Rural Development Plan:
 - Establish FPSU in the area, linked with Capacity Building.
 - Establish mill in the area to allow farmers to add value to products.
- Provide training to diversify crops as well as infrastructure.

F: Built-up areas (Densification: Vacant Land)

- All vacant land within the urban edge must first be developed before any future extensions are considered. A mixed land use approach should be considered e.g. residential, community services etc.

G: Proposed Future Extension

- Once all vacant land and proposed mixed-use zones are developed only then should any proposed future extensions be considered.
- Mixed use development in Zone G may become a priority within the Year 10 – Year 20 timeframe. However, development on the edge of the existing urban footprint should only happen when no more vacant or developable land is available elsewhere.

Existing Infrastructure Projects (Badplaas/eManzana)

Short Term Projects (2015-2016)

Projects	Project Description/Feasibility	No of Units	Funding Requirements
Project 1: Badplaas Town	The township consists of 125 stands and is vested with Public Works. The area needs to be densified through the amendment of the layout.	250	R 250 000.00

Projects	Project Description/Feasibility	No of Units	Funding Requirements
Project 2: Badplaas Town	Confirm the status of the application to Public Works to obtain the 125 sites at Badplaas	250	R 100 000.00
Project 3: Badplaas Farm	Confirm the status of the application to Public Works to obtain the 125 sites at Badplaas	500	R 850 500.00
Project 4: Water Treatment Works	Enlargement of the Water Treatment Works. The sewerage treatment works have sufficient capacity at the moment.		R 16 000 000.00

Medium Term Projects (2017-2018)

Projects	Project Description/Feasibility	No of Units	Funding Requirements
Project 5: Badplaas farm	The Department of Rural development and Land Administration has entered into an agreement to purchase the portion of land and establish 500 residential sites (see project 3 above)	500	R 100 000.00
Project 6: Badplaas Town	The amendment of the General Plan should be undertaken to create the 250 sites.	250 (100 rental stock, 150 FLISP, 90 high income)	R 425 250.00
Project 7: Badplaas Farm	The township establishment should be concluded, and the engineering services should be planned and installed.	250	R 6 000 000.00

Long-Term Projects (2019-2020)

Projects	Project Description/Feasibility	No of Units	Funding Requirements
Project 8: Rural Community	A comprehensive study needs to be commissioned for the surrounding informal settlement at Badplaas. The units are located on Communal Trust Land. The study needs to classify the settlements in line with the requirements of the National Upgrading Support Programme.		R 200 000.00
Project 9: Badplaas Farm	The top structures for the area should be constructed The beneficiaries for the proposed 500 houses should be sourced from the immediate area.	500	R 37 300 000.00 (Unit cost R74 600)

Projects	Project Description/Feasibility	No of Units	Funding Requirements
Project 10: Badplaas Town	The revised layout should allow for the development of 100 rental units. The top structures for the rental units should be constructed. The layout will further allow for 150 FLISP erven which should be provided to the qualifiers. The remaining 90 high-income stands should be sold in line with the MFMA.	200	R 10 411 200.00 (R104 112-unit cost)

- Elukwatini Tjakastad

Central Business District

- Substantial growth has taken place within the Elukwatini node. It is recommended as far as possible that all business and retail activities should be restricted to the areas indicated in RED (Map 43), to strengthen the existing business node and to fulfill its purpose as a service node. The node also provides some community services e.g., medical facilities.

B: Built-up areas (Densification: Vacant Land)

- All vacant land within the urban edge must first be developed before any future extensions are considered. A mixed land use approach should be considered e.g. residential, community services etc. Figure 55 shows the current formal vacant stands within the Elukwatini node.

Figure 55: Elukwatini/Tjakastad formal vacant stands

C: Proposed Future Extension

- Once all vacant land within the existing formal and rural areas are developed only then should any proposed future extensions be considered.

Existing infrastructure projects (Elukwatini/Tjakastad)

Short Term Projects (2015-2016)

Projects	Project Description/Feasibility	No of Units	Funding Requirements
Project 1: Elukwatini B Ext	The area has been earmarked for future housing in the SDF. The area is located north of Elukwatini B Ext 1 and is currently being utilised for agricultural purposes.	1500	R 350 000.00
Project 2: Elukwatini BA ext	The area is located west of Elukwatini BA Ext 1 and has been earmarked in the SDF as a Strategic Development Area.	500	R 350 000.00

Project 3: Elukwatini BA	The layout for the area has been approved. The General Plan for the area needs to be completed and submitted to the Surveyor General for approval	500 (100 high income, 150 rental stock, FLISP 250)	R 850 500.00
Project 4: Elukwatini	Construct bulk pipelines to all unserviced settlements		R 60 million
Project 5: Tjakastad	Construct additional reticulation at Tjakastad		R 9 million

Medium Term Projects (2017-2018)

Projects	Project Description/Feasibility	No of Units	Funding Requirements
Project 6: Nhlanzatshe	The area has been identified as an SDA in terms of the Chief Albert Luthuli SDF. A feasibility study needs to be conducted for the area	750	R 250 000.00
Project 7: Elukwatini B Ext	The portion of land needs to be procured is the feasibility studied deemed it feasible.	T.B.D	T.B.D
Project 8: Elukwatini B Ext	Township establishment	1500	R 2 551 500.00
Project 9: Elukwatini BA	Plan and install the required engineering services.	500	R 12 000 000.00
Project 10: Elukwatini BA	The need in the area is for FLISP stands and rental housing. The 150 rental houses need to be constructed for the area.	150	R 15 616 800.00 (R104 112-unit cost)

Long-Term Projects (2019-2020)

Projects	Project Description/Feasibility	No of Units	Funding Requirements
Project 11: Elukwatini	The settlements in the area should be categorised in terms of the standards of the national Upgrading Support Programme.		R 400 000.00

Project 12: Elukwatini BA ext	The portion of land needs to be procured if the feasibility studied deemed it feasible	T.B.D	T.B.D
Project 13: Nhlazatshe	The portion of land needs to be procured if the feasibility studied deemed it feasible	750	T.B.D
Project 14: Nhlazatshe	Township Establishments	750	R 1 275 750.00
Project 15: : Elukwatini BA ext	Township Establishments	500	R 850 500.00
Project 16: Elukwatini BA	Construct the top structures in the area.	1500	R 111 900 000. (R 74 600.00 unit cost)

- Ekulindeni

A: Future Mixed Use Developments

Some formal areas exist within the Ekulindeni node, and it is recommended that mixed use development should occur. Walking and cycling become more viable by grouping residential, commercial, and recreational uses in close proximity to one another. Mixed land use zones also enhance the vitality and perceived security of an area.

B: Built-up areas (Densification: Vacant Land)

All vacant land within the urban edge must first be developed before any future extensions are considered. A mixed land use approach should be considered e.g., residential, community services etc.

The figures below depict the current formal vacant stands within the Ekulindeni area.

Ekulindeni formal vacant sites

- Dundonald

A: Business Activities

A detailed study is required to determine a suitable location for a proposed business node. The previous Spatial Development Framework of CALLM identified a business node highlighted in red on the map below. This is an ideal area to develop a node for business activities.

B: Built-up areas (Densification: Vacant Land)

All vacant land within the proposed urban and rural edge must first be developed before any future extensions are considered. A mixed land use approach should be considered e.g. residential, community services etc. The figure below depicts the current formal vacant stands within the Dundonald area.

C: Cultivated Commercial Fields

Map 46: Agriculture is an important sector within the CALLM. No development should occur within this area.

D: Proposed Future Extension

Map 46: Once all vacant land within the existing formal and rural areas are developed only then should any proposed future extensions be considered.

In order to comply with SPLUMA regulations the following principles will apply to the node:

- Year 0 – Year 5: Densification
- Year 5 – Year 10: Enhance Business and Industrial Activities
- Year 10 – Year 20: Future Extensions

Existing infrastructure projects Dundonald

Short Term Projects (2015-2016)

Projects	Project Description/Feasibility	No of Units	Funding Requirements
Project 1: Mafumulo	The area has been identified as an SDA in terms of the Chief Albert Luthuli SDF. A feasibility study needs to be conducted	2000	R 350 000.00
Project 2: Robbinsdale	Township Establishment	302	R 513 700.00
Project 3: Dundonald	138 Top Structures for the PHP program has been allocated to the area. The structures need to be completed.	138	R 10 294 800 (Unit cost R74 600)
Project 4: Mafumulo	168 Top Structures for the PHP program has been allocated to the area. The structures need to be completed	168	R 12 532 800.00 (Unit cost R74 600)
Project 5: Belvidere	Ward Councillor indicated that an unknown number of top structures in terms of the Rural Subsidy are required for the area.	±70	R 5 222 000.00 (Unit cost R74 600)

Medium Term Projects (2017-2018)

Projects	Project Description/Feasibility	No of Units	Funding Requirements
Project 6: Mafumulo	If the feasibility study deemed the area feasible the portions of land need to be procured.	2 000	T.B.D
Project 7: Redhill	Township Establishment	241	R 410 000.00
Project 8: Hereford	Township Establishment	261	R 450 000.00
Project 9: Dundonald	Upgrade reservoir capacity at Dundonald		R 7 million
Project 10: Dundonald	There are approximately 500 available sites for the area that require top structures according to the municipality	500	R 37 300 000.00 (Unit cost R74 600)

Long-Term Projects (2019-2020)

Projects	Project Description/Feasibility	No of Units	Funding Requirements
Project 11: Mafumulo	Township Establishment	2000	R 3 402 000.00
Project 12: Dundonald	Construct additional reticulation at Dundonald	T.B.D	R 1.2 million
Project 13: Dundonald	There are approximately 500 available sites for the area that require top structures according to the municipality	500	R 37 300 000.00 (Unit cost R74 600)

- Empuluzi

A/D: Activity/Business Node

It is proposed that the area indicated in Red (A) in the figure below be strengthened as a minor business node. An existing filling station is located on site. The areas depicted in Purple (B) & (C) identify some industrial activities within the node. A detailed study is required to create a business node in the area depicted in Blue (D).

Empuluzi economic activities

E: Built-up areas (Densification: Vacant Land)

All vacant land within the proposed urban and rural edge must first be developed before any future extensions are considered. A mixed land use approach should be considered e.g. residential, community services etc. Figure 70 depicts the current formal vacant stands within the Empuluzi area.

Empuluzi formal vacant stands

F: Proposed Future Extension

Once all vacant land within the existing formal and rural areas are developed only then should any proposed future extensions be considered. A detailed geotechnical study is required for any future proposed developments.

In order to comply with SPLUMA regulations the following principles will apply to the node:

- Year 0 – Year 5: Densification
- Year 5 – Year 10: Enhance Business and Industrial Activities
- Year 10 – Year 20: Future Extension

CHAPTER 5

PROGRAMMES AND PROJECTS OF OTHER SPHERES OF GOVERNMENT

5.1. National Legislative Framework

The Constitution of the Republic of South Africa (1996) states that housing delivery falls within the ambit of national and provincial government. National and Provincial departments are required to do integrated planning with the municipalities, as guided by inter-governmental relations (IGR).

5.2. Department of Public Works, Roads, and Transport

The DPWRT is responsible for the maintenance and expansion of the road networks in Mpumalanga province which stretch for 13 874km. 72% of the road network are in poor condition; 30% of the network is responsible for coal haulage. In Gert Sibande District, 1, 970km are paved, 5,006km are unpaved.

Table 5.1: DPWRT Project List

Proposed project:

Project	Project Description	Location (GIS coordinates)	Timeframes	Budget (2022/23) R
Upgrade: Road D481 from Ebuhljeni to Manhaar Mooiplaas and Ekulindeni (7.2km)	Upgrade: Road D481 from Ebuhljeni to Manhaar between Mooiplaas and Ekulindeni (7.2km)	-26.09818, 30.957	2022/23	67,468

5.3. Department of Agriculture

The vision of the department is of vibrant, equitable, integrated, and sustainable urban and rural communities with world-class, united, and prosperous agricultural, forestry and fisheries sectors, with food security for all.

Table 5.2: Department of Agriculture Projects
Current projects:

No	Project name	Outputs	Project description	Total Estimated cost R
1	Mkholo Lonsundvu Trust	Milking Parlour Revamp - EIA, boreholes registered/ borehole yield results	Refurbishment of milking parlour and Cultivated pastures	500 000
2	Styndorp	Packhouse - Replacement of 600m riblock pipeline and sprinkler irrigation	Establishment of packhouse and refurbishment of ribblock pipeline (2nd phase) and infilled irrigation	14 259 020
3	Ezamadolwane	Poultry and Vegetable - Planning level - EIA, boreholes registered/ borehole yield results	Planning for Vegetable and broiler production	1 540 000
4	MT Farming	Poultry Layer House - 1 X 15 000-layer house completed	Completion the Construction of 1 X 15 000-layer house	3 000 000
5	Arnhemburg AHC and Dundonald Animal health clinics	Vet Clinic - (Painting, plumbing, electrical works, air conditioning maintenance, Ceiling and flooring maintenance)	Refurbishment of an animal health clinic	1 500 000
6	Stynsburg, Izindonga and Dundonald Dipping Tanks	Vet Dipping Tank - Dipping tanks repaired	Refurbishment of 3 dipping tanks in GALM	1 068 000
7	Grootvlei	Portion 24, 26 of the farm Grootvlei 293 IS		10 000 000,00
8	Theeboom	Remaining Extent of the farm Theeboom 729 JT		10 000 000,00
9	Vriesland, Doornhoek, Onverwacht	Portion 1 of the farm Vriesland 620 IT, Cater ridge 615 JT, Portion 2, 3 and 4 of the farm Doornhoek 607 JT, Portion 1 and 2 of the farm Onverwacht 544 JT, Portion 0 of the farm Belmont 606 JT		40 000 000,00
10	Zilverkop and Iwula Farm	Remaining Extent of Portion 10, Portion 11 of the farm Zilverkop 25 IT and, Remaining Extent of the farm Iwula 29 IT		38 000 000,00
11		Sizama Impilo		5 938 190,55
12		Siphila Ngomhlabathi		5 938 190,55

No	Project name	Outputs	Project description	Total Estimated cost R
13		Vuma Ngiphile		1 624 208,32
14	Nederland			200 000
15	Komatidraai 417 JT			3 728 409
16	Buhlebungeza CPA			Not yet determined
17	Portion 8 of farm Welgevonden 412 JT			19 000
18	Appointment of a service provider to render Professional Engineering Services to Land Development Support programme in all Districts of Mpumalanga Province as and when required for a period of thirty six (36) months			11 550 000,00
19	Construction of tractor shed and installation of milling equipment in Dundonald			3 000 000
20	Construction of waste treatment plant and			2 000 000

No	Project name	Outputs	Project description	Total Estimated cost R
21	<p>additional infrastructure for Mkhondo AGRIHUB</p> <p>Request for approval to appoint a panel of expert service providers to provide strategic commodities for a period of 36 months in Mpumalanga province</p>			3 500 000
22	<p>Request for approval to appoint a panel of expert service providers to provide strategic commodities for a period of 36 months in Mpumalanga province</p> <p>(supply, drilling and equipping of boreholes across the 3 districts in Mpumalanga province.)</p>			2 500 000
23	<p>Provision for engineering firm to establish a technical support unit which will provide designs and specifications, planning and</p>			5 000 000

No	Project name	Outputs	Project description	Total Estimated cost R
	project management with built environment			
Total				4. 67 520

Proposed Projects – 2022/23

Local municipality	Project/Programme Name/Description	Project Beneficiary/ Ward/Location/ GPS Coordinate	2022/23 Target	2022/23 Budget Allocation (Annual) R'000	Total project cost R'000
Chief Albert Luthuli LM	Frischgewaagd	-26,923391 Ward 7 29,85854	Number of hectares acquired for farm dwellers and/or labour tenants	R200 000,00	R200 000,00
Chief Albert Luthuli LM	Glentyne	-26,204555 Ward 14 30,343124	Number of hectares acquired for farm dwellers and/or labour tenants	R100 000,00	R200 000,00
Chief Albert Luthuli LM	De Emigratie	-27,048978 Ward 11 29,916636	Number of hectares acquired for farm dwellers and/or labour tenants	R150 000,00	R7 400 000,00

Chief Albert Luthuli LM	Portion 3 of the farm Krogshoop 213 IS	-25,780782 Ward 10 29,300128	Number of hectares acquired for farm dwellers and/or labour tenants	R60 000,00	R200 000,00
Chief Albert Luthuli LM	R/E of farm Driehoek 346 IT	-25,988484 Ward 17 28,682438	Number of hectares acquired for farm dwellers and/or labour tenants	R3 120 000,00	R3 120 000,00

Chief Albert Luthuli LM	Dundonald FPSU (Personnel, Security, Electricity)	26.225183 Ward 5	30.824392	Number of FPSUs supported towards functionality	R1 200 000,00	R3 000 000,00
Chief Albert Luthuli LM	Dundonald FPSU (Production inputs)	26.225183 Ward 5	30.824392	Number of FPSUs supported towards functionality	R-	R1 000 000,00
Chief Albert Luthuli LM	Dundonald FPSU (Rabbitry project)	26°9'47.153 Ward 9	30°53'44.631	Number of FPSUs supported towards functionality	R200 000,00	R300 000,00
Chief Albert Luthuli LM	Dundonald FPSU (Skills development)	26.225183 Ward 5	30.824392	Number of agricultural cooperatives trained	R1 500 000,00	R1 500 000,00
Chief Albert Luthuli LM	Dundonald Tractor Shed	26°13'30.95"S 30°49'28.39"E Ward 5		Number of infrastructure projects completed to support FPSUs	R2 300 000,00	R4 250 000,00
Chief Albert Luthuli LM	Avmp, construction of fencing in various villages from dundonal to oshoek, tjakastad to nhlazatshe	Oshoek, Tjakastad, Nhlazatshe		Number of infrastructure projects completed to support production (AVMP and RVCP)	R1 000 000,00	R3 500 000,00

Chief Albert Luthuli LM	Nederland	-25,231093 Ward 25	30,087286	5.3.2 Number of hectares acquired for farm dwellers and/or	R140 000,00	R200 000,00
----------------------------	-----------	-----------------------	-----------	--	-------------	-------------

5.4. Department of Human Settlements

The municipality plays a coordinating role regarding human settlements, where the implementing department remains the department of human settlements, under the following legislations:

- o Constitution of the Republic of 1996
- o National Housing Act 107 of 1997
- o Division of Revenue
- o National Development Plan
- o Intergovernmental Relations Framework 13 of 2005
- o The Housing Code
- o Municipal Structures 117 Act of 1998
- o Municipal System Act 32 of 2000
- o Master Plan on Human Settlements

Table 5.3: Department of Human Settlements Projects

Current Project:

Project	Project Description	Location (GIS coordinates)		Target	Timeframe	Budget 2021-22
		Latitude	Longitude			
Provincial Specific Programmes	Military Veterans/KD Madonsela/Elukwatini/Fenie/Diep/Nhlaz/Chief Albert Luthuli (8)	Various Areas	Various Areas	2 Units	2021 - 22	377 768
Incremental - 2.2c Integrated Residential Development Programme: Phase 2: Top Structure Construction	Ph2 Info/Asishiyelane Supply/Silobela/Chief Albert Luthuli (44)	Various Areas	Various Areas	44 Sites	2021 - 22	4 400 000

Incremental - 2.2c Integrated Residential Development Programme: Phase 2: Top Structure Construction	Ph2 Infor/Umcebo Projects/Silobela/Chief Albert Luthuli (200)	-26,080767	30,107111	50 Units	2020- 21	5 000 000
Incremental - 2.3a Peoples Housing Process	PHP(Crdp)/Mbhene Trading/Various Areas/Albert Luthuli Mu (500)	-26,135335	18:49:12	75 Units	2020- 21	7 500 000
Incremental - 2.6 Emergency Housing Assistance	Ph2 Emergency/Seco Construction/Elukwatini/Albert Luthuli Mun - Phase 1	Various Areas	Various Areas	Planning	2021- 22	3 161 685
Total						R20 439 453

Proposed Projects:

No	Project/Programme Name/Description	Project Beneficiary	2021/22 Target	2021/22 Allocation (Annual)	Budget (Annual)	Total project cost
○	Incremental - 2.2c Integrated Residential Development Programme: Phase 2: Top Structure Construction	Silobela/Fernie/Chief Albert Luthuli (200) - Phase 1	50 Units		R5 949 996	R8 539 819
○	Incremental - 2.3a Peoples Housing Process	Various Areas/Albert Luthuli Mu (500) - Phase 1	100 Units		R13 006 000	R35 406 454
○	Incremental - 2.2c Integrated Residential Development Programme: Phase 2: Top Structure Construction	Silobela/Chief Albert Luthuli (44) - Phase 1	44 Units		R4 837 992	R5 038 572
Total			194 Units		R23 793 988	R48 984 844

5.5. Department of Health

The department of health is responsible for the improvement of the quality of health and well-being of all the people in the province. It does so by providing a needs-based, people-centred, equitable healthcare delivery system through integrated network of health care services, provided by a cadre of dedicated and well-skilled health workers.

Table 5.4: DOH Project List

Current Projects:

Project	Project Description	Location (GIS coordinates)	Budget (2019/20-2024/25)
Nhlazatshe 6 clinic	Nhlazatshe 6 clinic (Construction of new Clinic and accommodation units including associated external works) (Phase 2)	Albert Luthuli LM	R 70,823 000
Total			70 823 000

Proposed Projects: No projects have been planned for the Chief Albert Municipality for 2021-2022 financial year.

5.6. Department of Rural Development and Land Reform

The department is responsible to initiate, facilitate, coordinate' catalyze and implement an integrated rural development programme. They do so through the focus on Outcome 7 of the Government's key focus areas. Outcome 7 is implemented through five (5) outputs:

- Output 1: Sustainable agrarian reform with a thriving farming sector
- Output 2: Improved access to affordable and diverse food

- Output 3: Improved rural services to support livelihoods
- Output 4: Improved employment and skills development opportunities
- Output 5: Enabling institutional environment for sustainable and inclusive growth.

Table 5.5: DRDLR Projects List

Current Projects: Project/Programme Name	Ward/Location	2018/19 Target	2019/20 Budget R	Total project cost R
Portions 0,4,5 of the farm Strathsrae 495 JS-Land acquisition	Carolina	0	42 000 000	42 000 000
Portion 1 of the farm Onbekend 54 IT measuring 508,61 15ha – Land Acquisition	Carolina	0	2 335 000	2 335 000
Portion 1 and 4 of the farm Welgevonden No.412 JT – Simunye CPA Recap	Ward 10	11 412 540	0	11 412 540
Portion 3 of the farm Suikerbosfontein 429 JT and portion 10 of the farm Leeuwfontein 427 JT – Litjelenkosi CPA Recap		6 000 000	0	6 000 000
Portion 10 of the farm Hebron 421 JT	Carolina	0	0	9 000 000
Portion 8 Of the farm Welgevonden 412 JT	Carolina	0	0	24 000 000
Total		17 412 540	44 335 000	94 747 540

Proposed Projects: Currently awaiting list of proposed projects for the new financial year from the department.

5.7. Department of Community Safety, Security and Liaison

The department is responsible for the improvement of road traffic and community safety through mass mobilization, police oversight, and security services.

Table 5.6: DCSSL Projects List

Current Projects:

Municipality	Project/Programme Name/Description	Project Beneficiary/Ward/Location	2022/23 Target	2022/23 Budget Allocation (Annual) R'000	Total project cost R'000
Safety Promotion					
Chief Albert Luthuli Local Municipality	Educational awareness campaigns <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 Human Trafficking campaign • 1 Gender Based Violence Campaign 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carolina • Haartebeesko p 	02 Educational awareness campaigns	TBC	TBC
	Contact Crime Initiative <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 Campaign against domestic violence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mayflower 	1 Contact Crime Initiative	TBC	TBC

Municipality	Project/Programme Name/Description	Project Beneficiary/ Ward/Location	2022/23 Target	2022/23 Budget Allocation (Annual) R'000	Total project cost R'000
Community Police Relations					
Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality	1 Community Safety Forum (CSF) assessed on functionality	• Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality	01 Community Safety Forum (CSF) assessed on functionality	TBC	TBC
	8 Community Police Forums assessed on functionality	• Elukwatini • Haartebeeskop • Ekulindeni • Mahamba • Mayflower • Badplaas • Carolina • Fernie	08 Community Police Forums (CPFs) assessed on functionality	TBC	TBC
Municipality	Project/Programme Name/Description	Project Beneficiary/ Ward/Location	2022/23 Target	2022/23 Budget Allocation (Annual) R'000	Total project cost R'000
Transport Regulation					

Chief Luthuli Municipality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety Engineering • Traffic Enforcement • Road Education • Transport Administration and Licensing. • Overload Control 	Msukaligwa Municipality	05 Transport Regulation Programmes implemented	Operational	Operational
---	---	------------------------------------	---	--------------------	--------------------

5.8. Department of Culture, Sports, and Recreation

The department of Culture, Sports and recreation is discharged with maintaining and promoting unity of the people of Mpumalanga by acknowledging their cultural diversity. They also carry out that mandate by creating a learning AND READING culture to enable the people of Mpumalanga; and by improving the mental and physical wellbeing of the people through participation in various sports.

Table 5.7: DCSR Projects List

Proposed Projects:

Project Name	Project Beneficiary/	2022/23 Target	2022/23 Budget Allocation (Annual)	Total project cost
Raise awareness about national symbols conducted in local municipalities	All Local Municipalities within Gert Sibande	3 campaigns on national and orders conducted	118	118
Proposal of name change are submitted to LGNC, and PGNC to the minister of Sports, Arts and Culture for reviewal	All Local Municipalities within Gert Sibande	1 local municipality within Gert Sibande District	167	167
Cooperatives supported to increase marketing platforms for arts and crafts products	All Local Municipalities within Gert Sibande	5 Arts and Craft Cooperatives supported	120	120
Structures supported to promote Arts and Culture	All Local Municipalities within Gert Sibande	3 community structures supported	1,333	1,333

<p>Library Reading Material provided to empower learners and communities through supply of library materials to Public libraries</p>	<p>Gert Sibande District</p>	<p>7 in Albert Luthuli, 4 in Mkhondo, 8 in Msukaligwa, 4 in Dipaleseng, 11 in Govan Mbeki, 5 in Lekwa and 6 in Dr Pixley ka-Isaka Seme</p>	<p>6,663</p>	<p>6,663</p>
<p>Mini library project implemented to increase access to library services for people living with sight disability</p>	<p>2 x Elukwatini and ZM Mkhwanazi</p>	<p>2 libraries offering service to the blind</p>		
<p>New Mpumalanga Library Management System which is an enterprise resource planning system for libraries. The system will be used to track items owned, orders made, bills paid, and patron who have borrowed</p>	<p>All Local Municipalities within Gert Sibande</p>	<p>7 in Albert Luthuli, 4 in Mkhondo, 8 in Msukaligwa, 4 in Dipaleseng, 11 in Govan Mbeki, 5 in Lekwa and 6 in Dr Pixley ka-Isaka Seme</p>	<p>4,615</p>	<p>4,615</p>
<p>People actively participating in organized sport and active recreation events such as indigenous games, big walk rural sports, golden games etc.</p>	<p>All Local Municipalities within Gert Sibande</p>	<p>4 136 athletes in all local municipality within Gert Sibande District</p>	<p>427</p>	<p>427</p>
<p>Local leagues organized by federations or associations communities where club development program is established.</p>	<p>All Local Municipalities within Gert Sibande</p>	<p>8 local leagues supported</p>	<p>6,571</p>	<p>6,571</p>

Schools, hubs, and clubs supported with equipment and attire to provide opportunities for participation	All Local Municipalities within Gert Sibande	25 schools, 10 hubs and 20 clubs provided with sport equipment	1,152	1,152
Learners participating in school sports tournaments at district, provincial and national level	Learners participating in all local municipalities	3 600 learners participating in school sports tournaments at District level	4,681	4,681
Refers to athletes that are supported through a sports academy programme. A holistic support through Academy Framework Support.	Athletes supported through the Sports Academy Program in Gert Sibande District	100 athletes supported through the sports academy	617	617

The department is tasked with the responsibility to drive all economic development and planning initiatives in the province, and provides oversight over three (3) agencies; namely

- Mpumalanga Economic Growth Agency (MEGA)
- Mpumalanga Gambling Authority, and
- Mpumalanga Tourism and Parks Agency (MTPA).

5.9. Department of Social Development

The department derives its MTST mandate from chapter 11 of the National Development Plan which gives the department a central role to lead and coordinate social protection through Outcome 13. "An inclusive and responsive social protection system to address the critical challenges of eradicating poverty, unemployment and reducing inequality". The department supports ECDs, old-age homes and orphanages.

Table 5.9: Department of Social Development

Current Projects:

Priority Output	Annual Target	Town	Key Milestones	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Annual Budget R
Improve the provision of early childhood development services for children aged 0-5								
ECD – Khulani Preschool (Maintenance and Repairs)	Elukwatini	Repairs compliant to norms and standards	Signing of contract documents	Maintenance	Completion certificates	Transfer		178 831

Proposed Projects: There are no specific projects proposed for Chief Albert Local Municipality for 2021-2022 financial year

5.10: Department of Water and Sanitation

Local municipality	Project/Programme Name/Description	Project Beneficiary/ Ward/Location/ GPS Coordinate	2022/23 Target	2022/23 Budget Allocation (Annual) R'000	Total project cost R'000
Chief Albert Luthuli	RBIG Schedule 5B- Empulizi/Methula/Amsterdam Bulk Water Supply	Empulizi/Methula/Amsterdam	Construction Phase	70 000	300 000
	RBIG Schedule 5B- Eerstehoek/Ekulindeni Bulk Water Supply	Eerstehoek/Ekulindeni		95 142	205 142
	WSIG- Chief Albert Luthuli	LM to prioritise Beneficiaries	Chief Albert Luthuli LM	62 745	• 5

5.11. Department of Education

This project list from the Department of Education contains the infrastructure projects, particularly the improvement of sanitation at school. It also covers the upgrade or maintenance of classrooms and administration blocks which are essential infrastructure towards the improvement of the quality of teaching and learning.

5.12. LIST OF ESKOM PROJECTS

This section contains the confirmed electrification projects to be implemented in Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality in the 2022 / 2023 Financial Year.

Current Projects: ESKOM 2022 / 2023 Programs

PROJECT NAME	PROJECT DESCRIPTION	RECOMMENDED / NOT RECOMMENDED	NUMBER OF CONNECTIONS	RECOMMENDED FUNDING	STATUS OF HOUSES ON THE GROUND	GENERAL COMMENT
Electrification of 30 households at Mandela	Households	Recommended	30	R600,000.00	Eskom area of supply. Households available	Households are in Eskom area of supply
Electrification of 20 households at ZCC / Dundonald	Households	Recommended	20	R400,000.00	Eskom area of supply. Households available	Households are in Eskom area of supply
Electrification of 250 households at Rocky Park	Households	Recommended	250	R5,000,000.00	Eskom area of supply. Households available	Households are in Eskom area of supply
Electrification of 90 households at Heningklip	Households	Recommended	90	R1,800,000.00	Eskom area of supply. Households available	Households are in Eskom area of supply
Electrification of 60 households at Lochiel	Households	Recommended	60	R1,200,000.00	Eskom area of supply. Households available	Households are in Eskom area of supply
Electrification of 50	Households	Recommended	50	R1,000,000.00	Eskom area of	Households are in

households at Faith Section			500	R10 000 000.00	supply. Households available	Eskom area od supply
-----------------------------	--	--	-----	----------------	------------------------------	----------------------

5.9. Gert Sibande District Municipality

GSDM is responsible for supporting local municipalities with bulk services such as bulk water supply, drilling, and equipping of boreholes, integrated rural mobility, spatial planning, amongst others.

PROJECTS BY GSDM

DESCRIPTION	Budget 2021 R	Budget 2022 R	Budget 2023 R
Siyathuthuka Project	1 250 000	1 312 500	1 378 125
Water Quality Testing	210 000	220 500	231 525

PROJECTS BY GSDM

Project Description	Total Project Value (R)	Budget Allocated R	Expenditure	Accumulated Expenditure	Progress to Date %	Completion date	Level of intervention required

Renovation of Tjakastad Community Hall Phase 2	345 532	345 532	-	-	0%	30-Jun-20	Project completed. 95% of the funds claimed.
Maintenance of Kerk Street in Carolina	1 460 000	1 460 000	1 460 000	1 460 000	100%	18-Nov-19	Project completed, 6018m ²
Pothole Repairs - Jetpatcher truck	Departmental	In house	-	-	100%	30-Sep-19	Project completed.
Regravelling and Blading	Departmental	In house	-	-	100%	30-Sep-19	Project completed.
Total	3 533 732	3 533 732	1 932 454	1 932 454	55%		

ANNEXURE B: LIST OF DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION (DBE) PROJECTS

Project/Programme Name	Ward/Location	2021/22 Target	2022/23 Budget Allocation (Annual) R	Total Project Cost R
New Mobile Facility	All	24 779 484	10 148 910	
Construction of new circuit Offices				
Security High Mass lights around all boarding schools	Badplaas Circuit	8 141 016	1 465 383	9 606 398
Supply and install the backup generators	All	5 000 000		5 000 000
Demolish 20x pit toilets, demolish 4x waterborne toilet, demolish septic tanks including pipeline (Assessment of waterborne toilets before demolition)	All	5 000 000		5 000 000
Demolition of 6 pit toilets to clear for environmental health and safety and refurbishment of borehole	Masakhane Primary School	45 000	0	45 000
	Lusushwana Secondary School	1 350 000	168 885	1 394 865
Replace roof coverings with trusses, gutters, down pipes, fascia and badge boards; replace ceilings, floor tiles and skirting, windowpanes, paint walls, chalk and pin boards; and install electricity in four (4) classrooms.	Chief Jerry Secondary School	420 365	42 037	462 402
Replace roof covering and purlins, ceilings, and paint in two (2) blocks of classrooms and library				
Replace roof structure, ceilings, floor tiles, windowpanes and retreat termites in the Admin block, computer centre and library	Engelsedraai Primary School	425 336	42 037	462 402
Replace the roof structures affected by termites in Grade 4,5&6				

Replace roof structure, ceilings, floor tiles, windowpanes and retreat termites on trusses	Ngilandi Secondary School	423 585	42 357	465 922
Replace roof coverings, trusses, ceiling, electrical works, and pin boards	Ematjeketjeni Primary School	442 565	44 257	486 822
Repairs to toilet roof covering, ceilings, electrical works piping, windowpanes and treat for termites	Violet Jiyane Primary School	265 898	26 590	292 488
Replace roof structure, ceilings, electrical work, floor tiles, windowpanes and retreat termites and replace damaged water tanks and stands	D&C Comprehensive School	360 252	36 025	396 277
Scope to be confirmed	Lusushwana Primary	421 365	42 137	463 502
Roof of Admin Block and Computer Laboratory and Laboratory blown off. Pit toilets only on site. No kitchen on site. Cracks in building structure to be inspected by engineer. Unreliable water source, borehole is broken. All roof structure to be inspected by engineer. Possible problem with termites.	Ekuphakameni Primary School	2 350 000	352 500	2 702 500
Renovate 8 toilets	Badjiesbult Primary School	300 547	30 055	330 602
Electricity not installed in some classrooms. The school does not have library, hall, parking and kitchen.	Ngilandi Secondary School	412 455	41 246	453 701
Renovate 8 classrooms and office	Waverly Secondary School	412 455	41 246	453 701
Refurbishment of 12 classrooms (leaking roof)	Siphumelele Primary School	2 024 125	202 413	2 226 538
Sewer, Roof and Electricity	Mpuluzi Circuit Offices	3 547 741	354 774	3 902 515
Renovate 19 classrooms, Admin and 10 toilets	Engabezweni Secondary School	5 311 214	531 121	5 842 335
Renovate 19 classrooms, Admin and 18 toilets	Carolina Academy Combined School	4 201 488	420 149	4 621 637
Replace the roof structure and the roof coverings, ceilings including the veranda, chalk and pin boards, screeds, floor tiles, doors, paint walls, window and door frames in 12 classrooms, seal the leaks and paint the roof in Admin block and paint	Chief TD Nkosi Secondary School	2 085 796	208 580	2 294 376

internally, replace one tank stand and fence the outstanding perimeter length of the fence.

Replace roof structure, floor tiles, chalk and pin boards, electricity, doors, windowpanes in 20 classrooms and Admin block.	Ekulindeni Primary School	3 321 229	332 123	3 653 352
Renovate 16 classrooms, Admin and 20 waterborne toilets	Eloyengweni Primary School	5 112 453	511 245	5 623 698
Renovation of 20 classrooms, laboratory block and office. Replacement of damaged roof covering, complete with timber trusses and ceiling. Electrical wiring, plugs, switches and lights.	Hlabangemehlo Secondary School	4 423 443	442 344	4 865 787
Replace damaged windowpanes, replace damaged floors and paint works.				
Renovate 21 classrooms and office	Insika Secondary School	4 423 443	442 344	4 865 787
Renovate 23 classrooms and library	Ligugu Secondary School	3 057 539	305 754	3 363 293
Renovate 12 classrooms, Admin and 18 waterborne toilets.	Lindzalokuhle Primary School	2 074 789	2 074 789	2 074 789
Renovate 13 classrooms, Admin block, and 20 toilets	Magotshwa Secondary School	3 951 448	3 951 448	3 951 448
Renovate 16 classrooms	Maqhawuzela Secondary School	4 321 774	4 321 774	4 321 774
Renovate 36 classrooms, library, Admin block and 30 toilets	Mbalenhle Secondary School	4 322 346	4 322 346	4 322 346
Renovate 20 classrooms	Sebenta Primary School	5 214 741	5 214 741	5 214 741
Renovate 20 classrooms and Admin	Simtfolile Primary School	5 322 457	5 322 457	5 322 457
Renovate 16 classrooms, 1 office and 18 toilets	Siyeta Primary School	4 698 481	4 698 481	4 698 481
Seal the leaks and replace worn-out roof coverings and repalce all purlins, replace worn-out ceilings including the veranda, paint walls and ceilings including the veranda, re-plaster, paint external gable ends and replace fascia, barge and fascia boards and gutters and down pipes, check the timber trusses and replace where necessary, treat termites in all buildings and resuscitate the borehole.	Tisiteni Primary School	2 143 215	2 143 215	2 143 215
Renovate 18 classrooms and offices	Tsembekani Primary School	451 488	451 488	451 488

Equip a borehole, supply 2 x 5000L water storage tanks on elevated steel tank stand, replace cast iron water connection, replace 39 toilet cisterns and 3 stainless steel urinals, replace 23 HWB.	Carolina Academy Combined School	516 773	516 773	516 773
Resuscitate/ drill a new borehole, repair 2 dysfunctional urinals, replace 8 Toilet seat covers, replace 8 cisterns, replace 9 pocolin and replace 1 urinal and 2 HWB.	Ligugu Secondary School	3 057 539	3 057 539	3 057 539
Phase 1: Renovation of the toilet facilities including basins and or drinking fountain and investigate, analyze, and design sewer and electricity reticulation including construction of the new septic tank and French drain and a new borehole. Refurbish Circuit Offices, Hall and EDC Centre including electricity and sewer.	Mashishila Circuit Office	644 511	96 677	741 188
Connect 4 x 5000L Jojo tanks to existing 2 Jojo Tanks, drill and equip a borehole and install a pressure pump, clean, and refurbish septic tank, install water reticulation, sewerage reticulation, replace 5 cisterns and repair 4 toilets.	Mashishila Circuit Office	644 511	116 012	760 523
Phase 1: Renovation of 16 toilet facilities including basins and refurbish or add drinking fountain and refurbish septic tank and Renovation and refurbishment of four (4) classrooms	Silindzile Primary School	864 998	129 750	994 748
Resuscitate/ drill a new borehole, replace 2 urinals, replace 5 seat covers, replace 5 cisterns, replace 4HWB, replace 50mm diameter pipe of the urinals.	Chief TD Nkosi Secondary School	1 232 921	1 232 921	1 232 921
Construct 2 x 4 drinking fountains, supply and fit 8 brass taps and replace 8 toilets set.	Tsembekani Primary School	295 412	295 412	295 412
Supply 2 drinking fountain with 4 taps, replace 2 cistern, 2 urinals, 2 HWB, 2 Toilet seats complete with cisterns, replace 3 doors and supply and fit 5 x 3 lever lock sets, replace 2 windowpanes.	Ekulindeni Secondary School	3 321 229	3 321 229	3 321 229
Phase 1: Renovation of toilets and Refurbishment of a borehole	Ntabanhle Primary School	111 654	111 654	111 654
Renovation of toilet facilities and refurbishment of a borehole	Lilanga Secondary School	209 443		209 443
Resuscitate a borehole, replace 4 Pit Toilets, unblock Teacher's septic tank, replace 2 urinals 12 seat covers, 11 cisterns and 4 HWB, construction of 2 drinking fountains.	Mbalenhle Secondary School	4 322 346	4 322 346	4 322 346
Resuscitate a borehole, replace a pressure pump and connect water tanks system and install non-return valve, add 2 taps, unblock a toilet, fix leakages in 3 toilets and replace 3 cisterns,	Insika Secondary School	4 423 443	4 423 443	4 423 443

<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>
<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>
<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>
<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>
<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>
<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>	<p>10/20/2010</p>

CHAPTER 6

SECTOR PLANS

6.1. Background

This chapter contains a summary of the status of the sector plans within the municipality. These plans constitute the core components of the municipality's IDP and play an important role in the process of integration. The Municipality does not have all its sector plans in place. However, in partnership with other stakeholders and role players, the municipality is in the process of developing those plans. The plans that are in place but need to be reviewed since they are either outdated or do not assist the situation. The Municipality approached various stakeholders to assist financially to get these plans in place and the situation is slowly improving.

Table 6.1: A summary of the sector plans includes the following:

No.	Sector Plans
1.	Skills Development Plan (SDP)
2.	LED Strategy
3.	Integrated Waste Management Plan (IWMP)
4.	Integrated Transport Plan (ITP)
5.	HIV/AIDS Plan
6.	Communication Plan
7.	Environmental Management Framework Plan (EMFP)
8.	Housing Chapter

No	Status of key sector/master plan:	In place (approved?)	Implemented	Last update	Scheduled next review
		Yes/No	Yes/No		
1.	Spatial Development Frameworks	Yes	Yes	2017	2022
2.	Land Use Scheme	Yes	Yes	2018	Updated as and when there are amendments
3.	Local Economic Development Strategy	Yes	Recently approved	2019	2026
4.	Performance Management System/ Framework	Yes	Yes	2018	2021
5.	Disaster Management Plan	yes	Yes	2017	2022 – But critical areas of concern or identified threats are integrated as and when they get identified.
6.	3 year Financial Plan	Yes	Yes	2019	2021

7.	Water Services Development Plan	No	No	2016	The process to update one is underway for 2021
8.	Sanitation Master Plan	Yes	Yes	2017	2021
9.	Electricity/Energy Master Plan	Yes	Yes	2018	2021
10.	Integrated Waste Management Plan	Yes	Yes	2016	2026
11.	Roads and Storm-water Plan	Yes	Yes	2017	2022
12.	Human Settlements Plan (Housing Chapter)	Yes	yes	2022	2027
13.	Comprehensive Infrastructure Plan	Yes	Yes	New plan under development.	2021
14.	Environmental Management Plan	Yes	Yes	2018	2021
15.	Public Participation Strategy	Yes	Yes	2018	2019
16.	Human Resources Management Strategy	Yes	Yes	2019	2020

6.2. Skills Development Plan

The Skills Development Plan of the Municipality was developed in terms of the Skills Development Act, 1998 (Act No 97 of 1998) Skills Development Plan (1998) and the Skills Development Levy Act, 1999 (Act No 9 of 1999) Skills Development Act (1999) which require an employer to ensure quality of education and training in the workplace, and to assist job seekers, retrenched and the unemployed to enter the job market with the required skills. The Workplace Skills Plan (WSP) is derived from the organizational objectives contained in the IDP and the strategic priorities of the Sector Skills Plan of the Local Government SETA. Through interaction with Organized Labour and the municipal Training Committee, the Municipality will submit the WSP and Annual Training Report (ATR) for the coming financial year to the SETA as required. As required, the Municipality submits the WSP and ATR by 30 June annually.

6.3. LED Strategy

The LED Strategy is a key sector plan required by a municipality to guide all economic development and functions in the municipal space. The Municipality's LED Strategy was reviewed internally by the LED Section in the 2019/2020 financial year. Council approved the final LED Strategy for 2019 - 2024. The reviewed LED Strategy will assist to direct all issues relating to local economic development. The current LED Strategy created (5) five LED Working Groups, and of those, (3) three are effective and (2) two are not effective. Annual target is to convene four LED forums, which means one forum per quarter coordinated.

The purpose of the LED Strategy is to assist the Municipality as follows:

- It will guide all local economic development initiatives.
- It will provide a formal framework within which SMME's in CALM would function.
- It will assist with the revival of the LED Forum and other sub-forums such as the Mining Forum,

Agriculture Forum, etc.

6.4. Waste Management

The Waste Management Section is responsible for refuse removal services, including garden waste and building rubble; cleaning of streets in CBD areas, sidewalks, gardens, and pension pay-points; which services are done on a continuous basis. The nature of the work exposes the staff to hazardous and health risks, and it therefore requires regular medical surveillance of staff in terms of the Occupational Health Act (1997). Domestic waste needs to be selected and packed according to the nature of the material it contains e.g., garden waste, domestic waste, industrial waste, e-waste etc. Staff deals with waste that is not classified as recommended, due to the lack of a proper refuse removal system. This poses health risks or injury to staff collecting waste on a weekly basis, in that, for instance, it may be necessary to lift a 200-liter refuse bin filled with waste or ash, as is the case at some residential sections and households. The Department utilizes the tailor-made compactor, grabber and skip bin trucks for the removal of solid waste for households and business community. The Municipality operates two licensed landfill sites and three licensed transfer stations. These landfill and transfer station sites are expected to accommodate an average of 594 tons of waste per month. The municipality is administering waste in accordance with the CALM Integrated Waste Management Plan. The key strategic approach to improve the waste management Service is to engage the community and mobilize stakeholders in the following key interventions programs:

Figure 6.1: Waste treatment initiatives:

The municipality currently has the following functioning landfill sites, reflected in Figure 6.2 below:

Figure 6.2: Landfill sites and transfer stations:

The Municipality is not able to maintain its disposal sites effectively due to a lack of the required plant and equipment because of financial constraints.

6.4.1. Reduction, re-use, and recycling

The municipality has limited control over the waste pickers in various disposal centers which are responsible to sorting and recycling waste for business opportunities. The department needs to formalize the recycling by assisting waste pickers to register cooperatives which would assist them in access the markets.

i. Access to the waste removal service

The municipality consists of 53 480 households in which 12 909 (24 %) households receives kerb site refuse removal with the backlog of 40 571 (76 %). The refuse removal service is conducted to the following areas Carolina, Silobela, Emanzana, Elukwatini, Ekulindeni and Empuluzi. The refuse removal services for households and areas without access is augmented with the provision of communal skip bins which are placed on strategic points at various wards of the municipality. The department has recently dispatched additional seven communal skip bins to expand the service in areas of Elukwatini and Empuluzi. The department also provides refuse removal to businesses and public centres at Carolina and surroundings and Elukwatini business centers as per the approved tariff rate. The refuse removal services are available on weekly basis and on monthly basis. The Municipality manages the service through the Department Community Services: Waste Management Section.

Table 6.2: Waste Management Challenges

No	Challenges
1.	Inadequate tools and equipment
2.	Difficulty to fully comply with the stringent waste management regulations
3.	The mushrooming of illegal dumps in the municipal areas.
4.	Financial constraints due to low revenue collection
5.	Shortage of additional household refuse bins

Table 6.3: Refuse Removal:

Share of households with weekly refuse removal		Percentage
Year	No. of households	
2011	10 360	61%
2016	12 909	76%
2021	13911	74%

The refuse removal services are rendered to 13911 households (26% of the total number of households). The department provides the service on weekly basis as the approved weekly plan and schedules.

Table 6.4: Households with Access to Refuse Removal Facilities (Community Survey 2021)

Households	Serviced Household	Backlog
53 480	13911	39560

Table 6.5: Proportion of Households with Minimum Level of Basic Services

Proportion of Households with minimum level of Basic Services	Percentage
---	------------

Electricity service connections	92%
Water - available within 200 m from dwelling	97%
Sanitation - households with at least VIP service	80%
Waste removal - kerbside collection once a week	27%
Percentage of Total households receiving basic water services daily	74%

Table 6.6: Number of Households with No Electricity Connections

Number of households not connected		Share of total households	
2011	2016	2011	2016
5 868	1 902	12.3%	3.6%

6.5. Cemeteries

The municipality is responsible for the provision of graves to the communities for burials and maintenance of 6 municipal cemeteries. They are at Emanzana, Carolina, Ekulindeni, Elukwatini, Mayflower and Silobela. Other areas are falling within the tribal authority and are using the tribal cemeteries, which are spread throughout the villages at times. There is no proper management of land use in the rural areas, and the municipality has identified that challenge; and would be working with relevant stakeholders including traditional leaders to identify one cemetery for a village, so that there is land available to provide other services such as serviced stands for residential purposes.

Fencing, toilets and water are some of the challenges that are faced in relation to cemeteries. Where these were installed, they were vandalized and stolen in no time. Several attempts were made in the past by the Municipality to engage the Tribal Authorities with a view to secure available space appropriate for cemeteries and to have those fenced, but more often than not the fences were removed where it was installed. However, graves were availed to needy community members to bury their loved ones in all municipal cemeteries. The establishment of new cemeteries at Ekulindeni, Elukwatini and Silobela, remain the priority since these cemeteries have reached their full capacity. The establishment of a new cemetery at Mayflower is at the final stages. The functions of environmental health are assigned to the district municipality in terms of the National Health Act (2003). The definition of these functions in the Health Act includes environmental pollution control, waste management, food health, and water quality monitoring. The environmental health inspections are done by the staff seconded to the Municipality by the Gert Sibande District Municipality.

6.6. Safety

The aims of the safety and security function is to ensure, promote, and sustain the safety and protection of municipal buildings and the guarding of and monitoring of access to municipal buildings, offices and other properties. Security guards are deployed at strategic municipal properties and are monitored by the Department of Community and Public Safety. The service has been outsourced to the service provider which remains accountable to the municipality through a service level agreement.

6.7. Traffic Management

The main function of this section is to ensure safety for all road users through traffic control, visibility and law enforcement. The Traffic Law Administration Sub-section rendered administrative support to traffic control by collecting traffic summons and administering of court registers. The traffic section also deals with the maintenance of the road markings, erect road traffic signs and pedestrian crossings.

Table 6.7: The objectives of the traffic and law enforcement function are:

No	Objectives
1.	To improve the quality of services by providing tools and equipment's
2.	To ensure that Traffic Officers are operating in all areas to reduce overloading and reckless driving
3.	To assist with the provision of scholar patrols at strategic points to ensure the safety of children
4.	To acquire specialized traffic control-oriented vehicles and equipment
5.	To reduce speed violations and promote traffic safety

The service is governed by the National Road Traffic Act (1996) to maintain road safety within the municipality area of jurisdiction including Identification of hot spots for over-speeding and providing traffic calming measures, Provision of visibility and law enforcement, Provision of escorts of abnormal loads and VIPs, Provision of roadblocks and scholar patrols, Maintenance of road signs, street names and road markings.

Table 6.8: Traffic Management Challenges

No	Challenges
1.	Certain part of the municipality receives erratic service.
2.	Insufficient provision of vehicles for the by-law enforcement unit

6.8. Disaster Management, Firefighting, Emergency and Rescue Service.

The objectives of the firefighting, emergency and rescue function is aimed at the effective and economic utilization of materials and personnel for the greatest benefit and protection of citizens and their property during major incidents; to save lives and property by providing firefighting and rescue services to the community; to educate the community in terms of risks and hazards; and to do emergency and rescue (disaster) planning, risk assessment, awareness programmes, consultation with stakeholders, provision of a disaster management framework, and a mitigation process.

The Municipality has a fully functional fire station in Carolina, and a satellite fire station in Elukwatini, and a Disaster Centre in Carolina. Every year fires result in irrecoverable loss of lives and property. Firefighting is a vital service for the realization of a number of human rights such as the right to life; the right to an environment; the right to property and is a matter which Local Government has the right to administer. However, due to the vastness of the Municipality, and insufficient vehicles and equipment it is not always possible to reach a scene in time. There are still areas within the municipality that do not have adequate access to fire and rescue services, and it remains a priority to the unit to extend cover to these areas especially in Empuluzi. Disasters, be it technological, natural, man-made and environmental disasters, pose a threat to the development

objectives of the Municipality. It is therefore important that disaster management principles are considered during the planning processes. The Municipality has implemented disaster risk management measures which aim to minimize the effects of disasters. Communities are educated and trained to recognize the importance of disaster management and formal emergency services are also extended to residents.

A Disaster Management Plan was reviewed; public consultation concluded only awaits council approval. .

Table 6.9: Key Issues relating to Fire and Rescue

No	Challenges
1.	Vast rural areas make it difficult to provide an effective service
2.	Unpredictable and uncertain natural rain and thunderstorms
3.	Non availability of services in some informal settlements
4.	Insufficient fire Equipment's to cover the municipal area
5.	Delay in response time due to the vastness of the municipal area
6.	Insufficient staff for the Emergency and Rescue (Disaster) Section

The Municipality is prone to natural disaster but the main related to meteorological patterns, mainly storms and floods, they occur in the main around festive seasons of December to early January, then occasionally over other periods. The areas mostly affected are those along the Empuluzi Valley, Lusushwana Valley, and Mlondozi Valley, Carolina and Elukwatini.

6.8.1. Drought

As with the rest of the country, the Municipality is susceptible to the outbreak of drought, which is as a direct result of the weather pattern known as El Nino, which results in warmer winters than usual and extremely hot summers than average. The offset of drought affects all facets of life, from agriculture to domestic use. The Water Treatment Works (WTW) in the municipality experience low water levels particularly in the dry winter months, which in turn affects the pumping capacity to reservoirs and reticulation networks.

6.8.2. Fires and Accidents

Burning of fossil fuels in power stations to the north of the municipal area also contribute towards the phenomenon of global warming. Moreover, periodical veld and forest fires and fires breaking at private residences pose another challenge. Motor Vehicle Accidents (MVA) especially on the main arterial roads (N17, R33, R38, R541) pose another danger. The municipality has only one fire engine which has to deal with all the five units which hampers adequate response to structural fires. The SDF gives guideline in terms of spatial configurations of structures and roads to deal with disasters including protection or mitigation and reduction of disasters by protected flood 100 years flood line in order to mitigate for disaster and the protection of the environment.

6.9. Social Development

The municipality has a challenge in facilitating the support for Youth to be able to participate in Sports, Arts and cultural activities safely and effectively. The major challenge faced by the municipality is inadequate and dilapidated facilities. Due to the huge backlog of basic service delivery by the municipality little is provided for the development and upgrading of these facilities. However, with a healthy partnership with other stakeholders

such the Gert Sibande District Municipality and the provincial Department of Culture, Sport and recreation, key objectives have been achieved. In order to promote healthy lifestyles and to unleash talent within the municipality through sport and recreational activities, the following key issues need to be prioritized as they relate to the National Sport and Recreation Plan; which are summarized in the tables below (**Table 6.10 – 6.12**)

Table 6.10: Priorities and programmes

No.	Priorities
1.	Use the 15% of the MIG allocation to construct and renovate the sport facilities.
2.	Facilitate the revival of Sports, Arts and Culture councils including school sport structures.
3.	Coordination and facilitation of opportunities for young talent to be exposed and supported through development
4.	Involvement and participation of the business sector and other stakeholders in promoting sport and recreational activities.
5.	This would indirectly promote a healthy society and would contribute towards local economic development.
6.	Coordinate the mayoral games annually and encourage full participation by the youth.

6.9.1 Culture, Sport, and Recreation Pillars:

As part of promoting social development, the following pillars from department of Arts and Culture have been adopted.

Table 6.11: Pillars

No	Recreational Pillars
1.	Indigenous knowledge system (IKS);
2.	Arts Administration, Language & Publishing;
3.	Cultural & Natural Heritage;
4.	Audio Visual and Interactive Media;
5.	Design Fashion Graphic and Interior design;
6.	Visual Art and Craft, the last being Performance;
7.	Theatre, Music, Dance; and
8.	Festival Rituals and Events.

Table 6.12: Key Issues pertaining to youth development includes the following:

No.	Key Issues
1.	Development of a Youth Development Strategy linked to current policies
2.	Enhance Youth Participation in Local Government matters e.g., involvement of youth in Monitoring municipality compliance on policy matters
3.	Ineffective of Youth developmental organizations [Youth Councils]
4.	Lack of Youth viable strategic partnership with relevant stakeholders [private & public institutions]
5.	Development and Capacitating of the Youth Unit within the Community Services Department
6.	Youth Summit and the adoption of the youth development policy and strategy
7.	Facilitate development of a comprehensive data base of youth or child headed households Facilitation and support of specific economic interventions for the youth to actively participate in the municipality's economic streams or access the local markets in collaboration with the LED Unit
8.	Set targets for preferential procurement and recruitment of young people in various sectors. Implementation of a comprehensive bursary scheme

6.9.2 Welfare and Disability Coordination and Support

There is a serious lack of reliable and relevant information on the nature and prevalence of disability in South Africa. Historically this has been due to a variety of reasons, such as failure to mainstream disability into Government statistical processes, the use of divergent survey methodologies, negative attitudes towards persons with disabilities, poor infrastructure and violence in underdeveloped areas which impedes data collection and diverse definitions of disability. People with disabilities in South Africa continue to face barriers that prevent them from enjoying their full civil, political, economic, social, cultural and developmental rights. This is largely due to ignorance and prejudice in our society. It is also because some legislation fails to protect the rights of people with disabilities. (Towards a barrier free society, SAHRC report, November 2002).

Universal access for people with disabilities is the ultimate goal of the disability movement. This means the removal of all cultural, physical, social and other barriers that prevent people with disabilities from entering, using or benefiting from the various systems of society that are available to other citizens. The SAHRC report mentioned above identified the following kinds of areas which need to be accessible to people with disabilities: activities, buildings, communication, education, facilities, gatherings, houses, information, jobs, kerbs, language, news, opportunities, parking, services, transport, voting, workplaces, youth groups and zebra crossings. The district as the country at large is faced with the challenge of ensuring that necessary support is given to the people with disabilities. A lot of work still needs to be done to ensure that as we strive for better life for all, people with disabilities are not excluded. All programmes that are implemented within the communities should prioritize the needs and conditions of people with disabilities and ensuring that employment opportunities are created for them.

Furthermore, people with disabilities are still confronted with challenges regarding their participation in economic activities, access to public facilities, housing and other social services rendered by the state and the private sector. Some strides have been made in terms of legislation to address the matter, but not much has been done to affect the intention and expectations of the legislation and the people with Disabilities. The municipality needs to resuscitate and revive the Disability Forums at unit office level. The Forum's objective was to promote coordination of services. Organizations of people living with disabilities have a platform to be involved in service delivery and these stakeholders have influence in policy matters. The local municipality has worked with the District Municipality and the Department of Health to meet its backlog of providing the needy people with wheelchairs while the Business sector has donated assistive devices including spectacles, talking watches and hearing aids to those in need of such. The Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality participates in the District and Provincial commemorations of the International Day for People with Disabilities on an annual basis to create awareness. To intensify our commitments, we have participated in various workshops on sign language organized for the deaf community by hosting workshops.

Table 6.13: Key Issues pertaining to people with disabilities include among others the following:

No.	Key Issues
1.	Inadequate facilities
2.	Accessibility in most of Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality offices (No ramps or lifts)
3.	Strengthening of Local Disability Forums
4.	Insufficient access to economic, training /development and employment opportunities
5.	Poor access to proper housing and public facilities
6.	Poor access to information for example sign language and Braille
7.	Discrimination
8.	Inadequate social and health services

6.9.3. Youth Development

South Africa has a youthful population most of which is either unemployed, underdeveloped or living under unpleasant poverty circumstances. This very picture is cascaded down in the context of CALM where most of our young people, due to their background, lack of information on career development, lack of skills necessary for the local economic growth, are confronted with bleak future prospects. All the CALM social partners have a responsibility to ensure that such challenges are addressed effectively. Young people alone cannot overcome the hurdles that they face without purposeful support of all the relevant stakeholders led by local government.

In the National Youth Commission Act, youth are defined as those people who are between 14 and 35 years of age (this is the definition that has been used in all youth planning and statistical representations of Statistics South Africa, 2001 and 2011). The Target Groups Identified in the National Youth Development Policy Framework 2002-2007 Young women; Youth with disabilities; Unemployed Youth; School aged and out of school Youth; Youth based in rural areas; and Youth at risk.

Given the status quo of the CALM youth population, the municipality has given priority to the youth through its EPWP programmes. It is also envisaged to create and support specific interventions for the youth to actively participate in the local economic growth areas and employment opportunities. The Local Municipality has over the years partnered and collaborated with the National Youth Development Agency in several workshops aimed at unemployed youth who either seek employment or to start their own businesses. The Department of Social Development over and above the supply of Social Welfare facilities within CALM is also doing social welfare/ community development programmes where youth organizations access money for life skills targeting the unemployed youth within the district. To date 7 youth organizations from the local municipalities have been receiving funding from the Department and they are as follows:

Table 6.14: Youth Organs receiving Funding from Department of Social Development:

No.	Youth Organizations
1.	Ekulindeni Youth Environment Club (EYEC)
2.	Elukwatini Youth Development Centre (EYDC)
3.	Mayflower Youth Development Centre (MYDC)
4.	Phumalanga Youth Development Centre (PYD, stationed at Red Hill)
5.	Silobela Youth Advisory Centre (SIYAC, stationed at Silobela)
6.	Sukumani Youth Advisory Centre (SYAC, stationed at Diepdale)
7.	Tjakastad Youth Development Centre (TYDC)

Monitoring is provided by the Community Development Practitioners appointed by DSD. They mainly focus on the following key programmes offered in these centres:

Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality sent at least 70 delegates to Youth Summit organized by Gert Sibande District Municipality in conjunction with the Department of Trade and Industry on the 30th and 31st of July 2011 at Ermelo under the theme “Youth in Action for Economic Freedom in our lifetime”. The District Youth summit was preceded by consultative meetings that were held in the seven Local Municipalities during the month of June and July 2011. It was attended by youth from all seven Local Municipalities that constitute the Gert Sibande District. About five hundred young people representing all the municipalities were in attendance. An additional hundred constituted other stakeholders. The following are the key issues as contained in the Youth Summit Report: Education and Skills Development:

Figure 6.3: DSD Programmes:

Figure 6.4: Key Educational and Skills Development Issues:

The following are the key challenges faced by youth within CALM:

Table 6.17: Youth’s Key Challenges:

No	Challenges
1.	Rural and Agricultural Development
2.	Access to State Land (farms)
3.	No Funds for maintenance of farm given to Youth farmers
4.	Tender on Land reform and agriculture.
5.	No youth is represented on senior management position on Rural, Agriculture and Land Reform from Gert Sibande District Municipality.
6.	Access to market is not possible, a special to youth who are currently farmers.
7.	No youth structure represented on Land reform office –in the approving committee of farm.
8.	A serious need for enterprises and skills development
9.	Regulation of Ownership
10.	Monitoring and Mentorship
11.	The Support to Land Rehabilitation Programmes
12.	Assistance from the public and private sector

6.9.4. Gender

There are many compelling reasons as to why Local Government must look at its gender policies and practices. Consider some of the ways in which women’s concerns, work and issues are interwoven into Local Governance issues on a virtually daily basis. Most of the everyday issues are of primary concern to women. Women are rooted in local areas, frequently unable to leave these, often because they lack the means to do so. Women are thus inclined to get involved in local politics because of their concern for “home” issues, as well as their commitment to their families and emancipation of other women.

Lack of access to water and fuel for cooking and heating affects women and children hardest. This often requires long erratic hours of hard labour. They also need to ensure the well-being of their families. Poor quality water and lack of sanitation can cause illness and strain their already depleted resources.

Ownership of land and housing is often restricted to men particularly in the tribal areas, excluding women from land and home security. Yet, women often maintain the home and attend to home activities for the sake of the family. High crime rates impact on women and children, often exacerbated by lack of electricity, water, sanitation and safer recreational facilities.

6.9.5. Children's Rights

Concerns have been raised both nationally and locally on the extent to which the rights of children have been violated amongst our communities. Out of many awareness programmes initiated by government there has been an improvement in some quarters of our society, yet more work remains so as to improve our neighbourhood and better the plight of children within the GSDM. In responding to some of these challenges the GSDM is committed to mobilize all the relevant stakeholders within our communities to support all initiatives intended to ensure upbringing of children in a safer and healthy neighbourhood, as they are being prepared to lead and inform decisions of future generations.

Figure 6.5: Key Issues pertaining to Rights of Children include, among others, the following:

6.9.6. Thusong Services Centre

The Thusong Service Centre programme is an initiative of government that was initiated in 1999 as a primary vehicle to integrate government services into rural communities. This was done to address historical, social, and economic factors which limited access to information, services, and participation by citizens, as they had to travel long distances to access these services. The rural areas were meant to benefit from services that would not be readily available in rural areas such as government departments, banks, and other public service

institutions. The Thusong Service Centre, situated in Fernie B, is a host to a few sector departments, state entities and other related agencies, to provide services to the people around the Empuluzi area. The following departments are hosted and provide services at the centre:

Figure 6.6: Thusong Main Tenants:

The major challenge with the centre is the maintenance of the buildings.

6.9.7. Library Services

The municipality is responsible for the provision of the library services to the community. This service is achieved through 6 operational libraries stationed at Emanzana, Carolina, Ekulindeni, Elukwatini, Empuluzi and Silobela. These libraries are open from Monday to Friday from 08:00 to 16:00. These libraries have books for most tastes and ages and are connected to the internet. A Memorandum of Understanding with the Department of Culture, Sport and Recreation was signed that would eventually avail a mobile library to the deep rural areas that did not have easy access to libraries. The challenge to the provision of this service is the lack of maintenance to the library buildings and in availability of internet service. In most cases, the libraries are stocked with old books.

Table 6.20: Key challenges relating to health service provision in the municipality are:

No	Key Challenges
1.	High rate of HIV/AIDS and TB. At 43% in 2015
2.	Increasing Non Communicable Diseases
3.	High teenage pregnancy rate;
4.	Sexual abuse in children younger than sixteen years
5.	Abuse of chemical substances (drugs and alcohol)
6.	High incidence of injuries and trauma
7.	It is difficult to report and account accurately since the environmental health service is rendered by the District Municipality
8.	The municipality does not have the equipment and staff for this service

No	Key Challenges
9.	Resistance is encountered from some outlets when compliance is demanded
10.	Shelf foodstuffs for disposal is usually demanded or retrieved by community members and reclaimers
11.	The issuing process of health certificates takes longer and delays services providers
12.	Insufficient Environmental Health Practitioners, only 2 for Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality

6.9.8. HIV/AIDS, Home Based Care and Orphans

Mpumalanga is one of the three (3) Provinces with the highest infection rates of HIV / AID's. Latest statistics for the province reveal an increase in the district infection rate. The table below compares the prevalence rate of HIV/Aids within the Gert Sibande District.

The municipality must develop an intervention strategy that will bring about significant changes in the incidence and prevalence of HIV. This strategy is guided by the provincial strategic plan which describes the vision for the 2012 – 2016 PSP:

- HIV prevalence rate of pregnant women was 43.2% in 2011 - increasing between 2001 & 2011.
- HIV prevalence rate excluding pregnant women was 21.6% (2011) - decreasing trend.
- TB cases – decreased between 2010 and 2012.
- Clinics – 17 of Gert Sibande's 62 clinics are in Chief Albert Luthuli: and
- Community health centres – 4 of Gert Sibande's 18 CHCs.

The Local Aids Council is the last level of the purposefully formed coordination structures as a strategic response to the pandemic ravaging the communities. It follows the National Aids Council, the Provincial Aids Council and the District Aids Council. It is necessary that the political and administrative leadership should be empowered on HIV & AIDS to ensure that the oversight role and monitoring and evaluation are respectively implemented. In addition, it should also ensure that LAC activities are strengthened. Strategies to prevent HIV infection should immediately be put into place and these include condom distribution and usage of same, education and distribution of information regarding HIV and AIDS should be increased. Medical Male Circumcision should also be encouraged as it reduces the spread of HIV and once circumcised, chances of contracting the disease are very minimal. More people have come out for counseling and to get tested for HIV.

6.10. Strategic Objective 5: To ensure Provision of Basic Services (Electricity, Water and Sanitation)

Key performance areas for the provision of basic services indicators are as follows:

Figure 6.7: Basic Services Key Performance Areas

Figure 6.7: Basic Services Key Performance Areas

6.10.1. Access to Electricity

The Municipality is committed to the provision of safe, affordable and reliable electricity to the community. Electricity is supplied in the municipal serviced area (Carolina, Silobela and Emanzana town); while Eskom is the sole distributor in the rest of the other municipal area. The Municipality is further committed to ensure the safe continuity of supply of electricity to households through its Electricity Section, and compliance with NERSA. In line with the National targets, the Municipality is committed to the achievement of the goal of having every house connected to the electricity network by 2030. However, it is worth noting that some of the remaining areas are costly to connect to the grid due to the sparse distribution of houses in those areas, coupled by the exorbitant cost-per-connection.

The Municipality is licensed to distribute electricity in Carolina, Silobela and part of Emanzana only. Eskom is licensed for the bulk supply and reticulation in the former Ekulindeni, Elukwatini and Empuluzi TLC areas. Electrification of households in the rural areas, the informal settlements and parts of Silobela Township is a compelling necessity. The Municipality is responsible for providing and maintain electricity to all households in its licensed area, maintenance and upgrading of existing electricity infrastructure including streetlights, high-mast lights, network and substations.

The maintenance of the electricity infrastructure is central to the achievement of the core goals of supplying safe, affordable and reliable electricity to the community. Despite the increase in access to electricity,

households prefer to use electricity for lighting rather than for cooking and heating. The use of electricity for cooking and heating was observed in less than 50% households and is not uniform, meaning even households with electricity choose not to use it for all their energy needs. Wood is the leading source of energy for cooking and heating.

Apart from providing electricity to consumers (averaging 5.7 Megavolt amperes or MVA), the Municipality continually installs new and replaces old electrical infrastructure, and ensures compliance with both Eskom and National Energy Regulator of South Africa (NERSA) standards and requirements. However, it is noted with great concern that vandalism, theft, illegal connections (including tampering with meters) are the core contributors to revenue loss, and threatens the sustainable provision of electricity services to businesses and households. The Municipality is 31% compliant with the NERSA electricity license requirements. Urgent intervention is required in order to achieve improved compliance. Statistics SA 2011 indicates that 5,978 households do not have electricity. The Municipality made some strides to address the backlog. Currently only 4 206 households do not have access to electricity. It appears that the choice of fuel for cooking may depend to a large extent on cultural preferences rather than whether or not electricity is available, although cost, availability and effectiveness are all factors. Paraffin may be selected over electricity for cooking purposes, and wood may be widely used in the more rural areas. However, it is argued that electricity would be the generally preferred choice for lighting, concluding that a process of a rapid expansion is reflected in the use of electricity as the preferred energy source for lighting - and therefore a lack of electricity for lighting should be considered a deprivation.

6.10.1.1. The Energy Plan

The Municipality does not have an Electricity Master Plan in place. The District Municipality previously indicated that they will be developing a district-wide Energy Master Plan.

Table 6.21: Electricity challenges:

No	Key Challenges
1.	In Gert Sibande District, only Chief Albert Luthuli did not record a favorable drop in the number and a percentage of households in informal dwellings;
2.	Theft and vandalism of electricity infrastructure
3.	Shortage of plant machinery (crane truck)
4.	Shortage of fleet
5.	Financial constraints
6.	Unavailability of Master Plan and O&M
7.	Inadequate customer care and emergence response due to shortage of fleet
8.	By-passing of meters (illegal connections), tampering with, vandalism and theft of infrastructure, especially cables and transformers
9.	Ageing of infrastructure
10.	Illegal electricity connections
11.	Electricity supply backlog mostly in the Eskom area of supply

However, the Municipality has performed exceptionally well in addressing the electricity backlog especially in deep rural villages and farm areas. To mitigate the challenge of tampering with electricity meters, the Municipality has started to roll out pre-paid meters. There were 51,383 households connected to electricity in

2016 - the share of households connected to electricity improved to a level of more than 96% in 2017, 1,902 households, however, are not connected to electricity at all by 2017.

Figure 6.8: Electricity Backlog / Fuel used for Lighting

6.10.2. Access to Water

The Municipality has been allocated the functions of a Water Services Authority. Potable (drinkable) water is water that is safe enough to be consumed by humans or used with low risk of immediate or long term harm. In order to achieve this, Section 12(1) requires that every water services authority must as part of the process of preparing an integrated development plan in terms of the Local Government Transition Act, 1993 (Act No 209 of 1993); or separately, if no process contemplated above has been initiated, prepare a draft water services development plan for its area of jurisdiction; and a summary of that plan. The Municipality has seven water schemes and four package plants, the latest having been completed at Eerstehoek Water Treatment Plant. The operation and maintenance of the infrastructure is done internally by the Department Technical Services, while other major repair and maintenance services are delegated to contracted service providers.

The existing infrastructure does not meet the demand of the current population, which leads to limited supply to other areas, particularly in Eerstehoek and Empuluzi where water supply was rationed. Package Plants were installed as an intervention at both areas to augment water supply. Reliable, uninterrupted and constant water supply is further affected by power supply outages and breakdowns of equipment. In terms of the Blue Drop and Green Drop Standards Programme, as well as the Blue Drop Risk Rating Report, there is a steady improvement in water quality with more and more of our communities having access to clean potable water, after they had been denied such access by poorly installed infrastructure and battling capacity to keep up with demand. Moreover, the Municipality secured three-year contracts with service providers for water treatment chemicals; water material; and maintenance of pumps and motors to ensure uninterrupted supply of water

services to our communities. Over and above the provision of water through piped water to households, boreholes and water tankers are extensively used to provide water to isolated and deep rural communities. Certain areas are characterized by severe development backlogs, and intervention is needed to uplift them. These areas are either rural in nature or peri-urban. The Municipality should develop programmes aimed at addressing service backlogs.

The water use in the municipality is mostly for domestic purposes. Another sector that uses some water is agriculture, and yet other big users are the mining companies. The Municipality, however, does not check the quantity of water used by these companies on an average daily basis, since they extract from dams and rivers. Another user of water is the forestry companies, though the Municipality does not know how many hectares of forests there are in its area of jurisdiction, as well as the types of plantations or trees in the municipal area. The last common enemy of water resources are alien plants and wattle, which consumes a sizeable volume of water.

The Municipality supplies water under difficult conditions to almost 95% of the population of which the majority is in rural towns. Some of those areas are surrounded by sparsely populated areas that are outside the bulk water infrastructure, and a different approach is taken to provide water to those areas by means of contracted water tankers. The Municipality is also faced with the challenge of ageing infrastructure, resulting in high water losses, and disruptions of water supply. The Municipality applied for RBIG funding in the previous financial year to upgrade the Elukwatini/Eerstehoek Water Scheme. The upgrade would provide adequate water to meet the demand. However, this is a phased project, which would take about 6 to 10 years to realize the desired outcome. The Department of Water and Sanitation would expedite the implementation of the project. Furthermore, through the RBIG programme, the Municipality was looking at options of augmenting the Methula/Fernie raw water source.

The Elukwatini Water Scheme was upgraded to normalize the rationing crisis, and the capacity of the water pumps were also improved. The completion of the Methula and Ekulindeni Bulk Systems benefits 9,265 households; however, there is still the problem of the raw water source in Methula, which dries up in winter. The Municipality is mandated to provide basic water and sanitation services by supplying clean drinking water to all settlements, including deep rural areas; the collection and treatment of wastewater to encourage a cleaner environment; to maintain the water and sewerage networks; and to clean reservoirs. The Municipality supplies water, sanitation, electricity, waste removal, firefighting, and sport and recreation services to provide in the basic needs of its residents; institutions (schools, hospitals etc.); businesses and offices; industries (farming, mining, manufacturing, tourism, etc.). The delivery of basic services is essential in improving the quality of life and sustainable development of communities. Government is committed to providing access to water, sanitation and electricity as basic services to address the infrastructural backlog. Government's development programmes were beginning to show tangible results, in that access to basic services has improved substantially since 1994.

The demand for basic service delivery is very high, and the Municipality is unable to meet the ever-growing demand with the available resources. The number of households is highest around towns and settlements, and is rapidly declining in the rural areas. The Municipality is doing well in the provision of some basic services.

It shows progress in three critical basic services, being water, sanitation and electricity, which are embraced by the Sustainable Development Goals. In contrast to this, is the solid waste removal service, which contributes adversely to global warming because the rate of litter that is not collected poses a challenge to the wellbeing of the people and the environment, but the Municipality is steadily improving. The reasons that lead to the slow improvement are the financial factor as well as the rural nature of the Municipality. An analysis of progressive trends is provided below on each of the basic services. The different levels of access to water in the various settlements are indicated in the following table:

Figure 6.9: Water sources

Table 6.22: Comparison of Access to Water with neighboring municipalities

Municipality (ranked from best to worst)	2012	2014
Steve Tshwete	97%	97.1%
Chief Albert Luthuli	18%	53.2%
Nkomazi	17%	51.5%
Emakhazeni	80%	50.0%
Dr Pixley Ka-Isaka Seme	41%	43.4%
Msukaligwa	21%	18.1%

Table 6.23: Blue Drop Performance previous status:

Performance Area	Standard	Emanzana	Bettys goed	Carolina	Ekulindeni	Elukwatini	Empuluzi	Fernie
Water Safety Planning (35%)	35%	22,23%	20,13%	23,80%	20,13%	22,23%	22,23%	20,13%
Treatment Process Management (8%)	8%	7,16%	7,16%	8,00%	5,20%	7,16%	6,00%	7,16%
DWQ Compliance (30%)	30%	18,00%	6,75%	22,65%	6,75%	6,75%	6,75%	6,75%
Management Accountability (10%)	10%	5,40%	5,40%	6,00%	5,40%	5,40%	6,00%	5,40%
Asset Management (14%)	14%	5,64%	4,80%	5,64%	5,43%	5,43%	6,48%	4,80%

Use Efficiency/Loss Management (3%)	3%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Bonus Scores	-	4,37%	3,00%	5,09%	5,25%	6,45%	4,50%	3,75%
Penalties	-	0,00%	1,77%	0,00%	1,72%	1,88%	1,90%	0,00%
2014 Blue Drop Score		62,79%	45,46%	71,17%	46,43%	51,53%	50,05%	47,98%

Table 6.24: Key access to water challenges:

No	Water Challenges
1.	Ageing infrastructure resulting in high water losses and disruptions of water supply.
2.	Illegal connections that lead to excessive leaks (systems losses).
3.	General wastages of water by communities.
4.	Sources: Only licenses will be updated, other sources that do not have sufficient water, like Empuluzi, will be supplemented through RBIG projects.
5.	Reticulation: The draft plan to replace the existing AC pipeline.
6.	Boreholes: The GSDM has a programme to assist the Municipality with installation of new boreholes and refurbishment of the existing boreholes.
7.	No cost recovery for water supplied from boreholes
8.	No water network in deep rural areas (bulk water infrastructure)
9.	Supply of water by means of water tankers is becoming unaffordable
10.	Rationing water supply due to the demand exceeding supply in the Elukwatini (Eerstehoek) Water Scheme area
11.	Inadequate water treatment plant in Elukwatini (Eerstehoek) area
12.	High unaccounted for water in Elukwatini (Eerstehoek) area as a result of ageing infrastructure
13.	Lack of bulk meters
14.	Limited budget allocation from Municipal Infrastructure Grant (MIG); competing needs of water and roads infrastructure development programmes, where water takes a large portion of the budget; and also the prioritization by Province on water supply
15.	The Carolina Wastewater Treatment Works requires urgent refurbishment in order to comply with legislative requirements

6.10.3. Provision of Sanitation

The Municipality is responsible to collect and treat waste water, and to ensure compliance to environmental standards as set out by the Department of Water Affairs. The Water Services Act states that everyone has a right of access to basic sanitation, which is defined as: The prescribed minimum standard of services necessary for the safe, hygienic and adequate collection, removal, disposal or purification of human excreta, domestic waste water and sewage from households, including informal households. The Regulations Relating to Compulsory National Standards and Measures to Conserve Water (Compulsory National Standards) states that the minimum standard for basic sanitation services is: The provision of appropriate education; and a toilet which is safe, reliable, environmentally sound, easy to keep clean, provides privacy and protection against the weather, well ventilated, keeps smells to a minimum and prevents the entry and exit of flies and other disease-carrying pests. The Municipality provides access to basic sanitation to 10,972 households (23%) through flush toilets, and 34,000 households (71%) in the rural areas where it is difficult to supply wastewater removal due to settlements having occupied these areas before planning was done for basic sewer infrastructure, households were provided with VIP toilets. Many of these toilets are nearing their carrying capacity or are full already. The Municipality has therefore launched a pilot project in the 2015/16 financial year to replace the VIP

toilets with Smartsan toilets.

6.10.3.1. Status of Sanitation Services

The backlog in the provision of basic sanitation is 1 801 households (StatsSA 2016). To address this challenge will require a huge financial injection. Approximately 61.4% of households are below the RDP standard for sanitation, with the exception of Carolina, part of Emanzana, Elukwatini and Mayflower. The wastewater treatment works and reticulation is provided only to the major urban areas in the municipal area. Other communities have access to pit latrines. Clearly a large portion of the population in the area does not have access to proper sanitation. The biggest challenge for the Municipality is to replace the pit latrines with VIP toilets, where it is suitable. Dumping and flushing of inappropriate materials to waterborne sewer systems and filling up of VIP toilets. At the current rate of funding, even if only sanitation projects were to be implemented with the grant funding provided annually, the SDG target for sanitation will not be met.

Table 6.26: Comparison of number of households without toilets:

Municipality	Number of households without toilets		Share of total households	
	2011	2016	2011	2016
Chief Albert Luthuli	2 476	1 801	5.2%	3.4%
Msukaligwa	987	1 295	4.9%	2.5%
Mkhondo	4 823	1 965	12.9%	4.3%

6.10.3.2. Green Drop Performance

The latest DWA Green Drop Report indicated that the Municipality is 17.2% compliant to the Green Drop Specifications and requires urgent assistance to improve all performance areas of the Green Drop Assessment. The Municipality's treatment plants are in high-risk situation in terms of their Critical Risk Rating and require urgent attention in terms of refurbishment, upgrades and additions to the current system. The Green Drop Score of the Municipality was 36,39% in 2013 (2011: 17,2%; 2009: 0,0%) which is a significant improvement on the figure for 2011.

6.10.3.3. Access to Sanitation

According to Statistics SA 2016, there was a backlog of 1 801 households in the provision of basic sanitation services. The Municipality provided ventilated pit latrines (VIP toilets) to approximately 32,800 households during the last 5 years to eradicate the sanitation backlog. However, the Province directed municipalities to cease this sanitation technology especially in rural areas where there is no infrastructure, and to look at alternatives, preferably waterborne sanitation. This will require a huge financial injection to address this challenge.

The types of sanitation provided by the Municipality are:

- waterborne sanitation in urban settlements, with the challenge of sewer blockages due to inadequate or rationing of water; and
- ventilated toilets system (VIP), which has a short lifespan; about 23% of households receive this

service in an acceptable standard, but over 65% receive it at a minimal level. Even though there is a challenge with the definition of what a standard was, it can be loosely accepted that any person who uses any other system than waterborne sewer is below the standard.

The Municipality faces budget constraints in relation to the sanitation service - the fact that less than 30% of households are receiving decent sanitation is a serious concern, given the fact that in terms of water supply, more than 77% of households receive water through piped water. If the Municipality were to convert the 77% of households receiving water to sanitation, it would have been in a position to increase its revenue base, because this is trading service.

6.10.3.4. Status of Sewer Treatment Plants and Related Bulk Infrastructure

The draft IDP commissioned by GSDM concluded that from the current situation the WWTWs do not have sufficient operation and maintenance, application of chemicals and staffing levels.

6.10.3.5. Operations and Maintenance Plan

A business plan is available. An O&M manual is being completed and will be implemented after technical training of all staff in terms of O&M.

Table 6.27: Sanitation Challenges:

No	Sewer Challenges
1.	VIP Toilets are filling up and need maintenance. The Municipality launched Smartsan a pilot project in the previous financial year. Again there is an issue of backlog.
2.	Sewer systems new / rehabilitation: None identified due to financial constraints.
3.	Recurring sewer spillages due to aged infrastructure also pump stations.
4.	Aging infrastructure
5.	Rationing water supply due to the demand exceeding supply in the Elukwatini (Eerstehoek) Water Scheme area
6.	Inadequate water treatment plant in Elukwatini (Eerstehoek) area
7.	The Carolina Waste Water Treatment Works requires urgent refurbishment in order to comply with legislative requirements.

Figure 6.10: Toilet Facilities (StatsSA 2016):

Figure 6.11: Sanitation Backlog (Department of Finance Mpumalanga Provincial Government):

Figure 6.12: Availability of Toilet Facilities

The backlog for toilets is 6.2% of households with no toilets or with bucket system.

Table 6.28: Green Drop Performance by Wastewater Treatment Works

Year	% CCR / CCR Max				
	Emanzana	Carolina	Kromdraai	Eerstehoek	Mayflower
2008	44	56	83	100	72
2011	72	94	89	89	89
2012	41	65	47	65	65
2013	94	76	94	94	94
2014	76	76	100	65	100

Table 6.29: Waste Water Services (Green Drop):

Green drop risk rating 2013	Green drop risk rating 2014
90.6%	83.5%

There is still a huge challenge in the Province at municipal level to improve the access of households in terms of hygienic and RDP level toilets - 593,606 households (47.9%) have access to other (non-hygienic) toilet facilities.

Table 6.30: Comparison of Households with No Access to Toilets:

Number of households without toilet access		Share of total households	
2011	2016	2011	2016
8 690	9 824	18.2%	18.4%
3 841	4 243	9.4%	8.3%
8 039	6 805	21.5%	14.9%
1 410	2 212	7.1%	9.8%
731	2 347	2.4%	6.3%
688	1 397	5.4%	9.4%

885	1 704	1.1%	1.6%
-----	-------	------	------

In general the Municipality is not performing well comparatively according to our household services index but improving.

Table 6.31: Comparison of Blue Drop and Green Drop Rating:

Local municipal area (ranked from best to worst)	Green drop risk rating 2013	Green drop risk rating 2014
Steve Tshwete	62.8%	61.9%
Nkomazi	87.1%	78.8%
Chief Albert Luthuli	90.6%	83.5%

Table 6.32: Comparison of Blue Drop and Green Drop Status:

Municipality (ranked from best to worst)	2012 Blue drop	2014 Blue drop
Thembisile Hani	78%	67.6%
Bushbuckridge	31%	64.2%
Chief Albert Luthuli	18%	53.2%
Dr Pixley Ka-Isaka Seme	41%	43.4%
Mkhondo	11%	32.4%

6.10.4. Access to Roads and Transportation Systems

The Municipal area of jurisdiction stretches roughly from Diepdale and Ekulindeni along Swaziland and South African border in the east towards Hendrina to the west and then roughly from Nooitgedacht and Vygeboom Dams in the North to Warburton in the South. The area is transversed by three prominent east-west and north-south provincial routes, namely (R33, R36 and R38), which pass through Carolina and serve as an important road network and backbone of the region providing access to different social and economic opportunities within the Mpumalanga Province. The municipal area is traversed by mainly gravel roads having a combined length of some 649 kilometers. The towns in the region are linked by tarred roads stretching over considerable distances. These are mainly high order Provincial roads which are a responsibility of the Department of Public Works, Roads and Transport. The deteriorating road network, Provincial proclaimed roads and access roads are the most significant infrastructural problem.

Road access is of critical importance for the economy of the region, social fabric, safety and security and tourism. Carolina is located on the main route to Swaziland and carries a high flow of regional-traffic. It also carries a high volume of coal transporting and other trucks that causes a lot of damage to the road surface. The arterial route (R38) forms an important link with N11 to the west, which in turn link with N4 (Maputo Corridor) to Johannesburg, Nelspruit and Mozambique and again forms link with R40 north of Ekulindeni, which in turn also link with the Maputo Corridor and Swaziland. The arterial routes (R33 and R39) serve as an important link between the Highveld and Eastvaal regions as it forms link with N17 West of Warburton, which in turn link with N11 and N2 to the South and the capital city of Swaziland to the East. The village clusters around the N17 and South of the N17 do not feature any significant concentration of business which should create a potential for economic development. All three provincial routes play a tremendous role in serving as

transport and economic linkages linking all areas not only within the Albert Luthuli Municipal area but also with other important areas in the Highveld, Lowveld and Eastvaal regions.

6.10.4.1. Roads and Storm Water

The Municipality has a total road network of 643km of which 132km is categorized as paved network, in the villages; there are no storm water drainage facilities as is evidenced by inputs from community participation. The roads are generally gravelled, and they have been graded (bladed) down to the level of infrastructure. Re-gravelling is the next possible option, but shortage of yellow fleet makes it almost impossible for re-gravelling to take place. There is another challenge with the paved roads, and some provincial roads with not enough storm water drainage. Three main provincial roads are gravelled, and make travelling between villages difficult, if not impossible especially in summer. These roads are Glenmore Road (from Hartebeeskop to Betty'sGoed), Redhill Road (from Oshoek to Dundonald and Swallows Nest), and Diepgezet Road (from Oshoek to Steynsdorp). Road infrastructure need to be upgraded to include storm water drainage systems, evaluate bridges every year, construct new bridges, construction of footbridges and rehabilitation of road networks.

6.10.4.2. Status of Arterial Roads or Internal Roads

The roads and streets in the municipal area have been in a bad state are becoming worse. Some of the gravel roads, especially those in the townships or urban areas, are inaccessible and the situation worsens in the rainy season. The storm-water drainage system needs urgent attention. The municipality has a plan in place to blade these roads using limited facilities which are not enough for the current demand.

6.10.4.3. Integrated Roads and Storm-water Master Plan

The Municipality's Roads and Storm-water Master Plan was adopted by Council in 2014. The objective of the Master Plan is to address and eradicate backlogs.

6.10.4.4 Resources available to support the delivery of the service

The Municipality has limited resources with regard to personnel (assisted by EPWP employees), vehicles, yellow plant, and equipment due to financial constraints.

Table 6.33: Roads and Storm Water Challenges:

No	Roads and Storm water Challenges
1.	No access roads to informal settlements
2.	Shortage of heavy construction plant (inadequate tipper trucks), limits construction of footbridges in deep rural areas, and maintenance of vehicle bridges disturbed by unrelated wear and tear situations
3.	Damage to street and pavement infrastructures in the CBD and residential areas by heavy motor vehicles
4.	Gravel roads that are eroded every year
5.	Unable to maintain gravel roads, motor bridges, foot bridges in the rainy season
6.	Lack of construction vehicles
7.	Recurring breakdowns of yellow plant and machinery
8.	Lack of repair of yellow plant and machinery due to financial constraints
9.	Unable to purchase materials due to financial constraints
10.	Damaged street edges due to failure of the pavement structure in Carolina
11.	Damage of tarred and paved streets by heavy vehicles in Carolina

6.10.5 Infrastructure Development and Maintenance

The Constitution (1996) assigns municipalities the duty of ensuring the provision of basic services; promoting social and economic development and a safe and healthy environment in which to live and work.

The Municipality is responsible for the planning of municipal infrastructure, and for utilizing the capital allocations to deliver the infrastructure. The Project Management Unit (PMU) is an institutional arrangement that was established to take responsibility for managing all capital projects, to ensure that the municipality is able to address all the capital challenges effectively and efficiently, that capital funds are utilized to build the necessary internal capacity in project management as well as to deliver the infrastructure.

Table 6.34: The overall roles and responsibilities of the PMU may be detailed as follows:

No	Roles and Responsibilities of PMU
1.	Infrastructure development planning
2.	Project identification
3.	Financial planning and management of capital funds
4.	Project feasibility studies
5.	Project planning
6.	Project implementation, including community participation and awareness, construction, capacity building and mentoring support
7.	Project management
8.	Building of capacity in the unit
9.	Monitoring and evaluation of the capital programme and projects; and
10.	Compilation and submission of reports in the formats prescribed for the capital programme

The Service Delivery and Budget Implementation Plan (SDBIP) is an important element in the service delivery process since it translates the IDP objectives into tangible and implementable projects, thereby making service delivery a reality and providing a basis for performance management.

Through the SDBIP, the Executive Mayor is able to hold the Municipal Manager as Head of Administration accountable, and the Municipality is able to account to communities. It enables the Municipal Manager to hold accountable the Managers that report directly to him. At the same time, communities are also able to monitor the functioning of the Municipality. The SDBIP must determine the performance agreements that are entered into between the employer and employees.

The Plan reflects the required elements, such as the performance of the Municipality by department, the targets as per the IDP as well as the budget for projects for the financial year. The Municipality's capital projects are funded by the following programmes:

Table 6.35: Infrastructure Grants:

No	Source of Funding
1.	Municipal Infrastructure Grant (MIG)
2.	Integrated National Electrification Programme (INEP) of the Department of Energy
3.	The Water Services Operating Subsidy of the Department of Water and Sanitation (DWS)
4.	Capital Funds from Gert Sibande District Municipality (GSDM)
5.	Own Funds

The Municipality has a number of priorities that it will pursue in the next few years, most of which align with national government's focus on infrastructure development and job creation.

Table 6.36: Key Infrastructure Development Challenges:

No	Key Challenges
1.	Limited access to basic household and community services especially in informal settlements
2.	Limited access to basic household and community services especially in informal settlements
3.	Limited funding available to deal with big backlogs
4.	The inability of households to pay for basic services due to high levels of poverty and unemployment
5.	Illegal water and electricity connections.

CHAPTER 7

PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (PMS)

7.1. Background

The Municipality's Performance Management System (PMS) entails a framework that describes and represents how the municipality's cycle and processes of performance planning, monitoring, measurement, review, reporting, and improvement will be conducted, organized and managed, including determining the roles of the different role-players (Chapter 3, Section 7, Municipal Planning and Performance Management Regulations, 2001).

The PMS Policy Framework defines the parameters, guidelines and standards for the development of a monitoring and evaluation system that enables delivery of consolidated and evidence-informed PMS reporting. The framework acts as a guideline for the development of PMS systems at the municipal level. The framework is important for the delivery of evidence-informed reports of performance and progress against plans, budgets, indicators and targets outlined in the municipality's strategic document the Integrated Development Plan (IDP) as actioned in the Service Delivery and Budget Implementation Plan (SDBIP) from different programmes of the Municipality, all of which are defined to help realize the different developmental goals, i.e. Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), National Developmental Plan (NDP), State of the Nation Addresses (SONA), State of the Province addresses (SOPA), Provincial Growth and Development Strategy (PGDS), IDP imperatives of the Municipality, as well as other priorities as decided by the Council on an annual basis.

The Policy Framework of the Municipality emphasizes the importance of monitoring and evaluation in realizing a more effective local government. It identifies three data terrains that together comprise the sources of information on the Municipality's performance: (i) evaluations; (ii) programme PI, and (iii) social, economic and demographic statistics. It assigns to the accounting officer the accountability of the systems responsible for the production and utilization of the information; and it requires prompt managerial action in relation to monitoring and evaluation (M&E) findings.

7.2. The Legal Premise of the PMS Framework

- The Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996;
- The Local Government: Municipal Systems Act, 2000 (Act No 32 of 2000) as amended by the
- Local Government: Municipal Systems Amendment Act, 2011 (Act No 7 of 2011);
- The Local Government: Municipal Planning and Performance Management Regulations, R.796 of 24 August 2001;
- The Local Government: Municipal Finance Management Act, 2003 (Act No 56 of 2003);
- The Batho Pele White Paper (1995);
- The White Paper on Local Government (1998);
- The Municipal Budget and Reporting Regulations, R.32141 of 17 April 2009;
- Regulations for Municipal Managers and Managers reporting directly to Municipal Managers, 1 August

2006;

- o The Local Government: Municipal Structures Act, 1998 (Act 117 of 1998); and
- o National Treasury Framework for Managing Programme Performance Information (FMPPI). In 2007 National Treasury issued the Framework for Managing Programme Performance Information (FMPPI). The document outlines key concepts in the design and implementation of the performance management system and it defines how to collect report and utilize performance information in local government.

Levels of Implementation

Figure 7.1: The system will be implemented for the review of the performance of:

7.3. PMS Key Role Players

No.	ROLE PLAYER	RESPONSIBILITY
1.	Internal Audit	Provide advice to the Accounting Officer on issues pertaining to legal compliance and performance reporting.
2.	Audit Committee	The Audit Committee acts as an independent advisory body that advises Council, Political Office- bearers, the Accounting Officer, and the management of the municipality on matters related to internal control, internal audits, risk management policies reliability and adequacy, and accuracy of financial reporting and information, performance management, effective governance compliance with the MFMA, the DORA, and provide comments to MPAC and Council on the Annual Report.
3.	Executive Mayor and Members of the Mayoral Committee	Manage the development of the municipal IDP, SDBIP, and PMS and oversee the performance of the Municipal Manager and the Directors.
4.	Council	Monitor performance of the Chief Albert Luthuli Local Municipality against all

		decisions of the Council and oversight over the performance of the Executive Mayor.
5.	Section 79 and Section 80 Committees	S79 Committees provide oversight over the performance of Council and the Executive, and consider reports from various portfolio committees in order to gauge their functionality and effectiveness. Section 80 Committees are processing committees which assist the members of the mayoral committee to take sound and concrete decisions in order to ensure the effective implementation of the planning and implementation.
6.	MPAC	It is an oversight committee, comprised of Councillors who are not part of the Executive, so that they (MPAC Members) can oversight over the function of the Executive functionaries. MPAC also make comments and recommendations on the Annual Report separately to Council.
7.	Community	The involvement of stakeholders such as citizens, community organizations, NGOs, members of organized labour, churches in the performance management increases the credibility and legitimacy of the performance reports and the audit process.

7.4. Status of Performance Management System in the Municipality

7.4.1. Corporate Scorecard

Section 41 of the MSA require municipalities to review and measure performance at least once a year. The Municipality devised a five-year corporate scorecard which is annually informed by the IDP, Municipal Performance Plan on a quarterly basis. Councillors should report back to their communities after every council sitting on matters related to actual performance against set targets.

7.4.2. Individual level

Section 57 Senior Management level is measured on their performance based on the Corporate Scorecard. The Senior Management Scorecard further considers their core competencies and managerial responsibilities. Evaluation of each senior manager's performance takes place quarterly and appraisals take place annually.

7.4.3. Cascading of PMS to lower levels

The PMS will be performed on Senior Management (Section 57) level, as indicated above. Furthermore, the Municipality envisages cascading the Performance Management System down to all the level during the next five years.

7.4.4. Performance Agreements

In terms of the MSA (2000), Chapter 6, the Municipal Manager and Managers directly accountable to the Municipal Manager must enter into Performance Agreements to comply with Section 56 and 57 of the Act and their employment contracts. The Performance Agreement must include a Performance Plan and Personal Development Plan. Performance Agreements of eight S56 and S57 managers were concluded for the 2016/17

financial year. The performance agreements are made public through the Municipal Website, and copies are submitted to Council and the Department of Cooperative Governance and Traditional Affairs (CoGTA). Performance Agreements are based on the Municipal SDBIP, which is based on the Municipality's IDP. Minimum competency levels for the Accounting Officer (Municipal Manager), Chief Financial Officer, Senior Managers, Other Financial Officials at Middle Management Level, and the Manager: Supply Chain, as well as Qualifications of S56 and S57 Managers and other Financial and Supply Chain Staff are prescribed by the MFMA (2003). All the relevant officials have obtained the Minimum Requirements in terms of the Act.

7.4.5. Monitoring, evaluation and reporting processes and systems

The Municipality is monitored by CoGTA by requiring submission of reports on monthly, quarterly, and mid-yearly basis, such as the back to basics report, the IMSP report, the mid-year budget and performance report and the Annual Performance Report (APR).

This annexure enlists all 6 Strategic Objectives of the Municipality with its Key Performance Indicators and Targets.

NO	KPA: Basic Service Delivery	MTEF TARGETS				OUTER YEARS		
		2022/23	2023/24	2024/25	2025/26	2026/27	2025/26	2026/27
Municipal Priority: Waste Management								
1	Number of areas receiving refuse removal services	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
2	Number of refuse bins supplied to billable households.	500	1125	1125	1125	1125	1125	1125
3	Number of disposal sites maintained	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
4	Library services available on week days from Monday to Friday	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Municipal Priority: Disaster and traffic law management								
5	Number of disaster management awareness campaigns conducted	14	14	14	14	14	14	14
6	% of disaster incidents reported and attended within 24 hours	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
7	Number of traffic law enforcement programmes implemented	10	10	10	10	10	10	15
8	Number of traffic infringements summons issued	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05
Municipal priority: eradication of informal settlements, establishment of townships								
9	number of studies conducted for the establishment of cemeteries (number of cemeteries established)	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
10	number of studies conducted for township formalization	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
11	number of studies conducted for township establishment	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
12	100 % of human settlements projects monitored	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
13	number forms captured on nhnr	200 forms captured						
14	no of consumer education conducted	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Municipal Priority: Infrastructure Development and Basic Service Delivery								
	To monitor water programs	100% of Water Programs	100% of Water Programs	100% of Water Programs	100% of Water Programs	100% of Water Programs	100% of Water Programs	100% of Water Programs

16	To monitor sanitation programs	100% Sanitation Programs	100% Sanitation Programs	100% Sanitation Programs	100% Sanitation Programs	100% Sanitation Programs
17	To monitor electrification programs	100% Electrification Programs	100% Electrification Programs	100% Electrification Programs	100% Electrification Programs	100% Electrification Programs
18	To monitor roads programs	100% Roads Programs	100% Roads Programs	100% Roads Programs	100% Roads Programs	100% Roads Programs
19	To monitor public facilities programs	100% Public Facilities Programs	100% Public Facilities Programs	100% Public Facilities Programs	100% Public Facilities Programs	100% Public Facilities Programs
20	To develop personnel/ Skills	2 Personnel capacitated	2 Personnel capacitated	2 Personnel capacitated	2 Personnel capacitated	1 Personnel capacitated
Municipal Priority: Provision of quality roads (Road and Storm water)						
21	To maintain all gravel roads	543km	543km	543km	543km	543km
22	To repair paved roads surfaces.	600m2	600m2	600m2	600m2	600m2
23	To reseal flexible paved roads	2km	2km	2km	2km	2km
24	To construct Footbridges	5	5	10	10	10
25	To Construct vehicle bridges	2	3	3	4	4
26	To construct Speed humps on existing paved roads	5	5	5	5	10
Municipal Priority: Provision of clean portable water (WATER)						
27	To maintain and repairs Boreholes	80	80	80	80	80
28	To maintain pumps and motors	87	102	102	102	102
29	To repairs Yellow fleet	7	7	10	10	10
30	To Maintain panels	10	10	10	10	10
31	To repair service delivery vehicle	19	19	19	19	19
32	Supply potable water	35ml	39ml	50ml	50ml	59ml

	15ml 3000m	15ml 3000m	12ml 3000m	10ml 3000m	10ml 3000m	2026/27
33	Supply potable water to deep rural areas					
34	Maintain water distribution network					
	Municipal Priority: Provision of reliable and sustainable Electricity Supply (ELECTRICITY)					
35	Inspect, repair and maintain transformers	88	88	88	88	88
36	Inspect, repair and maintain of public lights	490	490	490	490	490
37	Inspect, repair and maintain electricity network	70km	70km	70km	70km	70km
38	Inspect and maintain electrical panels at substation	12	12	12	12	12
39	Inspect and maintain pole and ground kiosk	30	30	30	30	30
40	Inspect and maintain Ring Main Units (RMU)	24	24	24	24	24
41	Installation of smart meters	150	150	100	100	100
	Total Indicators					4
						1

KPA: LED						
Municipal priority: Job creation, create enabling environment for investment for business and business expansion						
	2022/23	2023/24	2024/25	2025/26	2026/27	
42	Number of led strategy project implemented	1	0	1	0	1
43	Number of corporative offered support	50	50	50	50	50
44	Number of tourism awareness campaigns conducted	4	4	4	4	4
45	Number of led related fourms/meeting coordinated	4	4	4	4	4
	Total Indicators					4

KPA: TO ENSURE GOOD LEADERSHIP AND GOVERNANCE						
Municipal priority: Integrated development plan						
	2022/23	2023/24	2024/25	2025/26	2026/27	
46	Number of IDP, BUDGET, process plan and framework plan approved	1	1	1	1	1
47	Number of IDP process plan and consultations conducted	25	25	25	25	25
48	Develop a municipal strategic plan	1	1	1	1	1

49	Number of next year's IDP first draft approved by 31 may	1	1	1	1	1
50	Number of final IDP approved	1	1	1	1	1
Municipal Priority: ensuring good governance: Governance practices that are inline with the law, that are responsive to the needs of people and ethical.						
51	Number of Policies reviewed		20	20	20	20
52	Number of Policies developed		2	2	2	2
53	Number of by-laws reviewed		2	2	2	2
54	Number of Developed By-laws		2	2	2	2
55	Promoting the institution and compliance		1	1	1	1
56	To align the IDP and the SDBIP		1	1	1	1
Municipal Priority: ensuring good governance: Governance practices that are inline with the law, that are responsive to the needs of people and ethical.						
57	Number of Meetings held with Section 79 Committees		12	12	12	12
58	Number of Meetings held with Section 80 Portfolio Committees		12	12	12	12
59	Number of Meetings held with Mayoral		12	12	12	12
60	Number of Meetings held with Council		8	8	8	8
61	Number of Meetings held with Management		4	4	4	4
62	Number of Meetings held with Local Labour Forum		1	1	1	1
Municipal Priority: ensuring good governance: Governance practices that are inline with the law, that are responsive to the needs of people and ethical.						
63	Number of Meetings held with Section 79 Committees		12	12	12	12
64	Number of Meetings held with Section 80 Portfolio Committees		12	12	12	12
65	Number of Meetings held with Mayoral		12	12	12	12
66	Number of Meetings held with Council		8	8	8	8
67	Number of Meetings held with Management		4	4	4	4
68	Number of Meetings held with Local Labour Forum		1	1	1	1
69	Number of management reports submitted.		12	12	12	12

70	% of meetings attended	1	1	1	1	1
71	% of forum meetings attended as per invitation	1	1	1	1	1
72	% of contracts performance, drafted	1	1	1	1	1
73	Legal advice given	1	1	1	1	1
74	Number of Notices to the Public, internal and external communication.	12	12	12	12	12
75	Marketing and communicating the institution	4	4	4	4	4
76	Compliance with Bathopele principles and national symbols	9	9	9	9	9
77	Number of Municipal Buildings with proper signage	9	9	9	9	9
78	Number of Awareness programmes conducted on municipal services (Marketing)	4	4	4	4	4
79	Number of Community meetings held	12	12	12	12	12
80	Provide services as required by the Bathopele principles.	4	4	4	4	4
81	Number of Customer satisfaction surveys conducted	4	4	4	4	4
82	Safe keeping of records and files	1	1	1	1	1
83	Number of fire wall installed.	1	1	1	1	1
84	Number of anti virus installed.	1	1	1	1	1
85	Number of offside backup	12	12	12	12	12
86	Number of compliance with the MFMA uploaded	12	12	12	12	12
87	Percentage of ICT related devises maintained	1	1	1	1	1
88	number of submission	1	1	1	1	1
89	Number of trained employees as per the WSP	25	25	25	25	25
90	Number of trained Councillors as per the WSP	49	10	10	10	10
91	Compliance with Leave Policy	1	1	1	1	1
92	Sound labour relation between labour and management	1	1	1	1	1
93	Number of monthly Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) reports submitted to the Office of the Municipal Manager	12	12	12	12	12
94	Number of quarterly health and safety inspections and awareness's conducted	4	4	4	4	4
95	Number of employee wellness programmes conducted	4	4	4	4	4

96	Number of HIV and AIDS and COVID-19 campaigns conducted	4	4	4	4	4
97	Number of Municipal Buildings Maintained	4	4	4	4	4
98	Number of Council buildings cleaned and maintained	113	113	113	113	113
Total Indicators						
5						
3						

KPA: TO ENSURE A TRANSFORMED INSTITUTION WITH COMPETENT AND CAPABLE HUMAN CAPITAL

		MTEF TARGETS				OUTER YEARS	
		2022/23	2023/24	2024/25	2025/26	2026/27	
Municipal Priority: Enhance service delivery							
99	Number of critical positions filled	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	
10	Number of women, youth, racial groups and people with disability appointed	3	3	3	3	3	
10	Number of female appointments in Senior Management positions (To be in line with Employment Equity Plan)	1	0	0	0	0	
10	Number of female appointments in Middle Management positions (To be in line with Employment Equity Plan)	1	1	1	1	1	
10	Improved working conditions	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%	
10	Positive contribution to the reduction of the un employment	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	
Total Indicators							
6							

KPA: Municipal Financial Viability

		MTEF TARGETS				OUTER YEARS	
		2022/23	2023/24	2024/25	2025/26	2026/27	
Municipal Priority: Revenue: Revenue Enhancement management							
10	Safe environment for road users	19 600	19 600	19 600	19 600	19 600	
Municipal Priority: Supply Chain Management							
10	Number of procurement plans approved by 30 May	1	1	1	1	1	
10	Number of quarterly contract registers submitted to MMs office	4	4	4	4	4	

10	8	% of bids awarded within 90 days reported to council	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
10	9	Staff turnover rate maintained below 5%	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05
11	0	Number of Job Opportunities' / employment created.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Municipal Priority: REVENUE MANAGEMENT									
11	1	Number of additional grants sourced	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
11	2	Number of supplementary valuation rolls approved	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
11	3	% reduction in billing accuracy complaints	85%	90%	95%	100%	100%	100%	100%
11	4	% own revenue collected	70%	75%	80%	85%	85%	90%	90%
11	5	Revenue collected from investment properties	70%	75%	80%	85%	85%	90%	90%
11	6	Revenue collected through issued traffic infringements summons	70%	75%	80%	85%	85%	90%	90%
11	7	Amount of revenue collected	R50 000						
11	8	Amount of revenue collected from leased properties	R20 000						
11	9	Amount of revenue collected							
Municipal Priority: FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT AND EXPENDITURE									
12	0	Number of reconciliations prepared	96	96	96	96	96	96	96
12	1	Improved current ratio to be within accepted industry norm	01:01	01:01,1	01:01,2	01:01,3	01:01,4	01:01,4	01:01,4
12	2	Percentage of operational expenditure spent	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
12	3	Percentage of capital expenditure spent	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
12	4	Percentage of budget spent on training	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Municipal Priority: UNAUTHORISED, IRREGULAR, FRUITLESS AND WASTEFUL EXPENDITURE (UIF)

	2022/23	2023/24	2024/25	2025/26	2026/27
12 5 Percentage reduction of unauthorised expenditure	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
12 6 Percentage reduction of irregular expenditure incurred during the financial year	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
12 7 Percentage reduction of fruitless and wasteful expenditure	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%

Municipal Priority: ASSET MANAGEMENT, DEBT MANAGEMENT AND CREDIT MANAGEMENT

	2022/23	2023/24	2024/25	2025/26	2026/27
12 8 Number of quarterly physical asset verification conducted of movable assets	4	4	4	4	4
12 9 Number of re-assessment of useful lives, residual values and impairment test conducted	1	1	1	1	1
13 0 Reduction in average collection period	300 days	250 days	200 days	150 days	90 days
13 1 Reduction in average payment period	30 days	30 days	30 days	30 days	30 days

Total Indicators

2
7

KPA:

Municipal Priority: Sports, Art , Culture and Morale Regeneration Movement

	2022/23	2023/24	2024/25	2025/26	2026/27
13 2 Number of council assets and properties provided with safety and security	69	69	69	69	69
13 3 Number of sports and cultural events organised for the community	4	4	4	4	4
13 4 Number of Moral Regeneration Movement structures supported	4	4	4	4	4
13 5 Number of council assets and properties provided with safety and security	69	69	69	69	69

Total Indicators

4

CHAPTER 8

DISASTER MANAGEMENT

8.1. INTRODUCTION

This CALM Disaster Risk Management Plan has as much as possible been embedded in the current local reality of the CALM. Therefore, this brief description of the most salient features of the CALM is added to sketch this current local reality. This CALM DRMP has been structured in such a way as to address the requirements of a Level 1 Disaster Management Plan as per the guidance of the National Disaster Management Framework (NDMF). This document aims to be a practical and implementable work plan which will ensure an integrated approach to disaster risk management for the CALM. Each section contains relevant information necessary for disaster risk management to become a functional reality in the CALM through a multi-sectoral and multi-disciplinary approach. At the beginning of each section reference is made to the corresponding section in other documents, e.g. the CALM Disaster Risk Management Framework (DRMF), the NDMF, the Disaster Management Act (2002), or any other document as the case may be. It is therefore necessary to read the different sections in conjunction with the indicated documents in order to fully understand the disaster risk management environment in the CALM.

8.2. THE CUSTODIAN OF THE PLAN

The Head of the CALM Municipal Disaster Management Centre (MDMC) is the custodian of the Disaster Risk Management Plan for the CALM and is responsible to ensure the regular review and updating of the plan.

The Head of the Centre will ensure that copies of the completed plan as well as any amendments to the plan are submitted to:

- The Disaster Management Centre of the Mpumalanga Province;
- The National Disaster Management Centre (NDMC);
- The CALM's ward disaster management structures; and
- Each of the municipalities neighbouring the CALM; and
- The Disaster Management Centre of Gert Sibande District Municipality

In terms of section 52 of the Disaster Management Act, 2002 each municipal and organ of state operating within council's organizational structure is responsible for the development and maintenance of a disaster risk management plan for its functional area. Departmental plans are an integral part of council's comprehensive disaster management plan and therefore the head of each department and of each entity must ensure that copies of the plan and any amendments to the plan are submitted to the CALM MDMC.

No.	Action	Performance
2.1	Copies of the final plan to be submitted to the MP PDMC, NDMC, CALM ward structures and neighbouring municipalities	Copies of this DRMP have been submitted to all relevant role

8.3. THE PURPOSE OF THE PLAN

The purpose of the CALM's Disaster Risk Management Level 1 Plan is to document the institutional arrangements for disaster risk management planning which includes the assignment of primary and secondary responsibilities for priority disaster risks posing a threat in the CALM. It further provides the broad framework within which the disaster risk management planning requirements of the Act will be implemented by the departments and other entities included in the organizational structure of the CALM. It establishes the operational procedures for disaster risk reduction planning as well as the emergency procedures to be implemented in the event of a disaster occurring or threatening to occur in council's area. It aims to facilitate an integrated and co-ordinated approach to disaster risk management in its area of jurisdiction, which will ensure that the CALM achieves its vision for disaster risk management which is to build a resilient people in the CALM municipal area who are alert, informed and self-reliant by establishing risk reduction and resilience building as our core principles, and developing adequate capabilities for readiness; and effective and rapid, response and recovery.

8.4. OVERVIEW OF THE CALM

The municipal area of jurisdiction stretches roughly from Diepdale and Ekulindeni along the Swaziland and South African border in the east towards Hendrina to the west and then roughly from Nooitgedacht and Vygeboom Dams in the North to Warburton in the South. The area is transversed by three prominent east-west and north-south provincial routes, namely: the R33, R36 and R38, which pass through Carolina and serve as an important road network and backbone of the region providing access to different social and economic opportunities within the Mpumalanga Province. The municipal area is traversed by mainly gravel roads having a combined length of some 649 kilometers. The towns in the region are linked by tarred roads stretching over considerable distances. These are mainly high order Provincial roads which are a responsibility of the Department of Public Works, Roads and Transport. The deteriorating road network, Provincial proclaimed roads and access roads are the most significant infrastructural problem. Road access is of critical importance for the economy of the region, social fabric, safety and security and tourism. Carolina is located on the main route to Swaziland and carries a high flow of regional traffic. It also carries a high volume of coal transporting and other trucks that causes a lot of damage to the road surface. The CALM is well services with National, Provincial and Municipal roads. The arterial route (R38) forms an important link with the N11 to the west, which in turn links with the N4 (Maputo Corridor) to Johannesburg, Nelspruit and Mozambique and again forms a link with the R40 north of Ekulindeni, which in turn also links with the Maputo Corridor and Swaziland.

The arterial routes (R33 and R39) serve as an important link between the Highveld and Gert Sibande regions as it forms links with N17 West of Warburton, which in turn links with the N11 and the N2 to the South and the capital city of Swaziland to the East. The village clusters around the N17 and South of the N17 do not feature any significant concentration of business which should create a potential for economic development. All three provincial routes play a tremendous role in serving as transport and economic linkages linking all areas not only within the Chief Albert Luthuli Municipal area but also with other important areas in the Highveld, Lowveld and Gert Sibande regions.

8.4.1 Geographical location

The CALM's population of 187 935 (20.88%) of which the majority is from the Swazi tribe, is centrally situated in the Mpumalanga Province of South Africa - by far the largest province in South Africa. The province consists of agricultural, forest and mining areas with exceptions of natural and cultural attractions. However, it is one of the smallest provinces with a population of 7.8% (StatsSA 2011), thus low densities. It also has the smallest local economy in the country, in which agriculture, mining, local commerce and tourism count as the most significant economic sectors. Only 25% of the population in the CALM is economically active - mostly in the agricultural, forest, mining and tourism sectors.

The income distribution remains skewed, with socio-economic pressures such as poverty, poor skills, unemployment, and HIV/AIDS.

8.4.2 Demographic Profile

The *StatsSA 2001 Census* divides the CALM into the following main places:

Place	Code	Area (km ²)	Population
<u>Badplaas (Emanzana)</u>	<u>80102</u>	0.86	276
<u>Bhevula</u>	<u>80103</u>	11.91	4,092
<u>Carolina</u>	<u>80104</u>	18.69	2,952
<u>Diepgezet</u>	<u>80105</u>	4.89	229
<u>Duma</u>	<u>80106</u>	28.80	1,760
<u>Eerstehoek</u>	<u>80107</u>	638.65	41,780
<u>Ekulundeni</u>	<u>80108</u>	1.49	4,490
<u>Embhuleni</u>	<u>80109</u>	63.37	45,249
<u>Emfumbeni</u>	<u>80110</u>	24.29	1,314
<u>Emjindini</u>	<u>80111</u>	12.41	1,202
<u>Empuluzi</u>	<u>80112</u>	0.28	3
<u>Enikakuyengwa</u>	<u>80113</u>	73.34	9,235
<u>Lukwatini</u>	<u>80114</u>	4.86	5,181
<u>Mandlamakhulu</u>	<u>80115</u>	17.87	1,067
<u>Mpsikazi</u>	<u>80116</u>	49.57	19,415
<u>Mpuluzi</u>	<u>80117</u>	7.84	11,855
<u>Ndlela</u>	<u>80118</u>	14.56	3,012
<u>Sandleni</u>	<u>80119</u>	27.06	544
<u>Silobela</u>	<u>80120</u>	1.97	9,167
<u>Steynsdorp</u>	<u>80121</u>	1.14	585
<u>Tshabalala</u>	<u>80122</u>	2.32	3,296

Demographic Indicators	StatsSA Census 2001	StatsSA Census 2011	StatsSA Community Survey 2016 / SERO Report
Population	187 751	186 010	187 630
Households	41 209	47 705	53 480
Area (km ²)	-	5 559km ²	5 559km ²
Population per km ²	-	35	35

The CALM's population represents 17.83% of the Gert Sibande District population.

8.4.3 Development Profile

The CALM has the mission to provide a transparent and accountable government by:

- rendering affordable and sustainable services; and
- encouraging economic and social development through community participation.

Spatially the CALM has developed around various nodes, for example Elukwatini and part of Emanzana. While the seat of the CALM's CBD is not predictable in the last five years, it has shown signs of decline, however currently it is starting to develop.

8.4.4 Economic Profile

According to *StatsSA 2011* 16% of the population is employed; 58% is in the economic productive years (15-64 years); and 34% are discouraged work seekers or not economically active. The percentage of employment in formal sector was 65.6%, and 21.9% in the informal sector. The proportion of the population in low-skilled employment is 44%. The average household income is R4 000 per month; 19% of households earn less than R800 per month. The low average household income is directly linked to the low employment rate (*StatsSA 2011*). The portion of households with no income is 15%. The average income inequality of the poorest 40% of the population is 10% (2011). The unemployment rate in the CALM was 35.4% in 2011 and the CALM registered an unemployment rate of about 32.7% in 2015/16, meaning there was a slight improvement. The CALM would, however, have to improve the unemployment rate for youth which is at 45%. The poverty rate in the CALM is high at 51.7%. The dependency ratio in the CALM is around 70%. Key Issues relating to Human Capital Development are *inter alia* the following:

- Improving levels of skills development and literacy;
- Skilled individuals leaving municipal area in search of jobs in other areas;
- Municipal personnel with scarce skills in short supply.

The key issues listed for each sector above would inform and guide the strategic direction that the CALM should take in addressing the challenges that are faced by its communities.

8.4.5 Infrastructure

Though the CALM's infrastructure has some impressive features, there is a need for extensive upgrades. This need relates to both physical infrastructure, such as roads and rail (Carolina part). The CALM has done well in supplying its community with water and sanitation. Specific strategic improvements are required for continued and equitable basic needs supply for rural communities, moreover those who are dwellers on farms.

8.4.5.1 Transport

The CALM has a concentric road and rail system (for goods only) around the Carolina CBD. This transportation system is however in need of upgrading. The slow economic growth in the CALM over the last few years has translated into slow increases in private car usage. Carolina roads become crowded in the peak hours and at

month end. The Elukwatini CBD is too crowded and needs more lanes.

8.4.5.2 Basic services

Access to Water

In relation to water services, the national target is to, by 2030, achieve access to adequate and equitable sanitation and hygiene for all; improve water quality; substantially increase water use efficiency; implement integrated water resource management; protect and restore water-related eco-systems; expand co-operation and support to developing countries; and support and strengthen public participation in improvement of water and sanitation management.

According to the Statistics SA Community Survey 2016, some areas such as household electricity connections in the CALM have improved between 2011 and 2016; however, there are challenges in terms of informal dwellings and access to piped water and sanitation.

- The number of informal dwellings increased from 2,857 in 2011 to 5,206 in 2016 - an increase of 2,349 households and almost 10% of the households in informal dwellings.
- The number of households with access to piped water is 43,656 with a share of 81.6% of households having access to water. This is slightly lower than the 81.8% access in 2011. A number of 9,824 or 18.4% of households are still without access to piped water in 2016, which is not a good figure at all.
- The number of households with access to flush/chemical toilets improved in the relevant period – 12,559 households or 23.5% have access to toilet facilities, whereas 1,801 households have no toilets.
- Households with connection to electricity were 51,383 in 2016 - the share of households connected to electricity improved to a level of more than 96% in 2016; however, 1,902 households do not have electricity.
- The average performance in terms of the latest published Blue Drop Report and high risk in terms of the latest published Green Drop Report are improving the importance, however, is that the CALM are addressing the challenges.
- In general, the CALM is not performing well compared to our household services index, but is improving.

Access to Sanitation

According to Statistics SA 2011, there was a backlog of 19,712 households in the provision of basic sanitation services. The CALM provided ventilated pit latrines (VIP toilets) to approximately 32,800 households during the last 5 years to eradicate the sanitation backlog. However, the Province directed municipalities to cease this sanitation technology especially in rural areas where there is no infrastructure, and to look at alternatives, preferably waterborne sanitation. This will require a huge financial injection to address this challenge.

The types of sanitation provided by the CALM are –

- a) waterborne sanitation in urban settlements, with the challenge of sewer blockages due to inadequate or rationing of water; and
- b) ventilated toilets system (VIP), which has a short lifespan; about 23% of households receive this service

in an acceptable standard, but over 65% receive it at a minimal level. Even though there is a challenge with the definition of what a standard was, it can be loosely accepted that any person who uses any other system than waterborne sewer is below the standard.

The CALM faces budget constraints in relation to the sanitation service - the fact that less than 30% of households are receiving decent sanitation is a serious concern, given the fact that in terms of water supply, more than 77% of households receive water through piped water. If the CALM were to convert the 77% of households receiving water to sanitation, it would have been in a position to increase its revenue base, because this is trading service.

8.4.6 Critical facilities

The CALM contains certain critical facilities such as Forever Resort, Nkomazi Game Lodge, and Songimvelo Natural Game Reserve, several coal mines in Carolina, Nkomati Mine, Sasol pipelines and government buildings. The safety of this infrastructure and high profile delegates needs to be insured. In addition the provision of basic services, the CALM is contingent on the operation of certain critical facilities. In particular there are two important dams in the area. Nootgedacht Dam is situated in Carolina (Ward 21) and Vygeboom Dam which is situated between the Emanzana and Barberton roads. It can therefore be expected that all of many of the buildings referred to above would be a priority with regards to basic service provision in an emergency or disaster. These critical facilities will also require specific contingency plans for their continued operation.

8.5. THE CALM DISASTER RISK MANAGEMENT INSTITUTIONAL CAPACITY

The following section provides clarity on the disaster risk management institutional capacity present, and necessary, for the CALM. This is in line with the requirements of a Level 1 Disaster Risk Management Plan as per section 3.1.1.2 of the National Disaster Management Framework.

8.5.1 Management Committee

The Management Committee of the CALM is used as the managerial coordinating body for inter-departmental liaison and coordination. In order for this plan to be implemented successfully it is imperative for the Management Committee to adopt disaster risk management as a standing agenda point of the meeting. This will ensure that disaster risk management is addressed on a regular and ongoing basis. Though the Management Committee, high-level decision-making will inform the tasks of the different disaster risk management focal points in the respective department.

8.5.2 Disaster Risk Management Advisory Forum

In order for all relevant role-players in disaster risk management in the municipal area to co-ordinate their actions on matters relating to disaster risk management as prescribed in Section 4.1.3 of the CALM DRMF and Section 44 of the Act, Council has to establish a Disaster Risk Management Advisory Forum as provided for in Section 51 of the Disaster Management Act (2002). The Forum comprises of the following relevant stakeholders and role-players including NGOs and CBOs; individuals or groups with special technical

expertise:

- CALM Social Development (Transversal Unit)
- CALM Water and Sanitation
- CALM Communication Centre
- CALM Office of the Speaker
- CALM Office of the Executive Mayor
- CALM Legal Services
- CALM Roads and Storm water
- CALM Economic Development
- CALM Unit Managers
- CALM Governance Operations Support Development
- CALM Fire Services
- Mpumalanga Department of Health
- Department of Education
- MP PDMC
- SAPS: Operational Coordination (Chief Albert Luthuli Cluster)
- SAMWU
- IMATU
- SAFA
- NGO
- Local Ambulance Services
- Religious Leaders (Pastors Forum)
- Local Medical Doctors
- Department of Minerals and Energy
- Local Mines
- Gert Sibande FET
- Gert Sibande District Municipality

No.	Action	Performance indicator
5.1	Include disaster risk management as a standing agenda point on the Management Committee agenda	The Management Committee accepts disaster risk management as a standing agenda point and discusses related issues on an on-going basis
5.2	The MDMC to arrange a meeting of the DRMAF and invite all the relevant role-players as per the relevant sections of the DMA and CALM DRMF	A meeting of the DRMAF is arranged
5.3	The DRMAF to establish permanent membership and establish terms of reference	All relevant role-players who will enjoy permanent membership on the DMAF are recorded and terms of reference is developed

No.	Action	Performance indicator
		and adopted
5.4	The DRMAF to consider the content of the CALM DRMF and DRMP and to provide input and advice in this regard	Advice and input from the DRMAF has been noted and incorporated into the relevant documents where needed
5.5	The DRMAF to consider the indicative disaster risk profile of the CALM and provide input to the MDMC	The indicative risk profile of the CALM is assessed by the DRMAF with written advice and comments to the MDMC
5.6	The DRMAF to consider the different sub-committees to function under the DRMAF (in relation to the indicative disaster risk profile)	Different permanent and ad hoc sub-committees for the DRMAF have been established
5.7	The DRMAF to meet at least quarterly	Four successful meetings of the DRMAF have been arranged and completed
No.	Action	Performance indicator
5.8	The NGO sub-committee to meet in conjunction with the meetings of the DRMAF	Quarterly meetings of the NGO sub-committee has been planned and completed
5.9	The NGO sub-committee to align their terms of reference with the CRMP and CALM DRMF and for social disaster relief	An NGO sub-committee terms of reference is developed and adopted by the DRMAF
5.10	The NGO sub-committee to develop a social disaster relief contingency plan	A social disaster relief contingency plan is developed and aligned with the indicative disaster risk profile of the CALM
5.11	The NGO sub-committee to develop a contingency plan for social disaster relief in line with the guidelines in the CALM DRMF	A social disaster relief contingency plan has been developed in line with the requirement of the CALM DRMF and adopted by the DRMAF
5.12	The NGO sub-committee to develop standardised and agreed relief requirements in terms of food provision, shelter and clothing	Relief requirements have been develop and adopted by the DRMAF

8.5.3. NGO Forum

The NGO Forum as a sub-committee of the CALM DRMF is responsible for the development and alignment of their own terms of reference with this DRMP and the CALM DRMF, and for the development of a social disaster relief contingency plan. Such a plan must be developed according to *Template MDMC 2: Contingency Plan Development* as contained in the CALM DRMF.

According to the Terms of Reference of the NGO Forum it is responsible for:

- Relief resources mobilization;
- Assist in relief distribution;

- Damage and needs assessment;
- Hazard identification;
- Assistance during response;
- Coordination of relief efforts from various NGOs and CBOs;
- Participate in DRM activities in the CALM such as awareness campaigns; and
- Provision of first aid services (especially during events in the community).

The NGO Forum consists of the following regions or units of the CALM:

- Carolina
- Elukwatini
- Emanzana
- Ekulindeni
- Empuluzi.

8.6. DISASTER RISK ASSESSMENT FOR THE CALM

Phase one of the projects included a literature and document study in order to ensure that all known and relevant information in the CALM is taken into consideration. Part of this phase was meetings with the staff of the MDMC in order to conduct a macro disaster risk assessment based on the experience and perceptions of the MDMC staff.

Phase two of the project included data and information sourcing from various internal as well as external sources. The sources obtained enabled the consultant to ground truth the macro risk assessment of phase one and also to add to the existing knowledge base of disaster risk in the CALM. Through the geo-referencing of historical incidents an accurate profile of hazardous events could be recorded and probability analysis could be conducted. This allowed ensure a better and verified macro-risk assessment. By making use of the macro-risk assessment, a prioritized list of disaster risks in the CALM could be identified which in turn provided the impetus to phase three of the project.

The third phase included the identification of disaster risk management planning priorities for the CALM. In this phase the current developmental (IDP) projects of the CALM was assessed in terms of their contribution to disaster risk reduction in the CALM and in doing so their disaster risk reduction factor in relation to the indicative disaster risk profile of the CALM could be determined. This allowed for the adaptation of the macro-risk profile of the CALM to take into consideration the developmental initiatives by various CALM divisions and departments to reduce disaster risk. In addition to the above, the fourth phase of the project identified special disaster risk reduction projects which different departments and divisions should consider which will lead to the further reduction of disaster risk.

The fifth phase of the project related to the requirements for the development of generic and specific contingency plans for the prioritized risks of the CALM. Institutional arrangement for the development of contingency plans was specified. The contingency plans must be developed in accordance with the specified

template of the CALM DRMF. The final phase in the project established (as an integrated component to the whole DRMP) action steps towards the development of a Level 2 Disaster Risk Management Plan.

8.7. THE DISASTER RISK PROFILE OF THE CALM

The research found the following risks to be of greatest priority in the CALM. This priority was determined by taking into consideration the frequency and magnitude of the event as well as the associated vulnerabilities and the mandate of the MDMC to manage such risks (as an example, the risk of floods and tornados were taken into consideration but due to the sensitive nature of this hazard and the mandate of other government departments e.g. environmental affairs , water and sanitation department this was not placed on the prioritized list but the MDMC are compelled to coordinate with these relevant departments in order to ensure appropriate disaster risk management plans and contingency measures are in place).

Table 5: Priority Disaster Risks of the CALM

Disaster Risk Priority	Risk Type
1	Fires (shack)
2	Fires (veld and forest)
3	Flooding
4	Severe weather conditions
5	Hazardous materials (storage, transportation and usage)
6	Donga Erosion
7	Special events (mayoral imbizo, football, music festivals and other)
8	Mission Critical Systems Failure (MCFS)
9	Transportation accidents
10	Building collapse
11	Drought

The assessment indicated the areas that are most at risk to a variety of hazardous impacts in the CALM are those located through the SASOL pipeline. Particularly the following areas were identified as the most at-risk areas:

- o Emanzana (Badplaas)
- o Carolina

8.7.1 Macro hazard assessment

The following table contains a macro hazard assessment for the CALM in order to prioritize disaster risks. A three-point scale was used for the standardization of the assessment. Scale used: **High; Medium; Low**

HAZARD	GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION	PROBABILITY	FREQUENCY	INTENSITY	PREDICTABILITY/FOREWARNING	EXPOSE	IMPACT	KNOCK-ON EFFECT
1.Fires (shack)	Informal Settlements e.g.	High	High	High	Low	Properties and communiti	Medium	Veld fires

HAZARD	GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION	PROBABILITY	FREQUENCY	INTENSITY	PREDICTABILITY/FOREWARNING	EXPOSE	IMPACT	KNOCK-ON EFFECT
	1) Silobela 2) Kromkran 3) Emanzana					es		
2.Fires (veld)	1) Carolina 2) Emanzana 3) Vygeboom 4) Dundonald 5) Empuluzi unit 6) Nhlazatsh 7)Ekulindeni	High but seasonal	High	High	High	Environment, properties	High	
3.Floods	All wards	High but seasonal	High	High	Low	Properties, livelihoods and infrastructure	High	
4.Severe weather conditions	All wards	High but seasonal	Medium	Medium	Low	Properties, livelihoods and infrastructure	Medium	Damaged infrastructure
5.Hazardous materials	Along the major routes, e.g. N17, R38, R36, R38, Sasol Pipeline	Medium	Medium	Medium	Low	Environment Community	Low	Pollution
6.Donga Erosion	Lochiel Dundonald Fernie Tjakastad Nhlazatsh	Medium	Medium	Medium	Low	Communities and infrastructure	Medium	
7.Special events (music and football)	All facilities handling events such as	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	People attending the gatherings	Medium	

HAZARD	GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION	PROBABILITY	FREQUENCY	INTENSITY	PREDICTABILITY/FOREWARNING	EXPOSE	IMPACT	KNOCK-ON EFFECT
matches)	sports, large gathering, e.g. 1) Silobela Stadium 2) Elukwatini Stadium 3) Mayflower Stadium 4) Carolina Academy 5) Forever Resorts 6) Manzana Cultural Centre							
8.Mission Critical Systems Failure (MCFS)	All facilities Nooitgedacht Dam	Low	Low	Low	Low	All infrastructure and facilities	High	
9.Transportation accidents	Carolina /Sliding side stations, on major routes (R38,R36, N17 and other)	Medium	Medium	Medium	Low	Commuters and infrastructure	High	
10.Building collapse	All wards	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	Buildings and people	High	
11.Drought	All wards	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	People and livestock	Medium	

8.7.2 Macro Vulnerability Assessment

The macro vulnerability assessment considered the elements which are vulnerable due to the possible impact of a hazard on the indicated geographical areas. The table below contains a breakdown of the social, physical, economic, environmental and political/institutional vulnerability factors which contributes to the increase in disaster risks.

COMMUNITY:	Vulnerable elements exacerbating the possible impact of the hazard				
HAZARD	SOCIAL	PHYSICAL	ECONOMIC	ENVIRONMENTAL	POLITICAL/INSTITUTIONAL
1. Fire (shack)	1.Lack of knowledge on fire prevention 2.Incorrect risk perception 3.Unemployment 4.Child headed households 5.Domestic disputes 6.Social behaviour e.g. substance abuse 7.Lack of natural conservation 8.Need for self-preservation	1.Building methods Type of structures, use of combustible materials 2.Incorrect use of fuels for heating 3.No access to fire protection/equipment 4.Lack of electricity services 5.Shacks build too close to each other 6.Displacement 7.Unsafe/old equipment 8.Unsafe practices e.g. placement of cooking utensils 9. Storage of bulk fuels used generally for heating close to shacks 10. Incorrect farming techniques	1.Poverty 2.Lack of awareness and education 3.Conflict between various "classes" in communities 4.Lack of safety nets	1. Settlement in fire prone area. 2. Weather conditions, seasonal factors e.g. windy season, dry season etc. 3. Presence of high trees next to settlement especially alien vegetation	Faction fighting 1.Inadequate enforcement of building codes 2. Inadequate development 3. Land redistribution 4. Political expectations 5. Inadequate planning 6. Exclusivity 7. Unchecked urbanisation and urban sprawl 8. Unchecked land invasion
2.Fires (veld)	1. Lack of knowledge on fire prevention 2. Arson	1. Absence of fire breaks 2. Illegal dumping of combustible	1. Uncontrolled might lead to burning of	1. Overgrowth of alien vegetation 2. Maintenance of road reserves	1.Lack of information 2. Influencing people to

COMMUNITY:	Vulnerable elements exacerbating the possible impact of the hazard				
HAZARD	SOCIAL	PHYSICAL	ECONOMIC	ENVIRONMENTAL	POLITICAL/INSTITUTIONAL
	3. Environmental ignorance 4. Social behaviour e.g. smoking, unchecked open fires. 5. Incorrect agricultural practices 6. Lack of access to early warning messages through IT/media	material 3. Unavailability of fire protection equipment 4. Grazing fields destroyed 5. Fire breaks getting out of control	feedlots, loss of farming equipment, tools etc	3. Negative impact on ozone layers 4. Air and land pollution 5. Wild animals attracted to suburbs in search of food / running from fires 6. Pest control problems 7. Damage to sensitive environmental species	settle in specific areas for political gain 3. Insufficient resources to combat veld fires. 4. Unchecked land invasion
3. Floods	1. Settling in flood prone areas 2. Settling too close to riverbanks 3. Settling in pathway of storm water 4. Illegal dumping in storm water drains 5. Dumping in rivers and streams blocking water runways	1. Improper household drainage systems 2. Absence of storm water drainage systems 3. Effective urban storm water drainage systems might cause floods in receiving end areas and suburbs 4. Soil type and structure 5. Unplanned developments 6. Plane areas	1. Lack of education 2. Lack of safety nets 3. Availability of budget for maintenance of storm water management 4. Lack of access to early warning messages through IT/media	1. Improper management and or development in wetlands 2. Deforestation 3. Seasonal factors	1. Poor development planning 2. Poor storm water planning 3. Poor maintenance of dam wall structures 4. Maintenance of storm water systems

COMMUNITY:	Vulnerable elements exacerbating the possible impact of the hazard				
HAZARD	SOCIAL	PHYSICAL	ECONOMIC	ENVIRONMENTAL	POLITICAL/INSTITUTIONAL
	6. Acts to deforest immediate environment				
4. Severe weather conditions	1. Lack of awareness/training 2. Non-compliance to building codes 3. Settling in illegal areas 4. Types of housing structures and materials used 5. Dangerous social behaviour 6. Ignorance of early warning signals	1. Soil type (drainage) 2. Geographic location 3. Storage of hazardous material 4. Insufficient lightning protection 5. Poor building structures 6. Abuse of natural water resources 7. Poor maintenance of farming and other equipment, storm water manholes	1. Lack of access to early warning messages through IT/media 3. Poor farming practices 4. Urbanisation 5. Lack of development and implementation of early warning systems	1. Abuse of natural resources 2. Poor farming practices 3. Research / advanced technological interference with nature processes	1. Poor urban planning 2. Lack of integrated development planning
5. HAZMAT	1. Social behaviour e.g. smoking in prohibited areas, drunken driving etc. 2. Non-compliance to legal requirements 3. Continuous	1. Storage facilities compliant with regulations, location etc. 2. Transporting vehicles compliant with legislation	1. Clean-up costs 2. Maintenance of roads mainly used for HAZMAT transport 3. Protective clothing provision and	1. Spillages impact 2. Pollution 3. Early warnings in place for extreme weather conditions 4. Environmental impact assessment	1. Building regulations 2. Enforcement of legislation and regulations 3. Keeping of HAZMAT registers 4. Monitoring

COMMUNITY:	Vulnerable elements exacerbating the possible impact of the hazard				
HAZARD	SOCIAL	PHYSICAL	ECONOMIC	ENVIRONMENTAL	POLITICAL/INSTITUTIONAL
	training of HAZMAT workers		maintenance		and planning of transport routes
6. Donga Erosion	1. Settling on specific soil types prone to sinkholes 2. Lack of information and education 3. Unsafe practices e.g. lack of repair of water leakages 4. Uncontrolled watering of gardens 5. Ignorance 6. Misinterpretation of Councils responsibility relating to repair of private property damage 7. Overgrazing	1. Building structures 2. Maintenance of water pipes and taps 3. Control over mining activities 4. rehabilitation plan Control de-forestation	1. Lack of safety nets 2. Poverty 3. Delays in informal settlement relocations 4. Geological survey funding 5. Insurance coverage for dolomite areas	1. Soil type 2. Lack of drainage 3. Geological surveys prior to development 4. Environmental impact assessments	1. Building codes enforcement 2. Aggressive awareness programs 3. Strict development and settlement control mechanisms
7. Special events	1. Risky social behaviour 2. Large gatherings	1. Specific location 2. Venue capacity 3. Permanent / temporary	1. Public entry fees 2. Emergency resources and	1. Extreme weather conditions 2. Environmental	1. Sufficient security 2. Event planning

COMMUNITY:	Vulnerable elements exacerbating the possible impact of the hazard				
HAZARD	SOCIAL	PHYSICAL	ECONOMIC	ENVIRONMENTAL	POLITICAL/INSTITUTIONAL
	3. Uninvited attendees 4. Cultural clashes 5. Lack of crowd control 6. Substance abuse 8. Unusual emotional states 9. Type of event 10. Crowd expectations 11. VIP presence	structures present 4. Adequate facilities/amenities 5. Security at adjacent premises 6. Lack of knowledge of access and evacuation routes	costs for stand-by	analysis	3. Safety and security regulations compliance 4. No disaster prevention plans
8. Mission critical systems failure	1. Sabotage 2. Irresponsible care for equipment 3. Improper usage 4. Crime e.g. theft 5. Bypass of meters/equipment 6. Illegal connections 7. Abuse of natural resources	1. Illegal connections overloading systems 2. Planning and maintenance of systems	1. Non-payment for services rendered 2. Maintenance of systems 3. Non-compliance to control measure over resources e.g. watering outside restriction times	1. Pollution 2. Extreme weather conditions	1. Accurate accounting systems 2. Alternative sourcing options available 3. Disaster risk management plans 4. Safety and environmental regulations enforcement 5. Compliance to national and provincial

COMMUNITY:	Vulnerable elements exacerbating the possible impact of the hazard				
HAZARD	SOCIAL	PHYSICAL	ECONOMIC	ENVIRONMENTAL	POLITICAL/INSTITUTIONAL
	8. Rage 9 Despondent council employees				regulations
9. Transportation incidents	1. Social behaviour e.g tiredness, substance abuse 2. Road rage 3. Crime e.g. hi-jackings , vandalism 4. Adherence to road regulations 5. Overloading of vehicles 6. Rubbernecking at incidents	1. Lack of clear road names/signs Poor road conditions 3. Poor vehicle condition 4. Lack of appropriate lighting after hours 5. Overloaded vehicles 6. Vehicles not roadworthy 7. Lack of SOS communication assistance 8. Insufficient trained and effective SAPS and EMS personnel in incident management	1. Road maintenance 2. Emergency service provision and costing 3. Policing costs 4. Safety nets 5. 3rd party insurance 6. Availability of alternative routes	1. Extreme weather conditions	1. License renewals 2. Enforcement of traffic regulations 3. Integrated infrastructure planning
10. Building collapse	1. Exceeding max people capacity 2. Vandalism	1. Building structure 2. Building maintenance	1. Reconstruction costs 2. Insurance costs	1. Environmental impact assessment prior to development	1. Lack of compliance to building and safety

COMMUNITY:	Vulnerable elements exacerbating the possible impact of the hazard				
HAZARD	SOCIAL	PHYSICAL	ECONOMIC	ENVIRONMENTAL	POLITICAL/INSTITUTIONAL
	3. Crowd and spectator control 4. Terrorism 5. Poor workmanship	3. Location	3. Search and rescue costs 4. Law suits	2. Geological analysis prior to development (soil analysis) 3. Early warning systems in place	regulations 2. Lack of emergency planning

8.8. FORMAL CONSULTATIVE MECHANISM FOR DISASTER RISK REDUCTION PROJECTS

<i>Referral section in the CALM DRMF:</i>	4.1.1; 4.1.3
---	--------------

The appropriate mechanisms for consultation for disaster risk reduction projects are indicated in the CALM DRMF. These mechanisms must be established or enhanced according to section 5.2 and 5.3 above. Though these forums and in partnership with the activities of the IDP structures of the CALM, disaster risk reduction projects must be identified and planned for in line with the disaster risk priorities in section 8 above. The rationale is that disaster risk can largely be addressed through developmental initiatives and projects. The IDP process is therefore ideally suited for such actions. In order to ensure the continuous incorporation of disaster risk related information into the IDP planning process and projects it is important that the MDMC have access to the IDP planning structures and become an active member of its meetings. Although cognizance is taken of the fact that disaster risk management will not be incorporated into all developmental projects in the short-term, it remains imperative that current IDP projects are aligned with the disaster risk profile of the CALM.

8.8.1 IDP projects contributing to vulnerability and hazard reduction

<i>Referral section in the CALM IDP:</i>	Chapter 4, Table 4.2
--	-----------------------------

An assessment of the current IDP projects indicated that a number of developmental project are already contributing to disaster risk reduction in the CALM so some extent. Although these projects form part of the normal line function responsibilities, it already indicate that a vast number of projects are inherently taking issues of disaster risk reduction into account. It remains impetrative to conduct a detailed analysis of these as well as all future planned projects and align these with the disaster risk priorities as alluded to earlier in this plan.

The following IDP projects are linked to the disaster risk priorities. Note that some projects are repeated as they address more than one priority risk.

8.8.1.1 Fire (Shack)

Project name	Project Location/ Ward	Department	Type of vulnerability
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0038_MIG	10, 13, 14, 16, 18, 20, 24, 25	Technical Services	Physical
	Construction of Elukwatini Fire Station & Elukwatini Management Centre		
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0035_INEP	21	Technical Services	Physical
	Construction of Piet Debruin Park: Switching Station		

8.8.1.2 Fire (Veld)

Project name	Project Location/ Ward	Department	Type of vulnerability
Procurement of Fire Fighting Equipment	Carolina Elukwatini	Community and Safety	Physical
Acquisition Fire fighting vehicles	Carolina Elukwatini	Community and Safety	Physical

8.8.1.3 Flooding

Project name	Project Location/ Ward	Department	Type of vulnerability
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0019_MIG	1 Diepdale Ring Road	Technical Services	Physical
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0020_MIG	12 Ekulindeni Ring Road	Technical Services	Physical
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0021_MIG	4, 9 Mayflower Ring Road	Technical Services	Physical
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0023_MIG	2 Mahoxo Ring Road	Technical Services	Physical
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0025_MIG	19 Mooiplaas Ring Road	Technical Services	Physical
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0026_MIG	13 Tjakastad Paving Road	Technical Services	Physical
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0030_MIG	24 Paving Road Nhlazatshe	Technical Services	Physical
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0029_MIG	25 Paving Road Nhlazatshe 2&4	Technical Services	Physical
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0039_MIG	4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11 Construction of Dundonald Taxi rank	Technical Services	Physical

8.8.1.4 Severe weather conditions

No specific project

8.8.1.5 Hazardous materials (storage, transportation and usage)

Project Name	Project Code	Department	Type of Vulnerability
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0041_MIG	12	Community and Safety	Physical
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0042_MIG	4, 5, 7, 9, 11	Community and Safety	Physical
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0040_MIG	17, 23	Technical Services	Physical

8.8.1.6 Sinkholes

No specific development projects

8.8.1.7 Special events

Project Name	Project Location/Ward	Department	Type of Vulnerability
Construction of Silobela Sport Fields	15, 21, 22	Community and Safety	Physical

8.8.1.8 Mission Critical Systems Failure (MCFS)

Project Name	Project Location/Ward	Department	Type of Vulnerability
MP301_TEC_RDS_Upgrading of Silobela Substation	15, 21, 22	Technical Services	Physical
MP301_TEC_COM_Construction of Elukwatini Management Centre	10, 13, 14, 16, 18, 20, 24, 25	Technical Services	Physical
MP301_TEC_RDS_Upgrading of Emanzana Substation	17, 23	Technical Services	Physical
MP301_TEC_ELE_Construction of High mast lights	All Wards	Technical Services	Physical

8.8.1.9 Transportation accidents

No specific development projects

8.8.1.10 Building collapse

No specific development projects

8.9. DISASTER RISK MANAGEMENT PLANNING PRIORITIES FOR THE CALM

Although the CALM disaster risk profile has identified a wide range of risks posing a potential threat to its area, it is not practical nor is it financially achievable to address all the risks simultaneously. Effective and focused disaster risk management planning by all municipal organs of state can only be achieved through the identification of priority disaster risks and by the identification of the areas, communities and households most at risk to disaster in council's area. It is therefore necessary to adopt a carefully considered process which will enable this prioritization. Part of the prioritization process will also be to adopt a three - phased approach to disaster risk management planning. This does not however imply that once the third phase is completed that the planning process is over. It must be clearly understood that disaster risk management planning is not a stop/start activity or project but a continuous process which of necessity must produce dynamic, real time plans which remain current in a continuously changing environment.

The process of prioritization for disaster risk planning is critically informed by the disaster risk assessment findings for the CALM. The CALM must focus on the development of plans and the implementation of explicit programmes, projects and practices which give priority to building resilience and reducing the impact of a wide range of different disaster risks in areas, communities and households known to be to risk

The CALM priorities must therefore focus on preventing or limiting the impact of the following disaster risks:

Wide scale events that due to their magnitude is likely to affect the CALM as a whole. These include widespread floods and other severe weather events such as severe storms; veld fires; and hazardous materials (storage, transportation and usage).

- Recurrent high and medium impact events that may require CALM intervention or the mobilization of resources and infrastructure such as sinkholes, special events, floods and other severe weather events, large informal settlement fires, veld and urban fringe fires.
- Low frequency high and medium magnitude disaster risks with potential for severe loss and which require specialist support possibly not available in the CALM such as nuclear accidents, major transport accidents, Mission Critical Systems Failure and building collapse.
- Disaster risks that affect neighboring authorities which may have consequences for the CALM.

In the above regard it is the responsibility of each department and any other section included in the organizational structure of the CALM to identify and prioritize those disaster risks relevant to their functional area and prepare their departmental disaster risk management plan accordingly.

No.	Action	Performance Indicator	Time frame	Budget	Responsible Department
10.1	Disaster risks must be prioritized by different municipal departments and departments in line with the key functions	All CALM departments and entities have prioritized the CALM disaster risks in line with their specific function and include this in their planning			Community Service & Public Safety

8.10 RESPONSE TO CORONA (COVID19) PANDAMIC

8.10.1 BACKGROUND

Chief Albert Luthuli Local Municipality has a Disaster Management division within Fire Services Department. Section 43 of the Act 57 of 2002 delegate various powers and duties to the Municipal Disaster Management Centre which include among others: to specialise in issues concerning disasters and disaster management in the municipal area, promote coordination and integration of activities meant to reduce and promote the mitigation and prevent disaster risk within the municipal area.

8.10.2 INTRODUCTION

The novel Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome CoV-2 coronavirus that emerged in the city of Wuhan, China, last year 2010 and has since caused a large scale COVID-19 epidemic and spread to more than 70 other countries is the product of natural evolution.

8.10.3 SCOPE

The contingency plan of COVID-19 developed in response to the classification and declaration of the National State of Disaster due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The contingency plan for COVID-19 to be used for the

duration of the declaration of the National State of Disaster. The enabling document for this contingency plan is the Chief Albert Luthuli Municipal Disaster Management plan and regulations issued in terms of section 27(2) of the Act 57 of 2002.

8.10.4 SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT OF COVID-19

In terms of growing the local economy, the Municipality is mandated to “create an enabling environment for local economic development”. The current global Covid-19 pandemic (Corona virus) are likely to have severe socio-economic consequences throughout the globe. Closer to home, the Chief Albert Luthuli Local Municipality is also experiencing the adverse socio-economic impact of COVID-19 on our local economy and community. The National State of Disaster and subsequent lockdown comes amidst already dire macroeconomic conditions which have seen South Africa slump into a technical recession and downgraded to sub-investment grade (“junk” status) and worsening already high levels of unemployment. The declining economic growth which might be impacted on further by the Corona virus pandemic and international companies closing down as a result, the deteriorating state of the finances for state-owned entities, continued high unemployment and water and electricity shortages will put pressure on the ability of municipalities to raise revenue.

8.10.5 Financial impact of COVID 19

Municipalities will be impacted negatively due to a loss of revenue streams as businesses, households and communities reel from the economic fallout caused by COVID-19. Revenue streams will remain actively protected to mitigate the financial impact of COVID-19, understanding that most business and households will feel the financial impact of COVID-19 and will likely reprioritize our own spending patterns. In response to the impact of COVID-19, CALM are currently considering the reprioritization of the funding allocations for the 2020/21 and 2021/22 financial year. The economic growth rate achieved over the past periods is lower than forecast with an average growth rate of 0, 9% predicted for 2020. These challenges will continue to pressurize municipal revenue generation hence a conservative approach was followed to project revenue. Therefore, the municipality is required to improve its efforts to limit non-priority spending and to implement stringent cost containment measures. Cost containment regulations were promulgated in June 2019 which came into effect from 1 July 2019. Council subsequently approved the cost containment policy to give effect to the regulations.

8.10.6 Safety measures for Covid-19 (Adhere to Disaster Management Covid-19 Regulations)

To curb the spread of the virus the municipality adhere to the following:

1. Provision of personal protective equipment (PPE) to staff
2. Sanitizing of Municipal buildings and public areas e.g Taxi Rank
3. Sanitizing of Municipal vehicles and equipment.
4. Sanitizing of parking spaces.
5. Sanitizing of homeless centres and Quarantine area.

8.10.7 EDUCATION AND TRAINING

The Municipality conducts awareness weakly through email and during every change of level. The training or awareness covers Measures to prevent transmission of COVID-19 that apply to all workplaces and all people at the workplace include frequent hand-washing or disinfection with alcohol based hand sanitizer, respiratory hygiene such as covering coughs, physical distancing of at least 1 meter or more according to the national recommendations, wearing of masks where distancing is not possible, regular environmental cleaning and disinfection, and limiting unnecessary travel.

8.10.8 IDENTIFIED QUARANTINE AREA.

The municipality is partnering with the department of health in the event where an employee requires quarantine or isolation. However, the municipality conducts contact tracing and encourage the people who were a contact to self-quarantine at home and to seek medical attention if they experience any symptoms.

8.10.9 CONCLUSION

Since the beginning of the of Covid 19 in South Africa till 28 March 2021 the municipality has recorded a 45 cases of both Employees and Councillors, 44 recoveries and one fatality. Employees and community members are encouraged to continue observing the Covid 19 regulations.

Service Delivery
and budget
implementation
plan(SDBIP)
2021/2022

Chief Albert Luthuli Local Municipality
28 Kerk Street
P O Box 24
Carolina 1185
Mpumalanga

Telephone	:	017 843 4010
e-mail address	:	<u>mm@albertluthuli.gov.za</u>
web address	:	<u>www.albertluthuli.gov.za</u>

TABLE OF CONTENTS

A.	GLOSSARY	1
4.	Purpose of the SDBIP	3
5.	Legislative requirement	3
11.	Strategic Focus of Local Government	6
12.	Financial Plan	6
	A: FINANCIAL PROJECTIONS	8
	Table 2: Revenue (schedule A4)	8
	Table 3: Expenditure: Departmental allocation	8
1.	TABLE 4: CAPITAL PROJECTS 2021/2022 – 2023/2024	9
B.	SUMMARY OF STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES AND KEY PERFORMANCE AREAS AND TARGETS	12
2.	STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 1: TO ENSURE GOOD LEADERSHIP AND GOVERNANCE	13
3.	STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 2: TO ENSURE EFFICIENT AND EFFECTIVE INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT)	17
4.	STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 3: TO ENSURE TRANSFORMED INSTITUTION WITH COMPETENT AND CAPABLE HUMAN CAPITAL	19
5.	STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 4: TO ENSURE FINANCIAL HEALTHIER AND SUSTAINABLE ENVIRONMENT	20
6.	STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 5: TO ENSURE PROVISION OF BASIC SERVICES	23
7.	STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 6: TO ENSURE SUSTAINABLE LOCAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT	26
8.	ANNEXURE C TO THE SDBIP 2021/2022	Error! Bookmark not defined.

A. GLOSSARY

AFS	Annual Financial Statements
AG	Auditor-General
BBBEE	Broad Black Based Economic Enterprise
CALM	Chief Albert Luthuli Municipality
CFO	Chief Financial Officer
COGTA	Department of Co-operative Governance and Traditional Affairs
DoRA	Division of Revenue Act
GRAP	Generally Recognised Accounting Practices
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IDP	Integrated Development Plan
IMSP	Integrated Municipal Support Plan
KI	Kiloliter
km	Kilometer
KPA	Key Performance Area
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
kwh	Kilowatt hour
LED	Local Economic Development
LGSETA	Local Government Sectoral Education and Training Authority
LLF	Local Labour Forum
MEC	Member of the Executive Committee
MFMA	Local Government: Municipal Finance Management Act, 2003 (Act No 56 of 2003)
MIG	Municipal Infrastructure Grant
MSA	Local Government: Municipal Systems Act, 2000 (Act No ?? of 2000)
MTEF	Medium Term Expenditure Framework
MTREF	Medium Term Revenue and Expenditure Framework
NEMA	National Environmental Management Act, 1998 (Act No 107 of 1998)
NHNR	National Housing Needs Register
PED	Planning and Economic Development
PMS	Performance Management System
PMSF	Performance Management System Policy Framework
PMU	Project Management Unit
RMU	Ring Main Unit
S121	Section 121 of the Local Government: Municipal Finance Management Act, 2003
S38-41	Section 38 to 41 of the Local Government: Municipal Systems Act, 2000
S57/S54	Section 57/Section 54 of the Local Government: Municipal Systems Act, 2000
S72	Section 72 of the Local Government: Municipal Finance Management Act, 2003
SALGBC	South African Local Government Bargaining Council
SAQA	South African Qualifications Authority
SCM	Supply Chain Management
SDBIP	Service Delivery and Budget Implementation Plan
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMME	Small, Medium and Macro Enterprises
SPLUM	Spatial Planning Land Use Management
SPLUMA	Spatial Planning Land Use Management Act, 2013 (Act No 16 of 2013)
Strat Plan	Strategic Plan
WSP	Workplace Skills Plan

SERVICE DELIVERY AND BUDGET IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

2021/2022

1. Vision Statement

The **Vision** of the Municipality is to be a transparent, innovative and developmental municipality that improves the quality of life of its people.

The Municipality's vision refers to the achievement of a financially sustainable institution, good corporate governance that reflects best practice, a high performance institution, with high capacity and skills levels, sustainable delivery of quality services, an integrated and growing economy, ecological sustainability, and integrated communities that are self-reliant.

2. Mission Statement

The **Mission** of the Municipality is to provide a transparent and accountable government by rendering affordable and sustainable services, and encouraging economic and social development through community participation

The Municipality's mission responds to the objectives of government stipulated in Section 152 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa (1996) and is represented in the IDP. Improving the quality of life is central to our mission and is realized through the efficient and effective delivery of quality and affordable services to the people.

The Municipality's aim is to have empowered self-reliant citizens, who are entrepreneurs and leaders. In order to realize this, the municipality subscribes to the broader corporate values of customer focus, accountability, responsiveness, excellence, service orientation.

3. Values

Figure 1: Core values of the municipality are:

4. Purpose of the SDBIP

The Service Delivery and Budget Implementation Plan (SDBIP) 2021/2022 is a detailed plan for implementing the delivery of services and the Budget for the 2021/22 financial year according to the Local Government: Municipal Finance Management Act, 2003 (Act No 56 of 2003). It is based on the Council approved revised IDP and MTREF. The SDBIP therefore serves as a contract between the Administration, Council and the community expressing the goals and objectives set by the Council as quantifiable outcomes that can be implemented by the Administration over the next twelve months. The SDBIP facilitates the process of holding management accountable for their performance. It provides the basis for measuring performance in the delivery of services.

5. Legislative requirement

The Local Government: Municipal Finance Management Act, 2003 (Act No 56 of 2003) prescribes that each municipality must compile a SDBIP. The mayor of the municipality is required to approve the SDBIP within 28 days after the approval of the Budget and table the same at a municipal council meeting, and make the document public no later than 14 days after approval of the information.

6. Other guidelines

The National Treasury MFMA Circular No 13 further states that the SDBIP is a layered plan - once the top layer targets have been set, as in this document, the various departments of the municipality develop the next lower level.

7. Strategic objectives

The organisation of the SDBIP is in terms of the following prescribed key strategic objectives:

- To ensure good governance;
- To ensure efficient and effective Information Communication Technology (ICT);
- To ensure transformed institution with competent and capable human capital Municipal Financial Viability and Management;
- To ensure financial healthier and sustainable environment;
- To ensure provision of basic services; and
- To ensure sustainable Local Economic Development.

8. The Context of the SDBIP

Municipal strategic planning forms an integral part of the Municipality's annual IDP review and alignment, and Budget preparation processes. In turn these processes, in essence, are part of the broader system of performance management within the municipality.

The following figure illustrates the link between and the sequence from the IDP, strategic planning, Budget, SDBIP, PMS up to the annual report.

9. Performance Management System

Chief Albert Luthuli Local Municipal Council had established Performance Management System which will be used as a tool to monitor the implementation of the IDP and budget through the SDBIP, and using an approved PMS frame work policy which gets revised every year at a start of a, for implementation in 2021/2022 financial year. The Performance Management System provides for quarterly and mid-year performance reporting and reviews on the implementation of the SDBIP.

A performance management system is a systematic approach that aligns performance at all levels of an organisation to achieve strategic objectives. It uses measurements to understand, predict and improve organisational performance. The three major components in a typical performance management system are an integrated set of key performance indicators (KPIs) linked to the strategic objectives of the organisation.

Key performance indicators and targets are set for each strategic objective in order to quantify measurable outcomes, which is an easy way to navigate service delivery, and to determine if these strategic objectives were realised or achieved.

10. Institutional Framework

Performance management follows a process with the following activities:

11. Strategic Focus of Local Government

12. Financial Plan

The financial plan of Chief Albert Luthuli Local Municipality is presented in this section. The financial plan comprises:

- Financial projections of revenue, operational and capital expenditure (Annexure A)
- Service delivery targets and performance indicators for each quarter (Annexure B).

A: FINANCIAL PROJECTIONS
Table: 1 Summary Schedule (schedule A1)

	Annual budget 2021/2022 to 2023/2024					
	Budget year 2020/2021	Supplementary budget 2020/2021	Adjustment budget 2020/2021	Budget year 2021/2022	Budget year 2022/2023	Budget year 2023/2024
Total revenue	R974 908 475	R952 809 685	R957 453 673	R897 078 036	R900 780 517	R885 041 554
Total expenditure	R974 423 580	R952 753 580	R956 881 363	R897 019 125	R892 198 125	R884 870 983
Surplus/deficit	R484 895	R56 105	R572 309	R58 398	R8 582 398	R170 570

Table 2: Revenue (schedule A4)

	Annual budget 2021/2022 to 2023/2024					
	Budget year 2020/2021	Supplementary budget 2020/2021	Adjustment budget 2020/2021	Budget year 2021/2022	Budget year 2022/2023	Budget year 2023/2024
Property rates	R99 663 775	R99 663 775	R99 663 775	R105 643 601	R111 982 217	R118 701 150
Service charges – electricity revenue	R37 834 495	R37 834 495	R37 834 495	R44 342 028	R48 288 468	R52 586 142
Service charges – water revenue	R45 586 628	R45 586 628	R45 586 628	R48 321 825	R51 221 135	R54 294 403
Service charges – sanitation revenue	R12 194 228	R12 194 228	R12 194 228	R12 925 861	R13 701 434	R14 523 520
Service charges – refuse revenue	R10 447 969	R10 447 969	R10 447 969	R11 074 847	R11 739 337	R12 443 698
Rental of facilities and equipment	R13 891	R126 101	R126 701	R134 303	R142 361	R150 902
Interest earned – external investments	R2 170 774	R2 170 774	R179 247	190 001	R201 401	R213 486
Interest earned – outstanding debtors	R10 638 209	R10 638 209	R7 587 221	8 042 454	R8 525 001	R9 036 501
Fines	R179 247	R179 247	R179 247	R190 001	R201 401	R213 486
Transfers recognised	R329 123 225	R388 051 225	R398 049 000	R352 626 000	R371 785 000	R368 063 000
Other own revenue	R794 034	R794 034	R482 162	R511 091	R541 757	R574 262
Capital projects	R426 262 000	R345 123 000	R345 123 000	R313 076 000	R282 451 000	R254 241 000
Total revenue	R974 908 475	R952 809 685	R957 453 673	R897 078 036	R900 780 517	R885 041 554

Table 3: Expenditure: Departmental allocation

	Annual budget 2021/2022 to 2023/2024			Percentage of budget		
	Budget year 2020/2021	Supplementary budget 2020/2021	Adjustment budget 2020/2021		Budget year 2021/2022	Variance
Planning and Economic Development	R15 488 235	R15 488 235	R16 420 520	R15 599 494	R821 026	2%
Corporate Services	R36 996 567	R36 996 567	R31 043 099	R29 940 944	R1 552 154	3%
Financial Services	R123 072 988	R143 027 988	R105 325 584	R100 059 305	R5 266 279	11%
Project Management Unit	R432 213 194	R351 650 193	R345 123 000	R313 076 000	R32 047 000	35%
Municipal Manager	R9 092 803	R9 092 803	R9 092 803	R8 638 162	R454 640	1%

Council General	R31 042 469	R31 042 469	R29 490 345	R1 552 123	3%
Community Services	R67 083 720	R68 525 801	R65 100 460	R3 426 340	7%
Technical Services	R259 433 605	R298 371 605	R335 564 925	R14 742 161	37%
Total Expenditure	R974 423 580	R952 177 581	R897 019 638	R59 861 725	100%

1. **TABLE 4: CAPITAL PROJECTS 2021/2022 – 2023/2024**

2021/2022 DRAFT CAPITAL PROJECTS BUDGET						
IDP No	MUNICIPAL PRIORITY OR IDP PROGRAMME	PROJECT DESCRIPTION	REGION SEGMENT	2021/2022 DRAFT BUDGET FORECAST	2022/2023 DRAFT BUDGET FORECAST	2023/2024 DRAFT BUDGET FORECAST
Currency				R	R	R
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0005_MIG	Water	Upgrading of Carolina Water Treatment Works: Phase 4	15, 21 & 22	11 000 000		
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0006_MIG	Water	Replacement of AC Pipes at Ekulindeni Water Scheme	12	3 000 000		
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0007_MIG	Water	Replacement of AC Pipes at Empuluzi Water Scheme	4,5,7,9 & 11		10 000 000	15 000 000
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0012_WSIG	Water	Non-Revenue Water & Revenue Enhancement Programme for the Schemes in CALLM	10, 13, 14, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 23, 24 & 25	64 000 000	57 745 000	60 000 000
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0013_RBIG	Water	Upgrading of Eerstehoek, Empuluzi & Methula Water Bulk Supply.	01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 07, 09, 10, 11, 13, 14, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 23, 24 & 25	145 000 000	110 000 000	78 000 000

2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0014_MIG	Sanitation	Upgrading of Empuluzi Waste Water Treatment Works (WWTW)	4,5,7,9 & 11	12 000 000	10 000 000	13 000 000
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0015_MIG	Sanitation	Upgrading of Carolina Waste Water Treatment Works (WWTW)	15, 21 & 22		8 000 000	10 000 000
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0017_MIG	Sanitation	Upgrading of Elukwatini Waste Water Treatment Works (WWTW)	10,13,14,16,18,20,24 & 25	12 000 000	12 000 000	15 000 000
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0018_MIG	Sanitation	Installation of Smartsan or Environsan Toilets	To be determined	11 502 600	12 000 000	15 000 000
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0020_MIG	Roads	Construction of Ekulindeni Ring Road	12	7 000 000		
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0023_MIG	Roads	Construction of Mahoxo Ring Road	2		10 000 000	
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0027_MIG	Roads	Construction of Paving Road in Carolina Town	15	10 000 000		
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0029_MIG	Roads	Construction of Paving Road in Nhlatzatshe 2 & 4	20 & 25			10 000 000
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0030_MIG	Roads	Construction of Paving Road in Nhlatzatshe	24	8 000 000		
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0032_MIG	Electricity	Construction of High mast lights	01, 07, 09, 10, 13, 14, 16, 18, 19, 22 & 24	8 000 000	10 000 000	9 028 950
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0033_INEP	Electricity	Upgrading of Silobela Substation, Infills, Connections & Feeder Line	15,21&22	8 468 000		
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0034_INEP	Electricity	Upgrading of Emanzana Substation	17&23		12 000 000	
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0035_INEP	Electricity	Construction of Piet Debruin Park: Switching Station	21			12 000 000
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0036_FEEDSM	Electricity	Energy Efficiency Demand Side Management		3 500 000	3 000 000	
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0037_MIG	Community Asset	Construction of Silobela Sport Fields	15&22	5 000 000	5 720 700	7 000 000

2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0039_MIG	Community Asset	Construction of Dundonald Taxi rank	4,5,7,9 & 11		10 000 000	5 000 000
2020/21_CALLM_TEC_0040_MIG	Community Asset	Construction of Emanzana Transfer Station	17&23		7 000 000	
Total Budget					277 465 700	249 028 950

B. SUMMARY OF STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES AND KEY PERFORMANCE AREAS AND TARGETS

NO	STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE	KEY PERFORMANCE AREA	PERFORMANCE TARGET
•	To ensure good leadership and governance	KPA: Policies and Procedures KPA: Governance Structures KPA: Good Governance and Leadership KPA: Legal and Compliance KPA: Public Participation KPA: Marketing and Communication KPA: Performance Reporting KPA: Risk Management KPA: Internal Audit KPA: Data Integrity and Security	2 1 7 2 6 4 7 2 2 4
•	To ensure efficient and effective Information Communication Technology (ICT)		
•	To ensure transformed institution with competent and capable human capital	KPA: Learning and Development KPA: Management of vacancies KPA: Leave Management	3 6
•	To ensure financial healthier and sustainable environment	KPA: Supply Chain Management (SCM) KPA: Revenue Management KPA: Expenditure Management KPA: Financial Management KPA: Unauthorised, Irregular, Fruitless and Wasteful Expenditure (UIF) KPA: Asset Management KPA: Debt Management KPA: Creditors Management KPA: Access to Electricity KPA: Access to Water and Sanitation KPA: Access to Roads and Transportation System KPA: Waste Management KPA: Project Management KPA: Social Development KPA: Economic Development KPA: Land use management KPA: Job Opportunities KPA: Disaster Management KPA: Healthy and Safer Environment KPA: Traffic Management	1 3 6 5 2 3 2 2 1 1 6 5 5 4 5 4 3 3 2 2 5 2 2
•	To ensure provision of basic services		
•	To ensure sustainable local economic development		
Total number of targets			116

2. STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 1: TO ENSURE GOOD LEADERSHIP AND GOVERNANCE

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022					Annual Target
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Quarter 4	
KPA: POLICIES AND PROCEDURES									
1.	Number of developed and reviewed policies	All Departments	39	1	1	1	2	5	
2.	Number of departmental of service charters reviewed.	All Departments	1	0	0	1	0	1	
KPA: GOVERNANCE STRUCTURES									
3.	Number of departmental strategies and department plans approved	All Departments	0	0	0	0	1	1	
KPA: GOOD GOVERNANCE AND LEADERSHIP									
4.	Number of management reports submitted to relevant governance structures	All Departments/ Council and Executive	197	15	15	15	15	60	
5.	Council Structures Meetings attended (Section 80, Mayoral and Council)	Corporate Services	34	9	7	9	9	34	
6.	% of forum meetings attended as per invitation	All Departments	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022				
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Annual Target
7.	% of internal audit findings resolved within 90 days after internal audit report has been issued	Office of the Municipal Manager	68%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
8.	% of external audit findings resolved within legislated 60 days (31 January)	Office of the Municipal Manager	96%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
9.	Number of annual report approved within legislated timeframe	Office of the Municipal Manager	1	0	1	0	1	1
10.	Number of unqualified audit opinion received	Office of the Municipal Manager	1	0	1	0	0	1
KPA: LEGAL AND COMPLIANCE								
11.	Percentage of Service Level Agreements (SLAs) finalised within 30 days of awarding the contract	Corporate Services	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
12.	Number of by-laws reviewed and drafted	Corporate Services	4	0	1	0	1	2
KPA: PUBLIC PARTICIPATION								
13.	Number of IDP, Budget, process plan and framework plan approved on 31 August	Planning and Economic Development	1	1	0	0	0	1

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022					Annual Target
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Quarter 4	
14.	Number of IDP process plan and consultations conducted	Planning and Economic Development	25	0	0	0	0	25	
15.	Number of next year's IDP first draft approved by 31 March	Planning and Economic Development	1	0	1	0	1	1	
16.	Number of first draft IDP consultations conducted by 30 April	Planning and Economic Development	1	0	0	0	1	1	
17.	Number of next year's IDP final draft approved by 31 May	Planning and Economic Development	1	0	0	0	1	1	
18.	Number of Final IDP consultations conducted by 30 June	Planning and Economic Development	1	0	0	0	1	1	
KPA: MARKETING AND COMMUNICATION									
19.	Number of monthly internal newsletters produced	Executive Mayor office	12	3	3	3	3	12	
20.	Number of external quarterly newsletters produced	Executive Mayor office	1	1	1	1	1	4	
21.	Number of satisfaction surveys conducted.	Corporate services	0	1	1	1	1	4	
22.	Number of display of national symbols in all buildings.	Corporate services	5	5	5	5	5	5	
KPA: PERFORMANCE REPORTING									

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022				
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Annual Target
23.	Number of next year's SDBIP approved before 30 June	Performance Management	1	0	0	0	1	1
24.	Number of PMS Frameworks approved by 30 September	Performance Management	1	0	1	0	0	1
25.	% of senior management performance agreements approved by 31 July	Performance Management	100%	100%	0	0	0	100%
26.	% of senior management performance agreements submitted to relevant stakeholders by 14 August	Performance Management	0%	100%	0	0	0	100%
27.	% of annual performance assessment of senior management by 30 July	Performance Management	0%	100%	0	0	0	100%
28.	Number of mid-year institutional performance evaluations conducted by 25 Jan	Performance Management	1	0	0	1	0	1
29.	% of middle management employees with signed performance plans	Performance Management	100%	100%	0	0	0	100%
KPA: RISK MANAGEMENT								
30.	Number of risk assessment workshops conducted	Risk Management	2	1	0	1	0	2

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022					Annual Target
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Annual Target	
31.	Number of quarterly risk registers approved	Risk Management	4	1	1	1	1	4	
KPA: INTERNAL AUDIT									
32.	Number of Internal Audit plans approved before reporting period	Internal Audit	1	0	0	0	1	1	
33.	% of implemented IA plan	Internal Audit	80%	25%	50%	75%	100%	100%	

3. **STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 2: TO ENSURE EFFICIENT AND EFFECTIVE INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT)**

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022					Annual Target
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Annual Target	
KPA: DATA INTEGRITY AND SECURITY									
34.	Number of Firewall and anti-virus installations completed	Corporate Services	1	0	0	1	0	1	
35.	Number of monthly offsite backup storage conducted	Corporate Services	12	3	3	3	3	12	
36.	Number of compliance to Section 75 (MFMA) requirements in terms of the Website updating monthly	Corporate Services	12	3	3	3	3	12	

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022				
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Annual Target
37.	Percentage of ICT related devises maintained	Corporate Services	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

4. STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 3: TO ENSURE TRANSFORMED INSTITUTION WITH COMPETENT AND CAPABLE HUMAN CAPITAL

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022				Annual Target
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	
KPA: LEARNING AND DEVELOPMENT								
38.	Number of Workplace Skills Plan (WSP) and Annual Training Plan submitted (ATP) to LG SETA before 30 April	Corporate Services	1	0	0	1	0	1
39.	Number of employees trained as per the WSP	Corporate Services	79	5	5	5	5	20
40.	Number of councillors trained as per the WSP	Corporate Services	49	2	2	2	4	10
KPA: MANAGEMENT OF VACANCIES								
41.	Number of critical, vacant and funded positions filled	Corporate Services	16	5	5	3	2	15
42.	Number of women, youth, racial groups and people with disability appointed	Corporate Services	7	2	2	2	2	8
43.	Number of female appointments in Senior Management positions	Corporate Services	0	0	0	0	1	1
44.	Number of female appointments in Middle Management positions	Corporate Services	0	0	0	1	0	1

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022					Annual Target
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Annual Target	
45.	Staff turnover rate maintained below 5%	Corporate Services	0.21%	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%
46.	Number of intern positions filled	All Departments	0	1	1	1	2	5	5
KPA: LEAVE MANAGEMENT									
47.	Number of monthly leave registers approved	All Departments	13	3	3	3	3	12	12

5. STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 4: TO ENSURE FINANCIAL HEALTHIER AND SUSTAINABLE ENVIRONMENT

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022					Annual Target
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Annual Target	
KPA: SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT (SCM)									
48.	Number of procurement plans approved by 30 May	Financial services	1	0	0	0	1	1	1
49.	Number of quarterly contract registers submitted to MMs office	Financial services	4	1	1	1	1	4	4
50.	% of bids awarded within 90 days reported to council	Financial services	100%	85%	85%	85%	85%	85%	85%
KPA: REVENUE MANAGEMENT									

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022				
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Annual Target
51.	Number of additional grants sourced	All departments	0	0	1	0	1	2
52.	Number of supplementary valuation rolls approved	Financial Services	1	0	0	0	1	1
53.	% reduction in billing accuracy complaints	Financial Services	80%	80%	80%	80%	80%	80%
54.	% own revenue collected	Financial Services	65%	65%	65%	65%	65%	65%
55.	Revenue collected from investment properties	Corporate Services	13 892	13 892	13 892	13 892	13 892	55 568
56.	Revenue collected through issued traffic infringements summons	Community and Safety Services	142 850	18 750	18 750	18 750	18 750	75 000
KPA: EXPENDITURE MANAGEMENT								
57.	Percentage of operational expenditure spent	Financial Services	90%	25%	50%	75%	100%	100%
58.	Percentage of capital expenditure spent	Financial Services	90.13%	90%	90%	90%	90%	90%
59.	Maintenance of employee costs percentage over revenue	Corporate Services	27%	40%	40%	40%	40%	40%
60.	Number of final operating & capital expenditure budget approved before 31 May	Finance Department	1	0	0	0	1	1

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022				
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Annual Target
61.	Percentage of budget spent on training	Corporate Services	97%	25%	50%	75%	100%	100%
KPA: FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT								
62.	Number of reconciliations prepared	Financial Services	96	24	24	24	24	96
63.	Improved current ratio to be within accepted industry norm	Financial Services	1.06:1	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1
KPA: UNAUTHORISED, IRREGULAR, FRUITLESS AND WASTEFUL EXPENDITURE (UIF)								
64.	Percentage reduction of unauthorised expenditure	Financial Services	100%	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%
65.	Percentage reduction of irregular expenditure incurred during the financial year	Financial Services	62.5%	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%
66.	Percentage reduction of fruitless and wasteful expenditure	Financial Services	5.67%	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%
KPA: ASSET MANAGEMENT								
67.	Number of quarterly physical asset verification conducted of movable assets	Financial Services	4	1	1	1	1	4
68.	Number of re-assessment of useful lives, residual values and impairment test conducted	Financial Services	1	0	0	0	1	1

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022				
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Annual Target
KPA: DEBT MANAGEMENT								
69.	Reduction in average collection period	Financial Services	980 days	1 492 days	1 025 days	558 days	250 days	30 days
KPA: CREDITORS MANAGEMENT								
70.	Reduction in average payment period	Financial Services	457 days	354 days	246 days	138 days	60 days	30 days

6. STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 5: TO ENSURE PROVISION OF BASIC SERVICES

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022				
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Annual Target
KPA: ACCESS TO ELECTRICITY								
71.	Number of transformers maintained	Technical Services	72	20	20	20	20	80
72.	Number of public lights maintained	Technical Services	376	122	122	123	123	490
73.	Number of KMs of electrical network maintained	Technical Services	55.8	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	50
74.	Number of panels maintained	Technical Services	12	3	3	3	4	13

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022				
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Annual Target
75.	Number of Ring Main Units (RMU) maintained	Technical Services	30	5	7	7	5	24
76.	Number of smart meters installed	Technical Services	0	50	50	50	50	200
KPA: ACCESS TO WATER AND SANITATION								
77.	Number of boreholes repaired	Technical Services	39	10	10	15	15	50
78.	Number of pumps & Motors maintained	Technical Services	29	10	10	10	10	40
79.	Number of meters of water network maintained	Technical Services	0	750	750	750	750	3 000
80.	Percentage of new households water connection received and responded to	Technical Services	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
81.	Percentage of findings on environmental impact responded to	Technical Services	0%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
KPA: ACCESS TO ROADS AND TRANSPORTATION SYSTEM								
82.	Number of KMs of gravel roads maintained	Technical Services	235.3	100	100	100	100	400
83.	Number of square meters of road repaired	Technical Services	684	150	150	150	150	600
84.	Number of foot bridges constructed	Technical Services	2	2	2	3	3	10

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022				Annual Target
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	
85.	Number of vehicles bridges maintained	Technical Services	0	0	1	1	2	
86.	Number of speed humps constructed	Technical Services	16	2	2	3	10	
KPA: WASTE MANAGEMENT								
87.	Number of areas receiving refuse removal services	Community and Safety Services	6	6	6	6	6	
88.	Number of refuse bins supplied to billable households.	Community and Safety Services	213	100	150	100	500	
89.	Number of disposal sites maintained	Community and Safety Services	5	5	5	5	5	
90.	Number of cemeteries maintained	Community and Safety Services	6	6	6	6	6	
KPA: PROJECT MANAGEMENT								
91.	Number of water programs monitored	Project Management	5	1	2	1	3	
92.	Number of sanitation programs monitored	Project Management	3	2	0	1	3	
93.	Number of electrification programs monitored	Project Management	2	0	1	2	3	

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022				
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Annual Target
94.	Number of roads programs monitored	Project Management	5	1	0	1	1	3
95.	Number of public facilities programs monitored	Project Management	2	0	0	0	1	1

7. STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 6: TO ENSURE SUSTAINABLE LOCAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022				
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Annual Target
KPA: SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT								
96.	Number of employee wellness programmes conducted	Corporate Services	3	3	3	3	3	12
97.	Number of personnel/skills development	Project Management	4	0	3	3	3	9
98.	Number of sports and cultural events organised for the community	Community and Safety Services	1	1	1	1	1	4
99.	Number of Moral Regeneration Movement structures supported	Community and Safety Services	7	2	2	2	2	8
KPA: ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT								

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022					Annual Target
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4		
100.	Number of LED strategy projects implemented	Planning and Economic Development	0	0	0	1	1	1	
101.	Number of Co-ops offered support	Planning and Economic Development	2	6	6	6	6	24	
102.	Number of tourism awareness campaigns conducted	Planning and Economic Development	3	3	3	3	3	12	
KPA: LAND USE MANAGEMENT									
103.	Number of cemeteries established	Planning and Economic Development	1	0	0	0	2	2	
104.	Number of Land-audit conducted and finalised	Planning and Economic Development	0	0	0	1	0	1	
105.	Percentage of RDP houses Monitored	Planning and Economic Development	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	
KPA: JOB OPPORTUNITIES									
106.	Number of programmes implemented for job opportunities	Planning and Economic Development	4	1	1	1	1	4	
107.	Number of employment Equity Report (EER) submitted before 15 January	Corporate Services	1	0	0	1	0	1	
KPA: DISASTER MANAGEMENT									

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022				Annual Target
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	
108.	% of disaster incidents of attended	Community and Safety Services	82%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
109.	Number of disaster awareness programme conducted	Community and Safety Services	4	1	1	1	1	4
KPA: HEALTHY AND SAFER ENVIRONMENT								
110.	Number of monthly Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) reports submitted to the Office of the Municipal Manager	Corporate Services	5	3	3	3	3	12
111.	Number of health and safety inspections and awareness's conducted	Corporate services	9	3	3	3	3	12
112.	Number of HIV and AIDS campaigns conducted	Office of the Executive Mayor	4	1	1	1	1	4
113.	Number of library awareness programme implemented	Community And Safety	30	8	10	2	10	30
114.	Number of environmental campaigns conducted	Community and Safety Services	4	1	1	1	1	4
KPA: TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT								
115.	Number of traffic law enforcement programmes implemented	Community and Safety Services	8	3	3	3	3	12

No	Key Performance Indicator	Department	Baseline	Quarterly targets 2021-2022				
				Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Annual Target
116.	% increase in traffic fines issued	Community and Safety Services	34.6%	20%	20%	20%	20%	20%

MANDLA S DLAMINI
 Accounting Officer
 Chief Albert Luthuli Local
 Municipality
 28 June 2022
 Date

CLR DANIEL P NKOSI
 Executive Mayor
 Chief Albert Luthuli Local
 Municipality
 28 June 2022
 Date

ANNEXURE C

GERT SIBANDE DISTRICT MUNICIPALITY

DISTRICT DEVELOPMENT MODEL

GERT SIBANDE ONE PLAN SUMMARY

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	INTRODUCTION.....	1
2.	DIAGNOSTIC SUMMARY.....	4
	2.4.1 Integrated Service Provisioning	12
	2.4.2 Demographic and District profile	14
	2.4.3 Economic Positioning	16
	2.4.4 Governance and Administration	17
	2.4.5 Spatial Restructuring	18
	2.4.6 Infrastructure Engineering	19
	2.4.7 COVID-19 Impact	21
3.	VISION (OVERALL DESIRED FUTURE).....	21
4.	STRATEGIES.....	26
5.	IMPLEMENTATION PLAN.....	32
6.	CONCLUSION.....	35
7.	ANNEXURE: CATALYTIC COMMITMENTS.....	36

TABLES AND FIGURES

Figure 1: One Plan integration at different levels.....	3
Figure 2: Theory of change graphical representation	4
Figure 3: Gert Sibande DDM Institutional composition	5
Figure 4: Gert Sibande District Municipality	6
Figure 5: Average age, racial composition, and gender	7
Figure 6: Household composition and tenure options.....	7
Figure 7: Economic situation in relation to household income.....	8
Figure 8: Gert Sibande population data and projections.....	8
Figure 9: Access to services.....	10

Figure 10: DDM Approved workstreams	32
Figure 11: Gert Sibande DDM one Plan reporting structure	32
Table 1: Population figures per municipal area	8
Table 2: Gert Sibande Human Development Index per municipal area	9
Table 3: Poverty rate per municipal area	9
Table 4: Income inequality per municipal area	9
Table 5: Gert Sibande Economic Growth	11

2.2. INTRODUCTION

2.1. Problem statement

The Gert Sibande District along with the rest of South African municipalities is facing numerous challenges that include, inadequate resources and infrastructure to cope with the demands of a growing population with dynamic socio-economic demands. Poor service delivery and general poor government services lead to the decline of resources, lack of opportunities, and overall poor living conditions.

The Presidency Budget Speech (2019) identified the "pattern of operating in silos" as a challenge that led to a "lack of coherence in planning and implementation and has made monitoring and oversight of government's programme difficult". The President further called for the rolling out of "a new integrated district-based approach to address service delivery challenges [and] localise[d] procurement and job creation, that promotes and supports local businesses, and that involves communities."

2.1. District Development Model (DDM)

The District Development Model (DDM) was conceptualised and presented to the Joint Cabinet Committee on 13 August 2019 receiving overwhelming support. The Local Government MinMec (Minister, MECs and SALGA) extended its support of the DDM and recommended a balanced pilot approach looking at two Districts (rural) and one metro (urban) context. The recommended pilot sites identified were OR Tambo District, Waterberg District and eThekweni Metro.

The DDM was endorsed by the Presidential Coordinating Council (PCC) on 20 August 2019. The PCC supported the "One Plan" instrument proposed by the DDM and emphasized that the One Plan must express the National Development Plan and overlay the MTSF priorities, Provincial Priorities and Municipal IDP/SDBIPs. The PCC endorsed that resource allocation and budgeting must be aligned to supporting the implementation of the District Model. The DDM was subsequently approved by Cabinet on 21 August 2019.

The District Development Model is an operational model for improving Cooperative Governance to build a capable, ethical Developmental State. The DDM focus on an "All of Government and Society Approach". The underlying methodology requires government and state enterprises to work towards higher performance accountability and effective service delivery and development outcomes. The "All of Government and Society Approach" expresses jointly agreed outcomes and commitments to the One Plan. This inter-governmental plan focuses on development outcomes for each space over the short, medium and long term. The DDM introduces new inter-governmental planning, budgeting and implementation paradigm and discipline (spatial targeting and budgeting towards common long term outcomes).

The Model consists of a process by which joint and collaborative planning is undertaken at local, district and metropolitan by all three spheres of governance resulting in a single strategically focused One Plan for each of the 44 districts and 8 metropolitan geographic spaces in the country, wherein the district is seen as the 'landing strip'.

2.1.1 The relationship between DDM and One Plan

The DDM is anchored on the development and implementation of the One Plan. The “One Plan” is defined as an intergovernmental plan setting out a 25-30 years long-term strategic framework (consisting of short, medium and long-term actions) to guide investment and delivery in relation to each of the 52 district and metropolitan spaces.

District Development Model is aimed at transforming the economy and improving the quality of life of people by enhancing cooperative governance and overall state coherence and performance. It is focused on bringing about fundamental change with the following strategic goals:

1. To stimulate new thinking, new socio-economic paradigms, new and bold solutions and alternatives;
2. To fundamentally change conditions on the ground:
 - 2.1 People
 - 2.2 Economy
 - 2.3 Space
3. To develop resilience and prosperity of the Country;
4. To facilitate Responsive Institutions and Change Management; and
5. To embed a Programmatic Approach to Cooperative Governance;
6. To respond strategically to the socio-economic impact of Covid-19.

2.1.1 The purpose explained

The purpose of the Gert Sibande District One Plan is:

- To give effect to the **District Development Model (DDM)** approved by cabinet as a practical method to improve service delivery and development impact in the Gert Sibande District through integrated planning, budgeting and delivery by all three spheres of government working together with stakeholders and communities;
- To localise and synergise the **National Development Plan (NDP)**, the Medium Term Strategic Framework (MTSF), National Spatial Development Framework (NSDF), Integrated Urban Development Framework (IUDF) and key national and provincial sector policies/strategies/plans with socio-economic and spatial development logic of the Gert Sibande District.
- To express a **coherent and predictable government approach in relation to these key priorities** through a **Long-Term Strategic Framework (One Plan)** for growth and development of the Gert Sibande District that is co-produced by all three spheres of government together with stakeholders and communities introducing “One Plan=One budget”;
- To enable a programmatic Intergovernmental Relations approach in relation to the implementation of the One Plan that will serve as an **impact performance framework** tracking the commitments and spending of national and provincial sector departments and the Gert Sibande District Municipality according to the **shared vision** and ultimately usher in a new dawn that will result in a new and improved standard of living for the residents of the district.

Figure 1: One Plan integration at different levels

2.1. One Plan composition

The One Plan is a visionary and transformative plan addressing the following interrelated DDM key transformation focus areas, content themes or principles, namely:

1.1 Demographic Change/People Development: The process of understanding the current population profile and development dynamics and by which a desired demographic profile and radical improvement in the quality of life of the people is achieved through skills development.

1.2 Economic Positioning: The process by which a competitive edge is created that enables domestic and foreign investment attraction and job creation based on an inclusive and transformed economy. The economic positioning informs the spatial restructuring and has to be sustained through protecting, nurturing and harnessing natural environment and resources.

1.3 Spatial Restructuring and Environmental Sustainability:

The process by which a transformed, efficient and environmentally sustainable spatial development pattern and form is created to support a competitive local economy and integrated sustainable human settlements. Spatial restructuring informs infrastructure investment in terms of quantum as well as location and layout of infrastructure networks.

1.4 Infrastructure Engineering: the process by which infrastructure planning and investment especially bulk infrastructure installation occurs in order to support the transforming spatial pattern and form, meet the needs of a competitive and inclusive local economy and integrated human settlements, and ensure demand for housing and services is met in a sustainable way over the long-term.

1.5 Integrated Service Provisioning: the process by which infrastructure planning and investment especially bulk infrastructure installation occurs in order to support the transforming spatial pattern and form, meet the needs of a competitive and inclusive local economy and integrated human settlements, and ensure demand for housing and services is met in a sustainable way over the long-term.

1.6 Governance and Financial Management: the process by which leadership and management is exercised, in particular, that planning, budgeting, procurement, delivery, financial and performance management takes place in an effective, efficient, accountable and transparent manner. It also includes spatial governance, that is, the process by which the spatial transformation goals are achieved through assessing and directing land

development and undertaking effective land use management and release of municipal/public land.

The transformation focus areas (content themes or principles) do not exist in isolation but rather as interchangeable and integrated mechanisms to achieve the One Plan vision. The One Plan vision articulates a spatial and development vision through economic growth, financial sustainability, good governance practices, infrastructure and services investment.

Figure 2: Theory of change graphical representation

The DDM One Plan's preparation is guided by a logical framework that rests on the principles of the "Theory of Change". The theory of change concept essentially encapsulates the identification of the desired end-

state, desired outcomes, or a changed state, and a detailed assessment and strategy of how to achieve this through an outcome framework.

An outcome framework outlines the desired set of long-term goals that are engineered backwards to identify strategies and measurable actions to achieve these long-term goals. The process of an outcome framework also requires a reporting framework to assess progress made on goal achievement and the impact of implementing strategies and actions.

In relation to each transformation focus area, the One Plan has to articulate the following:

- 1.7 The current situation, status quo or diagnostic assessment;
- 1.8 The desired future or vision;
 - The strategies and interventions needed to move from the current situation to the desired end state, and;
 - The implementation of commitments by all three spheres of government, and;
 - key stakeholders will enable the identified strategies/interventions to be implemented.

2.2. DIAGNOSTIC SUMMARY

This chapter seeks to highlight the state of development in Gert Sibande District Municipality looking at the regional context and status quo of development with a focus on certain indicators. Furthermore, this chapter highlights the demographic analysis of the district in a form of prevailing trends.

a. Institutional arrangements

The DDM structures in the Gert Sibande District are aligned with other similar structures in the province. The Council is chaired by the Executive Mayor to allow for sufficient political oversight by members of the Executive of the Gert Sibande District Municipality. The Municipal Manager chairs the Technical Team which is comprising of all government and private sector officials. The deployed Head of Department from one provincial department and municipal managers from all local municipalities are also members of the technical team.

The District Municipality has revised its organizational structure to strengthen the administrative support provided to the DDM function. The function is placed in the Office of the Municipal Manager to ensure strategic administrative support.

Figure 3: Gert Sibande DDM Institutional composition

b. Geographic context

GSDM is designated as DC30 by the Municipal Demarcation Board and is one of the three (3) District Municipalities that constitute Mpumalanga Province. The District Municipality is bordered by the Ekurhuleni Metropolitan Municipality and Sedibeng District Municipality to the west. Thabo Mofutsanyane District Municipality is located towards south-west. The Ehlanzeni District Municipality is located to the north-east and Nkangala District Municipality to the north. Amajuba and Zululand District Municipalities in KwaZulu-Natal

Province are located to the south, and the Kingdom of Eswatini to the east.

Gert Sibande District Municipality is the largest of the three Districts in Mpumalanga Province at 31 841 km², covering 40% of the Mpumalanga Province's land mass. The western portion of the district mostly comprises typical Highveld vegetation and climate, with the eastern end of the District being more mountainous and characterised by extensive forestry and rural settlements and villages (Chief Albert Luthuli and Mkhondo Local Municipalities).

The concentration of conservation and protected areas also increases towards the east. Apart from the east-west orientated N17/N2 corridor running through the GSDM, there are also two main north-south routes running through the District: the N3 freeway to the west, and the N11 route running through the central part of the District.

The District comprises of seven (7) constituent local municipalities as depicted in the table below and Map 1 overleaf.

Figure 4: Gert Sibande District Municipality

Name of Municipality	Main Location	Admin	Area (km ²)
Chief Albert Luthuli	Carolina		5559
Dipaleseng	Balfour		2616
Dr. Pixley Isaka Ka Seme	Volksrust		5227
Govan Mbeki	Secunda		2955
Lekwa	Standerton		4585
Mkhondo	Piet Retief		4882
Msukaligwa	Ermelo		6017

c. District Demographics Analysis

According to Stats SA (2016 Community Survey), Gert Sibande District population increased from 1 043 194 in 2011 to 1 135 409 people in 2016. This makes the District the smallest district in population amongst the three districts in the province. Population grew by 92 215 in the same period and recorded a population growth rate of 1.9% per annum. The population projection for 2019 is estimated at 1 203 807 people and projected at 1 505 441 people in 2030 based on historic population growth patterns.

Figure 5: Average age, racial composition, and gender

The number of households in Gert Sibande increased from 273 490 in 2011 to 333 815 households (more than 60 000 households increase) in 2016 representing 27% of the Mpumalanga household figure. Household size declined from 3.8 to 3.4 people in the same period. Youth population (15-34 years) forms 39.3% of the total population. The share of the female population in 2016 according to the CS was 50.3% and males 49.7%.

Figure 6: Household composition and tenure options

ii. Population figures per municipal area

Local Municipal Area	Population		Average annual population growth 2011-2016	Projected 2019 number	Projected 2030 number
	2011 (Census)	2016 (CS)			
Govan Mbeki	294 538	340 091	3.3%	374 883	535 798
Mkhondo	171 892	189 036	2.1%	201 197	252 874
Chief Albert Luthuli	186 010	187 630	0.2%	188 758	192 952
Msukaligwa	149 377	164 608	2.2%	175 713	223 236
Lekwa	115 662	123 419	1.5%	129 057	152 022
Dr Pixley Ka Isaka Seme	83 235	85 395	0.6%	86 941	92 855
Dipaleseng	42 390	45 232	1.5%	47 298	55 715

Table 1: Population figures per municipal area

iii. Gert Sibande Human Development Index (HDI)

The Human Development Index (HDI) is a composite, relative index that attempts to quantify the extent of Human Development, literacy and income. It is based on measure of life expectancy, literacy and income. The HDI can assume a maximum level of 1, indicating a high level of Human Development, and a minimum value of 0. According to the United Nations, HDI is considered high when it is 0.8 and medium high when it ranges between 0.5 and 0.8 and index value of 0.5 and lower will be considered as a low rating.

Figure 7: Economic situation in relation to household income

i. Gert Sibande population data and projections

Figure 8: Gert Sibande population data and projections

Local Municipal Area	Human Development Index		Trend
	2014	2017	
Govan Mbeki	0.65	0.67	↗
Lekwa	0.59	0.63	↗
Msulungwa	0.60	0.62	↗
Dipaleseng	0.59	0.60	↗
Chief Albert Luthuli	0.55	0.59	↗
Dr Pixley Ka Isaka Seme	0.54	0.57	↗
Mkhondo	0.52	0.55	↗

Table 2: Gert Sibande Human Development Index per municipal area

There is an improved overall Human Development Index (HDI) from 0.59 in 2014 to 0.62 in 2017. Govan Mbeki Municipality's Human Development Index has been leading for the period 2014 to 2017 with HDI of 0.65 and 0.67 in 2014 and 2017, respectively. Chief Albert Luthuli, Dr Pixley Ka Isaka Seme and Mkhondo local municipalities have improved over the same period but still remain below the 0.6 mark.

iv. Poverty aspects in Gert Sibande

The share of the population in Gert Sibande below the lower-bound poverty line (of Stats SA deteriorated the last couple of years to 45.1% in 2017, making it the 2nd highest of the 3 Districts in the province. The total number of people below the lower-bound poverty line was high at 496 921 in 2017 with Mkhondo having the highest.

v. Poverty rate per municipal area

The share of the population below the lower-bound poverty line has deteriorated over the last couple of years to 46.5% in 2019 in the district, making it the second highest of the 3 districts in the province. The total number of people below the lower-bound poverty line was

high at 496 920 in 2017, with Govan Mbeki having the highest number at 111 815 persons

Local Municipal Area	Poverty rate LBPL 2014	Poverty rate LBPL 2017	Trend	Poverty numbers LBPL 2017
Govan Mbeki	30.2%	34.6%	↗	111 815
Lekwa	37.4%	39.7%	↗	47 199
Dipaleseng	33.9%	42.4%	↗	18 663
Msulungwa	37.6%	42.9%	↗	68 491
Chief Albert Luthuli	48.5%	50.0%	↗	92 627
Dr Pixley Ka Isaka Seme	50.5%	56.1%	↗	46 756
Mkhondo	54.1%	59.5%	↗	111 369

Table 3: Poverty rate per municipal area

vi. Income inequality per municipal area

According to IHS Markit, The Gini coefficient for Gert Sibande District (2019) is 0.60, indicating that there are severe levels of inequality or severe income gap.

The data on the figure below indicates that income share is decreasing in Mkhondo LM, Chief Albert Luthuli LM and Lekwa. This is predominately due to increasing unemployment and a dwindling economy that is unable to offer opportunities to a large labour market.

Local Municipal Area	Share of income by poorest 40%		Trend
	2014	2017	
Dipaleseng	8.4%	9.1%	↗
Mkhondo	9.1%	8.9%	↘
Dr Pixley Ka Isaka Seme	8.1%	8.3%	↗
Msulungwa	8.1%	8.2%	↗
Chief Albert Luthuli	9.4%	8.1%	↘
Lekwa	8.4%	8.1%	↘
Govan Mbeki	6.3%	6.6%	↗

Table 4: Income inequality per municipal area

vii. Household services in Gert Sibande

There has been notable improvement with household services in Gert Sibande between 2011 and 2016 according to the Community Survey (2016). The challenges in terms of access to flushing/chemical toilets in informal dwellings persist. The number of informal dwellings decreased from 45 935 in 2011 to 44 862 in 2016 but with 13.4% of the households still living in informal dwellings. Dipaleseng has the highest percentage of households in informal settlements followed by Govan Mbeki and Lekwa .

The Statistics (2016) shows a marginal decrease in the number of people without access to piped water in only two municipalities in the district (Msukaligwa and Mkhondo). There is an increase in the backlogs between the period 2011 and 2016. There is however a difference in the research approach between the two counting periods which renders the counts incomparable.

Mkhondo LM recorded the highest decline in the backlog in this category of service from 12.9% in 2011 to 4.3% in 2016. Dipaleseng recorded the highest backlog at 6%. The GSDM is planning to do upgrades to the bulk water supply network to respond to the water and sanitation challenges in Dipaleseng.

Note: * Question on piped water for 2011 was not phrased in the same way as in CS 2016, therefore the results are not completely comparable.

Figure 9: Access to services

viii. Economic position

The Gert Sibande District Municipality is an economic hub for mining, manufacturing, agriculture, and tourism. It is also a home for huge industries such as Sasol, Eskom, Mondi and other gold and coal mines.

The district economic activity is predominantly concentrated within the urban / industrial complex formed by Secunda, Evander, Kinross, and Trichardt (Govan Mbeki LM). However, other areas of economic importance are distributed throughout the district includes Ermelo, Piet Retief, Standerton, Carolina, Balfour and Elukwathini.

GSDM has a strong economy within the region which is predominantly mining, the coal belt starts from Govan Mbeki, Msukaligwa & Mkhondo & Dr Pixley Ka Isaka Seme local municipalities and gold deposits from Govan Mbeki to Dipaleseng local municipality.

The District's forestry stretches from Mkhondo, Dr Pixley Ka Isaka Seme & Chief Albert Luthuli local municipality where most agricultural activities like farming of cattle & sheep breeding and maize production. The District also hosts one of the largest petro-chemical industries in the country (SASOL) and 4 Eskom coal powered stations.

1. Gross domestic Product

The economic growth rate for Gert Sibande was 0.6% per annum on average over the period 1996 to 2019. Contribution to the Mpumalanga economy is 27.0% which is the smallest economy among the districts in the province.

Govan Mbeki local municipality is the largest contributor to the economy of the GSDM at 56.3% of the total GDP followed by Lekwa and Msukaligwa at 12.8% and 12.2% respectively.

Region	Contribution to Gert Sibande economy 2019	Average annual economic growth 1996-2019	Average annual economic growth 2014-2019	Average annual economic growth 2019-2024
Chief Albert Luthuli	6,4%	2,7%	1,7%	-0,4%
Msukaligwa	12,2%	2,4%	0,6%	0,2%
Mkhondo	6,6%	3,1%	1,3%	0,1%
Dr Pixley Ka Isaka Seme	3,3%	1,5%	0,2%	0,0%
Lekwa	12,8%	0,5%	-0,4%	0,3%
Dipaleseng	2,3%	1,9%	-0,1%	-0,4%
Govan Mbeki	56,3%	0,4%	-0,7%	-0,8%
Gert Sibande	100,0%	1,1%	0,0%	-0,4%

Table 5: Gert Sibande Economic Growth

The Gert Sibande District Municipality's economy is made up of various industries. The mining and manufacturing sectors are strong economic drivers in the district and have a significant presence in Govan Mbeki LM. Manufacturing activities are naturally clustered in proximity to the main concentrations of natural resources. Large scale manufacturing activities generated in the region include petro-chemical and coal as the major energy source. The service-related sectors of trade, transport, finance and community services are dominant economic drivers in Lekwa and Msukaligwa.

d. Prevailing trends matrix

i. Integrated Service Provisioning

DDM TRANSFORMATION AREA TRENDS	KEY ISSUES- POSITIVE	KEY ISSUES-NEGATIVE
Integrated Service Provisioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community Safety Forum have been established in all the 7 local municipalities that need support from relevant stakeholders. SALGA in partnership with GIZ has initiated a support program to enable municipalities to develop Community Safety Plans. 	<p>Absent street naming & numbering reduces the ability to respond to crime alerts.</p> <p>Design of public places not allowing crime prevention.</p> <p>Inadequate Drug Master Plan to deal with the increase in drug use by youth.</p> <p>Poor integration among stakeholders (including the Justice System) involved in the quelling of drug use.</p> <p>Lack of synergy between liquor board, municipalities on licensing of liquor outlets and</p> <p>Illegal transfer of liquor licenses.</p> <p>Community Safety Plans not existing in local government.</p> <p>Poor or no prosecution against vandalism of government infrastructure.</p> <p>No funding and investment in environmental resources / capital fleet and land investment for promotion, conservation, and protection of environment.</p> <p>Environmental Services are handled and attended to by officials that are not competent and relevant to the services.</p> <p>Councils are reactive and do not promulgate bylaws to combat environmental degradation.</p> <p>Failure to implement National Biodiversity Plan.</p> <p>Ineffective disaster management services in local government.</p> <p>Poor integration between public & private sector on issues of disaster management.</p> <p>Misallocation by LMs of the 15% from Municipal Infrastructure Grant set aside for sporting facilities.</p> <p>Poorly supported sporting structures and activities by government.</p>

ii. Demographic and District profile

DDM transformation Area: Demographic and District Profile	Trends Challenge/ Priority Issues	Key Issues- Positive	Key issues-Negative
Basic education	<p>Mis-alignment of schools against norms and standards</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growing recognition for online education • Impact of artificial intelligence • Intensifying demand for affordable, accessible quality education • Educators' willingness to teach beyond the allocated times and days including school holidays • The introduction of fully-fledged boarding schools in Gert Sibande District • Home schooling is growing in the past few years • Introduction of re-orientation for the realization of the millennium goals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges of large classes • Reorientation of new subjects • Reluctance in the development and use of local African languages • Gangsterism and access to substance abuse is threatening curriculum delivery • Organizers of service delivery protests totally disregards curriculum delivery • Lack of professionalism especially among young educators, e.g., poor presentability • Overall financing for education has been on the decline in the past 12 year • Widening the gap between the privileged and poor due to access and inability to access to resources
Building capable and sustainable institutions	<p>Mis-aligned extra-curricular (sporting codes) across different quantiles</p> <p>Mis-alignment of entry requirements between higher education and at the exit level of basic education</p> <p>PMS not adequately implemented to achieve the intended goals of the municipalities</p>	<p>PMS established in all municipalities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in sports by schools depends on the socio-economic factors of the school • Urban schools are far more advanced in terms of extra-curricular activities compared to rural counterparts • PMS is not cascaded to the lowest level • Trainings are not PMS informed • Performance reviews are inconsistently implemented • Persistent lack of quality service delivery leading to undesirable audit opinion • Training is not career pathing oriented

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Performance bonuses are inconsistently paid Senior managers often resign, suspended, or fired before the end of the term of contract Loss of institutional memory Institutional instability
		Establishment of LED units	Inability to create economically viable municipalities
		Non adherence to recruitment policy	Long time taken to fill section 54A and 56 Managers
		No standardised organisational structure for different levels of municipalities	Different municipalities have different operational structures and organograms even though they have similar functions and mandates
		Training and capacitation is not in line with the requirements of 4IR/AI	Paper and manual based approach of processing information and data
Health		Certain health facilities do not meet the ideal required standard/ criteria for the services they are rendering	Some of the facilities are in dire structural condition and not properly classified
		Shortage of ambulance services	Delayed response/ turnaround time to reported cases
		Lack of emotional support due to Covid-19 regulation	Family and friends unable to visit
		Security in health facilities.	Gangsters attacking health practitioners
Social development		Inadequate transport for employees who need it as a tool of trade for work related visits and subsidised vehicles take long	Delayed response/ turnaround time to reported cases
Research and development		The IDP does not explicitly support scientific and service delivery research	Inadequate research capacity- only GSDM has service delivery and scientific research capacity which is still a relatively new initiative and consequently has no budget
		Inadequate research facilities, infrastructure, and human resource	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GSDM has only 1 laboratory which is not research capacitated and has no scientifically fit equipment for research purposes There is limited training
		Inadequate innovation and knowledge generation capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inability to quantify contributions to socio-economic development

iii. Economic Positioning

DDM TRANSFORMATION AREA TRENDS	KEY ISSUES- POSITIVE	KEY ISSUES-NEGATIVE
Economic Positioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing of key sector , manufacturing , agriculture and mining • Strong petrochemical industry • Good transport network N3, N17, N2 and N11 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequate employment opportunities. • Increasing unemployment rate • Old and ageing infrastructure (Roads and Energy supply) • Limited resources to support and rescue key sector • Declining sector performance especially mining and manufacturing sector • The slow pace of Local Economic development

iv. Governance and Administration

DDM TRANSFORMATION AREA TRENDS	KEY ISSUES- POSITIVE	KEY ISSUES- NEGATIVE
<p>Governance and Administration</p>	<p>Council meetings are sitting although randomly and/or for compliance reasons only</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	<p>Design of public places not allowing crime prevention.</p> <p>Inadequate Drug Master Plan to deal with the increase in drug use by youth.</p> <p>Underutilization of structures such as Operation Vuka Sisebenze(OVS) and the creation of duplicating structures introduced within the same period causes confusion amongst ward committee members</p> <p>Unavailability of community development workers (CDWs) in some wards</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No uniform rules and standing orders for the sitting of Council meetings • No adopted schedule of council meetings • No monitoring of the implementation of Council resolutions • No procedure for submitting items to Council <p>Financial Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regression on audit outcomes for most municipalities • Most municipalities are not financially viable • Increasing level of unauthorized, irregular, and fruitless and wasteful expenditure in 7 of the 8 municipalities in District • Most municipalities have difficulties in compiling and submitting annual financial statements • Unable to collect revenue due to non-implementation of revenue enhancement strategy and debt collection policy

V. Spatial Restructuring

DDM TRANSFORMATION AREA TRENDS	KEY ISSUES- POSITIVE	KEY ISSUES-NEGATIVE
Spatial restructuring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Densification (through rezoning and subdivision) especially in urban areas to accommodate a large number of households in relatively smaller parcels of land. • The DDM approach is introducing meaningful engagement between planning & service delivery structures • Development of shopping centres (decentralization and nodal development) in former black townships bringing some economic activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor land ownership information & management in the District. • Land invasion. • Government's inability to meet demand for land (especially for residential purposes). • Failure to reverse apartheid spatial planning patterns • Misalignment between Planning & Infrastructure provision • Inadequate systems and bylaws for spatial planning and land management.

DDM transformation Area Trends	Key Issues- Positive	Key issues- Negative
<p>Infrastructure Engineering</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The definite positive input from Sector Departments to continuously keep on funding project which allows for the upgrade and extension of infrastructure towards projects at Local Municipal level (grant funding). ▪ The DDM approach is introducing meaningful engagement between planning & service delivery structures and advocates for District One Plan & One Budget which will strengthen and enforce coordination and integration ▪ The definite positive input from Sector Departments to continuously keep on funding project which allows for the upgrade and extension of infrastructure towards projects at Local Municipal level (RBIG and other grant funding). 	<p>Water, electricity, Sanitation, Roads, waste management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The definite positive input from Sector Departments to continuously keep on funding project which allows for the upgrade and extension of infrastructure towards projects at Local Municipal level (grant funding). ▪ The DDM approach is introducing meaningful engagement between planning & service delivery structures and advocates for District One Plan & One Budget which will strengthen and enforce coordination and integration ▪ The definite positive input from Sector Departments to continuously keep on funding project which allows for the upgrade and extension of infrastructure towards projects at Local Municipal level (grant funding). 	<p>Water, electricity, Sanitation, Roads, waste management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sewer spillages and poor effluent discharge is all related to the lack of maintained infrastructure and the lack of funding to maintain such infrastructure; • Interruptions on sustainable Electricity provision is all related to the lack of maintained infrastructure and the lack of funding to maintain such infrastructure. • Potholes and poor road maintenance is all related to the lack of maintained infrastructure and the lack of funding to maintain such infrastructure. • Theft and vandalism do create a definite restriction on service delivery on a sustainable basis due to the fact that the repeated maintenance of vandalised infrastructure is just not possible. • Misalignment between Planning of Infrastructure towards Construction trends within financial years is problematic and Local Municipalities finds themselves in the position where the procurement processes always encroach on and take up the planned time for physical construction • The “capacity restrictions” at Eskom to provide electricity contribute to challenges far beyond the discomfort of residents and do have a negative impact on the economic situation in all local municipalities. The rising Eskom debt and limited municipal revenue remains a challenge. <p>Failing infrastructure provision key attributes :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ageing infrastructure, • Poor maintenance • Inadequate maintenance budget • Overloading of systems

vii. COVID-19 Impact

The COVID-19 pandemic has created profound disruptions to our economy and society. Many South African industries are experiencing an adverse impact from the pandemic, which is consistent with other countries fighting the disease. In its response to the crisis, the South African government has (from 27 March 2020) placed the country under a national lockdown to reduce the spread of the virus, resulting in the closure of many businesses.

The businesses affected by the national lockdown are those that are not regarded as providing essential services. These industries include, amongst others, those reliant on the movement of goods (supply chain disruptions), the telecommunications sector, selected mining activities due to a decrease in demand for minerals, accommodation, and tourism due to travel bans, construction, transport, and various services.

South Africa's economic outlook is heavily influenced by global trends. However, it is primarily domestic fiscal policy measures and implementation of economic reforms over the next six to 12 months that will determine the growth trajectory over the next several years. These will be outlined in the 2020 MTBPS.

Critical risks to the economy include continued volatility in global financial markets, sudden interruptions in capital inflows, the reliability of electricity supply, additional commitments to fund financially distressed state-owned companies, low levels of confidence, policy uncertainty and concerns about government's commitment to the independence of the central bank. In a scenario in which tough fiscal policy and broader economic reforms are not implemented, there would be further prolonged weakness in economic growth, currency depreciation and higher borrowing costs.

2.2. VISION (OVERALL DESIRED FUTURE)

The vision is based on the diagnostic findings discussed in the section above and is informed by the vision of the country as set out in the National Development Plan (NDP) and other key policies and plans across government. The One Plan is a visionary and transformative plan addressing the following interrelated DDM key transformation focus areas.

Furthermore, it is to ensure that the vision framework is context-related, informed by evidence-based findings as opposed to aspirational, clinical and dimensionless statements. These components include:

- **Vision:** A Vision, is a detailed, write-up that lays out a clear, logical vision of what an organisation or area will look like in the future. When completed, it's meant to guide decision making and giving all involved clear direction to strive for.
- **Goal:** A goal is an idea of the future or desired result that an organization envisions, plan and commit to achieve.
- **Outcomes:** An outcome is something that follows as a result or consequence of one or many actions. An outcome involves an intentional change being imposed on a system with the resulting end state being measured, typically by indicators.
- **Objectives:** An objective is something which you plan to do or achieve, with the aim or purpose to realise an outcome. It is typically related to specific, measurable actionable, relevant and time-bound strategies and actions that if implemented, will bridge the "where we are" to the "where we want to be".
- **Strategies:** A strategy is a course of action, to achieve a specific objective

GERT SIBANDE ONE PLAN ADOPTED VISION:

A COMMUNITY DRIVEN DISTRICT OF EXCELLENCE, DEVELOPMENT, AND INNOVATION

TRANSFORMATION AREA: INFRASTRUCTURE ENGINEERING	
Vision: Improved quality of life and economic prosperity through reliable access to services and infrastructure	
DESIRED FUTURE STATEMENT:	
Functional, Efficient and reliable Infrastructure that supports dynamic economic demands	
Goal: (Measurable): Access to reliable basic services for all by 2050	Functional, Efficient Infrastructure Network to Facilitate Growth
STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES (High level)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve sanitation infrastructure and eradicate spillages • Innovative asset management • Improve grant expenditure • Introduction of alternative energy sources to take the pressure of the Grid • Sustainable water and sanitation provision in Rural Area • Service Delivery (Potholes and Poor Roads maintenance) • Promote compliant and efficient land fill sites 	
i. OUTCOMES	

ii.	The provision of Bulk Services on Sewer Treatment together with the maintenance of Reticulation networks servicing the community timeously with well qualified and capacitated employees of Council
iii.	The provision of Bulk Services on Electricity distribution in accordance with the allocated bulk NMD in a sustainable manner.
iv.	To service Eskom's current account and adhere to repayment plans.
v.	To allow for the needed budget and resources to maintain a reliable electricity network in the provision of electricity in accordance with all Health and Safety measures.
vi.	To implement projects as per the procurement plan ensuring the management of each contract or services to be provided to be of good quality and value for money.
vii.	To allow for the needed budget and resources to maintain a reliable electricity network in the provision of electricity in accordance with all Health and Safety measures
viii.	To implement projects as per the procurement plan ensuring the management of each contract or services to be provided to be of good quality and value for money.
ix.	Compliant to blue drop and green drop
x.	Safe disposal of effluent and prevent river pollution

TRANSFORMATION AREA: DEMOGRAPHIC AND DISTRICT PROFILE	
Vision: Integrated smart data platforms across all stakeholders supporting evidence-based decision making	
DESIRED FUTURE STATEMENT (S):	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have adequate infrastructure and systems in place that lean more towards research, development and innovation initiatives. • Have advanced technologically driven economy. • Have well-resourced health, education and social welfare services with an in-built capacity. 	
STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES (High level)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well-resourced Performance Management Unit established and PMS implemented at all municipalities according to the Performance Management Framework • Develop and implement policies that are pro senior manager retention • Align training and capacitation to 4IR / AI requirements • Classify and accredit all health facilities according to their level of service and office of the health standard • Have adequate availability of medical emergency vehicles as per emergency norms and effective call centre operations • Support service delivery research, development and innovation (RDI) initiatives in strategic Local Government functions 	
OUTCOMES	

Aligned entry requirements from basic to higher education	Standardised organisational structure for municipalities with similar functions and mandates
Phased out multi-graded classes	Work skills development programmes aligned to 4IR/AI
Schools with basic minimum infrastructural requirements	Increased life expectancy, decreased maternal and child mortality, combat HIV/AIDS and decreased burden of disease; and strengthened health systems
Aligned and regulated school sports, culture and other extra-curricular activities at all schools	Increased coverage of and access to all health services to the population
Aligned inter-governmental planning frameworks and cycles	Increased coverage of and access to social services to the population
Workable performance frameworks across departments in the public service	Enhanced research and development capabilities in frontier areas of service delivery and reliable research information
Senior managers appointed on long term contracts of 10 years or on a permanent basis	Effective and efficient use of resources and the pooling of expertise that will enable improvement in service delivery

TRANSFORMATION AREA: INTEGRATED SERVICE PROVISIONING	
<p><i>Vision: In 2050 we want to create a district where ALL people:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are free from crime and violence in both urban and rural communities • Feel safe at home, at school, and at work • Feel free from fear and conditions that contribute to crime and violence <p>Desired future statement: To protect and Conserve Environmental assets through stringent policy directives, dedicated conditional investment and resource allocation, AND To integrate resources geared towards the management of Environment, Social Ills, and Disasters.</p> <p>Goal: (Measurable)</p> <p>Development of By-Laws and Policies; Resuscitation of FFV facilities dealing with GBVF; AND Alignment of institutional arrangement for the provision of Environmental, Social Services and Disaster Management</p>	
STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES (High level)	
List of objectives; link them to outcomes	
i.	Monitoring the Adherence of Environmental Laws
ii.	Provision of adequate resources for disaster management
iii.	Deliver biodiversity and conservation programmes
v.	Provision of Environmental services
List outcomes	List outcomes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved compliance to environmental laws (Community and Environmental Safety) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved disaster management services (Disaster Mitigation and Response) • Allocation of funding resources

TRANSFORMATION AREA: ECONOMIC POSITIONING	
<p>Vision: a district with a growing economy that supports effective resource use and strong entrepreneur</p> <p>Desired future statement: A Government that is innovative in supporting economic growth</p> <p>Goal: To reduce unemployment by 15% for the nine years (Vision 2030) And grow the economy by 5%.</p>	
<p>STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES (High level)</p> <p>List of objectives; link them to outcomes</p> <p>Create job opportunities that will develop, transform and sustain the local economy</p>	
<p>List outcomes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provision of support to the key/main sectors within the district is imperative for sustainability purposes. - Provide support to enable entrepreneurship and skills development - Promote diversified economies and foster the creation of value chain - Create enabling environment to all business 	<p>List outcomes</p>

TRANSFORMATION AREA: SPATIAL TRANSFORMATION	
<p>Vision: "Smart, integrated and sustainable human settlements that promote spatial justice, resilience, equality and spatial transformation".</p> <p>Desired future statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Efficient Land Administration System / Mechanism - Spatial priorities and initiatives that guide and stimulate development & investment - Capacitated Planning Societies <p>Goal: (Measurable)</p> <p>Eradication 50% of informal settlements by 2030</p>	
<p>STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES (High level)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Curbing land invasion • Creation of integrated human settlement through township establishment (green field) and formalization of informal settlements where feasible. • Integrated rural develop with access to goods and services • Unlocking economic potential through nodal development 	
<p>List outcomes</p> <p>Integrated human settlements</p> <p>Protected sensitive environment</p> <p>Coherent spatial patterns (curbing urban sprawl)</p>	<p>List outcomes</p> <p>Improved socio-economic profile</p>

TRANSFORMATION AREA: DEMOGRAPHIC AND DISTRICT PROFILE	
Vision: Integrated smart data platforms across all stakeholders supporting evidence-based decision making	
DESIRED FUTURE STATEMENT (S):	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Have adequate infrastructure and systems in place that lean more towards research, development and innovation initiatives. Have advanced technologically driven economy. Have well-resourced health, education and social welfare services with an in-built capacity. 	
Goal: (Measurable)	
STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES (High level)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Schools that are aligned to the set norms and standards in collaboration with stakeholders Provide extra-curricular programs to all schools Well-resourced Performance Management Unit established and PMS implemented at all municipalities according to the Performance Management Framework Develop and implement policies that are pro senior manager retention Align training and capacitation to 4IR / AI requirements Classify and accredit all health facilities according to their level of service and office of the health standard Have adequate availability of medical emergency vehicles as per emergency norms and effective call centre operations Support service delivery research, development and innovation (RDI) initiatives in strategic Local Government functions 	
OUTCOMES	
Aligned entry requirements from basic to higher education	Standardised organisational structure for municipalities with similar functions and mandates
Phased out multi-graded classes	Work skills development programmes aligned to 4IR/AI
Schools with basic minimum infrastructural requirements	Increased life expectancy, decreased maternal and child mortality, combat HIV/AIDS and decreased burden of disease; and strengthened health systems
Aligned and regulated school sports, culture and other extra-curricular activities at all schools	Increased coverage of and access to all health services to the population
Aligned inter-governmental planning frameworks and cycles	Increased coverage of and access to social services to the population
Workable performance frameworks across departments in the public service	Enhanced research and development capabilities in frontier areas of service delivery and reliable research information
Senior managers appointed on long term contracts of 10 years or on a permanent basis	Effective and efficient use of resources and the pooling of expertise that will enable improvement in service delivery

2.2. STRATEGIES

The Strategies detailed below emanate from the above vision statements and desire future per each transformation area. These strategic goals provide clear direction on how the current status quo can be challenged and changed to a desired future. The strategies represent the approach, key shifts and a sharper focus by which Government as a collective will be pursuing service delivery and development in Gert Sibande working together with stakeholders and communities.

TRANSFORMATION AREA: INTEGRATED SERVICE PROVISIONING		
Strategic focus areas	Objective	Strategy (high level)
GBVF	Reduce incidents of GBVF.	Awareness campaigns and education.
Strengthen the Criminal Justice System	Promote effectiveness and efficiency of the criminal justice system.	Re-establish VFF in each municipality within GSDM. Monitor SAPS service delivery. Conduct Court briefs. Strengthen border patrols and security management.
Build community participation in Community Safety	Promote the whole of government and community approach in addressing Community Safety.	Promulgation of by-laws and enforcement through the establishment of municipal court days to deal with municipal cases. Development of Municipal Community Safety Plans. Retraining of CPFs. Integrated approach in dealing with drugs and substance abuse.
Build Safety using and integrated approach	Integrated approach in dealing with Safety and Security.	Build, strengthen and capacitate CSFs. Rural Safety Initiative: Paralegal workshops. Awareness campaign against stock-theft. Awareness campaign against domestic violence. School Safety Initiative School debates.

		<p>Prison visits. Awareness campaign against dangerous weapons and drug abuse including a campaign for the classification of synthetic drugs (Nyaope) through the revision of the Drug Master Plan.</p> <p>Vulnerable Group Initiative: Child protection week. Awareness campaign against abuse of the elderly.</p> <p>Contact Crime: Awareness campaign against common assault and GBH. Awareness campaign against rape.</p> <p>Educational Campaigns: Border security. Sports against crime. Liquor traders' workshops. Awareness campaign against human trafficking.</p>
Climate Change		<p>Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies to encourage and enhance green economy, environmental considerate infrastructural developments and environmental educational awareness paired with environmental skills development for green future; is conducted by GSDM for betterment and improvement of service delivery in all the seven (7) local municipal areas.</p>
Waste Management		<p>Waste management:- The municipality requires an adequate budget to assist the local municipalities to perform their mandate and comply with the required legislation. E.g. compliance to landfill sites</p>
Air Quality management		<p>Air Quality management:-The district requires assistance with the purchasing of its own ambient air quality monitoring network due to the Air pollution challenges within the district include emission of atmospheric pollutants due to active industrial emissions both in mining sites and industrial processing plants The mining and petrochemical industries produce huge quantities of gases with substantial amounts being hazardous to the environment and extremely dangerous to the living organism including human beings. There is a need for vigorous training on Air Quality in all the seven LMs within the district. Training should not only be made available to the district officials. It should be cascaded down to the local municipalities as well.</p>

TRANSFORMATION AREA: INFRASTRUCTURE		
Strategic focus areas	Objective	Strategy (the how) high level
Reduced water losses	Improve preventative maintenance	Develop and implement WCWDM Develop Operation and Maintenance plans Functional call centre to report water leaks Keep maintenance material in stock for quicker turn around time
Water Source Security and Water Conservation	Establishment of new water sources	Research for long term sources of water and establish new dams Establish water recycling and re-use for industries Establishment of production boreholes for small scale water schemes
Compliant WWTW and WTW	Improve operation and efficiency of plants	Deploys qualified personnel to run the treatment plants Develop SOPs and Maintenance plans for treatment plants
Safe roads network	Improved road capacity and no potholes	Continuous road maintenance and renewal Widen roads to match the increasing traffic
Neat towns and residential areas	Improve waste collection	Procure more waste removal trucks Establish new landfill sites
Stable Power Supply	Reliable electricity supply	Service Eskom debt and increase NMD Establish renewable energy power plants Public Private partnership with independent energy producers
Reduced Sewer Spillages	No sewer blockages and surcharging	Conduct preventative maintenance and maintain functional sewer pump stations Community awareness, to not deposit foreign objects to sewer network Procure jet trucks and roding equipment to fight blockages
Adequate infrastructure for future	Infrastructure upgrade and renewal	Renew infrastructure to cater for the increasing demand utilising the infrastructure grants, private funding and SLP funding Develop infrastructure master plans and improve alignment of projects within the district

TRANSFORMATION AREA: ECONOMIC POSITIONING		
Strategic focus areas	Objective	Strategy (high level)
i. Creation of new economies	Identify new commodities to diversify and support primary sector must be identified.	Create value chain of products(Agro-processing , fibre-crops(hemp , bamboo} ,furniture production
ii. Sector Development and Support	To develop and support key economic sectors	Projects to support the existing sectors. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rehabilitate mine land for agriculture use • Alien vegetation removal and reuse for biogas manufacturing. • Establish local Fresh Produce market • Provide bulk infrastructure to support current businesses
iii. strengthen stakeholder engagement	To foster and create a conducive business environment	Develop a Stakeholder engagement framework.
iv. Attract and retain investment in the district	Investment promotion	Develop Standard investment framework/policy to guide investors and government
v. Prioritize local entrepreneurship development	To enable entrepreneurship and skills development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify skills gaps. Reducing the skills deficit by attracting skilled immigrants. • Partnership with private sector and international chambers to provide training • Provide light industrial hubs for local SMME' s. • Revamping the skills framework and undertaking a range of reforms in basic education and the post-schooling environment to improve outcomes for workers – and the firms that can employ them.

TRANSFORMATION AREA: DEMOGRAPHIC AND DISTRICT PROFILE

Strategic focus areas	Objective	Strategy (high level)
Well focused and improved functioning government institutions and facilities	Create and facilitate effective, innovative and smart government institutions	Create smart government institutions by using modern technology to facilitate and support better planning and decision making, thus providing for government efficacy and sustainable development using consolidated information systems and communication networks

TRANSFORMATION AREA: GOVERNANCE AND ADMINISTRATION

Strategic focus areas	Objective	Strategy (high level)
Building a capable, financially sustainable and developmental governance system	To build a capable public service in the Gert Sibande district according to the principles for good governance as enshrined in the constitution of South Africa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve inter-departmental coordination and cooperation and proactively strengthen relationships with Nation and Provincial governments • Combine efforts of the public and private sectors as equal partners in the development of the Gert Sibande District • Improve accountability and transparency and strengthen oversight between departments and spheres of government
Effective performance management system	Implement an effective performance management system and monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work towards the standardization and integration of PMS practice throughout the district by supporting constituent local municipalities with their performance management systems • Enhance the capacity of the district to perform all its Performance Management responsibilities through training and staffing

TRANSFORMATION AREA: SPATIAL RESTRUCTURING

Strategic focus areas	Objective	Strategy (high level)
Curbing land invasion	To ensure sustainable development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Comprehensive Land Audits ▪ Land Administration Strategy • Strengthen By-Law enforcement capacity • Develop a nationwide state land release mechanism to fast track development
Develop Innovative planning packages to stimulate spatial transformation, economic growth and prosperity	To facilitate socio-economic inclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Lease land to private developers for a defined period ➤ Planning regulation and business licensing incentive ➤ Tax breaks (municipal rates) ➤ Development of enabling policies such as development charges policies.

2.2. IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

a. Institutional arrangements

The 3 impact zones of Nkangala, Gert Sibande and Ehlanzeni have established DDM Councils and Technical Teams and meetings of both structures are convened by district municipalities and coordinated by the department.

7 work-streams were established in each of the 3 impact zones to coordinate the implementation of projects and development of DDM One Plans.

3 DDM Dashboards were compiled by the department to monitor and report on the implementation of key DDM programmes and catalytic projects in the three impact zones.

The workstreams provides regular progress to DDM Technical Teams on the implementation of DDM programmes and projects through the Dashboards.

Figure 10: DDM Approved workstreams

Figure 11: Gert Sibande DDM one Plan reporting structure

b. One plan DDM budgeting

The DDM does not introduce a new budgeting process and system, however, a budgeting system that is based upon and is responsive to development plans that are in turn agile and responsive to community aspirations. There is also concern raised as to what happens to existing programmes and projects or project pipelines.

The DDM operates within the existing constitutional and legislative framework of the country. budget commitments that fall short of contributing to the medium term goals and the priorities that have been outlined in the 52 profiles should be revisited without changing the existing budgeting system. All structures and systems, which enable the DDM roll-out would remain key platforms for processing priorities emerging from joint planning and dealing with intergovernmental funding issues, and over time introducing reforms that would support spatial planning and budgeting principles that enhance gender based budgeting.

Further, DDM implementation constitutes intergovernmental formulation, approval, adoption implementation, monitoring and review of the One Plans. The medium-term plans to reprioritise budgets and stabilise the local government, form a critical step in addressing urgent and pressing gaps identified in the profiles and should be seen as a continuum, that establishes the basis upon which One Plans will be drawn, including how the process extracts from existing plans and budgets, improve what direction future plans and budgets ought to take in accordance with a more coherent approach to achieving agreed to intergovernmental outcomes.

The development and implementation of the One Plans can only be undertaken by the whole of government through review of each departments, entities or municipalities plans and budgets according to One Plan commitments, which constitute one of the phases towards the One Plan. Such review and/or reprioritisation can thus only take place through the prescribed Government Planning Cycle which includes the review of the Medium-Term Strategic

Framework (MTSF), formulation/review of sector-based master plans, departmental Strategic Plans and Annual Performance Plans, and municipal Growth and Development Strategies, SDFs and IDPs. In addition, the multi-year planning objectives and targets must be aligned to distinct programme and project resource commitments enunciated through the **government budgeting process** across all spheres of government.

c. Monitoring and reporting

The implementation of the One Plan shall be monitored through the existing governance structures established by the Gert Sibande District Municipality on the implementation of the District Development Model. The existing workstreams which have now been aligned with the six transformational areas of this One Plan shall serve as the key drivers of monitoring, reporting and reporting on the implementation of the One to ensure that set outcomes are realised.

This shall require that a detailed implementation plan is developed for each of the seven transformational areas with clearly defined results to be achieved during the various intervals of the execution of the plan. This includes the immediate, short, medium and long term implementation process and must be periodically reported to upper structures for strategic decision making and must be subjected to political oversight on a regular basis.

It is recommended that as part of the monitoring process, progress on the implementation of the One Plan must be reported to provincial oversight structures such as MuniMEC and the Executive Council to ensure that the district area is able to communicate strides and success made on the DDM. This

shall also ensure that upper structures of the province support district municipalities in unblocking challenges that might be experienced during the execution phase of the One Plan, including the mobilisation of resources to fund identified catalytic projects which are not budgeted.

It is also envisaged that through the involvement of the political champions assigned to the district area from both the national and provincial spheres of government, the district area shall be supported in the implementation of the plan by serve as its mouthpiece in the upper echelons of the government on development matters affect the region as a whole.

2.2. CONCLUSION

The Gert Sibande District One plan should be viewed as a living strategy document that is a work in progress. This is due to the dynamic nature of the municipal environment and the involvement of various role players. Stakeholder involvement is critical in shaping a plan that best represents all the aspirations of the community at large.

The district development model seeks to put district municipalities as lead coordinators in relation to development processes. It is the aim of the district development to ensure that district municipalities work collaboratively with all stakeholders such as various spheres of government, private sector, community-based organizations, non-governmental organizations as well as multi-disciplinary teams to achieve one goal, that is integrated planning and delivery in the context of one plan.

2.2. ANNEXURE: CATALYTIC COMMITMENTS

Priority Issues	Catalytic Projects / Programmes	Costs as Multiyear Projects 30 Years
<p>Service delivery challenges (Sewer spillages and poor effluent discharged)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To have a free environment from spillages on both reticulation network and on bulk / WWTWs Investment on infrastructure Establish Category C landfill site for the disposal of sludge 	<p>Capital of nature Cost approximately R 900 M</p> <p>Capital of nature Cost approximately R 1 000 M</p> <p>Capital of nature Cost approximately R 130 M</p>
<p>Service delivery challenges (Electricity interruptions)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operational and Master Plans Active master plan to be developed To ring-fence the electricity businesses in LMs Continuous metre audits Use one LM as a pilot study to alternate energy source <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart metering 	<p>Capital of nature Cost approximately R 3 M every 4 Years</p> <p>Capital of nature Cost approximately R 600 M</p> <p>Operational of nature Cost approximately R 6 M every 3 years</p> <p>Capital of nature Cost approximately R 500 M</p>

			Capital of nature Cost approximately R 500 M
Service delivery challenges (Water interruptions and leaks)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To upgrade WTPS in line with the projected 2030 demands • To introduce programs that would allow reuse of water in order to increase the yield. • To reference the services network through GIS in order to speedup the maintenance process especially during a response on breakdown 		Capital of nature Cost approximately R 900 M Capital of nature Cost approximately R 300 M Capital of nature Cost approximately R 30 M
Extension of water reticulation network to Rural areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Network upgrade and extension program ▪ Installation of JoJo tanks and boreholes ▪ Procurement of Borehole drilling machine 		Capital of nature Cost approximately R 900 M Capital of nature Cost approximately R 100 M Capital of nature Cost approximately R 25 M

<p>Poor water quality</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refurbishment / upgrade of water treatment works • Appointment and training of qualified PCs • Regular desludging of reservoirs 	<p>Capital of nature</p> <p>Cost approximately R 600 M</p> <p>Operational of nature</p> <p>Cost approximately R 2 M every 3 years</p> <p>Operational of nature</p> <p>Cost approximately R 2 M every 5 years</p>
<p>Service Delivery (Potholes and Poor Roads maintenance)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To procure reasonable yellow/ white Fleet to deal with blading and re gravelling of roads in the district • Model on maintenance of old infrastructure vs provision of new infrastructure • Develop a comprehensive district wide Master plan 	<p>Capital of nature</p> <p>Cost approximately R 60 M</p> <p>Operational of nature</p> <p>Cost approximately R 10 M every</p> <p>Operational of nature</p> <p>Cost approximately R 2 M every 5 years</p>

<p>PRIORITY INTERVENTION AREA</p>	<p>NAME OF PROGRAMME</p>	<p>LOCATION</p>	<p>KEY OUTPUT</p>
-----------------------------------	--------------------------	-----------------	-------------------

Infrastructure investment and delivery	Aerospace Development	Ermelo	<p>Development of Ermelo airport into an aerospace industrial hub to accommodate aircraft parts manufacturers and warehousing, flight school, aircraft mechanic training.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SEZ Declaration • Upgrade Roads and basic services infrastructure (water,electricity)
	Upgrading Main District Corridors	GSDM	Upgrading of the district's main corridors most notably the N17, N2, N11 and R33
	Light Industrial Hubs	7 X Local Municipalities	Renovation and conversion of old buildings to industrial workshops to accommodate artisans, auto mechanics and other skilled business traders
	Digital Infrastructure development	GSDM	Investment in the low cost and high speed and easily accessible digital infrastructure
	Volksrust 88kV Network (ESKOM)	Volksrust	This project will benefit Vukuzakhe SS which is feeding the Municipality in Volksrust Projected Cost R95m

Upgrade of Silobela Substation	Chief Albert Luthuli	Upgrade of electricity infrastructure total budget R47.8m
Upgrade of Philip Greyling Substation	Mkhondo	Upgrade of electricity infrastructure total budget R60m
Construction of New Balfour Substation Phase 5	Dipaleseng	Upgrade of electricity infrastructure total budget R67.8m

RBIG Projects 2021/22

Municipality	Project Name	Phases Under Construction	Planning
Mkhondo LM	Construction of Amsterdam Dam (Gabosch)	Refurbishment of Amsterdam WTW and Bulk pipelines (Phase 1 & 2 have been completed)	Phase 4: Construction of Gabosch Dam at Amsterdam is at detailed design and Finalisation of Regulatory requirements
Dipaliseng LM	Balfour/Siyathemba/ Greylingstad/ Nthorwane RBWS	-Phase 2: Upgrading of WTW from 6.5ML to 19,5ML is at 54% progress -Phase 3: Construction of Bulk Pipeline from Siyathemba to Greylingstad/ Nthorwane is at 65%	Phase 4: Upgrading of Bulk pipeline from WTW's to Siyathemba is at preliminary design stage
Govan Mbeki LM	Imbalenhle Bulk Sewer Project	Phase 2: Construction of new Pumpstation at Extension 24 and bulk sewer pipeline to WWTW's under construction	Upgrading of Embalenhle WWTW's by 25ML is at Implementation Readiness Study
Lekwa LM	Lekwa Water Services	None under RBIG (Upgrading of Rooikopen Sewer System is under implementation but funded under WSG)	-Construction of Outfall sewer from Extension 8 is at tender stage (documentation) -Feasibility Study for Bulk Sewer including WWTW's at tender Stage

Municipality	Project Name	Phases Under Construction	Planning
Chief Albert Luthuli LM	Empuluzi/Methula RBWS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Upgrading of eMpuluzi WTW's to 10ML/d -Construction of new 5ML WTW's at Methula -All Bulk pipelines and Reservoirs 	Construction of Off-Channel Dam at Feasibility
	Eerstehoek RBWS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Upgrading of WTW from 14ML to 21ML -All Bulk pipelines and Reservoirs 	Further upgrades of WTW's from 21ML to 29ML at design stage
Msukaligwa LM	Greater Msukaligwa RBWS Project	Cluster3: Refurbishment & Upgrading of WTW's and construction of Bulk pipelines at Davel	
		Cluster2: Upgrading of abstraction point at Torbanite Dam, Upgrading of Breyten WTW's and Bulk pipelines and Reservoir to supply Chrissiesmeer, Breyton, Lothair and Warburton	Cluster1: Upgrading of supply for Ermelo and Wesselton still at Feasibility stage

a. Spatial Transformation & Integrated Human Settlements

<p>Priorities Year 5 - 10</p>	<p>Priorities Year 10 - 15</p>	<p>Priorities Year 15 - 20</p>	<p>Priorities Year 20 - 25</p>
<p>Develop Innovative planning packages to stimulate spatial transformation, economic growth and prosperity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lease to private development for a defined period ▪ Planning regulation and business licensing incentive ▪ Tax breaks (municipal rates) ▪ Development charges ▪ Comprehensive credible Land Audit to be conducted per Municipality 	<p>Conduct feasibility studies on identified land parcels</p>	<p>Service sites</p>	<p>Service sites</p>

<p>Identify land parcels for economic nodes – form part of Land Audit</p>				
<p>Develop an nationwide state land release mechanism to fast track development</p>				
<p>Dedicated focus on the provision of bulk infrastructure across the district</p>	<p>Dedicated focus on the provision of bulk infrastructure across the district</p>	<p>Spatial transformation</p>	<p>A new city Smart settlements integrated settlements human</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Comprehensive Land Audits ▪ Expropriation of land where possible ▪ Land Administration Strategy ▪ Review legal Framework that frustrate efficiency in land administration • Strengthen By-Law enforcement capacity • Planning framework that is strategically aligned • Prioritize development of planning within the municipal space • Develop & scases skills policy for planners 	<p>Develop 4IR Capacity to manage land</p>	<p>Develop 4IR Capacity to manage land</p>	<p>A new city</p>	

b. Research, Institutional & community Development

- Develop and strengthen IGR programmes within all spheres of government.
- Review the curriculum to address the misalignment/gaps
- Conduct an audit on the implementation of PMS within the district.
- Research on the possibility of having senior managers appointed on permanent basis.
- Conduct research on the possibility of standardizing municipal organisational structures with similar mandates and functions.
- Foster investment programmes in 4IR/AI initiatives.
- Coordination of skills development programmes for specific focus areas to support local municipalities.
- Development of policy briefs and pamphlet documents and MOUs with various educational facilities and sectoral departments

c. Governance, Administration & ICT

i. Implementation Plan

PRIORITY ISSUES	ACTIVITY	RESPONSIBILITY	TIMEFRAME	FUNDING
Sitting of council and its committees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development, review and approval of standing rules and orders by-laws. • Adoption of a calendar or schedules for sitting of council and its committees 	Municipal councils	2022/2023 (Short-term)	Normal corporate services functions and no additional budget required
Non-functionality of section 79 & 80 committees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and approval of terms of reference for committees of councils. • Provision of leadership and management development programs for councillors (training/skills development) 	Municipal councils HRD in consultation with Speaker's offices	2022 - 2023 (Short-term)	Normal corporate services functions and no additional budget required HRD & Speakers' offices, SALGA,
Filling of vacant/ critical positions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funded critical vacancies to be filled with suitably qualified persons within the stipulated timeframe 	Municipal councils	2022 - 2025 (Medium-term)	Various departments within institutions

Functionality of ward committees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provision of relevant tools of trade to ward committees Provision of capacity building programmes to ward committees 	Local municipalities	2022 – 2024 (Medium-term)	Speakers' offices & HRD
Public Participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review of public participation strategies 	Departments, Local municipalities	2022-2023 (Short-term)	Various departments within institutions
Covid – 19 pandemic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provision of Covid -19 PPEs, screening, and awareness Amendment of HR policies to talk to the current situation Provision of ICT infrastructure for remote operation 	Dept. of Community and Social Services Corporate Services	2022/2023 (Short-term) 2022/2023 2022 - 2024	Corporate Services and Community & Social Development CS (HR) CS (ICT)

d. List of Funded Catalytic Projects and Key role players

The following catalytic projects are also identified:

PRIORITY ISSUES	ACTIVITY	RESPONSIBILITY	TIMEFRAME	FUNDING
ICT Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Installation of fibre network in the district 	Private sector	2021 - 2030 (Long - term)	Private sector funding
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online learning portal 	District municipality	2022 - 2024 (Medium-term)	GSDM (ICT)

Environment, Social Services & Disaster Management

- Commissioned regional landfill sites (x2)
- Yellow fleet for landfill sites
- Standard Waste management fleet for LM's
- 7 x waste recycling cooperatives
- Integrated waste management bylaws

- Cost recovery tariffs
- Efficient/ sustainable / cost reflective accessible waste management services by 2030.
- 3 x regional sports facilities meeting national federations standards 2030
- 3 x regional facilities meeting arts federations standards [auditorium / opera house .multi purpose centres. 2030
- Functional sports /arts and culture structures & Federations / forums.2025

Safety & Security

Priorities Year 5 - 10	Priorities Year 10 - 15	Priorities Year 15 - 20	Priorities Year 20 - 25
Strengthen the criminal justice system			
Monitor SAPS service delivery			
Conduct Court briefs			
Strengthen border patrols and security management			
Promulgation of by-laws and enforcement through the establishment of municipal court days to deal with municipal cases.			
Build community participation in Community Safety			
Development of Community Safety Plans			
Retraining of CPFs			
Integrated approach in dealing with drugs and substance abuse			
Strengthen and build CSFs			
Gender Based Violence and Femicide			
Awareness campaigns and education			
Re-establish VFFs in each municipality within GSDM			
Build Safety using an integrated approach			

<p>Inclusion of municipal public safety, private security service providers, SAPS, DoJ, Correctional Services, DSD, DARDLEA, Home Affairs, Business community in Community Safety and Crime Prevention initiatives through the CSFs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rural Safety Initiative <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Paralegal workshops (ii) Awareness campaign against stock theft (iii) Awareness campaign against domestic violence • School Safety Initiative <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) School debates (ii) Prison visits (iii) Awareness campaign against dangerous weapons and drug abuse including a campaign for the classification of synthetic drugs through the revision of the drug mater plan. • Vulnerable group initiative <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Child protection week (ii) Awareness campaign against abuse of the elderly (iii) Awareness campaign against gender-based violence • Contact Crime <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Awareness campaign against common assault and GBH (ii) Awareness campaign against rape • Educational campaigns <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Border security (ii) Sports against crime (iii) Liquor traders workshop (iv) Awareness campaign against human trafficking 		
Professionalise the police Training and reskilling of the service		